

CONGRESS
FARM TO FORK

Our food, our health, our future

16-17-18 NOV 23

Farm to Fork: Our Food,
Our Health, Our Future
Congress

Castelo Branco, Portugal

Farm to Fork: Our Food, Our Health, Our Future, Congress Castelo Branco, Portugal

ISBN

9782832512524

DOI

10.3389/978-2-8325-1252-4

Citation

Camelo, A., Lucas, A., Riscado, A., Silveira, A., Rodrigues, A.,
Marçal, B., Baptista, C., Ferreira, C., Santo, C.E., Pereira, F.,
Beato, H., Barreto, I., Brandão, I., Cabaço, I., André, I.,
Paulo, L., Cristóvão, M., Lucas, M., Santos, N., Coelho, P.,
Rato, R., Martins, S., Vasconcelos, V. (2024)

November 16– 18, 2023, Castelo Branco, Portugal

The abstracts in this collection have not been subject to any Frontiers peer review or checks, and are not endorsed by Frontiers. They are made available through the Frontiers publishing platform as a service to conference organizers and presenters. The copyright in the individual abstracts is owned by the author of each abstract or their employer unless otherwise stated. Each abstract, as well as the collection of abstracts, are published under a Creative Commons CC-BY 4.0 (attribution) licence (creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) and may thus be reproduced, translated, adapted and be the subject of derivative works provided the authors and Frontiers are attributed.

For Frontiers' terms and conditions please see: frontiersin.org/legal/terms-and-conditions.

Table of contents

- 24 Welcome to the Farm to Fork: Our food, Our health, Our Future Congress
- 26 Opening Remarks
- 48 Theme I – From global to local: Current challenges for the sustainable transformation of urban food systems
- Synopsis - Keynote Speakers
- 48 Radically re-thinking the food-water-energy nexus in the wake of the “Summer of Discontent 2023”
Baha Kuban
- 50 How can the transformation of urban food systems be governed?
Einar Braathen
- 51 Urban agriculture and its role in urban sustainable development
Patricia Hernandez
- 52 The contribution of urban food policies to the Agenda 2030 through SDGS targets and indicators
Andrea Calori
- 54 Gaps between food-related policies and their implementation: What we know about the Portuguese context
Cecília Delgado

56 **Selected Oral Communications**

56 **Abstract I.1 Transforming the local food system in Setúbal with local authorities**

V. Silva, A., Martins, A.

59 **Abstract I.2 Role of UAEU (thematic) partnership on food in supporting cities as catalyst for local food systems transformation**

Triboi, R., Rotaru, I., Pasarel, A.

62 **Abstract I.3 City agricultural systems, innovative alternatives for sustainability transitions: Evidence from case studies in France**

Boukharta, O.F., Sauvée, L., Fabri, F., Chico-Santamarta, L., Navas-Gracia, L.M.

65 **Posters**

65 **Poster I.1 Circular economy in the urban food system: The Italian case study of the Turin Living Lab focused on the circular cooking experimentation**

Savina, A., Fassio, F.

68 **Poster I.2 Urban food system transitions (FUSILLI project): The gender approach in Barcelona city**

Ramirez-Santos, Ana G., Yacoub, Cristina, Rivera-Ferre, Marta G.

71 **Poster I.3 An elaboration of role of alternative food initiatives in urban- peri urban linkages for short food supply chain**

Emel KARAKAYA AYALP, Sevim Pelin ÖZTÜRK, Feral GEÇER SARGIN

- 73 **Poster I.4 Smart cities through urban short supply chains of food**
Mata, F. , Dos - Santos, M., Baptista, N. , Natacha, S.
- 75 **Poster I.5 Sustainable consumption in urban short supply chains**
Mata, F. , Dos - Santos, M., , Baptista, N. , Natacha, S.
- 78 **Poster I.6 CLEVERFOOD: Connected labs for empowering versatile engagement in radical food system transformation**
Riviou, K.
- 81 **Poster I.7 FoodSHIFT2030 Open school lab, Athens: Schools as sites of food experience and food system (FS) transformation**
Riviou, K.
- 83 **Poster I.8 FoodSHIFT pathways for the food system transformation**
Riviou, K.
- 86 **Poster I.9 Promoting nutritional literacy and sustainable food education: Initiatives involving schools in the city of Castelo Branco**
Pereira, F., Rodrigues, A., Lucas, A., Ferreira, C., Lopes, G., Santos, J.F., Espírito Santo, C., Brandão. I.
- 88 **Poster I.10 School gardens in Castelo Branco: Fostering nature connection and sustainability in children**
Lucas, A., Cristóvão, M., Beato, A., Brandão. I., Espírito Santo, C., Ferreira, C.

- 91 **Theme II – Local territorial challenges & strategies**
- Synopsis - Keynote Speakers**
- 91 **Climate change and ecosystem degradation: Desertification**
 Maria José Roxo
- 93 **Selected Oral Communications**
- 93 **Abstract II.1 Pre-treatment of olive plants with a
 biostimulant based on *ascophyllum nodosum* promote
 drought stress tolerance**
 Figueiras, R., Araújo, M., Santos, C., Dias, MC
- 95 **Abstract II.2 Collaborative strategies to improve the local
 food system in Setúbal**
 Silva, A. , Martins, A.
- 98 **Abstract II.3 Identification of putative biomarkers from apple
 ciders of different geographical origins based on volatilmic
 signature**
 Medina, S., Pereira, R., Câmara, J. S., Perestrelo, R.
- 100 **Abstract II.4 Modelling maritime pine forest distribution in
 Portugal under climate change scenarios**
 Alegria, C., Almeida, A. M., Roque, N., Fernandez, P., Ribeiro, M. M.
- 102 **Abstract II.5 Soil erosion in agricultural landscapes in the
 Mediterranean context: a case study in Portugal**
 Gonçalves, J. P. C. , Figueiredo, A., Nunes, A.

104 Posters**104 Poster II.1 *Ascophyllum nodosum* improves olive physiological performance and fruit size under water deficit conditions**

Figueiras, R., Araújo, M., Santos, C., Dias, MC

106 Theme III – Food loss & waste**Synopsis - Keynote Speakers****106 Between food waste measurement, measures and transition: Academic insights meeting business practice**

Hilke Bos Brouwers

110 Tackling the food waste - The role of ASAE

Pedro Nabais

113 CynaraMulching – A strategy for the development of biodegradable mulching films

Maria F. Duarte

117 Food waste in Castelo Branco: Design, implementation, tools

Beatriz Pereira , Nuno Silva

118 Circular olive oil: A circular system at the olive grove level, contributing to increase olive oil sustainability and soil health

Gonçalo da Cunha Ferreira

119 Saving food to save the planet

Victoria Albiñana

123 **Selected Oral Communications**

123 **Abstract III.1 Food waste mitigation as feed: Microbiological, chemical and nutritional characterisation**

Oliveira, J., Trindade, A., Murta, D., Barroso, H., Gonçalves, L., Bernardo, A., Brito, J., Assunção, R.

127 **Posters**

127 **Poster III.1 Greener technologies towards the valorization of olive oil pomace**

Silva, L. A. P., Pereira, R. N., Vicente, A. A.

129 **Poster III.2 Full plate: Meals without leftovers or waste**

Soares, S.S.

131 **Poster III.3 Effect of different bulking agents on the composting time of olive pomace**

Segatelli, A. B. M., Figueiredo, D., Figueiredo, T., Hernández, Z.

133 **Poster III.4 Zero waste dairy: Whey inclusion in bread, a newly developed product**

Rodrigues, A., Cristóvão, M., Baptista, C., Silveira, A., Paulo, L., Beato, H., Vasconcelos, V., Espírito Santo, C., Brandão, I.

136 **Poster III.5 Alternative approaches for the treatment of swine wastewater**

Esperanço, P., Rodrigues, C., Costa, R. P. R.

140 Theme IV – Endogenous genetic resources

Synopsis - Keynote Speakers

140 Wild endogenous genetic resources in the cultivar area:
Case studies

Maria Margarida Ribeiro

143 Selected Oral Communications

143 Abstract IV.1 *Ex situ* conservation of agri-food germplasm:
Case studies from the CULTIVAR project in Portugal

Baltazar, E., Lopes, T., Pedrosa, A., Correia, M., Duarte, D., Figueiredo, B.,
Caeiro, S., Cardoso, A., Paiva, H., Canhoto, J., Correia, S.

146 Abstract IV.2 *In vitro* establishment and molecular analysis
of the micrograft union formation in almond (*Prunus dulcis*
(mill.) D. A. Webb)

Lopes, T., Pedrosa, A., Caeiro, S., Paiva, H., Correia, M., Baltazar, E., Caeiro, A.,
Marum, L., Canhoto, J., Correia, S.

149 Abstract IV.3 *Lavandula* section *stoechas* from Beira Interior:
Chemical and morphological approaches

Domingues, J., Ribeiro, S., Coelho, M. T., Barroca, C., Canavarro, C.,
Gonçalves, J. C., Roque, N., Delgado, F.

152 Abstract IV.4 Understanding drought tolerance in cowpea
Vigna unguiculata (L.) Walp.: Insights from three Portuguese
landraces

Duarte, D., Figueiredo B., Pedrosa A., Lopes T., Baltazar, E., Correia, M., Dias,
M C., Canhoto, J., Correia, S.

- 155 **Abstract IV.5 Physiological and biochemical responses of *Prunus* spp. rootstocks during water stress recovery**
Correia, M. J., Soares, T., Lopes, T., Dias, M. C., Canhoto, J., Zuzarte, M., Correia, S.
- 157 **Abstract IV.6 Physicochemical and nutritional characterization of quince (*Cydonia oblonga*) from the Cova da Beira region**
Vasconcelos, V, Paulo, L., Lopes, G., Mota, M., Beato, H., Martins, A., Camelo, A., Rodrigues, A., Pitacas, I., Rodrigues, A., Resende, M., Cristóvão, M., Espírito Santo, C.
- 160 **Posters**
- 160 **Poster IV.1 Public perception of the biotechnological valorisation of cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp.)**
Duarte, D., Paula, A., Correia, S., Castro, P.
- 164 **Poster IV.2 Exploring the genetic diversity of cultivated quince tree varieties using SSR markers**
Pedrosa, A., Cardoso, A., Lopes, T., Baltazar, E., Teixeira, M., Rato, C., Canhoto, J., Correia, S.
- 166 **Poster IV.3 *Cistus ladanifer* micropropagation - preliminary results**
Coelho, M. T., Frazão, D. F., Barroca, C., Gonçalves, J. C.
- 169 **Poster IV.4 Exploring antimicrobial and anti-biofilm activities of agrofood resources from central Portugal**
Soares, M., Barreto, I., Camelo, A., Ramos, R., Riscado, A., Silveira, A., Espírito Santo, C., Brandão, I.

173 Theme V – Biodiversity, ecosystem function & services

Synopsis - Keynote Speakers

173 From the ground up: the role of soil biota in maintaining soil health as a path for sustainable food production

Carmen Vazquez Martin

175 Flowers, pollinators and pollination: What have we learned through CULTIVAR about pollination services in Beira Interior agroecosystems?

Sílvia Castro

179 Selected Oral Communications

179 Abstract V.1 Morphological, molecular, and genomic identification and characterisation of *Monilinia fructicola* in *Prunus persica* from Portugal

Baltazar, E., Rodrigues, S., Ares, A., Camelo, A., Brandão, I., Espírito Santo, C., Trovão, J., Garcia, E., Costa, J.

183 Abstract V.2 The “Cultivar Soil” project: Characterizing the health of an overlooked resource

Leitão, R., Bartz, M., Bento, M., Dornellas, L. F., Durán, J., Mendes, S., Nascimento, E., Cunha, L., Costa, J., Sousa, J. P.

186 Abstract V.3 Expanding the knowledge on the pollinator’s entomofauna in Beira Baixa through ecology-based and taxonomic studies

Gaspar, H., Siopa, C., Lopes, S., Loureiro, J., Castro, S.

- 189 **Abstract V.4 Long-read metabarcoding approach for diagnosis and epidemiology in genetically heterogeneous *Prunus* sp. orchards**
Garcia, E., Figueira D., Trovão, J., Barateiro, A., Ramos, C., Fragoso, P., Lopes, S., Camelo, A., Brandão, I., Veríssimo, A., Espírito - Santo, C., Costa, J.
- 192 **Abstract V.5 Farmers' perception of soil fauna and their ecosystem services**
Dudas, R. T. , Bartz, M. L. C., Paula, A., Marques, F., Martins, C., Cunha, L., Castro, P.
- 195 **Posters**
- 195 **Poster V.1 Carrot experiment: Documenting effects of bioactive compost extract on carrot germination rate, growth and yield**
Tkalec, D.
- 198 **Poster V.2 Fungal community in declining *Prunus persica* orchards located in the Cova da Beira region**
Baltazar, E., Figueira, D., Rodrigues, S., Trovão, J., Garcia, E., Costa, J.
- 201 **Poster V.3 The "BENCHMARKS" project: Building a European network for the characterisation and harmonisation of monitoring approaches for research and knowledge on soils**
BENCHMARKS Consortium, Cunha, L., Guilherme R., Batista V., Silva J.S., Bartz M., Leitão, R., Conceição, I.L., Costa, J., Sousa, J.P.
- 204 **Poster V.4 The mycobiota of *Prunus dulcis* in a gradient of diseases and practices**
Figueira, D., Garcia, E., Marrão, R., Santos, A., Espírito-Santo, C., Costa, J.
- 206 **Poster V.5 Two novel *Pseudomonas* species isolated from kiwifruit leaves**
Rodrigues, S., Figueira, D., Rodrigues, C., Espírito Santo, C., Trovão, J., Garcia, E., Costa, J.

- 209 **Poster V.6 Four novel bacterial taxa isolated from kiwifruit leaves**
Coelho, C., Bento, M., Figueira, D., Garcia, E., Espírito Santo, C., Trovão, J., Veríssimo, A., Tiago, I., Costa, J.
- 212 **Poster V.7 Floral studies and its importance for crop production on Beira Interior – sweet cherry as a case study**
Siopa, C., Loureiro, J., Castro, S.
- 214 **Poster V.8 Plant and pollinator communities in agricultural mosaics of the Beira Interior region – an annual assessment under the CULTIVAR project**
Siopa, C., Gaspar, H., Lopes, S., Loureiro, J., Castro, S.
- 216 **Poster V.9 Earthworms in different land uses in Beira Baixa region, Portugal**
Bartz, M., Bento, M., Cunha, L., Dornellas, L. F., Durán, J., Leitão, R., Mendes, S., Nascimento, E., Costa, J., Sousa, J. P.
- 219 **Poster V.10 Are farm to fork strategy goals reasonable and achievable? State of the art of Península de Setúbal's winegrowers**
Cachão, M., Chambel, A., Pinto, S.
- 221 **Theme VI – Ecosystem services as tools for resilience & territorial sustainability**
- Synopsis - Keynote Speakers**
- 221 **MOSAICO approach for the implementation of fire-smart landscapes**
Fernando Pulido

- 223 **Selected Oral Communications**
- 223 **Abstract VI.1 Co-creation of sustainable development strategies for the CULTIVAR study area, based on the ecosystem services framework**
Paula, A., Martinho, D., Roque, N., Fernandez, P., Bouça, M., Figueiredo A., Castro S., Castro P.
- 226 **Abstract VI.2 Demographic tendencies of the EU citizens' perception about the greening subsidies given to farmers**
Mata, F., Cano - Diaz, C., Jesus, M.
- 228 **Abstract VI.3 Farmers' perceptions of the ecosystem services provided by agriculture**
Castro, P., Marques, F., Martins, C., Cação, A., Bartz, M., Cunha, L., Paula, A.
- 231 **Abstract VI.4 Production of quality forage using technical itineraries, aiming at the conservation of the soil and reducing the application of phytopharmaceuticals – PRR project**
Carita, T., Simões, N., Carneiro, J., Conceição, L., J. Santos - Silva
- 233 **Abstract VI.5 How do territorial approaches contribute to the sustainability of agri-food systems? A systematic review**
Duarte, L., Méndez, M. R., Muñoz - Rojas, J.
- 235 **Abstract VI.6 Influence of land use and crop types on organic matter decomposition in Mediterranean agroecosystems: An assessment using the Teabag Index methodology**
Nascimento, E., Bartz, M., Bento, M., Dornellas, L. F., Durán, J., Leitão, R., Mendes, S., Cunha, L., Costa, J., Sousa, J. P.

- 238 Posters
- 238 **Poster VI.1 Demographic characteristics of the EU citizens supporting the protection of the environment and climate change tackling as the main social responsibilities of the EU farmers**
Mata, F., Pinto, R., Barros, D.
- 241 **Poster VI.2 Strategies to mitigate post-wildfire erosion in NE Portugal through optimized placement of contour barriers and sediment traps**
Okada, V. K., Figueiredo, T. de, Fonseca, F., Hernández, Z.
- 243 **Poster VI.3 GOOD-agroecology for weeds: Building an agroecological weed management network**
Tataridas, A., Costa, J., Sousa, J. P., Oliveira, R. S., Bartz, M., Leitão, R., Alves, J., Freitas, H.
- 245 **Poster VI.4 Integrating morphological and molecular approaches for assessing soil biodiversity in agroecosystems**
Dornellas, L. F., Mata, V. A., Bartz, M., Leitão, R., Nascimento, E., Mendes, S., Costa, J., Sousa, J. P., Cunha, L.
- 248 **Poster VI.5 Epidemiology and ecogenomics of regulated *Prunus* diseases in Cova da Beira**
Garcia, E., Figueira D., Trovão, J., Barateiro, A., Ramos, C., Fragoso, P., Lopes, S., Camelo, A., Brandão, I., Veríssimo, A., Espírito - Santo, C., Costa, J.
- 251 **Poster VI.6 Endophytic microbiomes of wild plants susceptible to *Xylella fastidiosa* infection**
Ramos, R., Camelo, A., Garcia, E., Rodrigues, S., Trovão, J., Brandão, I., Espírito Santo, C., Costa, J.

- 253 **Poster VI.7 Public perceptions of ecosystem services associated with the endogenous resources Pyrenean oak forests, chestnut groves, and cowpea cultivation**
Castro, P., Passos, I., Marques, F., Cação, A., Duarte, D., Alves, F., Figueiredo, A., Ribeiro, M. M., Correia, S., Paula, A.
- 256 **Poster VI.8 Influence of land use on soil aggregate stability in different agroecosystems from central Portugal**
Nascimento, E., Bartz, M., Bento, M., Dornellas, L. F., Durán, J., Leitão, R., Mendes, S., Cunha, L., Costa, J., Sousa, J. P.
- 259 **Poster VI.9 Pollination ecosystem services in the Beira Interior region: Variation across the landscape**
Castro, S., Gaspar, H., Paula, A., Martinho, D., Castro, P., Siopa, C., Loureiro, J.
- 261 **Poster VI.10 Animal pollinator crops produced in Portugal – assessment of pollinator dependence values using the PolLimCrop database**
Siopa, C., Carvalheiro, L. G., Castro, H., Loureiro, J., Castro, S.
- 264 **Theme VII – Food disruption: Making sustainable, healthy, delicious & appealing foods**
- Synopsis - Keynote Speakers**
- 264 **A journey from agrifood to lab-driven innovations**
Belén Blanco
- 266 **The nutritional, economic, and social potential of *Arbutus unedo* (strawberry tree) cultivation in the national context**
Rui Lopes
- 270 **A forest-to-fork... to industry: A short value chain circular economy solution for acorns from Iberian native forests**
Pedro Babo

- 271 **Yogurt making: Keeping up with demands for healthier concepts**
Susana Ramos and Ana Rodrigues
- 273 **The insect bioindustry as a link for a circular economy**
Gonçalo J. Costa
- 276 **Selected Oral Communications**
- 276 **Abstract VII.1 Food preservation by hyperbaric storage: The effect of pH on the inactivation of *Listeria monocytogenes***
Lima, V., Pinto, C., Saraiva, J.
- 279 **Abstract VII.2 Hyperbaric storage as a new methodology for preservation of egg white at room temperature**
Matos, G., Tavares, J., Ferreira, I., Saraiva, J. A.
- 282 **Abstract VII.3 Valorization of starch and tannins from acorns by high pressure and pulsed electric field technologies**
Castro, L. M. G., Alexandre, E. M. C., Saraiva, J. A., Pintado, M.
- 285 **Posters**
- 285 **Poster VII.1 Valorization of 'Rocha' pear residues for gummies development and optimization: A sustainable and healthy approach**
Silva, A., Pinheiro, R. F., Luís, L. S., Guarino, M. P., Rodrigues, A. C., Gaspar, M. C.
- 289 **Poster VII.2 A comparative analysis of two new plant-based drinks: Product development and sensorial evaluation**
Dias, S., Gonçalves, D., Pino - Hernández, E., Alves, M.
- 291 **Poster VII.3 Proposal of strawberry tree fruits (*Arbutus unedo* L.) as chutney main ingredient**
Oliveira, J. A., Ressureição S., Dias Santos S., Gomes F., Botelho G.

- 293 **Poster VII.4 Innovative approaches to meat analogue production: High moisture extrusion and the role of plant proteins**
Ribeiro, G., Piñero, M. Y., Acebes P., Blanco, B.
- 296 **Poster VII.5 Increasing microalgae biomass feedstock by valorizing wine gaseous and liquid residues**
Cachão, M., Chambel, A., Pinto, S.
- 298 **Poster VII.6 Shelf-life study of carob & chickpea plant-based drink pasteurized by ohmic heating**
Dias, S., Gonçalves, D., Pino - Hernández, E., Pereira, R., Alves, M.
- 300 **Poster VII.7 Novel foods with persimmon: Snacking the smart way**
Ramos, F., Pintado, C., Riscado, A., Beato, H., Resende, M., Delgado, F.
- 303 **Poster VII.8 Characterization of acorn flour from *Quercus pyrenaica***
Borges, M., Mateus, C. G. S., Barros, L., Vilas - Boas, M., Falcão, S. I.
- 305 **Poster VII.9 Nutritional profile of hazelnuts from Beira Interior: A comparative study of nine varieties**
Vasconcelos, V., Paulo, L., Beato, H., Pitacas, I., Moitinho, A., Espírito Santo, C.
- 308 **Poster VII.10 EQVEGAN project as a platform for innovation and strengthening skills on plant-based products in the food industry**
Botelho, G., Rodrigues, C., Ferreira, N., Rodrigues, I., Costa, R.
- 310 **Poster VII.11 Novel product using a native sheep breed (Merino da Beira Baixa)**
Cristóvão, C., Rodrigues, A., Silveira, A., Baptista, C., Beato, H., Vasconcelos, V., Paulo, L., Pitacas, I., Rodrigues, A. M., Espírito Santo, C., Brandão, I.

- 313 **Poster VII.12 Perceptions of insect consumption among the Portuguese population**
Cristóvão, M. , Rodrigues, A. M.
- 315 **Poster VII.13 PROMEDLIFE: Novel food products for Promotion of Mediterranean LIFEstyle and healthy diet**
Riviou, K.
- 317 **Poster VII.14 Modelling the inactivation of *Bacillus subtilis* by hyperbaric inactivation at room temperature – dependence of ph and nutrients' availability**
Pinto, C., Ganjeh, A., Saraiva, J.
- 319 **Poster VII.15 When the atypical cases attack - hyperbaric storage/inactivation as a targeting tool to inactivate *Alicyclobacillus acidoterrestris* and *Byssochlamys nivea* spores**
Pinto, C, Ganjeh, A., Saraiva, J.
- 322 **Poster VII.16 Hyperbaric food preservation as a methodology hurdling bacterial toxins production at room temperature**
Tavares, J., Matos, G., Pinto, C., Casal, S., Teixeira, P., Saraiva, J
- 325 **Poster VII.17 The health and sustainability impact assessment in the context of a new bioindustry: the one health concept in InsectERA**
Assunção, R. , Quinteiro, P.
- 327 **Poster VII.18 Chestnut conservation: Evaluation of the impact of different treatments on quality and conservation**
Cristóvão, M., Camelo, A., Riscado, A., Rodrigues, A., Silveira, A., Baptista, C., Beato, H., Paulo, L., Vasconcelos, V., Pereira, F., Brandão, I., Espírito Santo, C.

- 331 **Poster VII.19 Development and characterization of an orange dehydrated crispy snack**
Cristóvão, M., Camelo, A., Martins, A., Silveira, A., Riscado, A., Rodrigues, A., Baptista, C., Beato, H., Vasconcelos, V., Paulo, L., Pitacas, I., Rodrigues, A. M., Espírito Santo, C., Brandão, I.
- 335 **Theme VIII – Bioactive compounds, nutritional characteristics, food matrices & human health impact**
- Synopsis - Keynote Speakers
- 335 **From nature to products: Natural ingredients for the food industry**
Lillian Barros
- 337 **Water metabolic effects**
Maria João Martins
- 338 **Plant-derived foods as a valuable renewable bioresource of a plethora of impactful bioactive molecules**
José S. Câmara
- 340 **Risk assessment of *Cynara cardunculus* L. in PDO cheeses**
Luís Pinto de Andrade
- 342 **Selected Oral Communications**
- 342 **Abstract VIII.1 Design of edible coatings for deep frying fish products under oceans' bioeconomy concept**
Sousa, G., Ferreira - Dias, S., Tecelão, C., Alves, V.
- 345 **Abstract VIII.2 Uncovering the nutritional and biological properties of honeydew honey from *Quercus pyrenaica***
Falcão, S. I., Mouffok, K. M., Rodriguez - Flores, M. S., Escuredo, O., Seijo, M. C., Vilas - Boas, M.

- 348 **Abstract VIII.3 Grape pomace - a renewable natural source of added-value molecules with potential industrial applications**
Abreu, T., Jasmins, G., Bettencourt, C., Teixeira, J., Câmara, J. S., Perestrelo, R.
- 350 **Posters**
- 350 **Poster VIII.1 Physicochemical characterization of grilled chicken meat in 2 regions of Portugal, Lisbon and Alto Alentejo**
Serrano, M. C., Gonçalves, H., Louro, M. L., Mourato, M., Roseiro, L. C.
- 353 **Poster VIII.2 Nutraceutical composition of Tunisian bee pollen towards its geographical origin**
Sakhaoui, A., Rodriguez - Flores, M. S., Seijo, M. C., Mejri, M., Vilas - Boas, M., Falcão, S. I.
- 356 **Poster VIII.3 Microbiology of Portuguese cheeses**
Sorathiya, K.
- 358 **Poster VIII.4 Antioxidant activity of edible halophyte plants for application in lipid food matrices**
Antunes, M., Tecelão, C. , Alves, V., Ferreira - Dias, S.
- 361 **Poster VIII.5 Chemical composition and nutritional profile of *Atriplex halimus* leaves**
Zaouadi, N., Bensehaila, S., Lafri, I., Mostefa Sari, F., Mataoui, H.
- 363 **Poster VIII.6 Relation between eating habits, lipid profile and body mass index**
Cabral, E. , Coelho, P. , Rodrigues, F.
- 365 **Poster VIII.7 A preliminary study to minimize the enzymatic browning in minimally processed potatoes**
Ferreira, J., Augusto, A., Silva, S., Pinheiro, J.

- 368 **Poster VIII.8 Assessment of decoction treatment on *Fucus vesiculosus* and *Ulva* sp. macroalgae**
Caetano, M., Ganhão, R., Pinheiro, J.
- 371 **Poster VIII.9 A new life in citrus lemon peels: Potential of different extracts as antifungal agents**
Rolo, J., Gama, A. R., Domingues, J., Delgado, F., Gonçalves, J. C., Palmeira - de - Oliveira, R., Martinez - de - Oliveira, J., Palmeira - de - Oliveira, A.
- 374 **Poster VIII.10 Occurrence of 2- and 3-MCPD esters and glycidyl esters in food supplements based on fish and microalgae oils**
Oliveira, A. P. F., Gomes, F. M. L., Milani, R. F., Vicente, E., Tfouni, S. A., Bragotto, A. P. A.
- 377 **Poster VIII.11 Monitoring the occurrence and levels of patulin in commercial apple juices by μ -QuEChERS/LC-ESI/MS approach**
Câmara, J. S., Fernandes, P., Barros, N., Perestrelo, R.
- 379 **Poster VIII.12 Assessment of the quality of milk from small ruminants used in the production of cheeses with PDO (chemical composition and somatic cells)**
Beato, H., Resende, M., Cristóvão, M., Caseiro, C., Veloso, A., Riscado, A., Brandão, I., Espírito Santo, C., Rodrigues, A. M.
- 381 **Poster VIII.13 Coffee industry by-products as a source of bioactive compounds**
Esperanço, P., Areias, B., Ferreira, D., Veloso A. C. A., Henriques, M., Rodrigues, C., Campos, L.
- 385 **Theme IX – Gut microbiota: a key player connecting nutrition & health**

Synopsis - Keynote Speakers

- 385 **Diet in health and disease: the role of microbiota**
Ana Faria
- 388 **Microplastics and microbiota: is there an interaction?**
Diogo Pestana
- 390 **Using probiotics to engage the natural microbiota back to health**
Vitor Cabral
- 398 **YourBiome: Where do we stand on fecal microbiota transplant**
Cláudia Marques
- 399 **Exploring the interconnection between edible plant microbiome and gut microbiome and its impact on human health**
Wisnu Adi Wicaksono
- 401 **Selected Oral Communications**
- 401 **Abstract IX.1 Blueberry leaves biomass: A prebiotic with gut immunomodulatory potential in type 2 diabetes**
Vieira, P., Nunes, S., Preguiça, I., Ferreira, C., Alves, A., Almeida, J., Alves, V., Sá, H., Reis, F., Viana, S.
- 405 **Abstract IX.2 A blueberry leaves-based nutraceutical improves gut immune imbalance and central impairments in experimental multiple sclerosis**
Ferreira, C., Palavra, F., Preguiça, I., Alves, A., Vieira, P., Nunes, S., Jesus, Â., Almeida, J., Alves, V., Sá, H., Reis, F., Viana, S.
- 409 **Abstract IX.3 The role of trimethylamine on intestinal fatty acid absorption in caco-2 cells**
Rodrigues, C., Ismael, S., Barreiros - Mota, I., Castela, I., Almeida, M. J., Santos, G., Calhau, C., Rocha, J. C., Faria, A., Araújo, J. R.

Welcome to the Farm to Fork: Our Food, Our Health, Our Future Congress

The «Farm to Fork: our food, our health, our future» congress, held in Castelo Branco from November 16th to 18th, 2023, brought together national and international experts in agri-food and nutrition & health areas. The event addressed the latest issues in the farm-to-fork journey, with a strong focus on sustainability and climate resilience.

The congress featured a comprehensive scientific program complemented by thematic workshops and site visits. It was an outgrowth of collaborative networks and research projects developed under the CULTIVAR and FUSILLI projects.

This event served as a platform for knowledge sharing, learning, and networking, fostering collaboration and innovation in the sector, bringing together researchers, scientists, policymakers, agrifood and nutrition professionals, students, and the agrifood industry.

LIST OF ORGANIZERS**Organizing Committee:**

Alexandra Camelo, CATAA
Alexandra Lucas, Municipality of Castelo Branco
Ana Riscado, CATAA
Ana Silveira, CATAA
Ana Rodrigues, CATAA
Bruno Marçal, InovCluster
Cátia Baptista, CATAA
Célia Ferreira, Municipality of Castelo Branco
Christophe Espírito Santo, CATAA
Filomena Pereira, CATAA
Helena Beato, CATAA
Inês Barreto, CATAA
Inês Brandão, CATAA
Inês Cabaço, InovCluster
Isabel André, CATAA
Luísa Paulo, CATAA
Mário Cristóvão, CATAA
Miguel Lucas, CATAA
Natanael Santos, CATAA
Patrícia Coelho, Municipality of Castelo Branco and CATAA
Rodrigo Rato, CATAA
Sara Martins, CATAA
Vanessa Vasconcelos, CATAA

Scientific Committee:

Albano Figueiredo, UC
Célia Ferreira, Municipality of Castelo Branco
Patrícia Coelho, Municipality of Castelo Branco and CATAA
Filomena Pereira, CATAA
Ana Faria, NMS-UNL
Christophe Espírito Santo, CATAA
Helena Freitas, UC
Inês Barreto, CATAA
Inês Brandão, CATAA
Joana Costa, CFE-UC
João Loureiro, UC
Julia Pinedo, CARTIF
Lillian Barros, CIMO
Margarida Ribeiro, ESA-IPCB
Paula Castro, CFE-UC
Sandra Correia, InnovPlantProtect CoLAB
Sílvia Castro, CFE-UC

Opening Remarks

Leopoldo Rodrigues

Mayor of Castelo Branco and President of CATAA'S Board of Directors, Portugal

Over three fulfilling days, we have highlighted Castelo Branco's role in sustainability and food production. Despite challenging climate conditions, including extreme temperatures and prolonged droughts, our region excels in producing high-quality, diverse food products, which we have been able to showcase, such as Castelo Branco and Alcains' cheeses; olive oil, since our region has the largest olive grove north of the Tagus River; and even honey, although its production has been facing challenges due to the Asian hornet. Additionally, we have been promoting local meat production, including the "Merino da Beira Baixa" sheep, known for its quality.

Castelo Branco is also rich in cultural and environmental assets, including traditional embroidery and the works of Manuel Cargaleiro, as well as the UNESCO Creative City designation.

CATAA plays a crucial role in advancing agricultural and agri-food research, collaborating with universities and companies to improve our products. This congress gathered a diverse group of scientists, researchers, and agricultural professionals, highlighting our region's achievements and dedication to the agri-food sector, enhancing local products, whenever possible. The discussions, presentations, and focus on agri-food issues were valuable for both our municipality and the broader region, ensuring continued progress and development.

Mary Kenny

Food Safety & Consumer Protection Officer, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), Italy

As we look at the challenges facing global food systems, sustainability must be central to our efforts. The FAO's Strategic Framework for 2022-2031 focuses on four key areas: better nutrition, production, environment, and quality of life. We must support smallholders, women, and youth in rural areas while driving innovation and digitalization.

One major issue is nutrition and food security. We're seeing a 'nutrition transition,' especially in urban areas, where people are consuming more processed foods, refined sugars, and animal-source products, and there is a persistence of malnutrition despite progress, with rising obesity rates and dietary accessibility issues. Therefore, it is essential to promote nutrition-sensitive agriculture and access to healthy diets.

Climate change, biodiversity loss, and resource scarcity are placing immense pressure on our natural resources. We must manage land, water, and forests sustainably to reduce emissions and protect ecosystems, and reduce the impact of climate changes.

Recent shocks, such as the COVID-19 pandemic and conflicts, have disrupted food supply chains and worsened food security. There is a need to strengthen shorter value chains and increase social protection for vulnerable populations and local governments play a vital role in achieving such solutions.

Lastly, the One Health approach is crucial. Human, animal, and environmental health are interconnected, and by addressing these together, we can build resilient, sustainable food systems. There should be a focus on environmental sustainability, encouraging a transition to climate-resilient food systems that reduce greenhouse gas emissions and address food loss and waste through circular economy models.

CULTIVAR - Network for sustainable development and innovation in the agri-food sector

Joana Costa

CFE-UC, Portugal

The CULTIVAR R&D program was developed to address the challenges faced by low-density areas in the Central Region of Portugal, characterized by vulnerability to climate change and pressure on natural resources. Responding to these challenges requires a holistic approach that integrates environmental, social, and economic dimensions in order to valorize the region's endogenous genetic resources and sustainably boost the agri-food sector. CULTIVAR was a strategic and innovative project led by the University of Coimbra, in partnership with the Pedro Nunes Institute, the Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar and the Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, CULTIVAR aimed to enhance regional expertise and foster collaboration between scientific institutions and the agri-food sector, focusing on the creation of environmental, economic, and social value through interdisciplinary innovation. It addressed the critical challenges identified in the region's agri-food sectors by promoting coordinated actions in knowledge and skills sharing. CULTIVAR emphasized the importance of identifying landscape units as testing areas for adaptation and mitigation strategies, thereby increasing resilience and promoting sustainable development.

A Consultative Forum has been established, bringing together public and private entities in the agri-food sector to facilitate coordinated knowledge exchange and strategic planning. This forum plays a crucial role in regional development by promoting cohesion within rural communities, addressing the challenges of rural depopulation and ageing, and actively contributing to improving the quality of life.

The research carried out under CULTIVAR was structured around understanding biophysical, social, and economic potential of the territory and characterizing the endogenous genetic resources to identify those

with high potential for valorization. By focusing on ecosystem services and the sustainability of these resources, CULTIVAR sought to innovate in agri-food products and enhance the region's competitive advantage. The development of the iCultivar platform (<https://icultivar.pt/plataforma>) was a key component, facilitating data management and decision-making by providing accessible, advanced analytical tools to stakeholders in the agri-food sector.

CULTIVAR identified 190 endogenous genetic resources and selected 10 key species, such as cherry, chestnut, and lavender, for detailed chemical, physical, and sensory analysis to explore new applications, including functional foods and nutraceuticals. Conservation efforts included establishing protocols for in vitro propagation and conducting studies to support the sustainable management of these resources, ensure their availability for future breeding programs and improve crop resilience.

Recognizing the importance of socio-environmental interactions, CULTIVAR engaged local communities through participatory workshops to integrate traditional knowledge into research and valorization strategies. This community involvement aimed to ensure that the outcomes of CULTIVAR benefited both the environment and the local economy. By identifying threats to ecosystem services and genetic resources, CULTIVAR developed targeted action plans, including in situ and ex situ conservation measures, to protect these valuable resources.

The impact of the CULTIVAR R&D program is evident in the increased resilience of agro-environmental systems, improved resource management, and strengthened rural economies. By fostering partnerships and applying its research findings to new initiatives, CULTIVAR continues to contribute to the sustainable development of the Central Region's agri-food sector, leaving a lasting legacy for regional development.

FUSILLI - Fostering the Urban food System Transformation through Innovative Living Labs Implementation

Julia Pinedo Gil

CARTIF and FUSILLI project coordinator, Spain

The FUSILLI project, an ambitious initiative aimed at transforming the food system, has brought together a diverse array of stakeholders, including researchers, policymakers, and professionals from the agrifood and nutrition sectors. FUSILLI stands for “Fostering Urban food System Transformation through Innovative Living Labs Implementation,” and it focuses on creating sustainable, resilient, and inclusive food systems. Central to the project’s methodology are the 12 Living Labs (LL), which serve as experimental environments in different cities across Europe. These Living Labs are crucial for testing and implementing innovative solutions tailored to local needs and challenges, thereby fostering a holistic approach to food system transformation.

A key outcome of the FUSILLI project has been the establishment of the Knowledge Community Platform (KCP), a collaborative digital space designed to facilitate the exchange of knowledge, experiences, and best practices among stakeholders. The KCP plays a pivotal role in ensuring that the insights gained from the Living Labs are disseminated widely and that the solutions developed are scalable and adaptable to different contexts. The creation of this platform underscores the project’s commitment to fostering a global community dedicated to sustainable food system transformation.

The outputs of the FUSILLI project are diverse and impactful, ranging from innovative food production and distribution models to new policies promoting sustainable consumption. These developments are not only critical for addressing current challenges such as climate change, resource scarcity, and public health but also for shaping a future food system that is resilient and equitable. The project has highlighted the importance of a

systemic approach, integrating technological, social, and policy innovations to create a food system that supports the well-being of both people and the planet.

As the world faces increasing pressures on its food systems, the work done through the FUSILLI project sets a precedent for future initiatives. The importance of continuing to innovate and collaborate cannot be overstated, as these efforts will be vital in building a sustainable food future. The project's legacy lies in its demonstration of the power of collective action and the potential of urban food systems to lead the way in creating healthier, more sustainable societies.

CONGRESS FARM TO FORK

Our food, our health, our future

16-17-18 NOV 23

CINE-TEATRO AVENIDA
CASTELO BRANCO, PORTUGAL

FARM TO FORK STRATEGY

- SOIL AND PLANT HEALTH
- SEEDS FOR THE FUTURE
- ECOSYSTEM SERVICES
- FOOD LOSS AND WASTE
- URBAN FOOD SYSTEMS
- FOOD INNOVATION
- FOOD MATRICES
- FOOD AND HEALTH
- GUT MICROBIOTA

SCAN ME
NATIONAL AND EUROPEAN FUNDING

**OPENING SESSION BY
FOOD AND AGRICULTURE
ORGANIZATION OF THE
UNITED NATIONS (FAO)**

EVENT IN PT/EN

ORGANIZED BY:

OFFICIALLY SUPPORTED BY:

Com o Alto Patrocinio de Sua Excelência
Under the High Patronage of the
President of the Portuguese Republic.

O Presidente da República

CONGRESS
FARM TO FORK
Our food, our health, our future

The **"Farm to Fork: our food, our health, our future"** congress will bring together renowned national and international experts in the fields of agri-food and nutrition, to address the latest issues affecting the journey from farm to fork.

Sustainability, a key element for a green transition and climate resilience, will permeate all discussions.

In addition to the main scientific program, the **"Farm to Fork"** congress will offer a wide range of thematic workshops and site visits.

The **"Farm to Fork"** congress is an outgrowth of the collaborative networks and research projects developed under the **CULTIVAR** and **FUSILLI** projects, joining specialists and researchers who will present results from both projects with other researchers working in the **Farm to Fork** strategy.

We envision this Congress as a platform for knowledge sharing, learning, and networking opportunities between researchers, scientists, policy makers, agrifood and nutrition professionals, students, and the agrifood industry.

Join us at the **"Farm to Fork: our food, our health, our future"** congress in Castelo Branco from **November 16th to 18th, 2023** and become an active participant in this innovative and enriching journey.

We are counting on the participation of all those interested in making a difference in the sector and contributing to the creation of a healthier and more sustainable, inclusive and innovative food system.

And of course, this comes with a better future for all!

CONGRESS

FARM TO FORK

Our food, our health, our future

DAY 1 (16 NOV 23)

09:00 WELCOMING SESSION

- **LEOPOLDO RODRIGUES**
Mayor of Castelo Branco and President of CATAA'S Board of Directors, Portugal
- **MARY KENNY**
Food Safety & Consumer Protection Officer, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), Italy

09:45 SEEDING INNOVATION & HARVESTING SUCCESS

- **"CULTIVAR" PROJECT CASE STUDY**
By Helena Freitas (UC, University of Coimbra, UNESCO Chair and CULTIVAR PI, Portugal)
- **"FUSILLI" PROJECT CASE STUDY**
By Julia Pinedo Gil (CARTIF and FUSILLI project coordinator, Spain)

10:15 NATIONAL & EUROPEAN FUNDING

MODERATOR: CARMO MARTINS
COTHN: Operative and Technological Center for Horticulture, Portugal

- **MARIA JOÃO FERNANDES**
ANI: National Innovation Agency, Portugal
- **PEDRO VIEIRA**
CCDR-C: Center's Regional Coordination and Development Commission, Portugal
- **ANA SEREJO**
DRAP: Centro: Regional Directorate of Agriculture and Fisheries of the Center, Portugal

11:00 COFFEE-BREAK

11:15 THEME I: FROM GLOBAL TO LOCAL: CURRENT CHALLENGES FOR THE SUSTAINABLE TRANSFORMATION OF URBAN FOOD SYSTEMS

MODERATOR: JULIA PINEDO GIL
CARTIF and FUSILLI project coordinator, Spain

- **RADICALLY RE-THINKING THE FOOD-WATER-ENERGY NEXUS IN THE WAKE OF THE "SUMMER OF DISCONTENT 2023"**
By Baha Kuban (Demir Energy, Turkey)
- **HOW CAN THE TRANSFORMATION OF URBAN FOOD SYSTEMS BE GOVERNED?**
By Einar Braathen (Oslo Metropolitan University, Norway)
- **URBAN AGRICULTURE AND ITS ROLE IN URBAN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT**
By Patricia Hernandez (City of Rome, Italy)
- **THE CONTRIBUTION OF URBAN FOOD POLICIES TO THE AGENDA 2030 THROUGH SDGS TARGETS AND INDICATORS.**
By Andrea Calori (ESto, Italy)
- **GAPS BETWEEN FOOD-RELATED POLICIES AND THEIR IMPLEMENTATION: WHAT WE KNOW ABOUT THE PORTUGUESE CONTEXT**
By Cecilia Delgado (UNL: Nova University Lisbon, Portugal)
- **ROUND TABLE DISCUSSION**
- **SELECTED ORAL COMMUNICATIONS**
- **ABSTRACT 1.1 - TRANSFORMING THE LOCAL FOOD SYSTEM IN SETÚBAL WITH LOCAL AUTHORITIES**
By Alexandra Silva (The K-Evolution Association)
- **ABSTRACT 1.2 - CITY AGRICULTURAL SYSTEMS, INNOVATIVE ALTERNATIVES FOR SUSTAINABILITY TRANSITIONS: EVIDENCE FROM CASE STUDIES IN FRANCE**
By Guisem Boukharta (University of Valladolid)

CONGRESS

FARM TO FORK

Our food, our health, our future

13:00 LUNCH

- HAMBURGER OFFER**
By CAMPICARN

(50 MIN)

13:40 PARALLEL WORKSHOP
"CREATING ABUNDANCE"
(A STORY ABOUT INCLUSIVE AGROFORESTRY)

By ALLAN SCHWARZ (MEZIMBITTE FOREST CENTRE, MOZAMBIQUE)

14:00 **THEME I: REAL EXAMPLES FROM CITIES** (SHORT VIDEOS)

14:30 **THEME II: LOCAL TERRITORIAL CHALLENGES & STRATEGIES**

MODERATOR: ALBANO FIGUEIREDO
(UC, Portugal) & JOANA COSTA (University of Coimbra, Portugal)

- CLIMATE CHANGE AND ECOSYSTEM DEGRADATION: DESERTIFICATION**
By Maria José Roxo (UNL, Portugal)
- SELECTED ORAL COMMUNICATIONS**
- ABSTRACT II.1 - PRE-TREATMENT OF OLIVE PLANTS WITH A BIOSTIMULANT BASED ON ASCOPHYLLUM NODOSUM PROMOTE DROUGHT STRESS TOLERANCE**
By Rui Pedro Figueiras (UC)
- ABSTRACT II.2 - COLLABORATIVE STRATEGIES TO IMPROVE THE LOCAL FOOD SYSTEM IN SETÚBAL**
By António José Martins (LIDERE / IPBeja)
- ABSTRACT II.3 - IDENTIFICATION OF PUTATIVE BIOMARKERS FROM APPLE CIDERS OF DIFFERENT GEOGRAPHICAL ORIGINS BASED ON VOLATILOMIC SIGNATURE**
By Rosa Perestrelo (University of Madeira and Madeira Chemistry Research Centre)

- ABSTRACT II.4 - MODELLING MARITIME PINE FOREST DISTRIBUTION IN PORTUGAL UNDER CLIMATE CHANGE SCENARIOS**
By Cristina Alegria (IPCB)
- ABSTRACT II.5 - SOIL EROSION IN AGRICULTURAL LANDSCAPES IN THE MEDITERRANEAN CONTEXT: A CASE STUDY IN PORTUGAL**
By Albano Figueiredo (UC)

16:00 COFFEE-BREAK

16:15 **THEME III - FOOD LOSS & WASTE**

MODERATOR: MARY KENNY
(Food Safety & Consumer Protection Officer, FAO, Italy)

- BETWEEN MEASURING - MEASURES - TRANSITIONS: ACADEMIC INSIGHTS MEETING BUSINESS PRACTICE**
By Hilke Bos Brouwers (WUR: Wageningen University & Research, Netherlands)
- TACKLING THE FOOD WASTE - THE ROLE OF ASAE**
By Pedro Nabais (ASAE: Economic and Food Safety Authority, Portugal)
- CYNARAMULCHING - A STRATEGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF BIODEGRADABLE MULCHING FILMS**
By Fátima Duarte (CEBAL: Alentejo Agricultural and Agri-Food Biotechnology Center, Portugal)
- FOOD WASTE IN CASTELO BRANCO: DESIGN, IMPLEMENTATION, TOOLS**
By Beatriz Pereira (EVGX: Technologies) and Nuno Silva (Castelo Branco's Municipalized Services) (Portugal)
- CIRCULAR OLIVE OIL: A CIRCULAR SYSTEM AT THE OLIVE GROVE LEVEL, CONTRIBUTING TO INCREASE OLIVE OIL SUSTAINABILITY AND SOIL HEALTH**
By Gonçalo da Cunha Ferreira (EntoGreen, Portugal)

CONGRESS
FARM TO FORK
Our food, our health, our future

• SAVING FOOD TO SAVE THE PLANET

By Victoria Albiñana (*Too good to go, Iberia*)

• ROUND TABLE DISCUSSION

• SELECTED ORAL COMMUNICATIONS

• ABSTRACT III.1 - FOOD WASTE MITIGATION AS FEED: MICROBIOLOGICAL, CHEMICAL AND NUTRITIONAL CHARACTERIZATION

By Joana Oliveira (*Egas Moniz School of Health & Science*)

• THEME III - ZERO WASTE DAIRY: WHY INCLUSION IN BREAD, A NEWLY DEVELOPED PRODUCT

By Ana Rodrigues (*SCHREIBER FOODS*)

19:30 SOCIAL MOMENT WITH "ORQUESTRA VIOLA BEIROA"

PARALLEL WORKSHOP (30 MIN)

17:30 "VALORIZATION OF ENDOGENOUS RESOURCES THROUGH QUALITY CERTIFICATES FOR AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS AND FOODSTUFFS"

BY CELSO DOS REIS LOPES (DRAP CENTRO)

PARALLEL WORKSHOP (1 HOUR 30 MIN)

17:30 "FOODSHIFT PATHWAYS: EDUCATIONAL STRATEGIES FOR THE FOOD SYSTEM TRANSFORMATION"

BY KATERINA RIVIOU (ELLINOGERMANIKI ACOGI, GREECE), GISELA OLIVEIRA & JOANA VIEIRA (CIÊNCIA VIVA, PORTUGAL)

18:00 POSTER PRESENTATION AND PRIZES (THEME I, II & III)

• THEME I - CIRCULAR ECONOMY IN THE URBAN FOOD SYSTEM: THE ITALIAN CASE STUDY OF TURIM LIVING LAB FOCUS ON THE CIRCULAR COOKING EXPERIMENTATION

By ALESSANDRA SAVINA (*University of Gastronomic Sciences of Pollenzo, Italy*)

• THEME II - ASCOPHYLLUM NODOSUM IMPROVES OLIVE PHYSIOLOGICAL PERFORMANCE AND FRUIT SIZE UNDER WATER DEFICIT CONDITIONS

By Rui Pedro Figueiras (*UC*)

CONGRESS FARM TO FORK

Our food, our health, our future

DAY 2 (17 NOV 23)

09:00 **THEME IV: ENDOGENOUS GENETIC RESOURCES**

MODERATORS: SANDRA CORREIA (InnovPlantProtect CoLab, Portugal) & **FERNANDA DELGADO** (Instituto Politécnica de Castelo Branco, Portugal)

- **WILD ENDOGENOUS GENETIC RESOURCES IN THE CULTIVAR AREA: CASE STUDIES**
By Maria Margarida Ribeiro (IPCB, Portugal)
- **SELECTED ORAL COMMUNICATIONS**
 - **ABSTRACT IV.1 - EX SITU CONSERVATION OF AGRI-FOOD GERMLASM: CASE STUDIES FROM THE CULTIVAR PROJECT IN PORTUGAL**
By Elsa Baltazar (Center for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associated Laboratory, CFE, UC)
 - **ABSTRACT IV.2 - IN VITRO ESTABLISHMENT AND MOLECULAR ANALYSIS OF THE MICROGRAFT UNION FORMATION IN ALMOND (PRUNUS DULCIS (MILL.) D. A. WEBB)**
By Tércia Lopes (UC)
 - **ABSTRACT IV.3 - LAVANDULA SECTION STOECHAS FROM BEIRA INTERIOR: CHEMICAL AND MORPHOLOGICAL APPROACHES**
By Joana Domingues (Centro de Biotecnologia de Plantas da Beira Interior)
 - **ABSTRACT IV.4 - UNDERSTANDING DROUGHT TOLERANCE IN COWPEA VIGNA UNGUICULATA (L.) WALP.: INSIGHTS FROM THREE PORTUGUESE LANDRACES**
By Daniela Duarte (CFE, UC)
 - **ABSTRACT IV.5 - PHYSIOLOGICAL AND BIOCHEMICAL RESPONSES OF PRUNUS SPP. ROOTSTOCKS DURING WATER-STRESS RECOVERY**
By Mariana Correia (UC)
 - **ABSTRACT IV.6 - PHYSICOCHEMICAL AND NUTRITIONAL CHARACTERIZATION OF QUINCE (CYDONIA OBLONGA) FROM THE COVA DA BEIRA REGION**
By Vanessa Vasconcelos (Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar)

(1 HOUR)

09:30 **PARALLEL WORKSHOP
"LOW COST SCIENCE VIDEO: FROM PRODUCTION TO COMMUNICATION"**

BY MIGUEL FERREIRA (UC, PORTUGAL)

10:30 **COFFEE-BREAK**

10:45 **THEME V: BIODIVERSITY, ECOSYSTEM FUNCTION & SERVICES**

MODERATORS: JOÃO LOUREIRO (UC, Portugal) & **MARIE BARTZ** (UC, Municipal Center for Culture and Development, Center for Regenerative and Organic Agriculture)

- **FROM THE GROUND UP: THE ROLE OF SOIL BIOTA IN MAINTAINING SOIL HEALTH AS A PATH FOR SUSTAINABLE FOOD PRODUCTION**
By Carmen Vazquez Martin (Wageningen University & Research, Netherlands)
- **FLOWERS, POLLINATORS AND POLLINATION: WHAT HAVE WE LEARNED THROUGH CULTIVAR ABOUT POLLINATION SERVICES IN BEIRA INTERIOR AGROECOSYSTEMS?**
By Sílvia Castro (UC, Portugal)
- **SELECTED ORAL COMMUNICATIONS**
 - **ABSTRACT V.1 - MORPHOLOGICAL, MOLECULAR, AND GENOMIC IDENTIFICATION AND CHARACTERISATION OF MONILINIA FRUCTICOLA IN PRUNUS PERSICA FROM PORTUGAL**
By Elsa Baltazar (CFE, UC)
 - **ABSTRACT V.2 - THE "CULTIVAR SOIL" PROJECT: CHARACTERIZING THE HEALTH OF AN OVERLOOKED RESOURCE**
By Ricardo Leitão (CFE, UC)

CONGRESS

FARM TO FORK

Our food, our health, our future

- **ABSTRACT V.3 - EXPANDING THE KNOWLEDGE ON THE POLLINATOR'S ENTOMOFUNA IN BEIRA BAIXA THROUGH ECOLOGY-BASED AND TAXONOMIC STUDIES**
By Hugo Gaspar (UC)
- **ABSTRACT V.4 - LONG-READ METABARCODING APPROACH FOR DIAGNOSIS AND EPIDEMIOLOGY IN GENETICALLY HETEROGENEOUS PRUNUS SP. ORCHARDS**
By Eva Garcia (Pedro Nunes Institute, Laboratory for Phytopathology)
- **ABSTRACT V.5 - FARMERS' PERCEPTION OF SOIL FAUNA AND THEIR ECOSYSTEM SERVICES**
By Marie Bartz (UC)

- **MOSAICO APPROACH FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF FIRE-SMART LANDSCAPES**
By Fernando Pulido (University of Extremadura, Spain)
- **SELECTED ORAL COMMUNICATIONS**

 - **ABSTRACT VI.1 - CO-CREATION OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES FOR THE CULTIVAR STUDY AREA, BASED ON THE ECOSYSTEM SERVICES FRAMEWORK**
By Anabela Paula (CFE, UC)
 - **ABSTRACT VI.2 - DEMOGRAPHIC TENDENCIES OF THE EU CITIZENS' PERCEPTION ABOUT THE GREENING SUBSIDIES GIVEN TO FARMERS**
By Fernando Mata (CISAS, Polytechnic of Viana do Castelo)
 - **ABSTRACT VI.3 - FARMERS' PERCEPTIONS OF THE ECOSYSTEM SERVICES PROVIDED BY AGRICULTURE**
By Paula Castro (CFE, UC)
 - **ABSTRACT VI.4 - PRODUCTION OF QUALITY FORAGE USING TECHNICAL ITINERARIES, AIMING AT THE CONSERVATION OF THE SOIL AND REDUCING THE APPLICATION OF PHYTOPHARMACEUTICALS - PRR PROJECT**
By Teresa Carita (National Institute of Agricultural and Veterinary Research, I.P. (INIAV))
 - **ABSTRACT VI.5 - HOW DO TERRITORIAL APPROACHES CONTRIBUTE TO THE SUSTAINABILITY OF AGRI-FOOD SYSTEMS? A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW**
By Luis Duarte (MED - Mediterranean Institute for Agriculture, Environment and Development, University of Évora)
 - **ABSTRACT VI.6 - INFLUENCE OF LAND USE AND CROP TYPES ON ORGANIC MATTER DECOMPOSITION IN MEDITERRANEAN AGROECOSYSTEMS: AN ASSESSMENT USING THE TEABG INDEX METHODOLOGY**
By Eduardo Nascimento (UC)

(30 MIN)

11:00 PARALLEL WORKSHOP
"VERMICOMPOSTING: HOW IT WORKS AND ITS BENEFITS"

BY RAFAEL CRISÓSTOMO AND PEDRO SANTOS (HUMIVERSO)

(30 MIN)

11:30 PARALLEL WORKSHOP
"ENSURING FOOD SAFETY FROM FARM TO FORK"

BY MARIA DE JESUS TAVARES AND ANA FREITAS (ASAE)

12:15 SPONSOR MOMENT

12:45 LUNCH

14:00 **THEME VI: ECOSYSTEM SERVICES AS TOOLS FOR RESILIENCE & TERRITORIAL SUSTAINABILITY**

MODERATOR: PAULA CASTRO (UC, Portugal) & **JOÃO PAULO CARNEIRO** (IPCB, Portugal)

(30 MIN)

14:30 PARALLEL WORKSHOP
"TASTING THE FUTURE - FOOD TRENDS 2024"

BY SUSANA CAIO (INOVCLUSTER)

CONGRESS

FARM TO FORK

Our food, our health, our future

(30 MIN)

15:00 PARALLEL WORKSHOP
"INNOVATION AT THE
CENTER OF INVESTMENT IN
PDR2020 AND MAR2020"

BY PAULO MORENTO (DRAP CENTRO)

15:30 **THEME VII: FOOD
DISRUPTION: MAKING
SUSTAINABLE, HEALTHY,
DELICIOUS & APPEALING
FOODS**

MODERATOR: PEDRO ASSUDE (*Gestor de
Inovação NovaDelta*)

- **A JOURNEY FROM AGRIFOOD TO LAB-DRIVEN INNOVATIONS**
By Belén Blanco (*CARTIF, Spain*)
- **THE NUTRITIONAL, ECONOMIC, AND SOCIAL POTENTIAL OF ARBUTUS UNEDO (STRAWBERRY TREE) CULTIVATION IN THE NATIONAL CONTEXT**
By Rui Lopes (*Medranho & Canela and Polytechnic of Leiria, Portugal*)
- **A FOREST-TO-FORK...TO INDUSTRY: A SHORT VALUE CHAIN CIRCULAR ECONOMY SOLUTION FOR ACORNS FROM IBERIAN NATIVE FORESTS**
By Pedro Babo (*Landratech, Portugal*)
- **YOGURT MAKING: KEEPING UP WITH DEMANDS FOR HEALTHIER CONCEPTS**
By Susana Ramos and Ana Rodrigues (*Schreiber Foods, Portugal*)
- **THE INSECT BIOINDUSTRY AS A LINK TO A CIRCULAR ECONOMY**
By Gonçalo J. Costa (*Cricket Farming Co., University of Lisbon, Portugal*)

- **ROUND TABLE DISCUSSION**
- **SELECTED ORAL COMMUNICATIONS**

16:30 PARALLEL WORKSHOP
"SAVING SEEDS FOR THE
FUTURE"

BY MICHA GROENEWEGEN (CO-FOUNDER SEMENTES VIVAS)

17:00 **COFFEE-BREAK**

17:15 **POSTER PRESENTATION
AND PRIZES** (THEME IV, V, VI & VII)

- **THEME IV - PUBLIC PERCEPTION OF THE BIOTECHNOLOGICAL VALORISATION OF COWPEA (VIGNA UNGUICULATA (L) WALP.)**
By Daniela Duarte (*UC*)
- **THEME V - EARTHWORMS IN DIFFERENT LAND USES IN BEIRA BAIXA REGION, PORTUGAL**
By Marie Bartz (*UC*)
- **THEME VI - INTEGRATING MORPHOLOGICAL AND MOLECULAR APPROACHES FOR ACCESSING SOIL BIODIVERSITY IN AGROECOSYSTEMS**
By Luisa Dornella (*CFE*)
- **THEME VII - HYPERBARIC FOOD PRESERVATION AS A METHODOLOGY HURDING BACTERIAL TOXINS PRODUCTION AT ROOM TEMPERATURE**
By Jéssica Tavares (*University of Aveiro*)

17:30 ***SITE VISIT TO CATAA
LABORATORIES & PILOT
UNITS** (BUS TRANSFER-BOOK YOUR FREE SEAT IN ADVANCE, LIMITED TO 50 PEOPLE)

PARALLEL WORKSHOP
"FOOD INNOVATIONS & PRODUCT
DEVELOPMENT"

BY MÁRIO CRISTOVÃO (CATAA)

(30 MIN)

FARM TO FORK
our food, our health, our future

CATAA
CENTROS DE APOIO
TÉCNOLOGICO AO AGRICULTOR

FC FRUIT CONTROL EQUIPMENTS

WORKSHOP

INOVAÇÕES TECNOLÓGICAS EM CONSERVAÇÃO DE HORTOFRUTÍCOLAS DE UMA FORMA MAIS SAUDÁVEL E SABOROSA

GRÁTIS

17 NOVEMBRO'23

14H30

CCCCB
CENTRO DE CULTURA CONTEMPORÂNEA
CASTELO BRANCO

PARCEIRO OFICIAL:

COM O APOIO DE:

CONGRESS
FARM TO FORK
Our food, our health, our future

DAY 3 (18 NOV 23)

09:00 **THEME VIII: BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS, NUTRITIONAL CHARACTERISTICS, FOOD MATRICES & HUMAN HEALTH IMPACT**

MODERATOR: TIAGO BRANDÃO (Super Bock Group, Portugal)

- **FROM NATURE TO PRODUCTS: NATURAL INGREDIENTS FOR THE FOOD INDUSTRY**
By Lillian Barros (Mountain Research Centre (CIMO) and Institute Polytechnic of Bragança, IPB, Portugal)
- **WATER METABOLIC EFFECTS**
By Maria João Martins (University of Porto and I3S, Portugal)
- **PLANT-DERIVED FOODS AS A VALUABLE RENEWABLE BIORESOURCE OF A PLETHORA OF IMPACTFUL BIOACTIVE MOLECULES**
By José S. Câmara (University of Madeira and Madeira Chemistry Research Centre, Portugal)
- **RISK ASSESSMENT OF CYNARA CARDUNCULUS L. IN PDO CHEESES**
By Luís Pinto de Andrade (IPCB, Portugal)
- **ROUND TABLE DISCUSSION**
- **SELECTED ORAL COMMUNICATIONS**
 - **ABSTRACT VIII.1 - DESIGN OF EDIBLE COATINGS FOR DEEP FRYING FISH PRODUCTS UNDER OCEANS' BIOECONOMY CONCEPT**
By Gabriela Sousa (LEAF)
 - **ABSTRACT VIII.2 - UNCOVERING THE NUTRITIONAL AND BIOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF HONEYDEW HONEY FROM QUERCUS PYRENAICA**
By Soraia Falcão (CIMO and IPB)
- **ABSTRACT VIII.3 - GRAPE POMACE - A RENEWABLE NATURAL SOURCE OF ADDED-VALUE MOLECULES WITH POTENTIAL INDUSTRIAL APPLICATIONS**
By Rosa Perestrelo (University of Madeira and Madeira Chemistry Research Centre)

10:00 **PARALLEL WORKSHOP "THE FASCINATING LIVE UNDER OUR FEET AND WHERE TO FIND IT"**
By JOSÉ PAULO SOUSA AND MARIE BARTZ (UC, PORTUGAL)

10:30 **COFFEE-BREAK**

10:45 **THEME IX: GUT MICROBIOTA: A KEY PLAYER CONNECTING NUTRITION & HEALTH**

MODERATOR: CONCEIÇÃO CALHAU (NMS: Nova Medical School, UNL, Portugal)

- **DIET IN HEALTH AND DISEASE: THE ROLE OF MICROBIOTA**
By Ana Faria (Comprehensive Health Research Center (CHRC), NMS, UNL, Portugal)
- **MICROPLASTICS AND MICROBIOTA: IS THERE AN INTERACTION?**
By Diogo Pestana (Center for Health Technology and Services Research (CINTESIS@RISE), Portugal)
- **USING PROBIOTICS TO ENGAGE THE NATURAL MICROBIOTA BACK TO HEALTH**
By Vitor Cabral (Gubienkian Science Institute, Portugal)
- **YOURBIOME: WHERE DO WE STAND ON FECAL MICROBIOTA TRANSPLANT**
By Cláudia Marques (CINTESIS@RISE, Portugal)

CONGRESS
FARM TO FORK
Our food, our health, our future

- **EXPLORING THE INTERCONNECTION BETWEEN EDIBLE PLANT MICROBIOME AND GUT MICROBIOME AND ITS IMPACT ON HUMAN HEALTH**
By Wisnu Adi Wicaksono (*Institute of Environmental Biotechnology, Graz University of Technology, AUSTRIA*)
- **ROUND TABLE DISCUSSION**
- **SELECTED ORAL COMMUNICATIONS**
 - **ABSTRACT IX.1 - BLUEBERRY LEAVES BIOMASS: A PREBIOTIC WITH GUT IMMUNOMODULATORY POTENTIAL IN TYPE 2 DIABETES**
By Pedro Vieira (*ICBR, UC*)
 - **ABSTRACT IX.2 - A BLUEBERRY LEAVES-BASED NUTRACEUTICAL IMPROVES GUT IMMUNE IMBALANCE AND CENTRAL IMPAIRMENTS IN EXPERIMENTAL MULTIPLE SCLEROSIS**
By Carolina Ferreira (*ICBR, UC*)
 - **ABSTRACT IX.3 - THE ROLE OF TRIMETHYLAMINE ON INTESTINAL FATTY ACID ABSORPTION IN CACO-2 CELLS**
By Catarina Rodrigues (*CHRC, NOVA Medical School*)

12:30 CLOSING SESSION

- By **ELVIRA FORTUNATO** (*Ministry of Science, Technology and Higher Education*)

12:45 POSTER PRESENTATION AND PRIZES (THEME VIII & IX)

- **THEME VIII - ASSESSMENT OF THE QUALITY OF MILK FROM SMALL RUMINANTS USED IN THE PRODUCTION OF CHEESES WITH PDO (CHEMICAL COMPOSITION AND SOMATIC CELLS)**
By Helena Beato (*CATAA*)

13:15 LUNCH

14:30 *SITE VISIT TO LOCAL PRODUCER "QUINTA DA ALDEIA"
(BUS TRANSFER-BOOK YOUR FREE SEAT IN ADVANCE, LIMITED TO 50 PEOPLE)

14:30 PARALLEL WORKSHOP "NUTRITION ACROSS THE LIFESPAN" (3 HOURS)
BY FILOMENA PEREIRA (CATAA, PORTUGAL)

CONGRESS
FARM TO FORK
Our food, our health, our future

AGRICULTURAL SECTOR MAGAZINE

voz do campo
Revista do Setor Agrário

ASSOCIATED SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL

 frontiers
in Nutrition

FOR MORE INFORMATION:
FARMTOFORK@CATAA.PT
OR VISIT OUR WEBSITE
www.cataa.pt/farm-to-fork/

ORGANIZED BY:

OFFICIALLY SUPPORTED BY:

CONGRESS
FARM TO FORK
Our food, our health, our future

GOLD

FRUIT
CONTROL
EQUIPMENTS

SILVER

Schreiber

BRONZE

Dias de Sousa
INSTRUMENTAÇÃO MANUTENÇÃO E SERVIÇOS, S.A.

NORMAX

NANTA

ERT

anipla

SPECANALÍTICA
Equipamentos Laboratoriais

syngenta.

avantor™

Fertiberia
TECH

ADDITIONAL SPONSORSHIP

POSTER AWARDS BY:

ADDITIONAL SUPPORT

ORGANIZED BY

OFFICIALLY SUPPORTED BY

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE

Comissão Europeia
Under the High Patronage of the
President of the Portuguese Republic

© Presidente da República

Theme I – From global to local: Current challenges for the sustainable transformation of urban food systems

Synopsis - Keynote Speakers

Radically re-thinking the food-water-energy nexus in the wake of the “Summer of Discontent 2023”

Author

Baha Kuban – Demir Energy, Turkey

Citation

Kuban, B., Radically re-thinking the food-water-energy nexus in the wake of the “Summer of Discontent 2023”.

As the Planet's incorrigibly destructive social and economic system lumbers along a climatically uncharted path, "*well outside the safe operating space for humanity*" as described by the Stockholm Resilience Center's Planetary Health Check 2023, '*...never before in its history, has humanity built a civilization that had at its disposal so many different technologies to monitor, measure and predict its own collapse - yet has been so incapable of doing anything about it...*'

The "polycrisis"; a convergence of global environmental, financial, political, social crises, aggregated by multiple decades of neoliberal governance and corporate financialisation, has introduced a double jeopardy - even in affluent economies- of food system vulnerability (ability to sustainably renew itself) and food system security (ability for the population to feed itself). The accelerated influx of complex financial products whose fictitious value, is linked to fixed and ordinary assets of the agro-food supply chains, trigger further rounds of re-commodification and rebundling. Which, facilitated by neo-liberalizing states simultaneously withdrawing public systems of support at the same time as stimulating private-risk financialization, explode as food shortages and price rises. The far-reaching tremors of these processes in agriculture and food are a topic of research but reversing them is a topic of politics! Can cities and municipalities act as strategic entry points for developing practices of transformative socio-economic change in the agri-food realm, mobilising a broad range of social forces, democratizing institutions and decision-making power on the way, as seen in the myriad of urban struggles and examples in energy, water, health care, transportation and waste? That is the question...

How can the transformation of urban food systems be governed?

Author

Einar Braathen – Oslo Metropolitan University, Norway

Citation

Braathen, E. How can the transformation of urban food systems be governed?

Urban food systems can be an entry point for significant changes towards sustainability. Their implementation needs to be supported by planned and radical transformation, moving away from the traditional top-down governance models that hinder innovation. In Europe, municipalities are local organizations that can play a crucial role in combining different governance principles –administration (public sector), service providers (private sector), and councilors (civil society). In addition, they can support the formation of living labs, which represent open innovation ecosystems in real-life environments, and that encourage participation and sharing results publicly, fostering experimentation and collaboration among different stakeholders. The FUSILLI project involves municipalities and living labs from 12 European cities and aims at creating a dynamic and transdisciplinary knowledge community that integrates citizen science and experiences. Notably, Rome, one of the cities included in this project, is a large city with more than 2 million inhabitants and with a significant agricultural presence (almost one third of its territory), that has seen a rise in citizen driven food movements, including over 2,600 farm cooperatives and 200 urban community gardens. In 2019, a committee was formed to develop a food policy for Rome, leading to the establishment of a council in 2022 that mobilized over 250 organizations and 5,000 individuals. This movement reflects a growing trend in Italy towards collaborative food policy development, which will potentially inspire and influence other European countries.

Urban agriculture and its role in urban sustainable development

Author

Patricia Hernandez – City of Rome, Italy

Citation

Hernandez, P. Urban agriculture and its role in urban sustainable development.

Urban Agriculture is not new: throughout history it has played an essential role in the urban food system. Since the earliest towns developed, humans have grown food in urban and peri-urban spaces. Urban Agriculture has evolved over the centuries in response to changing urban needs: new farming models have come into existence, and motivations to grow food in an urban context have correspondingly altered. Today, Urban Agriculture is not only valued for its food production, but also for the diversity of economic, social and ecological benefits it can provide. The Horizon 2020 project EFUA (European Forum on Urban Agriculture) running from 2020-2024, will unlock Urban Agriculture's potential to deliver Sustainable Development Goals and support the mission of achieving better networking, better knowledge, better deployment and better policies in this field. The project brings together a network of researchers, practitioners and citizens from all over Europe to create the Urban Agriculture Forum to increase stakeholder participation and dialogue around Europe. EFUA will also reach out to new stakeholder groups from around the world, including in Less Developed Countries (LDCs), thereby developing a truly global vision for Urban Agriculture.

Project EFUA: <http://www.efua.eu/>

The contribution of urban food policies to the Agenda 2030 through SDGS targets and indicators

Author

Andrea Calori – ESTà, Italy

Citation

Calori , A. The contribution of urban food policies to the Agenda 2030 through SDGS targets and indicators.

This talk will highlight the complex nature of urban food systems and how its policies can play a crucial role in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), integrated in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, through integration of multiple elements of sustainability into a cohesive strategy, particularly at the local governance level.

Urban food systems are interconnected with various sectors, and local authorities often have fragmented, sectorized policies. The challenge lies in shifting from a sectorial approach to a more integrated one that acknowledges and manages the complexity of these systems by improving the ability to align urban food policies with the SDGs.

The SDGs provide a diffuse yet essential narrative that can guide sustainability efforts. Urban food policies, if aligned with the SDGs, can be a significant contributor to sustainable development, offering measurable outcomes.

Local governance must, therefore, embed food system complexities into their policies. This shift can facilitate the integration of urban food policies into broader sustainability agendas.

Initiatives like FUSILLI aim to contribute to overall sustainability by demonstrating how food policies can directly address the SDGs and be effective at the local level.

Gaps between food-related policies and their implementation: What we know about the Portuguese context

Author

Cecília Delgado – Nova University Lisbon, Portugal

Citation

Delgado, C. Gaps between food-related policies and their implementation: What we know about the Portuguese context.

My presentation will be grounded on three of my latest publications: 1) Lack of Governance Capacity in Food Systems: Lessons from the Portuguese Initiatives.

RIVAR 2023 10(28), 195-214. <https://doi.org/10.35588/rivar.v10i28.5298> ; 2) Exploring agriculture, climate change, and food planning nexus: Where does territorial planning stands? Cuadernos De Investigación Geográfica 2023, 50(1), 109–121. <https://doi.org/10.18172/cig.5679>, and, 3) The role of land as the central piece to sustainable food systems: Lessons learned from Portugal national food-related policies, Geography and Sustainability, Volume 4, Issue 1,2023, Pages 84-90, ISSN 2666-6839, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geosus.2023.01.001>.

I will explore the gaps between, for one hand, a well-intentioned body of policies still missing a systemic vision on how to bring together all the food-related

policies and disciplines. And, on the other hand, a promising scenario of initiatives however rarely conceived as part of a food governance strategy.

To close, I will conclude with a single recommendation - in order to bridge the gap between the multiple entry points of the food system there is a need to create awareness and dissemination of robust information and data, among all the actors and sectors of the food system in decision-making. I believe that this awareness campaign must be made by national and local networks such as the Portuguese NGO – HYPERLINK "<https://acsa.org/>"Alimentar Cidades Sustentáveis Associação (Feeding Sustainable Cities in English).

Selected Oral Communications

Abstract I.1 Transforming the local food system in Setúbal with local authorities

Author

V. Silva, A – The K-Evolution Association, Setúbal, Portugal

Martins, A. – Instituto Politécnico de Beja, Beja, Portugal

Citation

V. Silva, A., Martins, A. Transforming the local food system in Setúbal with local authorities.

The present study provides a systematization of the approach developed in the context of the PLACE project: Transforming the local food system in Istanbul and Setúbal with local authorities (LAs), belonging the place program that aim to exchange for local authorities and civil society. The present work has a general objective to transform and improve local, agroecological short supply chains together with LAs. The main objectives are: i) identify the actors and the current situation in the local food systems (producers and local authorities and consumers); ii) establish networks for collaboration between the local actors; iii) increase the capacity of local authors and iv) increase participation of consumers and producers to local strategies and policies. In general, the project is connected to SDGs 2, 11 and 12 to achieve food security and improve nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture, make the cities and human settlements more inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable.

The methodology applied was based in partnership networks that sharing knowledge, strengthening democratic participation and governance, promote decision making in collaborative and participatory way, where is a continuous monitoring and evaluation, to update the reformulation and improvements. In the begin of the process was created 2 Teams: a Local Implementation Team formed by technicians, farmers and community and a Local Start Team, an interdisciplinary with techniques from local authorities.

The results of the survey applied to producers, consumers and restaurant owners, show that is necessary: a better use of natural resources (water, soil, energy); ability to adapt and respond to climate change (pests, floods and droughts), an investment in technical support (training and specialized support) and helping the producers to promote economic viability activity, such as, support for marketing circuits, modernizing production systems and products.

The study also shows the main challenges and strong points.

Acknowledgments

Association The K-Evolution and Bugday would like to thank the THE:PLACE program, jointly managed by ALDA and MAD and funded by Stiftung Mercator for supporting this work. We also would like to thank the producers involved in the study, the voluntary team (LIT) and the interdisciplinary team created in Setubal Municipality and the logistic support from Palmela Municipality.

References

European Commission, 2020, 'Farm to Fork Strategy: For a fair, healthy and environmentally-friendly food system', https://ec.europa.eu/food/system/files/2020-05/f2f_action-plan_2020_strategy-info_en.pdf, accessed on 7th Nov. 2021.

Horstink, L.; Schwemmlin, K. and Encarnaço, M. (2023). Food systems in depressed and contested agro-territories: Participatory Rural Appraisal in Odemira, Portugal. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*. DOI: 10.3389/fsufs.2022.1046549.

Waity, J., Farrell, M.; Eaton, V. A case study accessing the feasibility of a local Food Label among producers and consumers. *Assessing the Feability of a Local Food Label*. Sociation Vol.20, Issue 1, ISSN 1542-6300. Macedo, P. (2021). Municipalities in Transition: Experimenting a New Governance System for Tackling Climate Change. *Handbook of Climate Change Management*, pp 2459-2502.

Abstract I.2 Role of UAEU (thematic) partnership on food in supporting cities as catalyst for local food systems transformation

Author

Triboi, R. – LE:NOTRE Institute, Wageningen, Netherlands; URBACT, Paris, France

Rotaru, I. – URBACT, Paris, France

Pasarel, A. – USAMV, Cluj, Romania

Citation

Triboi, R., Rotaru, I., Pasarel, A. Role of UAEU (thematic) partnership on food in supporting cities as catalyst for local food systems transformation.

Innovative social practices are flourishing within food systems, bringing forth a range of advancements such as short food chains, community-supported agriculture, waste reduction strategies, urban farming, and creative public procurement initiatives. Cities and regions are assuming significant roles in driving these innovations, forging partnerships between public entities, local entrepreneurs, and civil society organizations. The role of the Thematic Food Partnership within the Urban Agenda for the European Union (EU) can be particularly pertinent in facilitating and amplifying these efforts.

A persistent gap remains between national and EU-level policies and these grassroots social innovations. Top-down policies, oriented towards standardization and competition for efficiency gains, often inadvertently lead to a loss of diversity. It is crucial for the EU to shift its focus and support the

richness of diverse approaches rather than promoting uniformity. Embracing the shift towards relocalisation and reterritorialization of food systems should be seen as an opportunity to create fairer and more sustainable models. The EU can play a vital role by facilitating these transitions, fostering collective learning, establishing networks of local actors, and ensuring the widespread sharing of the most successful innovations.

This paper underlines the necessity for more efficient multilevel governance at the EU level, focusing on how the Thematic Food Partnership in the Urban Agenda can support cities in developing integrated food policies. By showcasing successful case studies, including short food chains and urban farming initiatives, this paper illustrates the transformative potential of localized and community-driven approaches. The Thematic Food Partnership in the Urban Agenda stands as a relevant platform to consolidate and amplify these localized efforts, aligning with broader sustainability goals, and fostering a more diverse, equitable, and sustainable food landscape across the EU.

Acknowledgments

EUI, DG REGIO, IPES-food, ICLEI, Eurocities, EC

References

Triboi, R., Rotaru, I., & Pasărel, A. (2023). Ex-ante assessment of the “Food” thematic area under the Urban Agenda for the EU.

AESOP4FOOD Wiki. (n.d.). <https://wiki.landscapeportal.org>

IPES-Food. (n.d.). Long Food Movement. <http://www.ipes-food.org/pages/LongFoodMovement> SAPEA, Science Advice for Policy by European Academies. (2020). A sustainable food system for the European Union.

Manganelli, A. (2020). Realising local food policies: A comparison between Toronto and the Brussels-Capital Region’s stories through the lenses of reflexivity and colearning. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*. [Include the complete citation information here.]

Vaarst, M., Getz Escudero, A., Chappell, M. J., Brinkley, C., Nijbroek, R., Arraes, N. A. M., ... Halberg, N. (2018). Exploring the concept of agroecological food systems in a city-region context. *Agroecology and Sustainable Food Systems*, 42(6), 686-711. DOI: 10.1080/21683565.2017.1365321. erlin: SAPEA. <https://doi.org/10.26356/sustainablefood>

Abstract I.3 City agricultural systems, innovative alternatives for sustainability transitions: Evidence from case studies in France

Author

Boukharta, O. F. – Universidad de Valladolid, Palencia, Spain

Sauvée, L. – Institut Polytechnique UniLaSalle, Rouen, France

Fabri, F. – Institut Polytechnique UniLaSalle, Rouen, France

Chico - Santamarta, L. – Universidad de Valladolid, Palencia, Spain

Navas - Gracia, L. M. – Universidad de Valladolid, Palencia, Spain

Citation

Boukharta, O.F., Sauvée, L., Fabri, F. Chico-Santamarta, L., Navas-Gracia, L.M. City agricultural systems, innovative alternatives for sustainability transitions: Evidence from case studies in France.

The importance of urban agriculture and gardening in cities is growing and has been recognized by various initiatives such as Milan's Urban Food Pact [1]. There is also a growing awareness of the significant contribution that a link with nature makes to our mental health and well-being [2]. Indeed, urban agriculture is a form of farming that aims to ensure food security, maintain urban ecosystem services, and improve quality of life [3]. In addition, the use and transformation of abandoned areas is proving to be an appropriate way of creating new green spaces [4]. This study focuses on the analysis of urban agriculture practices in the city of Rouen, France, where an assessment

will be made of the distribution of the value created by the implementation, procedure and planning of urban agricultural practices, together with an evaluation of the benefits they bring in economic, social and environmental terms. The work consisted of interviews with stakeholders involved in the operation, including farmers, citizens, project managers and department head representatives, along with site visits for a better analysis and evaluation of each of the cases. This work employs an empirical analysis using NVivo software, which is now widely recognized for its efficiency in processing data related to qualitative research [5]. The findings show that the two social cases evaluated are both keen to ensure a better green environment for city residents, giving them the opportunity to reconnect people with nature while offering them the chance to grow their own fresh food and improve their health and well-being. Furthermore, the results show that there are a number of similarities between the different entities in terms of objectives and activities performed, along with a number of differences in terms of their structure, governance and management and the distribution of tasks.

Acknowledgments

The present work is related to FUSILLI Project, which is based on food and natural resources. This project is funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No.101000717. FUSILLI mainly focuses on supporting cities to facilitate their transition to more sustainable food systems, in accordance with FOOD2030 priorities. <https://fusilli-project.eu/>

References

- [1] Pact, M. U. F. P. (2015). Milan urban food policy pact..
- [2] Bailey, A., & Kingsley, J. (2020). Connections in the garden: Opportunities for wellbeing. *Local Environment*, 25(11-12), 907-920.

[3] Soga, M., Cox, D. T., Yamaura, Y., Gaston, K. J., Kurisu, K., & Hanaki, K. (2017). Health benefits of urban allotment gardening: Improved physical and psychological well-being and social integration. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 14(1), 71.

[4] Gros-Balthazard, M. (2018). *L'avenir productif des territoires industriels: analyse de la diversité des trajectoires économiques locales* (Doctoral dissertation, Université Grenoble Alpes).

[5] Zamawe, F. C. (2015). The implication of using NVivo software in qualitative data analysis: Evidence-based reflections. *Malawi Medical Journal*, 27(1), 13-15.

Posters

Poster I.1 Circular economy in the urban food system: The Italian case study of the Turin Living Lab focused on the circular cooking experimentation

Author

Savina, A. – University of Gastronomic Sciences of Pollenzo, Pollenzo (Bra, Piedmont), Italy

Fassio, F. – University of Gastronomic Sciences of Pollenzo, Pollenzo (Bra, Piedmont), Italy

Citation

Savina, A., Fassio, F. Circular economy in the urban food system: The Italian case study of the Turin Living Lab focused on the circular cooking experimentation.

In today's scenario, the current linear models of food production, transformation and consumption are increasingly leading to complex environmental, social and cultural repercussions that affect urban, peri-urban and rural areas, compromising human health and the balance of ecosystems. The design disciplines are improving theoretical and operational tools and approaches capable of addressing, in a transdisciplinary way, the multiple challenges that link the agri-food system to a series of critical issues that

can be defined as real wicked problems: soil degradation, biodiversity loss, increasing production of waste and emissions, weakening of local know-how, reduction of valuable relationships. Within these disciplines, Systemic Design and Circular Economy act as effective planning methods to model and apply sustainable systemic solutions aimed at reducing the environmental footprint, generating community development and progress, strengthening the identity and culture of territories and creating sustainable economic flows. The application of these tools has been effectively pursued within the Italian case study of the City of Turin (Piedmont, Italy), included in the broader framework of the European project FUSILLI (*Fostering the Urban Food System Transformation through Innovative Living Labs Implementation*). The joint development and coordination of a Food Living Lab, located on the urban outskirts of the *Mirafiori Sud* district, welcomed the systemic design of circular solutions applied to the urban catering sector. Specifically, the *University of Gastronomic Sciences of Pollenzo* (Bra, Cuneo), in collaboration with the *Fondazione Comunità di Mirafiori* and *Orti Generali*, is the protagonist of the design of a Circular Restaurant and a Circular Kiosk, today able to serve the public the results of a sustainable cuisine, capable of valorizing the less noble parts of food, reducing waste and restoring the value of local culture through the use of local resources and ancient traditions.

Acknowledgments

For the realisation of the Circular Restaurant and Circular Kiosk project, for the design, experimentation and testing of circular recipes, we would like to thank the experts from the Pollenzo FoodLab (Carol Povigna, Nahuel Buracco, Matteo Bigi) and all the staff of the Locanda nel Parco Social restaurant, part of the Fondazione Comunità di Mirafiori, who have enthusiastically welcomed and metabolised the project in its context of stories, people, support and solidarity.

References

- Bistagnino, L. *Systemic Design—Designing the Productive and Environmental Sustainability*; Slow Food Editore: Bra, Italy, 2011.
- Buchanan, R. Wicked Problems in Design Thinking. *Des. Issue.s* 1992, 8, 5–21.
- Calori, A.; Dansero, E.; Pettenati, G; and Toldo, A. Urban food planning in Italian cities: a comparative analysis of the cases of Milan and Turin. *Agroecology and Sustainable Food Systems*. 2017, 41, 8, 1026-1046.
- Ellen Macarthur Foundation (FME). Towards the Circular Economy: Economic and Business Rationale for an Accelerated Transition. Available online: <https://emf.thirdlight.com/link/x8ay372a3r11-k6775n/@/preview/1?o> (accessed on 15 September 2023).
- Fassio, F.; Cionchi, E.; Tondella, A. *The Circular Economy for Food in Future Cities. Good Practices That Define Smart Food. Agathón*|Int. J. Archit. Art Des. 2020, 8, 244–253.
- Manzini, E.; and Meroni, A. Catalyzing social resources for sustainable changes – Social innovation and community centred design, in Vezzoli, C., Kohtala, C. and Srinivasan, A. (eds), *Product - Service System Design for Sustainability*, Greenleaf Publishing, Sheffield, 2014, 362-379.
- Parente, M. and Sadini, C. *D4T – Design per i territori – Approcci, metodi, esperienze*, List Editore, Trento, Italy, 2019.
- Soma, T.; Wakefield, S. The emerging role of a food system planner: Integrating food considerations into planning. *J. Agric. Food Syst. Community Dev.* 2011, 2, 53–64.

Poster I.2 Urban food system transitions (FUSILLI project): The gender approach in Barcelona city

Author

Ramirez - Santos, Ana G – Leitat Technological Center, Terrassa, Barcelona, Spain

[Yacoub, Cristina](#) – Leitat Technological Center, Terrassa, Barcelona, Spain

Rivera - Ferre, Marta G. – INGENIO, CSIC, UPV, Valencia, Spain

Citation

Ramirez-Santos, Ana G, Yacoub, Cristina, Rivera-Ferre, Marta G. Urban food system transitions (Fusilli project): The gender approach in Barcelona city.

Based on the multilevel perspective (MLP) (Geels, F; 2002) we present a case study of the food system in Barcelona city. In a context where the city hall is making a great effort transitioning towards a healthy and sustainable urban food system. How is this opening new opportunities to agroecological initiatives? Are the ones existing/emerging gender-oriented? Which role gender is playing in the actions and actors involve in the process? These are some of the questions this research addresses.

Then, how agroecology and just transition frameworks are addressed in the context of the urban food system transitions in BCN city is assessed based on the MLP categories of Niches, Regime and Landscape. First, we identify and analyze actors and actions towards just food system transitions in the different categories in Barcelona. Second, we identify how aspects of gender

perspective and feminist approach are addressed within Niches, Regime and Landscape interactions.

The research design contemplated data collection and snowball sampling and we conducted 20 interviews with actors related to food initiatives (Niches) that are part of food systems transformation processes, and related to production, transformation, conservation, consumption activities, among others. The results obtained show diverse gender patterns (positive and negative) within the food system process of transitions and allowed us to identify gender aspects within the transitions categories and how to address them based on a just transition.

Acknowledgments

We acknowledge the European project Fusilli (GA N°101000717) for providing the facilities to complete our research. We thank BCN Niches for kindly spending the time with and allow us to meet and interview them. We thank Iván Carceller Sánchez who assisted in conducting the interviews, transcription and anonymisation process.

References

Geels, F., & Raven, R. (2006). Non-linearity and Expectations in Niche-Development Trajectories: Ups and Downs in Dutch Biogas Development (1973-2003). *Technol. Anal. Strateg. Manag.*, 18 (3-4), 375–392.

Geels, F. W. (2002). Technological transitions as evolutionary reconfiguration processes: a multi-level perspective and a case-study. *Research Policy*, 31(8–9), 1257–1274. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333\(02\)00062-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333(02)00062-8)

Geels, F. W. (2010). Ontologies, socio-technical transitions (to sustainability), and the multi-level perspective. *Research Policy*, 39(4), 495–510. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RESPOL.2010.01.022>

Geels, F. W. (2011). The multi-level perspective on sustainability transitions: Responses to seven criticisms. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 1(1), 24–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EIST.2011.02.002>

Geels, F. W. (2019). Socio-technical transitions to sustainability: a review of criticisms and elaborations of the Multi-Level Perspective. In *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability* (Vol. 39, pp. 187–201). Elsevier B.V. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2019.06.009>

Geels, F. W., & Schot, J. (2007). Typology of sociotechnical transition pathways. *Research Policy*, 36(3), 399–417. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RESPOL.2007.01.003>

Anderson, C., Bruil, J., Chappell, M. J. (Michael J., Kiss, C., & Pimbert, M. P. (2020). *Agroecology now! : transformations towards more just and sustainable food systems.*

Anderson, C., Bruil, J., Chappell, M. J., Kiss, C., & Pimbert, M. P. (2019). From Transition to Domains of Transformation: Getting to Sustainable and Just Food Systems through Agroecology. *Sustainability* 2019, Vol. 11, Page 5272, 11(19), 5272. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU11195272>

Tribaldos, T., & Kortetmäki, T. (2022). Just transition principles and criteria for food systems and beyond. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 43, 244–256. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EIST.2022.04.005>

Tschersich, J., & Kok, K. P. W. (2022). Deepening democracy for the governance toward just transitions in agri-food systems. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 43, 358–374. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EIST.2022.04.012>

Poster I.3 An elaboration of role of alternative food initiatives in urban- peri urban linkages for short food supply chain

Author

Emel Karakaya Ayalp – İzmir Democracy University, Turkey
Sevim Pelin Öztürk – İzmir Democracy University, Turkey
Feral Geçer Sargin – İzmir Democracy University, Turkey

Citation

Ayalp, E.K., Öztürk, S.P., Sargin, F.G. An elaboration of role of alternative food initiatives in urban- peri urban linkages for short food supply chain.

This study aims to argue the role of alternative food initiatives (AFIs) to understand, analyze and re-investigate urban, peri-urban, rural areas and peri-urban and rural interlinkages with respect to specific characters and specifications for an integrated sustainable urban food system. The findings are depending on the one of the tasks of FUSILLI* Horizon 2020 project.

This study explains (1) the spatial concentration and distribution of AFIs in 12 FUSILLI cities, (2) the food supply chains of 12 FUSILLI cities and (3) a bottom-up policy and action formulation to strengthen short food supply chain (SFSC) in 12 FUSILLI cities.

The study depends on big data collection and formulation of all the AFIs in 12 European cities, the analyzing food supply chain (FSC) in these cities and the coordination of policy and action formulation by cities through the results of analysis of AFI and FSC in cities. The results show that cities have unique character, potentials and requirements which provide lessons to be learned to strengthen SFSC in Europe.

Poster I.4 Smart cities through urban short supply chains of food

Author

Mata, F. – CISAS – Center for Research and Development in Agrifood Systems and Sustainability, Instituto Politécnico de Viana do Castelo. Rua Escola Industrial e Comercial Nun'Álvares, Viana do Castelo, Portugal

Dos - Santos, M. – Escola Superior de Comunicação Social, Instituto Politécnico de Lisboa, Campus de Benfica do IPL, Lisboa, Portugal; IUL DINÂMIAÇET, ISCTE- Instituto Universitário de Lisboa, Avenida das Forças Armadas, Lisboa, Portugal

Baptista, N. – Escola Superior de Comunicação Social, Instituto Politécnico de Lisboa, Campus de Benfica do IPL, Lisboa, Portugal; COMEGI, Centro de Investigação em Organizações, Mercados e Gestão Industrial, R. da Junqueira, Lisboa, Portugal

Natacha, S. – Research on Economics, Management and Information Technologies, Universidade Portucalense Infante D. Henrique, Porto, Portugal

Citation

Mata, F., Dos-Santos, M., Baptista, N., Natacha, S. Smart cities through urban short supply chains of food.

The cities around the world in general and in the Mediterranean area in particular are facing tremendous challenges at the environmental, social, economic and institutional levels (Fernandez-Anez et al., 2020). Currently, cities need to be sustainable and smart (Silva et al., 2018). An economically important and innovative sector in urban areas is food security. To the best of our knowledge, the majority of the literature explores the concept of smart cities from the point of view of information and communications technology, and the connection with sustainability aspects remains unsolved. This study tries to overcome this gap in the literature. The main aim is to analyse the

contribution of urban short-supply chains of foods in terms of sustainability of smart cities. The study reports the conclusions of a revision of the literature and the preliminary results of four research projects in this area, including the SGDsCONSUM project. The results confirm positive impacts of short supply chains of food in urban areas in the four dimensions of sustainable development and smart and sustainable cities. The conclusions of this study will be helpful for producers, consumers, traders, importers, exporters, tourists, financial institutions, and particularly for government sectors related to agricultural economic activities, projects, and programs in policy development.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to express their gratitude to the Instituto Politécnico de Lisboa (IPL) for the approval of the research project SGDsCONSUM and for providing this publication opportunity by granting financial assistance. To the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT, Portugal) for financial support to the CISAS UIDB/05937/2020 and UIDP/05937/2020, including the contract of the

References

- Fernandez-Anez, V., Velazquez, G., Perez-Prada, F. and Monzón, A., 2020. Smart City projects assessment matrix: connecting challenges and actions in the mediterranean region. *Journal of Urban Technology*, 27(4), pp.79-103.
- Silva, B.N., Khan, M. and Han, K., 2018. Towards sustainable smart cities: A review of trends, architectures, components, and open challenges in smart cities. *Sustainable cities and society*, 38, pp.697-713.

Poster I.5 Sustainable consumption in urban short supply chains

Author

Mata, F. – CISAS – Center for Research and Development in Agrifood Systems and Sustainability, Instituto Politécnico de Viana do Castelo. Rua Escola Industrial e Comercial Nun'Álvares, Viana do Castelo, Portugal

Dos - Santos, M., – Escola Superior de Comunicação Social, Instituto Politécnico de Lisboa, Campus de Benfca do IPL, Lisboa, Portugal; IUL DINÂMÍACET, ISCTE-

Instituto Universitário de Lisboa, Avenida das Forças Armadas, Lisboa, Portugal
M., Baptista, N. – Escola Superior de Comunicação Social, Instituto Politécnico de Lisboa, Campus de Benfca do IPL, Lisboa, Portugal; COMEGI, Centro de Investigação em Organizações, Mercados e Gestão Industrial, R. da Junqueira, Lisboa, Portugal

Natacha, S. – Research on Economics, Management and Information Technologies, Universidade Portucalense Infante D. Henrique, Porto, Portugal

Citation

Mata, F., Dos-Santos, M., Baptista, N., Natacha, S. Sustainable consumption in urban short supply chains.

The United Nations, national and regional public decision-makers, and the academy are increasingly paying attention to sustainable development. They are debating the main institutional ways and the respective restrictions to achieve a compromise solution among the economic, social, environmental, and institutional dimensions of sustainable development (Kumar, 2022). Sustainable food production and sustainable consumption in urban short-supply chains are dependent on the links between various stakeholders,

including companies, consumers and public decision-makers (Govindan, 2018). Previous literature lacks a systematic and holistic view of these actors and corresponding dependencies, limiting our understanding of how to leverage sustainable innovation and design sustainable strategies and policies for food production and consumption. Based on a systematic literature review of a large sample of representative publications included in the Web of Science and Scopus databases, this study tries to overcome this gap in the literature by exploring the relationship between ethical and sustainable consumption and production in short supply chains and offers an agenda for future research. This study, which was developed under the SDGsConsum project, proposes a holistic model of integrative development. The main results confirm that, despite the huge development in SDGs literature, and sustainable development of consumption, the focus on urban short supply chains of production in the literature is modest in general, and in particular in food sectorial activities. Moreover, the motivations and constraints that drive and restrain consumers and companies toward sustainable consumption and how these two dimensions complement each other or overlap remain a topic that needs to be further investigated. The results of this study can help shape policies that are adequate to promote a better adjustment of sustainable food supply and demand. Moreover, it might also bring new approaches to integrate and promote short supply chains of foods in urban areas for a more sustainable development of the world.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to express their gratitude to the Instituto Politécnico de Lisboa (IPL) for the approval of the research project SGDsCONSUM and for providing this publication opportunity by granting financial assistance.

References

Govindan, K., 2018. Sustainable consumption and production in the food supply chain: A conceptual framework. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 195, pp.419-431.

Kumar, M., Sharma, M., Raut, R.D., Mangla, S.K. and Choubey, V.K., 2022. Performance assessment of circular driven sustainable agri-food supply chain towards achieving sustainable consumption and production. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 372, p.133698.

Poster I.6 CLEVERFOOD: Connected labs for empowering versatile engagement in radical food system transformation

Author

Riviou, K. – Ellinogermaniki Agogi, Research & Development Dept., Athens, Greece

Citation

Riviou, K. CLEVERFOOD: Connected labs for empowering versatile engagement in radical food system transformation.

The current food system (FS) is contributing to 30% of the European share of global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions [1], with 24% alone coming from animal-based-food [2] and 6% from food loss and waste [3]. The need for arable soil to grow crops for feeding livestock results in a high pressure on land use, biodiversity, and water resources [4]. Furthermore, unhealthy diets associated with a high intake of red meat, sugar, and saturated fat, are linked with several non-communicable diseases that are contributing to more than 70% of all deaths in Europe [5]. More sustainable and plant-based food production and consumption is the most effective way to reduce GHG emissions and other impacts from the FS [6] and will also benefit human health [7]. However, despite increased acknowledgement of the need for a sustainable food system (SFS) transformation, dietary change is limited [8], and many farmers and other FS actors are hesitant to support a transition towards a more sustainable and plant-based FS [9]. Furthermore, the need for food aid solutions continues to rise due to the most recent crisis with rising poverty, migration and refugees.

CLEVERFOOD will overcome these barriers and support a SFS transformation by: i) establishing collaboration and mutual learning between EU FS projects, living labs, initiatives, partnerships, and networks (we have started the formation of the Food2030 EU Project network), ii) supporting integrated food policy development at the city, regional, national and EU level (a survey on all EU countries food policies is under progress), iii) connecting innovative CRFS approaches with relevant knowledge and innovation systems, iv) enabling radical FS innovation for co-benefits and high impact, v) providing impact investment and crowdfunding opportunities to support sustainable food businesses development, vi) ensuring that transition to more plant-based food production is attractive and economically viable for farmers and food sector companies, vii) promoting food environments where sustainable and healthy food is the preferred option, viii) educating, empowering and mobilizing citizens to change their diets and engage to transform national, European and global FSs. EA is co-leading and contributing mostly in the latter action.

Acknowledgments

The CLEVERFOOD project has received funding from the Horizon Europe under grant agreement 101086320 (<https://food2030.eu/>).

References

- [1] Crippa, M. et al (2021). Food systems are responsible for a third of global anthropogenic GHG emissions. *Nat Food* 2, 198–209.
- [2] Xu, X. et al (2021). Global greenhouse gas emissions from animal-based foods are twice those of plant-based foods. *Nat Food* 2, 724–732
- [3] Scherhauser, S. et al (2018). Environmental impacts of food waste in Europe, *Waste Management* 77, pp 98-113
- [4] Leip, A. et al (2017). Res. Lett. 10 115004. DOI: 10.1088/1748-9326/10/11/115004

[5] European Commission. (2016). European Research and Innovation for Food and Nutrition Security; WHO (2018) Data and statistics/CVD

[6] Poore, J., Nemecek, T. (2018). Reducing food's environmental impacts through producers and consumers. *Science* 216, pp 987–992.; Springmann, M. et al. (2018). Options for keeping the food system within environmental limits. *Nature* 562, pp 519–525; Chaudhary, A. et al. (2018). Multi-indicator sustainability assessment of global food systems. *Nat Commun* 9, 84.

[7] Springmann, et al. (2018). Health and nutritional aspects of sustainable diet strategies and their association with environmental impacts: a global modelling analysis with country-level detail. *The Lancet Planetary Health* 2, pp e451-e461; Willet, W. et al. (2019). Food in the Anthropocene: the EAT–Lancet Commission on healthy diets from sustainable food systems.

[8] Leme, A.C.B. et al (2021): Adherence to Food-Based Dietary Guidelines: A Systemic Review of High-Income and Low- and Middle-Income Countries. *Nutrients* 2021, 13, 1038

[9] Prag, A.A, Henriksen, C.B. (2020). Transition from Animal-Based to Plant-Based Food Production to Reduce Greenhouse Gas Emissions from Agriculture—The Case of Denmark. *Sustainability* 12, 8228; Aschemann-Witzel, J. et al (2021). Plant-based food and protein trend from a business perspective: markets, consumers, and the challenges and opportunities in the future, *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, 61, pp 3119-3128

Poster I.7 FoodSHIFT2030 open school lab, Athens: Schools as sites of food experience and food system (FS) transformation

Author

Riviou, K. – Ellinogermaniki Agogi, Research & Development Dept., Athens, Greece

Citation

Riviou, K. FoodSHIFT2030 open school lab, Athens: Schools as sites of food experience and food system (FS) transformation.

The Greater Athens Accelerator Lab goal in the context of FoodSHIFT2030 has been to explore new approaches for overcoming the growing divide between consumption and food knowledge by engaging schools in (re-) connecting young people with the land as well by strengthening the link between urban and agricultural communities, while providing hands-on learning opportunities for the leaders of tomorrow.

Our foci areas

(1) Social innovation by engaging schools in (re-) connecting young people with land, nature and use summer courses to promote healthy eating and plant-based foods.

(2) Community empowerment providing hands-on learning opportunities for the food-smart citizens of tomorrow.

(3) Strengthening the link between urban and agricultural communities by developing the dialogue between schools and food actor networks.

(4) Cooperating solutions for using leftovers in school canteens and kitchens.

Among actions implemented: application of the open schooling/living labs model (collaboration of school with food system stakeholders from the quadruple helix of innovation for the co-design of living labs projects related with the Green Deal^[1]), teacher trainings (workshops, webinars, 2 summer schools^[1] with the participation of educators all around Europe, 2 national contests^[2] for living labs^[3] projects on fs transformation the winners of which have been awarded participation in the summer schools, integration of the topic of fs in the curriculum, implementation of citizen science actions on healthy nutrition and promotion of physical activity (bands circulated to students, meals monitoring through smart app/daily diaries, data collection and analysis, students awards for enhancing motivation), community awareness through collaboration with municipality stakeholders and other fs actors, workshops with farmers, school garden, field visits to urban gardens, after school entrepreneurship club on the topic of the fs, food waste mitigation in the school restaurant/canteens, composting in school, creation of digital educational materials, online Community of Practice with digital resources and an Action Plan for schools to act as food system living labs.

Acknowledgments

The FoodSHIFT2030 project has received funding from Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme of the European Union under grant agreement number 862716 (www.foodshift2030.eu).

References

- [1] <https://esia.ea.gr/foodshift2030-summer-school/>
- [2] <https://foodshift2030.ea.gr/>
- [3] Schools as living labs: A road map for schools, https://www.schoolsaslivinglabs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/06/SALL_Roadmap_for_schools_v.1-2021.04.15.pdf

Poster I.8 FoodSHIFT pathways for the food system transformation

Author

Riviou, K. – Ellinogermaniki Agogi, Research & Development Dept., Athens, Greece

Citation

Riviou, K. FoodSHIFT pathways for the food system transformation.

To support a fundamental shift in our food system, it is essential to engage and educate youngsters about the connection between food, health and environment. Therefore, educating teachers and subsequently students about state-of-the-art approaches towards a sustainable and healthy fs (ShFS) is of major importance. Our approach aims to act as reference point for future-oriented curricula that better meet the current environmental challenges. FoodSHIFT Pathways are a series of practices enriched with interactive digital resources focusing on describing the status & presenting future-thinking approaches to ShFS.

So far, we have conducted state-of the art review and designed our pedagogical design¹ and training framework² with national Curricula mapping³; identified and analysed relevant EU policies⁴ and SC frameworks⁵; interviews and focus groups for needs analysis and initial outcomes validation with the participation of educators/experts/fs actors. Six (6) interactive videos⁶ have been produced in equivalent number of Countries (EL, PT, ES, SW, DK, NL) on the themes of: Local/healthy food; Organic food; Innovation/Digital tools for agriculture; Transition to alternative proteins; Food waste prevention, circular economy; Food advertisement, along with the accompanying suggested educational activities⁷ that educators might apply in formal, non-formal and informal educational settings with the collaboration of multiple

fs stakeholders from the quadruple helix of innovation (researchers, NGOs, CSOs, SMEs, farmers, families, and caregivers, etc.) We aim to develop teachers' & students' sustainability competence, also raising awareness of the importance of the current fs and environmental challenges in two pilot rounds. Our goal is to demonstrate how schools can be transformed to hubs of innovation for their local communities acting as change agents. Based on the initial open learning scenarios developed by our team, teachers & students will co-develop their own projects enriched with external expertise and will have the opportunity to become members of the relevant online community of practice.

Acknowledgments

The FOODSHIFT Pathways project is co-funded by the Erasmus+ programme of the European Union under grant agreement number 2022-1-SE01-KA220-SCH-0000899 (<https://www.foodshift-pathways.eu/>).

References

- 1 Pedagogical Design, https://foodshift-pathways.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/A2.4.PedagogicalDesign_final.pdf
- 2 Initial Trainees' Guide, https://foodshift-pathways.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/A3.5-TraineesGuide_final.pdf
- 3 Needs analysis, https://foodshift-pathways.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/A2.1.NeedsAnalysis_final.pdf
- 4 Harmonizing with European Policies, https://foodshift-pathways.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/A2.2.HarmonisingwithEuropeanPolicies_final.pdf

5 Key Features of the Sustainability Competence, https://foodshift-pathways.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/A2.3.KeyFeaturesSustainabilityCompetence_final.pdf

6 Storyboard Design, https://foodshift-pathways.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/A3.1.StoryboardDesign_final.pdf

7 Initial Open Learning Scenarios, https://foodshift-pathways.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/A3.6.OpenLearningScenarios_final.pdf

Poster I.9 Promoting nutritional literacy and sustainable food education: Initiatives involving schools in the city of Castelo Branco

Author

Pereira, F. – Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar - CATAA; Castelo Branco, Portugal

Rodrigues, A. – Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar – CATAA; Castelo Branco, Portugal

Lucas, A. – Quinta do Chinco Castelo Branco, Portugal

Ferreira, C. – Câmara Municipal de Castelo Branco Castelo Branco, Portugal

Lopes, G. – Associação do Cluster Agro-Industrial do Centro – InovCluster; Castelo Branco, Portugal

Santos, J. F. – Associação do Cluster Agro-Industrial do Centro – InovCluster; Castelo Branco, Portugal

Espírito Santo, C. – Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar – CATAA; Castelo Branco, Portugal

Brandão, I. – Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar – CATAA; Castelo Branco, Portugal

Citation

Pereira, F., Rodrigues, A., Lucas, A., Ferreira, C., Lopes, G., Santos, J.F., Espírito Santo, C., Brandão, I. Promoting nutritional literacy and sustainable food education: Initiatives involving schools in the city of Castelo Branco.

Introduction

The promotion of food and nutritional literacy and education is recognized as a key strategy in fostering healthy dietary habits. Thus, the school environment emerges as a suitable place for implementing initiatives in food and nutritional literacy and education, serving as a fundamental approach to prevent chronic non-communicable diseases and improve nutritional status.

Objective

To report the experiences of triangulation between education in healthy eating, sustainability and training actions in schools in the city of Castelo Branco.

Methods

The description of experiences in food and nutritional literacy and education is based on the training actions developed by CATAA in collaboration with Quinta do Chinco, Castelo Branco Municipality, InovCluster, and the FUSILLI Project. Since 2021, training actions have been conducted in schools highlighting the importance of adopting healthy and sustainable eating practices. Educational visits to both the municipal market and social gardens have been organized to facilitate a closer contact between participating children and locally-sourced products and seasonal fruits and vegetables.

Results

From 2021 to October 2023, we have reached over 3,000 students, spanning from the first cycle to higher education, distributed in: 102 workshops, 74 visits to social gardens, 31 visits to the municipal market with presentations and tasting of new products made from local and seasonal ingredients. Furthermore, we have participated in 17 markets and fairs, engaging the wider community.

Conclusions

In recent years schools have shown increased interest in participating in educational activities, highlighting the importance of articulation between public policies and the integration of food literacy and sustainable education within educational institutions.

Poster I.10 School gardens in Castelo Branco: Fostering nature connection and sustainability in children

Author

Lucas, A. – Câmara Municipal de Castelo Branco; Castelo Branco, Portugal
Cristóvão, M. – Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar – CATAA; Castelo Branco, Portugal

Beato, A. – Hortas Sociais Quinta do Chinco; Castelo Branco, Portugal

Brandão, I. – Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar – CATAA; Castelo Branco, Portugal

Espírito Santo, C. – Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar – CATAA; Castelo Branco, Portugal

Ferreira, C. – Câmara Municipal de Castelo Branco; Castelo Branco, Portugal

Citation

Lucas, A., Cristóvão, M., Beato, A., Brandão, I., Espírito Santo, C., Ferreira, C. School gardens in Castelo Branco: Fostering nature connection and sustainability in children.

Urban Living Labs are speeding up the shift towards greener, more sustainable and climate-resilient cities (Kronsell & Mukhtar-Landgren, 2018). These labs are all about getting people involved, including regular citizens, to improve their quality of life, facilitate the development of sustainable practices and make positive changes to our environment (Steen & Van Bueren, 2017).

One effective approach for promoting positive behaviours like sharing, collaboration, and debate, while also providing a hands-on learning experience for gardening skills, is the implementation of school gardens.

(Acharya et al., 2023). These educational tools offer an opportunity to improve both sustainable farming practices and healthy eating habits (Schreinemachers & Redwine, 2022). Also, children are pivotal as they are not only the future consumers but also influence the people who teach them.

The Castelo Branco Living Lab, part of the FUSILLI project, has taken on the task of introducing and maintaining school gardens. Initially, only 23% of the schools in the area had some form of a garden. Over time, these existing gardens underwent significant improvements, to meet the standards for accessible gardens that benefit the entire school community. Moreover, this initiative has expanded to include new gardens in other schools. As a result, the total percentage of schools in the Castelo Branco area with school gardens has now reached 44%.

This initiative highlights the remarkable progress made in integrating school gardens into the local educational landscape, fostering a deeper connection with sustainable agricultural practices and food origin. Creating and expanding school gardens, within the city Living Lab, shows potential in supporting the transition towards more resilient and sustainable urban systems.

References

Acharya, K. P., Budhathoki, C. B., Bjonness, B., & Duwadi, K. P. (2023). Pedagogical Transformation Through School Garden as a Living Laboratory in Public Schools in Nepal (pp. 110–129). <https://doi.org/10.4018/979-8-3693-0607-9.ch008>.

Kronsell, A., & Mukhtar-Landgren, D. (2018). Experimental governance: the role of municipalities in urban living labs. *European Planning Studies*, 26(5), 988–1007. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09654313.2018.1435631>.

Schreinemachers, P., & Redwine, T. (2022). Strategy Brief for School Garden Implementation. World Vegetable Center; Vivayic (ISBN 92-9058-236-7)

Steen, K., & Van Bueren, E. (2017). Urban Living Labs A living lab way of working. AMS Institute. ISBN: <http://www.ams-institute.org/news/out-now-urban-living-labs-a-living-lab-way-of-working/>

Theme II – Local territorial challenges & strategies

Synopsis - Keynote Speakers

Climate change and ecosystem degradation: Desertification

Author

Maria José Roxo – Nova University Lisbon, Portugal

Citation

Maria José Roxo. Climate change and ecosystem degradation: Desertification.

The presentation addresses the critical issue of desertification in Portugal, focusing on how climate change and human activities degrade ecosystems and landscapes. It highlights the importance of vegetation cover, soil, and water in maintaining productive ecosystems and the detrimental impacts when these resources are mismanaged. Factors contributing to degradation include human actions (market forces, policies), climatic changes (temperature rise, precipitation decrease), and biological influences (ecosystem health).

Some examples highlight the transformation of the Beira Baixa landscape, emphasizing the significant issue of desertification in Portugal, particularly in the Castelo Branco district. The presentation also showcases experimental studies and results from the Vale Formoso Soil Erosion Centre in Baixo Alentejo.

Key points include alarming statistics on global soil loss reported by the United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification, noting that between 2015 and 2019, the world lost around 100 million hectares of productive soil annually.

In Portugal, rising temperatures and decreasing precipitation have intensified droughts and aridity since 2000, impacting agriculture and increasing the frequency of extreme climate events. Improper land use practices exacerbate these issues, causing soil erosion, biodiversity loss, and reduced agricultural productivity.

It outlines the severe consequences of irrational natural resource use, linking desertification to climate change and stressing the importance of soil organic matter in mitigating these effects.

To combat desertification, the presentation advocates for soil conservation through ecosystem services and sustainable agricultural practices. It underscores the importance of soil organic matter in enhancing water retention, nutrient availability, and carbon sequestration, thereby mitigating climate change effects. The presentation calls for increased knowledge, experience, financial incentives, political will, and societal commitment to implement effective solutions and adapt to the new environmental realities.

Selected Oral Communications

Abstract II.1 Pre-treatment of olive plants with a biostimulant based on *ascophyllum nodosum* promote drought stress tolerance

Author

Figueiras, R. – University of Coimbra, Center for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Calçada Martim de Freitas, 3000-456 Coimbra, Portugal

Araújo, M. – University of Coimbra, Center for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Calçada Martim de Freitas, 3000-456 Coimbra, Portugal

Santos, C. – IB2 Lab, Department of Biology & LAQV/REQUIMTE, Faculty of Sciences, University of Porto, Rua do Campo Alegre 4169-007, Porto, Portugal

Dias, MC – University of Coimbra, Center for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Calçada Martim de Freitas, 3000-456 Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Figueiras, R., Araújo, M., Santos, C., Dias, M.C. Pre-treatment of olive plants with a biostimulant based on *ascophyllum nodosum* promote drought stress tolerance.

Olea europaea L. is one of the major crops on the Mediterranean Basin. This species is well adapted to environmental conditions of this region, but how olive orchards based on intensive irrigation practices and high input of fertilizers will respond to the increasing periods of drought is unknown. Adopting the “Farm to Fork” strategy, sustainable oliviculture systems need to be implemented to reduce water requirements. Bio-based products, such as the biostimulants that promote plant growth and stress tolerance can be sustainable agronomical tools to cope with the agricultural challenges imposed by climate change. This work aimed to study the effect of a pre-treatment with a biostimulant (based on extracts of *Ascophyllum nodosum*) on the olive tree’s tolerance to drought. Young olive trees, growing in 5L pots, were randomly divided into four groups: a) plants sprayed with biostimulant (3mL/L) and maintained well-irrigated (100% of field capacity); b) plants sprayed with water and maintained well-irrigated; c) plants sprayed with biostimulant and maintained under water deficit (50% of field capacity); and d) plants sprayed with water and maintained under water deficit. 69 days after the last application of biostimulant, leaves were collected to analyze the content of soluble sugars, starch, proline, antioxidant compounds (total phenols, orthodiphenols and flavonoids) and antioxidant enzymes (SOD and catalase), and oxidative stress markers. Water deficit increased proline levels, but reduced the availability of soluble sugars and starch, and the application of biostimulant under water deficit conditions increased the starch accumulation. Biostimulant treatment reduced lipid peroxidation and increased the levels of total phenols and orthodiphenols under water deficit. The application of this biostimulant reduced the negative impact of water stress and the antioxidants metabolites seems to have a relevant role in stress protection. These data highlight the potential of biostimulants based on *A. nodosum* to improve olive trees tolerance.

Acknowledgments

This work was financed by FCT: UIDB/04004/2020 and LA/P/0092/2020, SFRH/BD/116801/2016 and COVID/BD/151706/2021 (M Araújo), and SFRH/BPD/100865/2014 (MCDias).

Abstract II.2 Collaborative strategies to improve the local food system in Setúbal

Author

Silva, A. – K-Evolution Association, Setúbal, Portugal

Martins, A. – Instituto Politécnico de Beja, Beja, Portugal

Citation

Silva, A., Martins, A. Collaborative strategies to improve the local food system in Setúbal.

The research assumes that short food supply chains are ways to promote sustainable and equitable food systems. This is even more so when it explores the potential to boost the local economy, maintain landscape, make use of urban spaces, and define participatory and collaborative strategies to face the challenges.

The methodology was based on participatory principles, including regeneration and antifragility, namely: cooperation and partnership networks; continuous monitoring and evaluation; collaborative approach to decision-making; creation of a local implementing team of technicians, farmers, and community; creation of an interdisciplinary team with local authorities.

From the results, it is important to highlight the identification of challenges, such as the co-creation of local production and consumption strategies; the creation of a territorial brand for producers; the inclusion of clauses in the tender specifications that favour local producers; certification of

origin and local processing; the creation of an association of producers; professionalization in agroecological production; support for the installation of new producers.

The following challenges are identified as priorities: expansion of community gardens; healthy and sustainable food in schools; creation of a local production label; creation of associative structures for the sector.

The policy recommendations are made as a proposal for joint action to create value for the territory and building a system that can contribute to the goals of the SDGs. Major challenges are not always synonymous of large investments, but rather with integrated, cross-cutting, multi-level measures. This assumption is fundamental for the understanding of the proposals presented, for the creation of a local governance mechanism, focused on short market chains and sustainable production. These structures favour the creation of social and productive capital, empower community agents, and create incentive mechanisms for greater participation for local strategy.

Acknowledgments

Association The K-Evolution and Bugday would like to thank the THE:PLACE programme, jointly managed by ALDA and MAD and funded by Stiftung Mercator for supporting this work. We also would like to thank the producers involved in the study, the voluntary team (LIT) and the interdisciplinary team created in Setubal Municipality and the logistic support from Palmela Municipality.

References

Biermann, F.; Stevens, C.; Bernstein, S.; Gupta, A.; Kabiri, N.; Kanie, N.; Levy, M.; Nilsson, M.; Pintér, L.; Scobie, M. e Young, O. (2014); Integrating Governance into the Sustainable Development Goals, POST2015/UNU-IAS Policy Brief #3, Tokyo, United Nations University Institute for the Advanced Study of Sustainability;

Dallabrida, V.; Marchesan, J.; Rosseto, A.; Filippim, E. (2016), Governança nos territórios ou governança territorial: distância entre concepções teóricas e a prática; Revista GRIFOS - N. 40, pp 43-66;

Güney, T. (2017), Governance and sustainable development: How effective is governance? The Journal of International Trade & Economic Development, 26:3, 316-335;

Horstink, L.; Schwemmlin, K. and Encarnação, M.(2023). Food systems in depressed and contested agro-territories: Participatory Rural Appraisal in Odemira, Portugal. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*. DOI:10.3389/fsufs.2022.1046549.

Zeijl-Rozema, A.; Cörvers, R.; Kemp, R. e Martens, P. (2008), Governance for Sustainable Development: A Framework, in Wiley InterScience, Sustainable Development Sust. Dev. 16, 410–421, John Wiley & Sons, Ltd and ERP Environment.

Abstract II.3 Identification of putative biomarkers from apple ciders of different geographical origins based on volatilomic signature

Author

Medina, S. – CQM – Centro de Química da Madeira, Universidade da Madeira, Campus da Penteadá, 9020-105, Funchal, Portugal

Pereira, R. – Direção Regional de Agricultura, Divisão de Inovação Agroalimentar, Aveinda Arriaga, N.º 21 A, Edifício Golden Gate, 9000-060 Funchal, Portuga

Câmara, J. S. – CQM – Centro de Química da Madeira, Universidade da Madeira, Campus da Penteadá, 9020-105, Funchal, Portugal; Departamento de Química, Faculdade de Ciências Exatas e Engenharia, Universidade da Madeira, Campus da Penteadá, 9020-105, Funchal, Portugal

Perestrelo, R. – CQM – Centro de Química da Madeira, Universidade da Madeira, Campus da Penteadá, 9020-105, Funchal, Portugal

Citation

Medina, S., Pereira, R., Câmara, J. S., Perestrelo, R. Identification of putative biomarkers from apple ciders of different geographical origins based on volatilomic signature.

Apple cider is a traditional alcoholic beverage fermented from apple juice, with increasing consumption and production worldwide. In 2017, across Madeira Island, around 130 ha were dedicated to the production of 2000 tons of apples, corresponding to the production of 3328 hl of apple cider.

Moreover, contrary to evidence in the remaining country, cider-making by the traditional process has never been discontinued in Madeira Island. Currently, the food-quality program of the European Union encourages food-origin protection through Protected Designation of Origin (PDO) and Protected Geographical Indication (PGI) with the purpose of ensuring the quality of the final product. Therefore, it is necessary to develop analytical tools to establish the authenticity and genuineness of food-derived products.

In the current work, headspace solid-phase microextraction followed by gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (HS-SPME/GC–MS) combined with chemometric tools was used to establish the volatile fingerprint of apple ciders produced in different geographical regions of Madeira Island, to define their typicity and to identify putative geographical markers. A total of 143 volatile organic compounds (VOCs) belonging to different chemical families have been identified, of which 28 were found in all apple ciders independently of geographical region. Significant differences in terms of qualitative and quantitative volatile signatures of ciders were observed. A clear differentiation among cider-producing regions was observed on the developed partial least squares-discriminant analysis (PLS-DA) model. The results obtained recognize the specific and typical geographical characteristics of the cider, which will allow the forthcoming guarantee for the construction of a sustainable platform for the establishment of the authenticity and typicality of the regional cider.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by FCT-Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia through the CQM Base Fund - UIDB/00674/2020, and Programmatic Fund - UIDP/00674/2020, by Interreg MAC 2014–2020 Cooperacion territorial through AD4MAC project (MAC2/1.1b/350), by Madeira 14–20 Program, project PROEQUIPRAM - Reforço do Investimento em Equipamentos e Infraestruturas Científicas na RAM (M1420-01-0145-FEDER-000008), and by ARDITI - Agência Regional para o Desenvolvimento da Investigação Tecnologia e Inovação, through the projects M1420-01-0145-FEDER-000005 - Centro de Química da Madeira - CQM+ (Madeira 14–20 Program).

Abstract II.4 Modelling maritime pine forest distribution in Portugal under climate change scenarios

Author

Alegria, C. – IPCB—Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal; CERNAS-IPCB—Research Centre for Natural Resources, Environment and Society, Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal
Almeida, A. M. – IPCB—Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal
Roque, N. – IPCB—Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal; CERNAS-IPCB—Research Centre for Natural Resources, Environment and Society, Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal
Fernandez, P. – IPCB—Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal; CERNAS-IPCB—Research Centre for Natural Resources, Environment and Society, Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal
Ribeiro, M. M. – IPCB—Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal; CERNAS-IPCB—Research Centre for Natural Resources, Environment and Society, Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal; TERRA-CEF—Forest Research Centre, Associate Laboratory TERRA, School of Agriculture, University of Lisbon, Lisbon, Portugal

Citation

Alegria, C., Almeida, A. M., Roque, N., Fernandez, P., Ribeiro, M. M. Modelling maritime pine forest distribution in Portugal under climate change scenarios.

A variety of species potential distribution mapping approaches have been used to date, and different methodological approaches' maps agreement should be assessed. The study aimed at modelling species' distribution for the present and

future (2070) under two climate change scenarios (RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5), using two methodological approaches, namely: (1) the ML algorithm Maximum Entropy (MaxEnt), and (2) the GIS map algebra (ecological envelopes) considering a set of environmental variables and previously known thresholds. Lastly, the agreement analysis for the species distribution maps produced with both methodological approaches was made. Maritime pine was used as a study case since it has been severely affected by wildfires and measures are needed to overcome this situation. The results showed that species' distribution for the present using the MaxEnt modelling provided fitting efficiencies of around 70% and matched well the species' current distribution. The species ecological envelope map for the present was closer to the species' empiric potential distribution. Climate change impacts on the species' future distributions with the MaxEnt approach were moderate, with areas being relocated (47.3% regular-medium-high suitability area to 48.7%–48.3% in future climate change scenarios). The impacts in species' ecological envelopes maps were higher and with greater future losses than the former method (76.5% regular-favourable-optimum suitability area to 58.2%–51.6% in future climate change scenarios). The two approaches showed a 44% concordance in the present, decreasing to 30%–35% in the future under climate change scenarios. These maps are key to support recommendations to set species' best suitable areas for planning future afforestation to produce fire-resilient landscapes, and to enhance forest ecosystems' biodiversity, functionality, and productivity under climate change scenarios.

Acknowledgments

The CULTIVAR project (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020) and the Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia grants UIDB/00239/2020, UIDB/00681/2020, and UIDB/05183/2020, funded this work.

References

Alegria, C., Almeida, A.M., Roque, N., Fernandez, P., Ribeiro, M.M. (2023). Species Distribution Modelling under Climate Change Scenarios for Maritime Pine (*Pinus pinaster* Aiton) in Portugal. *Forests*, 14, 591. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f14030591>

Abstract II.5 Soil erosion in agricultural landscapes in the Mediterranean context: a case study in Portugal

Author

Gonçalves, J. P. C. – Master's Student in Physical Geography, Environment and Spatial Planning Department of Geography and Tourism - University of Coimbra (Portugal)

Figueiredo, A. – Centre of Studies in Geography and Spatial Planning (CEGOT); Department of Geography and Tourism - University of Coimbra (Portugal)

Nunes, A. – Centre of Studies in Geography and Spatial Planning (CEGOT); Department of Geography and Tourism - University of Coimbra (Portugal)

Citation

Gonçalves, J. P. C., Figueiredo, A., Nunes, A. Soil erosion in agricultural landscapes in the Mediterranean context: a case study in Portugal.

Soil erosion is considered an issue of high concern in the European Mediterranean area, especially in areas where land use pattern is dominated by agriculture and climate is marked by dryness. That combination is especially harmful where soil cover is low at the end of summer, the period of the year with higher erosivity, once vegetation cover is lower and records of episodes of intense rain are higher. In this work we assess the risk of soil erosion in different land use types (orchards, olive groves, pastures) considering the land use regime (intensive/extensive) in the Idanha Bioregion. The region is highly susceptible to desertification, namely because of the high potential to soil loss, and registers a significant change in terms of

land use patterns, namely associated to the expansion of intensive orchards based on irrigation. To compare the erosive responses of the intensive and extensive systems in the study area, rainfall simulations were performed at the end of the summer period (September). The assessment is based on the total amount of sediment collected in each simulation replicated by the land use types considered. The results that were obtained show a higher soil loss in intensive uses, associated with orchards installed in the last five years, which exhibit lower vegetation cover at soil surface, compared to traditional extensive uses (rainfed), where annual vegetation cover is present, namely dry mulch. The results of the simulations also demonstrate that higher values of erosion observed in intensive orchards might be mitigated through the maintenance of an herbaceous cover able to protect the soil from the direct impact of rainfall.

Posters

Poster II.1 *Ascophyllum nodosum* improves olive physiological performance and fruit size under water deficit conditions

Author

Figueiras, R. – University of Coimbra, Center for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Calçada Martim de Freitas, 3000-456 Coimbra, Portugal

Araújo, M. – University of Coimbra, Center for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Calçada Martim de Freitas, 3000-456 Coimbra, Portugal

Santos, C. – IB2 Lab, Department of Biology & LAQV/REQUIMTE, Faculty of Sciences, University of Porto, Rua do Campo Alegre 4169-007, Porto, Portugal

Dias, M. C. – University of Coimbra, Center for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Calçada Martim de Freitas, 3000-456 Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Figueiras, R., Araújo, M., Santos, C., Dias, M.C. *Ascophyllum nodosum* improves olive physiological performance and fruit size under water deficit conditions.

The olive tree, *Olea europaea L.*, is one of the main agricultural crops of the Mediterranean basin, where around 78% of the world's olive oil is produced. Olive tree has a high tolerance to drought, however, the extreme weather

events have been affected the productivity of olive groves and olive oil quality. Therefore, it is urgent to implement sustainable agriculture strategies to enhance olive resilience against stressful conditions. In this context, biostimulants are gaining interest, since they can improve crop quality and productivity, as well as tolerance to (a)biotic stressors. This work aimed to study the effect of a natural biostimulant based on extracts of *Ascophyllum nodosum*, on the olive tree's tolerance to drought and on the size of the olives. Potted young olive trees from the cultivar Arbequina were divided into four groups: a) plants sprayed with biostimulant (3mL/L) and maintained well-irrigated (100% of field capacity); b) plants sprayed with water and maintained well-irrigated; c) plants sprayed with biostimulant and maintained under water deficit (50% of field capacity); and d) plants sprayed with water and maintained under water deficit. At the end of the experiment (69 days), leaf relative water content and photosynthesis were evaluated. Additionally, the length and width of olives were determined. Water deficit negatively affected the physiological performance of olive plants, but the application of biostimulant reduced this impact. The biostimulant increased the plants water status and improved the water use efficiency in olive trees under water deficit conditions. Moreover, the biostimulant also favored the length and width of olives under both well irrigated and water deficit conditions. These data highlight the potential of these natural substances to improve olive tree performance and fruit size.

Acknowledgments

This work was financed by FCT: UIDB/04004/2020 and LA/P/0092/2020, SFRH/BD/116801/2016 and COVID/BD/151706/2021 (M Araújo), and SFRH/BPD/100865/2014 (MCDias).

Theme III – Food loss & waste

Synopsis - Keynote Speakers

Between food waste measurement, measures and transition: Academic insights meeting business practice

Author

Hilke Bos Brouwers – Wageningen University & Research, Netherlands

Citation

Brouwers , H.B., Between food waste measurement, measures and transition: Academic insights meeting business practice.

Introduction on Food Waste and Losses

Food waste is a visible and familiar issue for many, often encountered during daily activities like checking the refrigerator or inspecting fruit on the counter. This presentation explores the connection between food waste and the broader transitions necessary for a sustainable food system. It focuses on how various measuring measures can help identify problems, hotspots, and responsible stakeholders to facilitate the transition towards a circular bio-economy.

The food system is inherently complex, influenced by policy strategies, industrial actions, and societal behaviors. These factors operate at multiple levels, from international and European policies to national and regional strategies. Industry regulations and organizational designs also play a critical role in delivering effective products across diverse food supply chains. Societal behaviors, influenced by cultural and social contexts, further impact the food system, with NGOs highlighting the societal implications of food-related practices.

Food waste, regardless of how it is defined or visualized, is a symptom of a dysfunctional food system. It results from a mismatch between production and consumption requirements, whether these pertain to cost, nutrition, safety, or quantity. Addressing food waste necessitates a clear vision and target, a roadmap, and collaborative efforts involving various stakeholders, including food business operators, consumers, financiers, NGOs, knowledge institutes, and governmental institutions.

Achieving a reduction in food waste involves setting joint targets and raising awareness about the problem. Effective measurement is crucial; it helps identify where and how much waste occurs within the food supply chain and across different product categories. This data-driven approach facilitates targeted actions and enables the transition toward a food waste-free future.

Measuring Food Loss and Waste

Measuring food loss and waste raises essential questions: What should be measured? Where should counting start and stop? What data is needed, and how can it be made reliable and comprehensive? Currently, global food waste amounts are monitored by the FAO's Food Loss Index and UNEP's Food Waste Index, aligning with Sustainable Development Goal 12.3, which aims to halve food waste by 2030. Recent figures indicate that 13.3% of food produced globally is lost upstream, valued at \$400 billion, while approximately 931 megatons of food waste are generated annually, mostly at the household level.

The WWF has extended these estimates, suggesting that up to 40% of all food produced is uneaten, including significant losses at the farm level. This underscores the primary sector's substantial contribution to greenhouse gas emissions, accounting for 10% of human-induced emissions toward global warming.

Definitions and Data

Clear definitions are fundamental to measuring food waste. In 2018, a revised Waste Framework Directive introduced a new definition: "Food waste means all food as defined in Article 2 of Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 of the European Parliament and of the Council that has become waste." This combines the definitions of food and waste, but interpretation can vary due to cultural, geographical, and stakeholder differences.

Following this definition, the EU mandated member states to measure food waste. Recent data from 2021 indicates that the EU generates 259 million tonnes of food waste annually, valued at €132 billion. This represents 10% of available food in downstream segments, with significant variation across member states.

Practical Measures and Interventions

Effective measures to reduce food waste span various sectors. Preventative efforts include better planning, storage, portioning, and shelf-life management. Surplus food can be redirected to human consumption through donations and social initiatives, opening opportunities for social entrepreneurship. Reprocessing unsold products for human consumption also helps avoid waste and introduces new market opportunities.

At the retail level, strategies include better stock management, real-time quality measurement, dynamic discounting, and collaboration with suppliers. These efforts optimize assortments and packaging, provide customers with longer shelf life and better portion sizes, and facilitate food donations or reprocessing.

In food services, improving forecasts, offering smaller portions, adjusting buffet layouts, and using seasonal ingredients can reduce waste. Collaboration with chain partners and involving personnel and guests in waste reduction efforts also contribute significantly.

Household food waste requires increased awareness and involvement. Consumer campaigns and education at schools can effectively raise awareness and encourage responsible behavior. Engaging children and their parents through school projects and challenges fosters a culture of food waste reduction.

The Role of Academia

Academia plays a crucial role in preventing and reducing food waste. Researchers can improve measurement methodologies, collect and assess multi-actor data, and evaluate strategies and interventions. Academic insights support technological innovations, decision support, and scenario building, helping match causes of food waste with appropriate solutions. Knowledge transfer from academia to business and civil society is vital for implementing effective measures and policies.

Transitioning to a sustainable food system requires collaboration across sectors. The Dutch foundation Food Waste Free United demonstrates that joint efforts can significantly reduce food waste. By working together, stakeholders can achieve a more sustainable and efficient food system.

In conclusion, addressing food waste involves a multifaceted approach, integrating policy, industry, and societal efforts, supported by robust measurement and collaborative action. Academic contributions provide the scientific basis for informed decision-making and innovative solutions, driving the transition toward a sustainable food future.

Tackling the food waste - The role of ASAE

Author

Pedro Nabais – Economic and Food Safety Authority (ASAE), Portugal

Citation

Nabais, P., Tackling The Food Waste - The role of ASAE

The mission of the Food and Economic Safety Authority (ASAE) is to monitor and prevent compliance with the legislation that regulates the exercise of economic activities in the food and non-food sectors, as well as assessing and communicating risks in the food chain, and it is the national body that liaises with its counterparts at European and international level. Thus, although ASAE's main and most visible activity is inspection and risk management in the food chain, it is also responsible for risk assessment, which scientifically supports that activity, and for risk communication in the food chain.

Realising the importance and the worldwide impact of the food waste, in 2016 the Portuguese government created the National Commission for Combating Food Waste (CNCDA) with the mission of combating food waste, a shared responsibility from producers to consumers. This Commission, which ASAE has been part of since its creation, is made up of 10 government areas, 2 Local Government Associations and 1 Social Solidarity Association from the voluntary sector, and is coordinated by the Planning, Policies and General Administration Office (GPP) of the Ministry of Agriculture. The CNCDA was responsible for drawing up the National Strategy to Combat Food Waste (ENCDA), which included three main strategic objectives: to prevent, reduce and monitor, and for creating an Action Plan to Combat Food Waste (PACDA) which sets out 14 measures to be implemented by CNCDA

entities. All the monitoring reports are available on the CNCDA website, as well as the Guidelines, Manuals and Clarifications that have been produced to combat food waste and promote food redistribution.

As it is estimated that 10% of the 88 million tonnes of food waste is related to date marking, rising awareness of the distinction between the date of minimum durability ("Best before..." or "Best before the end of...") and the 'USE BY' date ("Use by...") is key to improving this situation. In order to better understand the national knowledge and perception of the consumers in Portugal about the food labelling, ASAE in close collaboration with the University of Lisbon, as part of a master's degree in veterinary medicine, launched a short questionnaire for research purposes on consumer perception of food labelling and its impact on food waste. The questionnaire consisted of 32 questions divided into 3 sections: General characterisation of the respondent, Consumption habits, Knowledge of labelling, and was applied online between 8 January and 8 August 2022. This questionnaire, which was distributed with the collaboration of the CNCDA, received 640 responses and the study reached the following main conclusions:

Labelling information on expiry dates is not always correctly interpreted, leading to avoidable waste.

Compared to Eurobarometer 425, the consumers included in our sample show a better understanding of this labelling.

Females, younger people and people with a higher level of education were more aware.

The lack of knowledge of the date of minimum durability, or 'best before' date revealed by almost 36 per cent of respondents could indirectly lead us to conclude that waste can occur due to the marking of expiry dates.

Reference

Pinho JO. 2023. Avaliação do impacto da rotulagem na mitigação do desperdício alimentar pelo consumidor [dissertação de mestrado]. Lisboa: FMV-Universidade de Lisboa <http://hdl.handle.net/10400.5/29160>

Cynaramulching – A strategy for the development of biodegradable mulching films

Author

Maria F. Duarte – Alentejo Biotechnology Center for Agriculture and Agro-food (CEBAL)/ Polytechnic Institute of Beja (IPBeja), Beja, Portugal;
MED – Mediterranean Institute for Agriculture, Environment and Development & CHANGE – Global Change and Sustainability Institute, CEBAL, Beja, Portugal

Citation

Duarte, M.F., CynaraMulching – A strategy for the development of biodegradable mulching films.

Plastic mulching has become a globally applied agricultural practice for its instant economic benefits such as higher yields, earlier harvests, improved fruit quality and increased water-use efficiency. However, plastic mulching is an important source of microplastics in agriculture with a tremendous impact on water and soil. CynaraMulch is a strategy based on biodegradable mulching films derived from non-feed crops, with high degradation rate, using lignocellulosic waste materials, so no plastic is left in the fields in the end of the season, towards a sustainable agriculture solution.

Plastic fragments and compounds released from plastic wastes are ubiquitous all over the world, and can be found in the atmosphere, in water resources, as well as into soils and organisms, including humans. Plastic waste release into land systems is estimated to be 4 to 23-fold higher than what is released into marine environments.

Global consumption of mulches grows worldwide, with an increase of 35% between 2006 and 2017, up to over 2 Mton, being forecast to double over the next 20 years. The plastic mulching application into agriculture became a globally practice, for its instant economic benefits such as higher yields, earlier harvests, improved fruit quality and increased water-use efficiency. The recycling rates for mulches are substantially lower than the already low global plastic recycling rate, estimated below 30%. Portugal agriculture plastics demand in 2019 rounded 70kton.

Biodegradable plastic mulches (BDM) have emerged as a promising alternative to alleviate polyethylene pollution. BDM, made of different polymers and compositions, are designed to biodegrade in situ, into the agricultural soil. Their use may entail environmental impacts for the agricultural system that deserve to be explored on the short and long-term. New bio-based materials represent a strategic approach for limiting environmental concern. Biodegradable components of lignocellulosic biomass, lignin, hemicellulose and cellulose are of particular importance for bio-based polymers development.

CynaraMulch targets the development of biodegradable bio-based mulching films, using renewable sources of lignocellulosic residues. With a biomass production that can reach 20 ton dried weight/ha, *Cynara cardunculus*, an industrial non-food crop, considered a multi-purpose crop its lignocellulosic fractions still widely unexplored, with aerial parts presenting 53,0% polysaccharides (~10 ton/ha) mainly cellulose and xylans, with stalks having 14.6% extractives, 17.0% lignin. With a crescent cultivation area in Portugal, *Cynara cardunculus* presents the requirements to a sustainable biorefinery concept, leading to the production of biobased ingredients with wide range of potential applications, such as biopolymers for agriculture, within a bioeconomy concept. By using sustainable extraction processes, with environmentally friend solvents potentiated by the application of non-conventional extraction and fractionation methodologies¹⁻²⁻³.

The present innovation achieves a complete value chain, intended to produce mulching films with different biodegradation rates, in order to fit

different agriculture/demands, potentiating the decrease of microplastics disposal within agriculture uses, potentiating sustainability at economic and environmental levels.

For farmers who care about sustainability at economic and environmental levels, CynaraMulch provides biodegradable plastics derived from non-feed crops, with high degradation rate, using lignocellulosic waste materials, so no plastics are left in the fields in the end of the season.

Acknowledgements

This work was also funded through FCT under the Project UIDB/05183/2020 to Mediterranean Institute for Agriculture Environment and Development (MED)

<https://doi.org/10.54499/UIDB/05183/2020>, Project LA/P/0121/2020 to CHANGE – Global Change and Sustainability Institute <https://doi.org/10.54499/LA/P/0121/2020>

The authors acknowledge EIT JumpStarter 2021 edition for the EIT Raw Materials 3rd prize award. This team was also winner of the prize of the “EIT Jumpstarter – X-KIC Prize”, a joint program by EIT Health, EIT RawMaterials EIT Food, EIT Innoenergy, EIT Urban Mobility and EIT Manufacturing. KICs are supported by the EIT, a body of the European Union.

References

1. Brás, T., Paulino, A.F.C., Neves, L.A., Crespo, J.G., Duarte, M.F., 2020. Ultrasound assisted extraction of cynaropicrin from *Cynara cardunculus* leaves: Optimization using the response surface methodology and the effect of pulse mode. *Industrial Crops and Products* 150, 112395, <https://doi.org/10>

2. Brás, T., Rosa, D., Gonçalves, A.C., Gomes, A.C., Brazinha, C., Neves, L.A., Duarte, M.F., Crespo, J.G., 2020. Fractionation of *Cynara cardunculus* ethanolic extracts using dianoanofiltration. *Separation and Purification Technology*, 117856, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2020.117856> (1016/j.indcrop.2020.112395)

3. Extraction processes for cynaropicrin present in leaves of *Cynara cardunculus* L. by, T. Bras, L. A. Neves, M. F. Ricardo, J. P. Crespo, (2019, April 10)

Food waste in Castelo Branco: Design, implementation, tools

Author

Beatriz Pereira – EVOX Technologies, Portugal

Nuno Silva – Castelo Branco's Municipalized Services, Portugal

Citation

Pereira, B., Silva, N., Food waste in Castelo Branco: Design, implementation, tools.

Effectively managing bio-waste is crucial for reducing environmental impact and promoting sustainability. Improperly handled bio-waste contributes to greenhouse gas emissions and overcrowded landfills, which intensifies climate change and squanders valuable resources. To combat these issues, Castelo Branco's Municipalized Services has started using an advanced waste management system developed by EVOX Technologies, which focuses on the city's urban cleaning and waste collection.

These efforts include the digitalization of waste services through EVOX's 360Waste system, enabling real-time monitoring of container fill levels and vehicles, optimized waste collection routes, RFID verification of container collection, and efficient container washing.

The "Leftovers are not waste" initiative is a key project created by Castelo Branco's Municipalized Services, which main goal is to encourage responsible resource use by promoting bio-waste collection from large producers like schools and restaurants. This initiative aims to minimize landfill use, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and transform organic waste into valuable resources such as compost and biogas.

Circular olive oil: A circular system at the olive grove level, contributing to increase olive oil sustainability and soil health

Author

Gonçalo da Cunha Ferreira – EntoGreen, Portugal

Citation

Ferreira , G.d.C. Circular olive oil: A circular system at the olive grove level, contributing to increase olive oil sustainability and soil health.

EntoGreen is an innovative Portuguese company in the bioindustrial sector that uses insects as a central tool to convert by-products from agro-industrial sector into added value products for animals, plants and soil. In this talk, EntoGreen will present one of its concepts, “The Circular Olive Oil”, in which insects are used to transform olive pomace, which was found to be an excellent food source for insect larvae, into organic fertilizer, protein and insect oil. In this way, the olive oil industry solves a problem by repurposing waste but also leads to the production of high-quality protein for animal feed and fertilizer, which has shown positive effects on soil health, while increasing the sector’s sustainability. The insect-based protein produced comes in two forms: dry, to be added to animal feed, and a protein-rich oil that can be used in various industries. Due to the massive amounts of wasted food products and the need for a larger protein supply to sustain population’s growth, solutions like the introduction of insects in human consumption are being considered, not to mention that insects offer economic, nutritional, and sustainability advantages over other animal proteins. Legal barriers, particularly concerning the use of other types of waste, are one of the biggest challenges EntoGreen faces.

Saving food to save the planet

Author

Victoria Albiñana – Too Good To Go, Spain

Citation

Albiñana, V. Saving food to save the planet.

Food waste is a massive issue

More than a third of all food worldwide is wasted (WFP, 2020). This presents us with social and economic challenges, as well as with ecological ones. While more than 2.500 million tonnes of food are wasted annually, 783 million people go hungry every day around the world. Also, from a financial perspective, our wasted food costs 1.1 trillion dollars each year. And it makes absolutely no sense for anyone. As for the economic impact, new data from WWF's Driven To Waste report shows that food waste is responsible for 10 percent of all greenhouse gas emissions. Food waste is thus one of the main drivers of global climate change (WWF, 2021). Because this share corresponds almost to that of the entire global road traffic (FAO, 2015) or to put it more bluntly: if food waste were a country, it would be the country with the third largest CO₂e emissions in the world – behind the USA and China and just ahead of India (FAO, 2016). This also impacts negatively on the use of primary materials. Producing food that ultimately goes to waste uses more than one quarter of available freshwater annually and takes up a land area larger than China (WWF, 2024).

There is an urgent need for action

Too Good To Go is a certified B Corp social impact company that connects users with partners to save unsold food and stop it from going to waste. With 95 million registered users and 160,000 active partners across 18 countries in Europe and North America, Too Good To Go operates the world's largest

marketplace for surplus food. Since its launch in 2016, Too Good To Go has helped to save over 330 million meals from going to waste, the equivalent to avoiding 891,000 tonnes of CO₂e, 267 billion litres of water use and 924 million m² of land use per year. According to Project Drawdown (2020), reducing food waste is the number one action you can take to help tackle climate change, by limiting the temperature rise to just 2°C by 2100. Putting a stop to food waste requires efforts by society as a whole at various levels. In addition to the app, Too Good To Go is also committed to reducing food waste in the areas of politics, education, companies and households. Through direct communication with the community through various communication channels and through large-scale campaigns with partner companies such as our cities against food waste, Too Good To Go is committed to more appreciation and knowledge about food. Also, as part of our active efforts to help reduce food waste in households, Too Good To Go created a powerful initiative with some of the world's leading consumer goods companies including Unilever, Danone, Carrefour, Nestle, Bel Group, and others, to incorporate Too Good To Go's bespoke 'Look-Smell-Taste' date label on their products with a Best Before date and to jointly communicate on the required behaviour change towards consumers. The label is printed on an estimated more than 6 billion packs of products with a Best Before date annually, encouraging consumers to trust their senses and 'Look, Smell and Taste' Best Before food items, before they waste them. Additionally, to achieve large-scale impact, we must continuously innovate the solutions we offer. We did so at the end of 2022 with the launch of 'Parcels' in some countries where we operate. This is a solution that empowers food manufacturers to unlock value from surplus food, maximising their profits and optimising their operations, while simultaneously offering consumers the chance to purchase surplus food at a fraction of the regular price. In January 2024, Too Good To Go launched Too Good To Go Platform, the end-to-end surplus food management solution that enables grocery retailers, from supermarkets to convenience stores, to unlock value from excess inventory. Powered by AI, Too Good To Go Platform seamlessly tracks and helps to redistribute surplus; and is the only system of its kind, thanks to its integration with the

world's largest consumer marketplace for surplus food, with over 95 million registered users.

Regulatory action is also needed

Many EU member states have already shown that food waste can be reduced with the right legislation. This is shown, among other things, by reports from the European Court of Auditors and by the experience of other European countries like Austria, Italy, Poland and France. In Portugal, Decreto-Lei n.º 102-D/2020, de 10 de dezembro oblige companies to take measures against food waste, being also mandatory for the above companies to share their data on food waste. From 1st January 2024 a new prohibition applies to retail, industry, wholesalers and the hospitality sector to discard food which can still be consumed. Finally, Lei n.º 62/2021, de 19 de agosto foresees that municipalities shall develop their own anti food waste plan. At Too Good To Go, we believe that the following policy measures should still be implemented in order to improve action against food waste in the country:

- Anti food waste measures throughout the whole of the value chain and applicable to all food operators, without distinction;
- Setting food waste reduction targets for every sector of the value chain;
- Develop and implement an effective food waste measurement & reporting system;
- Introduce a mandatory food waste hierarchy which prioritises prevention, followed by redistribution for human consumption, animal feed, revalorization, recycling, recovery and disposal;
- Applying incentives so that preferable options become both easier and cheaper for food businesses to apply. Less preferable options (those with high resource requirements and negative environmental impact) should become more difficult and expensive to apply, as a result;

- In order to achieve a change in consumer behaviour, it is necessary to integrate the topic into the school curricula in order to sensitise to the major negative impact of food waste and educate people about the proper way to handle food. Policymaking is a very valuable instrument that can reduce food waste, help us meet net zero and reduce hunger

Selected Oral Communications

Abstract III.1 Food waste mitigation as feed: Microbiological, chemical and nutritional characterisation

Author

Oliveira, J. – Egas Moniz Center for Interdisciplinary Research (CiiEM) Egas Moniz School of Health & Science, Caparica, Almada, Portugal

Trindade, A. – Egas Moniz Center for Interdisciplinary Research (CiiEM) Egas Moniz School of Health & Science, Caparica, Almada, Portugal

Murta, D. – Egas Moniz Center for Interdisciplinary Research (CiiEM) Egas Moniz School of Health & Science, Caparica, Almada, Portugal; Ingredient Odyssey SA (EntoGreen), Santarém, Portugal

Barroso, H. – Egas Moniz Center for Interdisciplinary Research (CiiEM) Egas Moniz School of Health & Science, Caparica, Almada, Portugal

Gonçalves, L. – Egas Moniz Center for Interdisciplinary Research (CiiEM) Egas Moniz School of Health & Science, Caparica, Almada, Portugal

Bernardo, A. – Egas Moniz Center for Interdisciplinary Research (CiiEM) Egas Moniz School of Health & Science, Caparica, Almada, Portugal

Brito, J – Egas Moniz Center for Interdisciplinary Research (CiiEM) Egas Moniz School of Health & Science, Caparica, Almada, Portugal

Assunção, R., – Egas Moniz Center for Interdisciplinary Research (CiiEM) Egas Moniz School of Health & Science, Caparica, Almada, Portugal

Citation

Oliveira, J., Trindade, A., Murta, D., Barroso, H., Gonçalves, L., Bernardo, A., Brito, J., Assunção, R. Food waste mitigation as feed: Microbiological, chemical and nutritional characterisation.

The population is rising exponentially, yielding considerable implications for planetary health (Wilmoth et al., 2023). One consequence is the rise in the production of organic waste, with food waste representing the majority of this waste (Kaza et al., 2018). This is an environmental and public health issue, as it contributes to greenhouse gas emissions, the spread of pathogens, and the excessive consumption of water and land resources (Alvarado et al., 2021; Jafari et al., 2020; Otles & Kartal, 2018). Efforts to reduce food loss and waste at households are increasingly promoted globally, such as utilising leftovers, donating surplus food to charitable organisations, and practising smarter cooking techniques (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 2023). However, on an industrial level, research is being carried out into the use of organic waste as a potential animal feed and organic fertiliser (Fowles & Nansen, 2019; Purnamasari & Khasanah, 2022; Surendra et al., 2020). Nonetheless, ruminant PAPs, that may be present on food waste, are prohibited as animal feed (Regulation (EC) No 999/2001). Furthermore, the absence of research on the contaminants found in food waste is another reason for this prohibition (EFSA, 2015). In this study, we aim to conduct a microbiological, chemical, and nutritional analysis of food waste in order to characterize and comprehend the significance of the potential contaminants in this feed source. Our methodology comprises microbiological techniques and chemical, chromatographic, and immunoenzymatic methods to assess food waste. A comprehensive assessment of the contaminants present in organic waste are being conducted and comprehend its potential impact on humans, animals, and the environment. In the near future, this type of recycling could offer a sustainable option for managing waste, while also presenting an opportunity to contribute to the demand for new sustainable protein sources in light of a growing population.

Acknowledgments

This study is funded by a PhD grant by Fundação para a Ciência e Tencnologia (grant number 2022.13540.BDANA); by Agenda Mobilizadora Insectera (<https://www.insectera.pt>) and by CiiEM Investiga “Flywaste” and CiiEM Investiga “GenFly”, both through Project UIDB/04585/2020, funded by FCT.

References

- Alvarado, R., Tillaguango, B., Dagar, V., Ahmad, M., Işık, C., Méndez, P., & Toledo, E. (2021). Ecological footprint, economic complexity and natural resources rents in Latin America: Empirical evidence using quantile regressions. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 318, 128585. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.128585>
- EFSA. (2015). Risk profile related to production and consumption of insects as food and feed. *EFSA Journal*, 13(10), 4257. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2015.4257>
- Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. (2023). Reducing food waste in the household: Simple tips that generate win-wins for people and the planet. <https://www.fao.org/platform-food-loss-waste/food-waste/food-waste-reduction/how-to-reduce-your-food-waste/en>
- Fowles, T. M., & Nansen, C. (2019). Insect-based bioconversion: Value from food waste. In *Food Waste Management: Solving the Wicked Problem* (pp. 321–346). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-20561-4_12

Jafari, Y., Dudu, H., Roson, R., & Sartori, M. (2020). Can Food Waste Reduction in Europe Help to Increase Food Availability and Reduce Pressure on Natural Resources Globally? *German Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 69(2), 143–168. <https://doi.org/10.30430/69.2020.2.143-168>

Kaza, S., Yao, L., Bhada-Tata, P., & Woerden, F. Van. (2018). WHAT A WASTE 2.0 A Global Snapshot of Solid Waste Management to 2050 OVERVIEW; Otles, S., & Kartal, C. (2018). Food Waste Valorization. In *Sustainable Food Systems from Agriculture to Industry* (pp. 371–399). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-811935-8.00011-1>

Purnamasari, L., & Khasanah, H. (2022). Black Soldier Fly (*Hermetia illucens*) as a Potential Agent of Organic Waste Bioconversion. *ASEAN Journal on Science and Technology for Development*, 39(2). <https://doi.org/10.29037/ajstd.780>

Regulation (EC) No 999/2001 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 May 2001 laying down rules for the prevention, control and eradication of certain transmissible spongiform encephalopathies. (n.d.)

Surendra, K. C., Tomberlin, J. K., van Huis, A., Cammack, J. A., Heckmann, L. H. L., & Khanal, S. K. (2020). Rethinking organic wastes bioconversion: Evaluating the potential of the black soldier fly (*Hermetia illucens* (L.)) (Diptera: Stratiomyidae) (BSF). In *Waste Management* (Vol. 117, pp. 58–80). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2020.07.050>

Wilmoth, J., Menozzi, C., Bassarsky, L., & Gu, D. (2023). As the World's Population Surpasses 8 Billion, What Are the Implications for Planetary Health and Sustainability?

Posters

Poster III.1 Greener technologies towards the valorization of olive oil pomace

Author

Silva, L. A. P. – MORE – Mountains of Research Collaborative Laboratory – Association, Côa Valley and Inland Center Region Office, Mêda, Portugal
Pereira, R. N. – Centre of Biological Engineering, University of Minho, Braga, Portugal
Vicente, A. A. – Centre of Biological Engineering, University of Minho, Braga, Portugal

Citation

Silva, L. A.P., Pereira, R.N., Vicente, A.A. Greener technologies towards the valorization of olive oil pomace.

The olive oil sector is extremely important to the economy of countries of southern Europe given this is where most of the worldwide production is concentrated (ca. 67%) (Eurostat., 2020). Portugal produced more than 2 million tons of olives for olive oil production in 2021 and 2022. (PORDATA, 2023). There are well known environmental issues related to this sector's main by-product, olive pomace, such as its high organic load, low pH and phytotoxicity, largely due to the presence of phenolic compounds (mainly oleuropein, tyrosol, and hydroxytyrosol). However, these bioactive compounds' antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory and anticarcinogenic activities provide several health benefits (Souilem et al., 2017). Thus, extensive efforts have been dedicated to the valorization of this residue through green

technologies such as pulsed electric fields, ohmic heating and ultrasound, microwave, and sub- and supercritical fluid extractions, among other technologies (Zhu et al., 2020). This presentation will discuss the different technologies available and their optimization potential in increasing the recovery efficiency of olive pomace's bioactive compounds, thus stimulating a step forward in the sector's sustainability and circularity.

References

Eurostat. (2020). Agriculture, forestry and fishery statistics : 2020 edition. Publications Office of the European Union. PORDATA. (2023). Olive production – Mainland Portugal.

Souilem, S., El-Abbassi, A., Kiai, H., Hafidi, A., Sayadi, S., & Galanakis, C. M. (2017). Olive oil production sector: Environmental effects and sustainability challenges. In *Olive Mill Waste: Recent Advances for Sustainable Management* (pp. 1–28). Elsevier Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-805314-0.00001-7>

Zhu, Z., Gavahian, M., Barba, F. J., Roselló-Soto, E., Bursać Kovačević, D., Putnik, P., & Denoya, G. I. (2020). Valorization of waste and by-products from food industries through the use of innovative technologies. In *Agri-Food Industry Strategies for Healthy Diets and Sustainability: New Challenges in Nutrition and Public Health* (pp. 249–266). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-817226-1.00011-4>

Poster III.2 Full plate: Meals without leftovers or waste

Author

Soares, S.S. – Ciência Viva - Agência Nacional para a Cultura Científica e Tecnológica, Lisboa, Portugal

Citation

Soares, S.S. Full plate: Meals without leftovers or waste.

The *Ciência Viva* Science Farms initiative is a programme that supports the adjustment of Portuguese society regarding emerging global challenges, focused particularly on the valorisation of local agri-food ecosystems and on the reinforcement of social and territorial cohesion, with a perspective of innovation and development.

This program is materialized through the creation of a network of *Ciência Viva* Science Farms spread across the country. Each Science Farm is a public venue for contact with science, culture, and innovation with a mission focused on education, promotion of scientific culture and valorisation of local resources.

With the aim of promoting social debate and ideation, the Cherry and Ideas Science Farm by *Ciência Viva* (at Fundão) gathered at the same table different stakeholders: from local policy makers to producers and educational and social institutions – for a discussion group on local strategies against food waste.

This discussion group was divided into two sequential moments – “1. From problem to action” and “2. Rooting ideas” – in which the territory was diagnosed, and challenges and priority lines of intervention were identified (first moment) and local action strategies were proposed to avoid wastage of food (second moment).

Among the main challenges identified, the need to promote food literacy in families stands out. The Cherry and Ideas Science Farm by *Ciência Viva* will mainly contribute to this objective through the promotion of events (such as “Meet the Scientist”) and training sessions for children and adults, and through the creation of open educational resources produced, which continue the awareness-raising work already carried out by schools in the region in this field.

In conclusion, as true productive fields, the *Ciência Viva* Science Farms are the ideal stage for sharing knowledge, raising awareness, and learning about food and the development of a healthy and sustainable relationship with food, from land to table.

Acknowledgments

The author would like to thank all the participants involved in the discussion group described here for their contributions. Thanks to the Municipality of Fundão, Gardunha 21 Development Agency and Professional School of Fundão (for hosting the event) for making this work possible.

Poster III.3 Effect of different bulking agents on the composting time of olive pomace

Author

Segatelli, A. B. M. – Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança (IPB), Bragança, Portugal; Laboratório Associado para a Sustentabilidade e Tecnologia em Regiões de Montanha (SusTEC), IPB, Portugal
Figueiredo, D. – MORE-Laboratorio Colaborativo, Edifício Brigantia Ecopark, Bragança, Portugal

Figueiredo, T. – Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança (IPB), Bragança, Portugal; Laboratório Associado para a Sustentabilidade e Tecnologia em Regiões de Montanha (SusTEC), IPB, Portugal
Hernández, Z. – Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança (IPB), Bragança, Portugal; Laboratório Associado para a Sustentabilidade e Tecnologia em Regiões de Montanha (SusTEC), IPB, Portugal

Citation

Segatelli, A. B. M., Figueiredo, D., Figueiredo, T., Hernández, Z. Effect of different bulking agents on the composting time of olive pomace.

Portugal is the fourth largest olive oil producer in the EU, with an annual average production of 100Gg. This results in a large production of olive pomace (OP), phytotoxic and high moisture by-product. The aim was assessment the composting process of OP using distinct bulking agents (AE) over time: almond husk (AL) and forest biomass (FB). Four compositions were tested: BA (100%OP, C/N 19); CA (50%OP+50%AL, C/N 33); BF (50%OP+50%FB, C/N 26); CABF (50%OP+25%AL+25%FB, C/N 33) at various composting stages. The composting process extended up to 105 days, during

which samples were analyzed by physical-chemical methods, such as routine chemical characteristics (pH, ash, C/N) and phytotoxicity index (MLV). One-way ANOVA was employed for statistical analysis. The results indicate an initial mesophilic phase (<7 days), with an acidic pH and high phytotoxicity, especially in the BA pile. The compost piles quickly reached the thermophilic phase in the first 20 days, with high temperatures during the first 60 days (>45°C), being reactivated by turning and humidifying until 90 days. During this period, CA and BA piles showed an increase in pH values (~7.8) and Nt (1.6-2.1mg/kg), showing that the ammonification process of organic remains occurs early in the thermophilic phase. At the beginning of the maturation phase, all treatments had a C/N ratio of 15% and had lost phytotoxicity, indicating that the composting process had ended. Highlighted BF pile, which lost its phytotoxicity at the beginning of the thermophilic phase, with BA being the last. During all process, treatments with AE had a weight loss of 15-20%, while the BA pile had lost ~30%. In conclusion, the presence of AE positively influenced the composting process, accelerating the loss of OP phytotoxicity, but has the disadvantage of greater N loss. Given the high cost of CA, BF may be a cheaper alternative, making OP composting economically sustainable.

Acknowledgments

The research has been supported by BIOMA Project (POCI-01-0247-FEDER-046112) and REACT UE project FORESTWATERUP (POCI-07-62G4-FEDER-181557). The authors thank the company Acushla for facilitating the conditions to carry out these industrial tests.

Poster III.4 Zero waste dairy: Whey inclusion in bread, a newly developed product

Author

Rodrigues, A. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Cristóvão, M. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Baptista, C. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Silveira, A. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Paulo, L. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Beato, H. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Vasconcelos, V. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Espírito Santo, C. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal; Centre for Functional Ecology, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal; Centre for Functional Ecology, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Brandão, I. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal; Centre for Functional Ecology, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Rodrigues, A., Cristóvão, M., Baptista, C., Silveira, A., Paulo, L., Beato, H., Vasconcelos, V., Espírito Santo, C., Brandão, I. Zero waste dairy: Whey inclusion in bread, a newly developed product.

The dairy industry, with cheese being the most popular, produces over 25 million tons yearly, primarily in Europe which accounts more than 50% of the production, according to Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAOSTAT, 2022).

However, cheese production generates substantial wastewater, approximately nine liters of whey for each kilogram of cheese (Kosikowski, 1979), from which we can estimate resulting in over 225 thousand million liters of whey globally. Additionally, due to the high biochemical oxygen demand, high biodegradability index, low alkalinity, and retains approximately 55% of milk nutrients, whey remains undervalued and pose a threat to the environment (Kosikowski, 1979; Guimarães et al., 2010).

In response to this environmental threat, governments are enacting policies to minimize contamination, and the dairy industry seeks more sustainable practices. One promising solution involves utilizing whey in popular food products like bakery items by substituting water with whey, potentially leading to zero waste in the dairy industry.

Our study involved producing bread using whey as a complete water replacement ($n=3$) and comparing it to control water-based breads ($n=3$). In nutritional analyses, only fat content showed significant differences ($p>0.05$). Sensory analysis via the hedonic test resulted in a rating average of 7 for whey bread on a scale of 1 to 9, with no significant difference ($p>0.05$) compared to the control bread. In terms of buying intent, 96% would buy the whey bread and 90% the control bread.

In conclusion, our study demonstrates the successful incorporation of whey into bread production with minimal nutritional differences, strong consumer preference, and buying intent similar to traditional bread. This highlights the potential for whey to be fully integrated into bread production, reducing the environmental impact of cheese production and promoting sustainable food practices.

Acknowledgments

FUSILLI (European Union's Horizon 2020 under grant agreement No. 101000717).

References

FAO.(2022). Food and agriculture data. www.fao.org/faostat/en/#home. Accessed in October 17,2023.

Guimarães, P. M., Teixeira, J. A., & Domingues, L. (2010). Fermentation of lactose to bio-ethanol by yeasts as part of integrated solutions for the valorisation of cheese whey. *Biotechnology advances*, 28(3), 375-384.

Kosikowski, F. V. (1979). Whey utilization and whey products. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 62(7), 1149-1160.

Poster III.5 Alternative approaches for the treatment of swine wastewater

Author

Esperanço, P. – Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Coimbra Agriculture School, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal; Research Centre for Natural Resources Environment and Society (CERNAS), Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal
Rodrigues, C. – Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Coimbra Agriculture School, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal
Costa, R. P. R. – Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Coimbra Agriculture School, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal; Research Centre for Natural Resources Environment and Society (CERNAS), Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Esperanço, P., Rodrigues, C., Costa, R.P.R. Alternative approaches for the treatment of swine wastewater.

Methods for the treatment of swine wastewater (SWW) are receiving increased attention, due to the rising world population and demand for animal protein, that leads to more farms and animal wastes around the world. The conventional wastewater treatment methods are limited by the high content of pollutants found in SWW, so there is a need to comprehend how different wastewater treatment technologies, as well as the combination of them, will act on this high chemical/biochemical oxygen demand wastewaters.

In this work, a physico-chemical treatment (PCT) through flocculation (Flocua ES 9062) alone and in combination with an activated sludge treatment (AST) for the removal of organic matter on the SWW was studied. Parameters such as total solids (TS), total volatile solids (TVS), chemical oxygen demand (COD), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN) and total phosphorous (TP) were quantified (Table 1) and determined the efficiency of removal from the SWW after each process.

As per the removal efficiency results, PCT only provided the removal of 58,3 % of the total solids, while PCT + AST provided 57,4 %, for the TVS the results were even better with removals of 92,5 % in the PCT and 90,0 % on the PCT + AST which suggests that the AST compromises the removal of solids compared to PCT. For the other parameters the PCT + AST led to greater efficacy on the treatment of the effluent. For COD, PCT led to the removal of 85,3 % and after AST 94,2 %. For BOD was determined a removal of 75.7 % in PCT and 95,7 % in AST. In TKN were obtained removals of 90.8 % in the PCT and 98,5 % in the AST. PCT led to 72.6 % removal of total phosphorous and the PCT + AST 88.0 %.

Results are expressed as mean values \pm standard deviation of three independent analyses (n = 3)
SWW – swine wastewater/slurry; PCT – after the PCT treatment; PCT + AST – after the PCT and AST treatment.

	TS	TVS	COD	BOD	TKN	PT
mg/L						
SWW	13980 \pm 687	8700 \pm 679	21967 \pm 702	3500 \pm 707	2017 \pm 24	92 \pm 0,75
PCT	5835 \pm 220	653 \pm 31	3237 \pm 230	850 \pm 71	186 \pm 18	25 \pm 2,4
PCT + AST	5950 \pm 902	867 \pm 101	1265 \pm 262	150 \pm 71	30 \pm 4	11 \pm 1

In conclusion, the combination of these two strategies leads to a better treatment than when applied alone, being promising for the treatment of SWW, but still further studies are required.

Acknowledgments

This work was financed by national funds by FCT – Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia, I.P., through the CERNAS project (UIDB/00681/2020). Acknowledge to the staff of BioSmart for providing the swine wastewater and to Aquafloc for providing the flocculant used in this work.

References

- Ding, W., Cheng, S., Yu, L., & Huang, H. (2017). Effective swine wastewater treatment by combining microbial fuel cells with flocculation. *Chemosphere*, 182, 567–573. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2017.05.006>
- Domingues, E., Fernandes, E., Gomes, J., & Martins, R. C. (2021). Advanced oxidation processes perspective regarding swine wastewater treatment. *Science of the Total Environment*, 776, 145958. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.145958>
- Guo, J., Yang, C., & Zeng, G. (2013). Treatment of swine wastewater using chemically modified zeolite and bioflocculant from activated sludge. *Bioresource Technology*, 143, 289–297. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2013.06.003>
- Nagarajan, D., Kusmayadi, A., Yen, H.-W., Dong, C.-D., Lee, D.-J., & Chang, J.-S. (2019). Current advances in biological swine wastewater treatment using microalgae-based processes. *Bioresource Technology*, 289, 121718. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2019.121718>

Suzuki, K., Waki, M., Yasuda, T., Fukumoto, Y., Kuroda, K., Sakai, T., Suzuki, N., Suzuki, R., & Matsuba, K. (2010). Distribution of phosphorus, copper and zinc in activated sludge treatment process of swine wastewater. *Bioresource Technology*, 101(23), 9399–9404. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2010.07.014>

Waki, M., Yasuda, T., Fukumoto, Y., Béline, F., & Magrí, A. (2020). Numerical assessment of nitrogen removal from swine wastewater in activated sludge systems: Comparison between continuous and intermittent aeration. *Bioresource Technology Reports*, 11, 100492. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biteb.2020.100492>

Waki, M., Yasuda, T., Fukumoto, Y., Béline, F., & Magrí, A. (2018). Treatment of swine wastewater in continuous activated sludge systems under different dissolved oxygen conditions: Reactor operation and evaluation using modelling. *Bioresource Technology*, 250, 574–582. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2017.11.078>

Theme IV – Endogenous genetic resources

Synopsis - Keynote Speakers

Wild endogenous genetic resources in the cultivar area: Case studies

Author

Maria Margarida Ribeiro – Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, School of Agriculture (ESACB), Castelo Branco, Portugal; CERNAS, Research Center for Natural Resources, Environment and Society, Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal; CEF, Forest Research Centre, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Superior Institute of Agronomy, Lisbon University, Lisbon, Portugal

Citation

Ribeiro, M.M. Wild endogenous genetic resources in the cultivar area: Case studies.

This talk summarizes three studies based on two wild regional endogenous resources. The first aimed to study climate change impact on *Cistus ladanifer* L. (rockrose) future potential distribution, and, looking into the past, to identify putative glacial refugia and migration routes, in a typically drought and temperature-resistant Mediterranean species. Two scenarios and time

slices were used for future projections. The precipitation variables had decreasing importance in the ensemble model, obtained by averaging four used algorithms, followed by the temperature variables. The past distribution projections were congruent with the fossil record and genetics. This species will dramatically be affected by global warming, despite its drought and temperature resilience. Northward migration is unlikely to happen in the future, but a collapse westward towards the Portuguese coast was pictured.

The second study described the common garden results, with the same species, set in the ESACB campus, which produces the increasingly valued labdanum resin. The experiment included one plant from distinct families (5) collected in 10 populations distributed range-wide (2 of them local) in each one of 5 blocks, aiming at selecting the best-performing individuals to build an improvement population. The total height and the crown-crossed diameters were measured. The plant volume, as an inverted cone, was computed. Two southern populations from the subspecies *africanus* (Morocco), one from the south of Spain, and the Bragança population had the highest accumulated mortality. The population with the lowest one also had the best results in growth, a nearby trial Spanish population. The local populations performed equally well, both in height and in volume, and the population from the subspecies *sulcatus* had the worst performance. The heritability generally decreased with time, valuing less than 40% for both height and volume, in the last measurement. The populations and families will further be evaluated regarding both biomass productivity and metabolite productivity and profile, using a destructive analysis approach.

The third study aimed to understand *Asphodelus bento-rainhae* subsp. *bento-rainhae* niche evolution for conservation purposes, a taxon with endangered species status. The land use and land cover changes will have a major impact on future species distribution than climate change, even in the worst-case scenario. To prevent this endemic species extinction in the future, conservation measures ought to be taken, namely species monitoring, replantation, germplasm conservation, and guidelines for habitat conservation.

Acknowledgments

The CULTIVAR project (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020) and the Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia grants UIDB/00239/2020, UIDB/00681/2020, and UIDB/05183/2020, funded this work.

References

Almeida, A.M., Ribeiro, M.M., Ferreira, M.R., Roque, N., Quintela-Sabaris, C., Fernandez, P., 2023. Big data help to define climate change challenges for the typical Mediterranean species *Cistus ladanifer* L. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution* 11, 12. [10.3389/fevo.2023.1136224](https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2023.1136224)

Almeida, A.M., Delgado, F., Roque, N., Ribeiro, M.M., Fernandez, P., 2023. Multitemporal land use and cover analysis coupled with climatic change scenarios to protect the endangered taxon *Asphodelus bento-rainhae* subsp. *bento-rainhae*, *Plants*. [10.3390/plants1216291](https://doi.org/10.3390/plants1216291)

Selected Oral Communications

Abstract IV.1 *Ex situ* conservation of agri-food germplasm: Case studies from the CULTIVAR project in Portugal

Author

Baltazar, E. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Calçada Martim de Freitas, Coimbra, Portugal

Lopes, T. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Calçada Martim de Freitas, Coimbra, Portugal

Pedrosa, A. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Calçada Martim de Freitas, Coimbra, Portugal

Correia, M. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Calçada Martim de Freitas, Coimbra, Portugal

Duarte, D. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Calçada Martim de Freitas, Coimbra, Portugal

Figueiredo, B. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Calçada Martim de Freitas, Coimbra, Portugal

Caeiro, S. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Calçada Martim de Freitas, Coimbra, Portugal

Cardoso, A.– University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Calçada Martim de Freitas, Coimbra, Portugal

Paiva, H.– University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Calçada Martim de Freitas, Coimbra, Portugal

Canhoto, J.– University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Calçada Martim de Freitas, Coimbra, Portugal

Correia, S.– University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Calçada Martim de Freitas, Coimbra, Portugal; InnovPlantProtect CoLab, Estrada de Gil Vaz, Elvas, Portugal

Citation

Baltazar, E., Lopes, T., Pedrosa, A., Correia, M., Duarte, D., Figueiredo, B., Caeiro, S., Cardoso, A., Paiva, H., Canhoto, J., Correia, S. *Ex situ* conservation of agri-food germplasm: Case studies from the CULTIVAR project in Portugal.

The Centro region of Portugal is particularly rich in agrobiodiversity. It combines the cultivation of local varieties with modern horticulture and fruit growing. Nevertheless, due to a combination of several factors, such as the abandonment of rural areas and the aging of the farming population, the genetic diversity of several crops in this region is at high risk of erosion. Moreover, several crops face significant constraints caused by extreme climatic events and emerging diseases. To ensure the adaptability and resilience of such production systems, the characterisation and conservation of the existing agrobiodiversity are imperative. The *ex situ* conservation of these traditionally cultivated varieties, underutilised crops, and their wild relatives represents a significant challenge with important environmental and economic consequences, as they represent a fundamental source of genetic diversity required for the successful implementation of breeding programs towards adaptability and resilience to different abiotic and biotic stresses. In this context, the main objective of this work was to implement strategies

for the *ex situ* conservation, namely by *in vitro* culture establishments, of different genetic resources identified and valorised within the framework of the CULTIVAR Integrated Programme (<https://icultivar.pt>).

Several endogenous resources with agri-food and conservation relevance were identified and selected, including several fruit crops (e.g. *Prunus spp.*, *Cydonia oblonga*, *Citrus spp.*). Efficient protocols for *in vitro* establishment and micropropagation were established according to the requirements of each culture.

The use of such biotechnological tools for *ex situ* conservation of these traditional varieties, plays an important role in their protection. Also, the maintenance of such germplasm in controlled laboratory and/or nursery conditions allows for the evaluation of stress resilience and further selection of valuable germplasm for local producers and for the development of future breeding programs with strong impact in the region.

Acknowledgments

This research was funded by project CULTIVAR (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), cofinanced by the Regional Operational Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020, and European Union, and supported by the R&D Unit Centre for Functional Ecology—Science for People and the Planet (CFE) UIDB/04004/2020 and Associated Laboratory TERRA LA/P/0092/2020 financed by FCT/MCTES through national funds (PIDDAC). EB is the recipient of the fellowship UI/BD/150981/2021 from the FCT/MCTES.

Abstract IV.2 *In vitro* establishment and molecular analysis of the micrograft union formation in almond (*Prunus dulcis* (mill.) D. A. Webb)

Author

Lopes, T. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Pedrosa, A. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Caeiro, S. – InnovPlantProtect CoLAB, Elvas, Portugal

Paiva, H. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Correia, M. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Baltazar, E. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Caeiro, A. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Marum, L. – Centro de Biotecnologia Agrícola e Agro-Alimentar do Alentejo (CEBAL)/ Instituto Politécnico de Beja (IPBeja), Beja, Portugal; MED-Instituto Mediterrâneo para a Agricultura, Ambiente e Desenvolvimento, CEBAL, Beja, Portugal

Canhoto, J. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Correia, S. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal;

InnovPlantProtect CoLAB, Elvas, Portugal

Citation

Lopes, T., Pedrosa, A., Caeiro, S., Paiva, H., Correia, M., Baltazar, E., Caeiro, A., Marum, L., Canhoto, J., Correia, S. *In vitro* establishment and molecular analysis of the micrograft union formation in almond (*Prunus dulcis* (Mill.) D. A. Webb).

Due to the current climatic scenario, natural resources management is essential, and agro biodiversity characterization and conservation are key points in the adaptability and resilience of productive systems. Nevertheless, for several important crops, traditional varieties have been neglected favouring commercially available materials, often with improved production traits and adaptability to modern agronomic techniques. This may lead to irreversible losses of resilient genetic resources better adapted to local edaphoclimatic conditions. Considering these premises, the work here presented aimed to i) conserve, by *in vitro* culture techniques, traditional almond (*Prunus dulcis* (Mill.) D.A. Webb) varieties, and ii) characterize the molecular mechanisms underlying the micrografting success of those varieties. Almond is a very important fruit crop, mainly produced by grafting. As micrografting consists of a functional union of a scion and a rootstock carried out *in vitro*, this system was used to evaluate the molecular mechanisms involved in scion-rootstock interactions, like wound-responsive and auxin-related factors. Using as starting material Portuguese traditional and commercially available varieties the workflow involved the *in vitro* establishment of those materials, their micropropagation and micrografting of the micropropagated shoots. Homografts of bitter almond (BA) and heterografts composed by BA or GF677 (GF) rootstocks and "Lauranne" (L) or "Ferraduel" (F) varieties as scions, were established. Sampling for IAA quantification by HPLC and qPCR analysis was made before grafting (t0) and 7 (t1) and 21 (t3) days after grafting (dag). Regarding GFxL micrografts, gene expression analysis of *WIND1* transcription factor appeared to be down-regulated, decreasing from t0 to t2. This was also observed for GFxF. On the contrary, *ESRI* was up-regulated. Total IAA quantification showed no significant differences between genotypes at t0. However, in GFxL micrografts an increase of IAA was observed from t0 to t1 followed by a significant decrease at t2. These results were in accordance with the auxin

receptor *TIR1* which expression decreased from t0 to t2. Down-regulation of *IAA26* was also observed in BAxF. These results were correlated with the survival rates of each scion-rootstock combination, providing important cues about the molecular mechanisms underlying micrografting success.

Acknowledgments

This research was funded by project CULTIVAR (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), cofinanced by the Regional Operational Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020, and European Union, and supported by the R&D Unit Centre for Functional Ecology—Science for People and the Planet (CFE) UIDB/04004/2020 and Associated Laboratory TERRA LA/P/0092/2020 financed by FCT/MCTES through national funds (PIDDAC). Inov-Amendo-AL: Microenxertia in vitro de amendoeiras seleccionadas para a promoção do amendoal no Alentejo (ALT20-03-0246-FEDER-000068) supported by Program Alentejo 2020, through the European Fund for Regional Development (ERDF), within the scope of the Collective Action Support System - Transfer of scientific and technological knowledge - Domain of Competitiveness and Internationalization. Authors also acknowledge FCT for Projects UIDB/05183/2020 to Mediterranean Institute for Agriculture, Environment and Development (MED), LA/P/0121/2020 to Global Change and Sustainability Institute (CHANGE). And for Contrato – Programa to L. Marum (CEECINST/00131/2018). Tércia Lopes is the recipient of the fellowship 2022.12898.BD from the FCT/MCTES.

Abstract IV.3 *Lavandula* section *stoechas* from Beira Interior: Chemical and morphological approaches

Author

Domingues, J. – CBPBI – Centro de Biotecnologia de Plantas da Beira Interior, Quinta Sra. de Mércules, Castelo Branco, Portugal; CICS-UBI- Centro de Investigação em Ciências da Saúde, Universidade da Beira Interior, Av. Infante D. Henrique, Covilhã, Portugal

Ribeiro, S. – Centro de Investigação em Agronomia, Alimentos, Ambiente e Paisagem (LEAF - Linking Landscape, Environment, Agriculture and Food), Instituto Superior de Agronomia, Universidade de Lisboa, Tapada da Ajuda, Lisboa, Portugal; Departamento de Paisagem, Ambiente e Ordenamento, Escola de Ciência e Tecnologia, Universidade de Évora, Évora, Portugal

Coelho, M. T. – Centro de Biotecnologia de Plantas da Beira Interior, Quinta Sra. de Mércules, Castelo Branco, Portugal; IPCB-ESA – Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Escola Superior Agrária, Quinta Sra. de Mércules, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Barroca, C. – Centro de Biotecnologia de Plantas da Beira Interior, Quinta Sra. de Mércules, Castelo Branco, Portugal; IPCB-ESA – Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Escola Superior Agrária, Quinta Sra. de Mércules, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Canavarro, C. – IPCB-ESA – Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Escola Superior Agrária, Quinta Sra. de Mércules, Castelo Branco, Portugal; CERNAS-IPCB – Centro de Estudos de Recursos Naturais, Ambiente e Sociedade, Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Portugal

Gonçalves, J. C. – CBPBI – Centro de Biotecnologia de Plantas da Beira Interior, Quinta Sra. de Mércules, Castelo Branco, Portugal; IPCB-ESA – Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Escola Superior Agrária, Quinta Sra. de Mércules, Castelo Branco, Portugal; CERNAS-IPCB – Centro de Estudos de Recursos Naturais, Ambiente e Sociedade, Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Portugal

Roque, N. – IPCB-ESA – Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Escola Superior Agrária, Quinta Sra. de Mércules, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Delgado, F. – CBPBI – Centro de Biotecnologia de Plantas da Beira Interior, Quinta Sra. de Mércules, Castelo Branco, Portugal; IPCB-ESA – Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Escola Superior Agrária, Quinta Sra. de Mércules, Castelo Branco, Portugal; CERNAS-IPCB – Centro de Estudos de Recursos Naturais, Ambiente e Sociedade, Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Portugal

Citation

Domingues, J., Ribeiro, S., Coelho, M.T., Barroca, C., Canavarro, C., Gonçalves, J.C., Roque, N., Delgado, F. *Lavandula* section *Stoechas* from Beira Interior: Chemical and morphological approaches.

Due to the hybridization and polymorphism phenomena that naturally occur in the genus *Lavandula*, it can be challenging to define species and subspecies, which can lead to inaccurate labeling of their by-products, such as essential oils. To try to distinguish between species and subspecies, morphological and chemical characterizations are essential assessments.

In this study, 120 *Lavandula* species specimens from eight different places in the Beira Interior region were collected for their aerial parts. Cebolais-Castelo Branco (CB), Penha Garcia (PG), Vila de Rei (VR), Ocreza-Castelo Branco (O), Vila Velha de Ródão (VV), Proença-a-Nova (PN), Penamacor (MC), and Oleiros (OL) were the locations for the collection. Only *Lavandula pedunculata* samples were gathered in Ocreza. To create a complete view, aerial parts of specimens of the *L. stoechas* complex were morphologically analyzed. The volatile profile of the essential oils of each specimen's, namely necrodane compounds (*trans*- α -necrodiyl acetate), was analysed by GC-MS. The information on ecological, edaphic, and physiographic traits was also extracted for each specimen from eight sites.

It is proven by the morphological study that among the 120 specimens of the *Stoechas* complex that were gathered, there are specimens with traits that are transitional between the two subspecies. Spike length and width

ratio and peduncle and spike length ratio are two crucial morphological traits that are used to distinguish between the two subspecies. According to the morphological and ecological results, the most different population was VV. In addition, the volatile profile of the essential oil of the VV population revealed the lowest content in the necrodane compound, statistically different ($p < 0.05$) from the others. The main ecological factors that may contribute to explain morphological and chemical variation include annual precipitation, temperature and altitude.

Acknowledgments

The study was funded by the project CULTIVAR (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), co-financed by the Regional Operational Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020. Further funded by the Forest Research Centre (UIDB/00239/2020) and CERNAS-IPCB (UIDB/00681/2020), research units funded by the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology, Portugal. Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) through the research unit UID/AGR/04129/2020 – LEAF.

Abstract IV.4 Understanding drought tolerance in cowpea *Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp.: Insights from three Portuguese landraces

Author

Duarte, D. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal
Figueiredo B. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal
Pedrosa A. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal
Lopes T. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal
Baltazar, E. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal
Correia, M. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal
Dias, M C. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal
Canhoto, J. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal
Correia, S. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal; InnovPlantProtect CoLAB, Estrada de Gil Vaz, Elvas, Portugal

Citation

Duarte, D., Figueiredo B., Pedrosa A., Lopes T., Baltazar, E., Correia, M., Dias, M C., Canhoto, J., Correia, S. Understanding drought tolerance in cowpea *Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp.: Insights from three Portuguese landraces.

Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* L.) is a nutritionally rich but underutilized crop. It is usually well adapted to drought and challenging climatic conditions. In the Lardosa region (Castelo Branco, Portugal), three cowpea landraces with interesting agronomical traits are produced (*Cara-verde*, *Arroz*, and *Cara-preta*). Nevertheless, a lack of more detailed knowledge of the genetics and physiology underlying those traits still impairs effective breeding programs for these landraces. Our study aimed to understand these plants' tolerance to water stress conditions, particularly emphasizing their phenotypic characterization and gene expression patterns under well-watered and water-deficit conditions. The phenotypic analysis did not show different growth patterns between varieties during the vegetative phase. When subjected to water-deficit conditions, *Cara-verde* showed a 47.8% root growth reduction and an augmentation in total phenol content. In contrast, *Arroz* and *Cara-preta* cultivars displayed non-significant differences in these parameters. Gene expression profiling of drought-responsive genes, specifically *VuCPRD14* and *VusHsp17.7*, indicated a general upregulation in their relative expression levels under stress conditions. *Cara-verde* displayed the most robust results suggesting a more efficient activation of stress response mechanisms, and consequently, a superior drought tolerance compared to *Arroz* and *Cara-preta*, positioning it as a promising candidate for breeding initiatives aimed at developing drought-resistant cowpea cultivars. This study offers valuable insights into the mechanisms underlying the response of Portuguese cowpea landraces to drought stress, an important matter in the context of global climate change and food security concerns.

Acknowledgments

This research was funded by project CULTIVAR (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), cofinanced by the Regional Operational

Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020, and European Union, and supported by the R&D Unit Centre for Functional Ecology—Science for People and the Planet (CFE) UIDB/04004/2020 and Associated Laboratory TERRA LA/P/0092/2020 financed by FCT/MCTES through national funds (PIDDAC).

References

- Timko M.P., Ehlers J.D. & Roberts P.A. (2007). Cowpea. In: Kole, C. (Ed.), *Genome Mapping and Molecular Breeding in Plants: Pulses, Sugar and Tuber Crops*. Springer-Verlag, Berlin, pp. 49–67
- Carvalho M., Castro I., Moutinho-Pereira J., Correia C., Egea-Cortines M., Matos M., & Lino-Neto T. (2019). Evaluating stress responses in cowpea under drought stress. *Journal of Plant Physiology*, 241, 153001
- Singh B.B, Chambliss O.L & Sharina B. (1997). Recent advances in cowpea breeding. in: *Advances in cowpea research*. B.B. Singh, B.R Mohan Raji, K.E Dasiell and L.E.N. Jackiat (eds) co-pub. Of IITA and JIRCAS IITA Ibadan, Nigeria
- Gomes A. M. F., Draper D., Nhantumbo N., Massinga R., Ramalho J. C., Marques I. & Ribeiro-Barros A. I. (2021). Diversity of cowpea [*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) walp] landraces in Mozambique: New opportunities for crop improvement and future breeding programs. *Agronomy*, 11(5), 991

Abstract IV.5 Physiological and biochemical responses of *Prunus* spp. rootstocks during water stress recovery

Author

Correia, M. J. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Soares, T. – Quality Plant - Investigation and Production in Plant Biotechnology, Lda., Coimbra, Portugal

Lopes, T. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Dias, M.C. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Canhoto, J. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Zuzarte, M. – Quality Plant - Investigation and Production in Plant Biotechnology, Lda., Coimbra, Portugal; University of Coimbra, Coimbra Institute for Clinical and Biomedical Research (iCBR), Faculty of Medicine, Coimbra, Portugal

Correia, S. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal;

InnovPlantProtect CoLab, Estrada de Gil Vaz, Elvas, Portugal

Citation

Correia, M.J., Soares, T., Lopes, T., Dias, M.C., Canhoto, J., Zuzarte, M., Correia, S. Physiological and biochemical responses of *Prunus* spp. rootstocks during water stress recovery.

Water stress conditions are among the most important abiotic factors affecting crops worldwide, due to their negative effects on development and consequently increased vulnerability of stressed plants to pests, resulting in major yield losses. Plants respond to water stress following diverse strategies that might include stress avoidance, stress tolerance and/or stress recovery. Recovery mechanisms are of particular interest, particularly in the current scenario of extreme climatic events. Nevertheless, only a restricted number of plants display a “recovery” phenotype after periods of water stress.

Water-stress recovery mechanisms were evaluated in stone-fruit trees (*Prunus* spp.) rootstocks, which are critical for the productivity of economically important crops worldwide. Two of the most used rootstocks in the stone-fruit industry, due to their adaptability to poor soils and drought tolerance are GxN15 and GF677. The main goal of this work was to understand the physiological and biochemical responses of these two hybrid rootstocks during recovery from extreme water stress conditions. Plants were exposed to a period of severe waterlogging and drought stresses followed by a post-stress recovery period. After each experimental step, physiological and biochemical parameters were measured. Both types of stresses left damage to the plants after the recovery period, although waterlogging was more detrimental. Pigment quantification and gas exchange measurements suggest that physiological recovery was more significant in post-drought than post-waterlogging for both rootstocks. Thus, waterlogging leads to more permanent damage or it could imply the need for longer recovery periods. An understanding of these stress recovery phenotypes and the mechanisms associated will ease the introducing of these traits into breeding programs.

Acknowledgments

This work is carried out at the R&D Unit Center for Functional Ecology - Science for People and the Planet (CFE), with reference UIDB/04004/2020, financed by FCT/MCTES through national funds (PIDDAC), and is co-financed by CENTRO2020, Portugal 2020 and European Union, through FEDER, in the scope of CULTIVAR project (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020). M.C.Dias (SFRH/BPD/100865/2014) and S.Correia (SFRH/BPD/91461/2012) thanks FCT.

Abstract IV.6 Physicochemical and nutritional characterization of quince (*Cydonia oblonga*) from the Cova da Beira region

Author

Vasconcelos, V. – CATAA - Associação Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Paulo, L. – CATAA - Associação Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Lopes, G. – CATAA - Associação Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Mota, M. – CATAA - Associação Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Beato, H. – CATAA - Associação Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Martins, A. – CATAA - Associação Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Camelo, A. – CATAA - Associação Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Rodrigues, A. – CATAA - Associação Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Pitacas, I. – Escola Superior Agrária do Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Rodrigues, A. – Escola Superior Agrária do Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal; CERNAS-IPCB, Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Resende, M. – CATAA - Associação Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Cristóvão, M. – CATAA - Associação Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Espirito Santo, C. – CATAA - Associação Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal; CFE - Centro de Ecologia Funcional, Departamento de Ciências da Vida, Universidade de Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Vasconcelos, V, Paulo, L., Lopes, G., Mota, M., Beato, H., Martins, A., Camelo, A., Rodrigues, A., Pitacas, I., Rodrigues, A., Resende, M., Cristóvão, M., Espirito Santo, C. Physicochemical and nutritional characterization of quince (*Cydonia oblonga*) from the Cova da Beira region.

Quince (*Cydonia oblonga*) is a fruit from autumn season, which is composed of 91% pulp, 5% seeds, and 4% peel (Velooso et al. 2020). The quince pulp is yellowish, hard, acidic and astringent, consequently, it is not normally consumed fresh. Therefore, it is commonly used in the preparation of jams and jellies (Regato et al. 2017). Consumption of quince provides health benefits due to its nutritional characteristics, for example, quince is rich in phenolic compounds, which have antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, anti-ulcerative and anti-carcinogenic properties (Zhang et al. 2019). Despite the health benefits of consuming quince and the ease of growing the quince tree, which is resistant to adverse weather conditions; quince production is often neglected and undervalued. To valorise quince from Portugal, the physicochemical and nutritional properties of four varieties of quince (Maçã, Pêra, Portugal and Galega) from Cova da Beira region were studied. Regarding the quality/physical-chemistry, weight, size, colour ($L^*a^*b^*$), texture, total soluble solids (TSS), pH and acidity were determined. Considering nutritional analysis, moisture, protein, fat, ash, fibre, sugars, and minerals were evaluated. In general, quinces from Cova da Beira are mainly composed of water (average value $78.5 \text{ g}\cdot 100\text{g}^{-1}$) and sugar (average value $8.6 \text{ g}\cdot 100\text{g}^{-1}$). Fructose is the major sugar followed by glucose and sucrose. The sweetest variety was Galega ($18,8 \text{ }^\circ\text{Brix}$). Portugal variety stands out for the highest amount of potassium ($227.4 \text{ mg}\cdot 100\text{g}^{-1}$) and the brightest skin ($L = 75.8$). Maçã variety presented the highest size (80.6 mm), weight (277.8 g) and the highest values for texture parameters. The variability in

the characterization data of quince varieties can be explored to develop new products, which can result in the valorisation of the resource and, consequently may encourage quince cultivation in Portugal.

Acknowledgments

This work was funded by National Funds in the scope of CULTIVAR project (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020).

References

- Regato, M. D., Guerreiro, I. M. & Regato, J. M. (2017). A cultura do marmeleiro no Alentejo. *Voz do Campo*, 203.
- Veloso, A., Sousa, R. & Sempiterno, C. (2020). Mineral composition of the fruits of five quince cultivars in the Portuguese region of Alcobaça. *Revista de Ciências Agrárias (Portugal)*, 43 (2), 220-230. <http://dx.doi.org/10.19084/rca.20025>.
- Zhang, M., Wang, Z., Mao, Y., Hu, Y., Yang, L., Wang, Y., Zhang, L. & Shen, X. (2019). Effects of quince pollen pollination on fruit qualities and phenolic substance contents of apples. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 256, 108628. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2019.108628>

Posters

Poster IV.1 Public perception of the biotechnological valorisation of cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp.)

Author

Duarte, D. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Paula, A. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Correia, S. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal; InnovPlantProtect CoLAB, Estrada de Gil Vaz, Elvas, Portugal

Castro, P. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Duarte, D., Paula, A., Correia, S., Castro, P. Public perception of the biotechnological valorisation of cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp.).

Cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp) (Fabaceae family), also known as black-eye-pea, is a spring/summer culture largely cultivated in Europe mainly for human and animal consumption. In Portugal, cowpea populations are an essential crop that is well-adapted to challenging environmental conditions. They are valuable genetic resources contributing to global food security and agricultural development. Nevertheless, these under-researched populations are facing rapid decline due to habitat change/degradation and intensive agricultural practices. Biotechnology can play a vital role in addressing the challenges that agricultural species and ecosystems face in the modern world, including the menaces of climate change and the increasing impact of pests and diseases. Using biotechnological techniques to characterise, conserve and utilize genetic resources for food and agriculture, we may derive multiple benefits that contribute to sustainable productivity and local biodiversity conservation. However, these techniques are often associated with public concerns. In the scope of the CULTIVAR project (<https://icultivar.pt>), this study, based on an online survey, focussed on better understanding public perceptions of biotechnological methods applied to cowpea valorisation. From our results, almost 92% of the respondents consider that cowpea should be more valorised, and 68% are aware that climatic changes may affect this resource production. Most of the respondents (75%) perceive as positive the use of biotechnology in agriculture and consider "Improving climate change resistance" and the "Development of pest and disease-resistant plants" as the main advantages. Based on our findings, there is potential to leverage biotechnology to tackle crop-related challenges in a balanced way with public perceptions and priorities. Specifically, there is an opportunity to explore the use of cowpeas, particularly the endogenous varieties found in the Beira Interior, as a means of creating value.

Acknowledgments

This work was carried out under the CULTIVAR project "Network for sustainable development and innovation in the agri-food sector" (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), co-financed by the Regional Operational Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020 and European Union, through the European Fund for Regional Development (ERDF). The work was also

supported by the R&D Unit Centre for Functional Ecology - Science for People and the Planet (CFE), with reference UIDB/04004/2020, financed by FCT/MCTES through national funds (PIDDAC) and the TERRA Associate Laboratory (LA/P/0092/2020).

References

Boukar O., Togola A., Chamarthi S., Belko N., Ishikawa H., Suzuk K. and Fatokun C. (2019). Cowpea [*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp.] breeding. In *Advances in plant breeding strategies: Legumes* (pp. 201–243). Springer

Gomes A. M. F., Draper D., Nhantumbo N., Massinga R., Ramalho J. C., Marques I. and Ribeiro-Barros A. I. (2021). Diversity of cowpea [*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) walp] landraces in Mozambique: New opportunities for crop improvement and future breeding programs. *Agronomy*, 11(5), 991

Lidder, P., & Sonnino, A. (2012). Biotechnologies for the management of genetic resources for food and agriculture. *Advances in genetics*, 78, 1-167.

Michel D.C., Guimarães A.A., da Costa E.M., de Carvalho T.S., Balsanelli E., Willems A., de Souza A.M. and de Souza Moreira F.M. (2020). *Bradyrhizobium uaiense* sp. nov., a new highly efficient cowpea symbiont. *Arch. Microbiol.*, 202, 1135–1141

Savadori, L., Savio, S., Nicotra, E., Rumiati, R., Finucane, M. L., and Slovic, P. (2013). Expert and public perception of risk from biotechnology. In *The Feeling of Risk* (pp. 245-260). Routledge.

Timko M.P., Ehlers J.D. and Roberts P.A. (2007). Cowpea. In: Kole, C. (Ed.), *Genome Mapping and Molecular Breeding in Plants: Pulses, Sugar and Tuber Crops*. Springer-Verlag, Berlin, pp. 49–67

Poster IV.2 Exploring the genetic diversity of cultivated quince tree varieties using SSR markers

Author

Pedrosa, A. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal
Cardoso, A. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal
Lopes, T. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal
Baltazar, E. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal
Teixeira, M. – InnovPlantProtect CoLAB, Estrada de Gil Vaz, Elvas, Portugal
Rato, C. – InnovPlantProtect CoLAB, Estrada de Gil Vaz, Elvas, Portugal
Canhoto, J. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal
Correia, S. – Centre for Functional Ecology, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal; InnovPlantProtect CoLAB, Estrada de Gil Vaz, Elvas, Portugal

Citation

Pedrosa, A., Cardoso, A., Lopes, T., Baltazar, E., Teixeira, M., Rato, C., Canhoto, J., Correia, S. Exploring the genetic diversity of cultivated quince tree varieties using SSR markers.

Quince (*Cydonia oblonga* Mill.) is an important pome fruit species in the Rosaceae family and one of the most underutilized. It is frequently cultivated for its rootstocks for apple and pear scions and for its nutritious fruits. In Portugal, cultivar breeding has been very scarce, and germplasm resources

are barely phenotypically described. Associated with efficient clonal propagation systems, phenotypic and molecular analysis of *C. oblonga* germplasm is crucial for breeding and conservation purposes. Insights about the existent genetic diversity and its quality are crucial for the effective use of selected genetic resources in breeding programs. The main aim of this work was to evaluate the genetic diversity of quince tree varieties cultivated in the Beira Interior region, employing Simple Sequence Repeat (SSR) markers. A total of 43 accessions representing five quince varieties ('Galega', 'Portugal', 'Espanhola', 'Champion', and 'Gigante de Vranja') were genotyped using six highly polymorphic SSR markers for fingerprinting. These SSR markers exhibited clear and reliable banding patterns, with Polymorphism Information Content (PIC) values ranging from 0.27 to 0.41, indicating their effectiveness in detecting genetic polymorphisms. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Hierarchical Cluster (HC) analyses unveiled distinct genetic clusters, with the 'Galega' variety standing out with a unique genetic profile. The primer COB 1 (CH04g09) demonstrated consistent performance, reinforcing its suitability for quince genetic analysis. Despite the quince genome's unavailability, utilizing genomic data from related species, such as apple and pear, has provided new insights into quince genetic characteristics. These discoveries offer new perspectives on quince genetic diversity and lay the foundation for forthcoming conservation and breeding efforts. Further validation studies are encouraged to refine specific quince samples' precise characterization. This study marks a significant step toward sustainable management and preservation of quince genetic resources in Portugal.

Acknowledgments

This work was made in the scope of CULTIVAR project (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), co financed by the Regional Operational Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020 and European Union, through European Fund for Regional Development (ERDF).

Poster IV.3 *Cistus ladanifer* micropropagation - preliminary results

Author

Coelho, M. T. – Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Escola Superior Agrária (IPCB-ESA), Quinta da Sra. de Mércules, Castelo Branco, Portugal; Centro de Biotecnologia de Plantas da Beira Interior (CBPBI), Quinta da Sra. de Mércules, Castelo Branco, Portugal; Centro de Estudos de Recursos Naturais, Ambiente e Sociedade / Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco (CERNAS/IPCB), Castelo Branco, Portugal

Frazão, D. F. – Centro de Biotecnologia de Plantas da Beira Interior (CBPBI), Quinta da Sra. de Mércules, Castelo Branco, Portugal; Centro de Biotecnologia Agrícola e Agroalimentar do Alentejo (CEBAL)/Instituto Politécnico de Beja (IPBeja), Beja, Portugal; Instituto Mediterrânico para a Agricultura, Ambiente e Desenvolvimento (MED)/ Instituto para as Alterações Globais e Sustentabilidade (CHANGE), Beja, Portugal

Barroca, C. – Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Escola Superior Agrária (IPCB-ESA), Quinta da Sra. de Mércules, Castelo Branco, Portugal; Centro de Biotecnologia de Plantas da Beira Interior (CBPBI), Quinta da Sra. de Mércules, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Gonçalves, J. C. – Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Escola Superior Agrária (IPCB-ESA), Quinta da Sra. de Mércules, Castelo Branco, Portugal; Centro de Biotecnologia de Plantas da Beira Interior (CBPBI), Quinta da Sra. de Mércules, Castelo Branco, Portugal; Centro de Estudos de Recursos Naturais, Ambiente e Sociedade / Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco (CERNAS/IPCB), Castelo Branco, Portugal

Citation

Coelho, M.T., Frazão, D. F., Barroca, C., Gonçalves, J. C. *Cistus ladanifer* micropropagation - preliminary results.

This rockrose species of promising value has a wide range of applications in the perfumery, cosmetics, pharmaceutical, food and feed, fine chemicals and fuel sectors. However, its use may require plants, in the near future, that result from plant breeding improvement programs. In this context, *in vitro* propagation can be a suitable method both for large-scale clonal propagation and to produce specific metabolites. In this work, the *in vitro* establishment of adult material was the most complex phase of the process given the morphophysiological characteristics of the plant. The survival rate was close to 30%, given the contamination of the explants and also death due to necrosis. After this difficult phase, the explants began the multiplication phase using the Murashige and Skoog (1962) culture medium supplemented with two different cytokinins, kinetin or 2-isopentyladenine, at a concentration of 0.5 mg/L. After 3 subcultures, the multiplication phase allowed to obtain, on average, multiplication rates of 3 explants for each established explant and elongations between 2.1 to 4.8 cm after 4 weeks. In addition, rooting rates were close to 100%, occurring naturally in the multiplication phase only by prolonging the *in vitro* cultivation time. Acclimatization required gradual reduction of humidity (from 98% to 45-50%) during the first 4 weeks. Then the plants were transferred to a marketing container with peat and perlite for subsequent cultivation.

In this work, a protocol was developed that allows high multiplication and rooting rates, allowing a competitive cost per plant and making its commercialization viable.

Acknowledgments

This work was funded by the CULTIVAR project (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020).

Reference

Murashige, T. & Skoog, F. (1962). A revised medium for rapid growth and bioassays with tobacco tissue cultures. *Physiological Plant*, 15, 473-497.

Poster IV.4 Exploring antimicrobial and anti-biofilm activities of agrofood resources from central Portugal

Author

Soares, M. – UBI – Universidade da Beira Interior, Covilhã, Portugal

Barreto, I. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal; CICS-UBI – Centro de Investigação em Ciências da Saúde, Av. Infante D. Henrique, Covilhã, Portugal

Camelo, A. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Ramos, R. – UBI – Universidade da Beira Interior, Covilhã, Portugal; CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal; Laboratório de Fitossanidade, Instituto Pedro Nunes – Associação para a Inovação e Desenvolvimento em Ciência e Tecnologia, Rua Pedro Nunes, Coimbra, Portugal

Riscado, A. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Silveira, A. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Espírito Santo, C. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal; CFE-Centre for Functional Ecology - Science for People and the Planet, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Calçada Martim de Freitas, Coimbra, Portugal

Brandão, I. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal; CFE-Centre for Functional Ecology - Science for People and the Planet, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Calçada Martim de Freitas, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Soares, M., Barreto, I., Camelo, A., Ramos, R., Riscado, A., Silveira, A., Espírito Santo, C., Brandão, I. Exploring antimicrobial and anti-biofilm activities of agrofood resources from central Portugal.

For thousands of years, plants and their extracts have been used in diverse contexts due to the presence of biologically active metabolites. In the food industry, the demand for products without synthetic preservatives and minimally processed is growing.

This study aimed to explore the antimicrobial and anti-biofilm potential of local agrifood resources in central Portugal, with the goal of repurposing these plants and their byproducts into natural products that can inhibit the growth of food-spoiling microorganisms.

Antimicrobial and anti-biofilm activities of different parts of endogenous plants like *Olea europaea*, *Sambucus nigra*, *Arbutus unedo* and *Castanea Sativa* were studied on three microorganisms: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Antimicrobial activity was observed in aqueous olive leaf extracts against *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus*, with ethanolic extracts effective only against *P. aeruginosa*, and methanolic extracts only against *S. aureus*. Aqueous extracts of elderberry leaves, as well as aqueous and ethanolic extracts from both *A. unedo* leaves and chestnut leaves, inhibited all microorganisms. *A. unedo* fruit methanolic extracts showed antimicrobial activity against all microorganisms.

Regarding the activity against biofilm formation, the aqueous olive leaf extracts interfered on biofilm by *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa*. Aqueous extracts of *A. unedo* leaves were effective in inhibiting biofilm by *S. aureus* and *L. monocytogenes*, and elderberry leaves aqueous extract was effective on *L. monocytogenes* biofilm.

In the biofilm dispersion assay, there was an almost complete trend of the extracts in promoting the formation of more biofilm. However, dispersal effects of aqueous and ethanolic extracts of olive leaves on *P. aeruginosa* biofilms and of *A. unedo* leaves aqueous extract on *L. monocytogenes* biofilms were observed.

The next phase involves identifying the antimicrobial compounds in these extracts, potentially paving the way for toxicological assessments, eventually offering a natural preservative alternative for food and packaging.

Acknowledgments

CULTIVAR project (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), co-financed by the Regional Operational Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020, and the European Union, through the European Fund for Regional Development (ERDF).

References

Nascimento, K. D. O. D., Paes, S. D. N. D., & Augusta, I. M. (2018). A Review 'Clean Labeling': Applications of Natural Ingredients in Bakery Products. *Journal of Food and Nutrition Research*, 6(5), 285-294. <https://doi.org/10.12691/jfnr-6-5-2>

Negi, P. S. (2012). Plant extracts for the control of bacterial growth: efficacy, stability and safety issues for food application. *International journal of food microbiology*, 156(1), 7–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijfoodmicro.2012.03.006>

Pinto, L., Tapia-Rodríguez, M. R., Baruzzi, F., & Ayala-Zavala, J. F. (2023). Plant Antimicrobials for Food Quality and Safety: Recent Views and Future Challenges. *Foods*, 12(12), 2315. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods12122315>

Theme V – Biodiversity, ecosystem function & services

Synopsis - Keynote Speakers

From the ground up: the role of soil biota in maintaining soil health as a path for sustainable food production

Author

Carmen Vazquez Martin – Wageningen University & Research, Netherlands

Citation

Martin, C.V. From the ground up: the role of soil biota in maintaining soil health as a path for sustainable food production.

This talk will give an overview over the importance of soil biota and the role each organism plays as a part of an ecosystem service, enabling sustainable food production in the long term. We usually associate such organisms as microbes, fungi and nematodes as responsible for disease development, when in reality they contribute for soil nutrition, pollution and climate

regulation and other fundamental processes. It should be noted that most of the processes that take place in the soil cannot be sustained without soil life, making it necessary to create ways of monitoring soil life, useful for implementation of new practices, directly impacting soil functions.

Flowers, pollinators and pollination: What have we learned through CULTIVAR about pollination services in Beira Interior agroecosystems?

Author

Sílvia Castro – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Castro, S. Flowers, pollinators and pollination: What have we learned through CULTIVAR about pollination services in Beira Interior agroecosystems?.

Pollination is the transfer of male gametes to female structures of a flower, culminating in fertilization and fruit production. This is crucial for the sustainability of terrestrial ecosystems and food security. However, plants rely on mutualistic interactions with animals as vectors and have diversified reproductive strategies. Thus, understanding pollination dynamics is crucial to design sustainable agroecosystem management practices. Pollination depends on flower functioning and compatibility among cultivars, as well as on pollinator communities in crop areas and surrounding landscapes, which depend on local and regional practices.

Within CULTIVAR, FLOWer Lab studied pollination in crops, aiming to produce knowledge, tools and local best-practices to promote pollination services in agroecosystems of Beira Interior. This was organized into the following

works: 1) compiling crop worldwide pollinator-dependence values and pollen limitation values to quantify pollinator contribution to crop production (Siopa et al. 2023a); 2) focusing on a key crop for the region, sweet cherry, by quantifying phenology and compatibility among cultivars and evaluating its impacts on crop yield (Siopa et al. 2023b); 3) identifying sweet cherry pollinators and quantifying local pollinator communities in an agricultural mosaic throughout an entire year to understand the dynamic with local practices and existing habitats (Siopa et al. 2023c); 4) expanding pollinator assessments to the region and mapping pollination ecosystem services in Beira Interior (Castro et al. 2023); and 5) expanding the knowledge on pollinator entomofauna, significantly increasing the number of known species for the region and for Portugal (Gaspar et al. 2022, 2023a, 2023b), including a new species for science (Wood et al. 2022). Knowledge of crop reproductive biology, pollinator community patterns at lower scales, and pollination services mapping provide valuable tools to optimize agriculture and conservation practices for spatial planning and designing policy instruments to support pollination services.

Acknowledgments

Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) financed CS through the fellowship SFRH/BD/145962/2019, HC through national funds by the framework contract foreseen in numbers 4-6 of article 23, Decree-Law 57/2016, 22 and SC through the Scientific Employment Stimulus 2021.02697. CEECIND. This work was funded by the Integrated Program of Scientific Research and Technological Development CULTIVAR (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), co-financed by the Regional Operational Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020 and European Union, through European Fund for Regional Development (ERDF).

References

Castro, S., Gaspar, H., Paula, A., Castro, P., Siopa, C., Loureiro, J. (2023) Pollination ecosystem services in Beira Interior region: how do they vary across the landscape? Congress Farm to Fork 2023, Castelo-Branco.

Gaspar, H., Wood, T., Siopa, C., Lopes, S., Loureiro, J., & Castro, S. (2022). New regional contributions to the knowledge of portuguese bee fauna (Hymenoptera: Anthophila). *Boletín de La Sociedad Entomológica Aragonesa*, 71, 54–62.

Gaspar, H., Wood, T., Siopa, C., Tavares, D., Loureiro, J., & Castro, S. (2023a). New contributions to the Portuguese bee fauna (Hymenoptera: Anthophila), with captures from recent pollination ecology studies. *Boletín de La Sociedad Entomológica Aragonesa*, 72, 199–211.

Gaspar, H., Siopa, C., Lopes, S., Loureiro, J., Castro, S. (2023b). Expanding the knowledge on the pollinator's entomofauna in Beira Baixa through ecology-based and taxonomic studies. Congress Farm to Fork 2023, Castelo-Branco.

Siopa, C., Carvalheiro, L., Castro, H., Loureiro, J., Castro, S. (2023a) Animal pollinator crops produced in Portugal – assessment of pollinator dependence values using the PolLimCrop database. Congress Farm to Fork 2023, Castelo-Branco.

Siopa, C., Loureiro, J., Castro, S. (2023b) Floral studies and its importance for crop production on Beira Interior – sweet cherry as a case study. Congress Farm to Fork 2023, Castelo-Branco.

Siopa, C., Gaspar, H., Lopes, S., Loureiro, J., Castro, S. (2023c) Plant and Pollinator communities in agricultural mosaics of the Beira Interior region – an annual assessment under the CULTIVAR project. Congress Farm to Fork 2023, Castelo-Branco.

Wood, T., & Ortiz-Sánchez, F. J. (2022). Description of three new *Andrena* Fabricius 1775 species from understudied parts of Iberia (Hymenoptera: Andrenidae). *Boletín de La Sociedad Entomológica Aragonesa*, 70, 114–123.

Selected Oral Communications

Abstract V.1 Morphological, molecular, and genomic identification and characterisation of *Monilinia fructicola* in *Prunus persica* from Portugal

Author

Baltazar, E. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal

Rodrigues, S. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal; Laboratory for Phytopathology, Instituto Pedro Nunes, Coimbra, Portugal

Ares, A. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal; Laboratory for Phytopathology, Instituto Pedro Nunes, Coimbra, Portugal

Camelo, A. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal; CATAA—Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Brandão, I. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal; CATAA—Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Espírito Santo, C. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal; CATAA—Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Trovão, J. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal; Laboratory for Phytopathology, Instituto Pedro Nunes, Coimbra, Portugal

Garcia, E. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal; Laboratory for Phytopathology, Instituto Pedro Nunes, Coimbra, Portugal

Costa, J. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal; Laboratory for Phytopathology, Instituto Pedro Nunes, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Baltazar, E., Rodrigues, S., Ares, A., Camelo, A., Brandão, I., Espírito Santo, C., Trovão, J., Garcia, E., Costa, J. Morphological, molecular, and genomic identification and characterisation of *Monilinia fructicola* in *Prunus persica* from Portugal.

The main production area for peaches and nectarines in Portugal is located in the Cova da Beira region. According to the latest national data, the overall production of *P. persica* was 34,776 tonnes, of which 18,706 tonnes were produced in the Centro region of Portugal [1]. However, this crop is susceptible to several pre- and post-harvest diseases [2].

In the spring of 2021 and 2022, signs of decline, such as cankers, gummosis, dry branches, flower abortion, mummified fruits and partial or complete death of selected plants, were observed in peach and nectarine orchards. Brown rot is a postharvest disease caused by three species of the genus *Monilinia*: *M. fructigena*, *M. laxa* and *M. fructicola*. The latter is classified as an OEPP/EPPO A2 quarantine organism on peach trees. Although brown rot

disease has been documented in the Cova da Beira region in the past, the current high mortality and severe symptoms have led to speculation about the species involved.

Symptomatic plant material was collected from thirteen orchards and used for fungal isolation and molecular detection according to the OEPP/EPPO standard. *M. fructicola* was confirmed morphologically and molecularly in two orchards, and it was molecularly detected (by duplex real-time PCR) in two others. Whole genome sequencing using Oxford Nanopore MinION was performed to confirm the identification. Pathogenicity tests according to Koch's postulates were performed on peach, nectarine, and sweet cherry fruits. According to the results obtained, *M. fructicola* was detected for the first time in Portugal on *P. persica*.

Acknowledgments

This research was funded by project CULTIVAR (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), cofinanced by the Regional Operational Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020, and European Union, and supported by the R&D Unit Centre for Functional Ecology—Science for People and the Planet (CFE) UIDB/04004/2020 and Associated Laboratory TERRA LA/P/0092/2020 financed by FCT/MCTES through national funds (PIDDAC). EB is the recipient of the fellowship UI/BD/150981/2021 from the FCT/MCTES.

References

1. Instituto Nacional de Estatística. Estatísticas Agrícolas 2020. Available online: https://www.ine.pt/xportal/xmain?xpid=INE&xpgid=ine_publicacoes&PUBLICACOESpub_boui=437147278&PUBLICACOESstema=55505&PUBLICACOESmodo=2 (accessed on 5 september 2023).

2. Sisquella, M.; Viñas, I.; Picouet, P.; Torres, R.; Usall, J. Effect of host and *Monilinia* spp. variables on the efficacy of radio frequency treatment on peaches. *Postharvest Biol. Technol.* 2014, 87, 6–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.postharvbio.2013.07.042>

Abstract V.2 The “Cultivar Soil” project: Characterizing the health of an overlooked resource

Author

Leitão, R. . – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Bartz, M. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal; Centre for Organic and Regenerative Agriculture, Idanha-a-Nova, Portugal

Bento, M. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Dornellas, L.F. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Durán, J. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal; Misión Biológica de Galicia, Pontevedra, Spain

Mendes, S. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Nascimento, E. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Cunha, L. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Costa, J. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Sousa, J.P. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Leitão, R., Bartz, M., Bento, M., Dornellas, L.F., Durán, J., Mendes, S., Nascimento, E., Cunha, L., Costa, J., Sousa, J.P. The “Cultivar Soil” project: Characterizing the health of an overlooked resource.

The importance of soil and soil health has been recognized globally. At the level of the European Union, healthy soils are pivotal to attaining climate, biodiversity and long-term economic goals, as evidenced by the Commission's recent proposal for the future Soil Monitoring Law (European Commission, 2023). Within the CULTIVAR Integrated Program, one of the several ongoing projects was dedicated to soil. It aimed at characterizing, conserving and valorising this unique resource in different agricultural production systems. The "Cultivar Soil" project focused on a specific area in the central region of Portugal, dominated by large farmland areas and contrasting management practices, where the soil is the backbone of the local economy. The project was designed to work in synergy and promote close links with multiple players in distinct sectors, and was somewhat inspired by the complexity of the soil itself. The sampling strategy consisted of collecting multiple data on physical, chemical, and biological soil health parameters over the course of a year, covering the major regional agricultural land uses. An innovative feature was the orthogonality of the design, which allowed the combination of different data layers to further unveil the high complexity of the soil. Rooted on the characterization of the health of different soils, the project results are expected to help local farmers and stakeholders to address practical challenges and improve their management strategies, to generate valuable scientific data, to ground future research projects, to support local administrations in regional planning and to contribute to future legislation in the agri-food sector. While the data is still being processed, the close partnerships established with some of the farmers and stakeholders directly involved in the project have been some of the most significant outcomes so far.

Funding

This work was made in the scope of CULTIVAR project (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), cofinanced by the Regional Operational Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020 and European Union, through the European Fund for Regional Development (ERDF). Ricardo Leitão is the recipient of the fellowship 2022.11630.BD from the FCT/MCTES.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank all farmers involved in the project for their unparalleled hospitality and all the time dedicated to the team.

Reference

European Commission. (2023). Proposal for a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience (Soil Monitoring Law). https://environment.ec.europa.eu/publications/proposal-directive-soil-monitoring-and-resilience_en

Abstract V.3 Expanding the knowledge on the pollinator's entomofauna in Beira Baixa through ecology-based and taxonomic studies

Author

Gaspar, H. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Siopa, C. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Lopes, S. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Loureiro, J. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Castro, S. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Gaspar, H., Siopa, C., Lopes, S., Loureiro, J., Castro, S. Expanding the knowledge on the pollinator's entomofauna in Beira Baixa through ecology-based and taxonomic studies.

Pollination services are vital to most crops and other flowering plants, sustaining human food security and most terrestrial ecosystems. In Portugal, insects are the main pollinators, and thousands of species are present. The main pollinator groups are bees (Anthophila: Hymenoptera), hoverflies (Syrphidae: Diptera) and butterflies (Rhopalocera: Lepidoptera), which

are highly diversified. Pollinators are threatened by climate change and inadequate landscape management and agricultural practices. In Portugal, faunistic surveys and reference collections constitute imperative mitigation efforts to understand species distribution and population trends that sustain conservation efforts.

Several pollination ecology-related studies were performed in Beira Baixa in 2021-2022, producing a significant number of species records. For that, we used sweeping entomological net in 30-minute random transects in 11-12 habitat types, monthly for one year in one location (*Vale de Prazeres*, in 2021) and two times a year in three regions (*Castelo Branco-Penamacor-Idanha*, *Cova da Beira* and *Planalto da Beira Transmontana*, in 2022). These surveys were performed during daily peak insect activity on vegetation with open flowers, targeting flying flower visitors. Afterwards, samples were processed in the laboratory, and specimens were prepared for reference collection and taxonomically identified to the lowest taxonomic ranking possible. This work resulted in a reference collection of about 3 800 insect specimens, including 2 485 bees, 225 syrphids and 41 butterflies, corresponding to 317, 63 and 20 species of each group, respectively. For bees, two checklists were published (Gaspar et al., 2022, 2023) reporting 184 new species to the region (plus 137 known previously), including seven new species to Portugal and one new species for science – *Andrena lusitania* WOOD & ORTIZ-SÁNCHEZ, 2022. For hoverflies, four new species to Portugal were discovered. As shown by these studies, regional efforts on pollinator sampling can significantly improve the knowledge about existing species and contribute to national efforts in pollinator conservation.

Acknowledgments

This work was funded by the Integrated Program of Scientific Research and Technological Development CULTIVAR (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), co-financed by the Regional Operational Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020 and European Union, through European Fund for Regional Development (ERDF).

References

Gaspar, H., Wood, T., Siopa, C., Lopes, S., Loureiro, J., & Castro, S. (2022). NEW REGIONAL CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE KNOWLEDGE OF PORTUGUESE BEE FAUNA (HYMENOPTERA: ANTHOPHILA). *Boletín de La Sociedad Entomológica Aragonesa (S.E.A.)*, 71, 54–62.

Gaspar, H., Wood, T., Siopa, C., Tavares, D., Loureiro, J., & Castro, S. (2023). NEW CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE PORTUGUEESE BEE FAUNA (HYMENOPTERA: ANTHOPHILA), WITH CAPTURES FROM RECENT POLLINATION ECOLOGY STUDIES. *Boletín de La Sociedad Entomológica Aragonesa (S.E.A.)*, 72, 199–211.

Wood, T., & Ortiz-Sánchez, F. J. (2022). Description of three new *Andrena* Fabricius 1775 species from understudied parts of Iberia (Hymenoptera : Andrenidae). *Boletín de La Sociedad Entomológica Aragonesa (S.E.A.)*, 70, 114–123.

Abstract V.4 Long-read metabarcoding approach for diagnosis and epidemiology in genetically heterogeneous *Prunus* sp. orchards

Author

Garcia, E. – University of Coimbra, Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Portugal; Instituto Pedro Nunes, Laboratory for Phytopathology, Coimbra, Portugal

Figueira D. – University of Coimbra, Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Portugal; Instituto Pedro Nunes, Laboratory for Phytopathology, Coimbra, Portugal

Trovão, J. – University of Coimbra, Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Portugal; Instituto Pedro Nunes, Laboratory for Phytopathology, Coimbra, Portugal

Barateiro, A. – APPIZEZERE – Associação de Proteção Integrada e Agricultura Sustentável do Zêzere

Ramos, C. – APPIZEZERE – Associação de Proteção Integrada e Agricultura Sustentável do Zêzere

Fragoso, P. – APPIZEZERE – Associação de Proteção Integrada e Agricultura Sustentável do Zêzere

Lopes, S. – APPIZEZERE – Associação de Proteção Integrada e Agricultura Sustentável do Zêzere

Camelo, A. – University of Coimbra, Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Portugal; CATAA - Centro de Apoio Agro-Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Portugal

Brandão, I. – University of Coimbra, Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Portugal; CATAA - Centro de Apoio Agro-Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Portugal

Veríssimo, A. – University of Coimbra, Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Portugal

Espírito-Santo, C. – University of Coimbra, Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Portugal; CATAA - Centro de Apoio Agro-Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Portugal

Costa, J. – University of Coimbra, Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Portugal; Instituto Pedro Nunes, Laboratory for Phytopathology, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Garcia, E., Figueira D., Trovão, J., Barateiro, A., Ramos, C., Fragoso, P., Lopes, S., Camelo, A., Brandão, I., Veríssimo, A., Espírito-Santo, C., Costa, J. Long-read metabarcoding approach for diagnosis and epidemiology in genetically heterogeneous *Prunus* sp. orchards.

Diagnostic challenges are increasing as globalisation and climate change favour the introduction of new plant pests. *Xylella fastidiosa*, *Xanthomonas arboricola*, *Pseudomonas syringae* and *Monilinia fructicola* are important pests affecting *Prunus* production with significant losses. Two different *Prunus* production systems were analysed: old orchards of *P. dulcis* and coexisting orchards of *P. avium* and *P. persica*, where significant areas of *P. dulcis* have recently been established. The high density of genetically heterogeneous *Prunus* sp. in which pests can coexist favours the development of highly adapted strains and/or the occurrence of coevolutionary phenomena associated with the spread and emergence of new diseases. This coexistence of phylogenetically close strains with drastically different phenotypes is a critical diagnostic challenge. In this context, molecular epidemiological studies were conducted by characterising the leaf and flower bacteriome and mycobiome of *Prunus* sp. using a long-read sequencing approach to assess the occurrence, distribution and impact of pests. Preliminary results showed that, in contrast to the leaf microbiome among *Prunus* species, significant differences were found between the flower and leaf microbiomes. Important pathogen-related groups were detected

with significant impact on the microbiome structure, supporting the use of this approach for large screening phytosanitary surveys.

Acknowledgments

This work was financed by Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (PTDC/ASP-PLA/3145/2021).

Abstract V.5 Farmers' perception of soil fauna and their ecosystem services

Author

Dudas, R. T. – Department of Soil and Agricultural Engineering, University Federal of Paraná, Curitiba, Brazil

Bartz, M. L. C. – Centro Municipal de Cultura de Desenvolvimento - Organic Farming: Parceria para Agricultura e Produção Biológica, Centro de Agricultura Regenerativa e Biológica, Idanha-A-Nova, Portugal; Centre for Functional Ecology, Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Paula, A. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Marques, F. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Martins, C. – CATAA- Associação Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agroalimentar de Castelo Branco, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Cunha, L. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Castro, P. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Dudas, R.T., Bartz, M.L.C., Paula, A., Marques, F., Martins, C., Cunha, L., Castro, P. Farmers' perception of soil fauna and their ecosystem services.

Soils play pivotal roles in ecosystem dynamics. Our study delved into how the rich soil biodiversity is perceived and managed by those on the frontlines, the farmers. Between December 2021 and April 2022, we surveyed (face-to-face questionnaire) 65 individuals, shedding light on their perceptions of soil fauna and its impact on agriculture. Concerning education, 5% did not complete their studies, 42% had primary education, 14% had secondary education, 35% had a degree, and 5% were postgraduate. All the respondents recognised soil organisms, such as earthworms and ants. Over 90% could identify spiders and crickets, and a significant majority recognised acari, cicadas, and slugs. However, lesser-known fauna such as millipedes, mole crickets, and scorpions had recognition rates below 60%. Regarding agricultural practices, 71% identified phytopharmaceuticals as detrimental to fauna, closely followed by chemical fertilisation (66%) and soil mobilisation (51%). In contrast, manure and composting emerged as pro-fauna practices with over 80% endorsement, and cover crops also garnered significant support (>50%). The perceptions about how the organism contributes to soil show that earthworms are the most common to be recognised as a helper, relevant for water storage (54%), organic matter decomposition (51%) and soil formation (43%). Ants were cited as consumers (48%) and seed dispersers (43%). Interviewees showed interest in adopting practices that help improve soil biodiversity and, consequently, ecosystem services, especially if incentivised by funding, if it reflects on the profitability of the agricultural production. Another way to help producers is by providing more information in an accessible manner since many farmers rely on cooperative associations for guidance. By understanding the perceptions and needs of agricultural stakeholders, actionable strategies can be crafted to improve soil management.

Acknowledgements

This work was carried out under the CULTIVAR project “Network for sustainable development and innovation in the agri-food sector” (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), co-financed by the Regional Operational Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020 and European Union, through the European Fund for Regional Development (ERDF). The work was also

supported by the R&D Unit Centre for Functional Ecology - Science for People and the Planet (CFE), with reference UIDB/04004/2020, financed by FCT/MCTES through national funds (PIDDAC) and the TERRA Associate Laboratory (LA/P/0092/2020).

Posters

Poster V.1 Carrot experiment: Documenting effects of bioactive compost extract on carrot germination rate, growth and yield

Author

Tkalec, D. – AhlmanEdu, Tampere, Finland

Citation

Tkalec, D. Carrot experiment: Documenting effects of bioactive compost extract on carrot germination rate, growth and yield.

Bioactive compost is aerobically decomposed, highly diverse, locally sourced organic material containing beneficial soil microorganisms in balanced and desired proportions, and as such is an optimal tool used for restoring the soil's functions. The method of making bioactive compost, as well as the Soil Food Web method of introducing missing microorganisms from the soil system, is developed by soil microbiologist and ecologist, Dr. Elaine Ingham, and is successfully practices all over the world.

The experiment on the carrot bed in the vegetable market garden at AhlmanEdu, Tampere, Finland was conducted in the season of 2023 to document the effects of bioactive compost extract on carrot germination

rate, growth and yield. Carrot bed was divided into 6 plots: three trial plots and three control plots.

Bioactive compost extract was applied to seeds before seeding, and to trial plots four times during the growth season (only water was applied on the control plots). Two weeks after each extract application soil samples were taken and tested for microbiological content. The steady rise in fungal biomass and protozoan numbers were visible on the trial plots.

Harvest showed a significant difference in numbers of carrots, yield per m² and average carrot weight on trial and control plots. Trial plots had 1085 carrots weighing 57kg (10.8kg/m²) and an average carrot weight of 52,5g, while the control plot had 770 carrots weighing 38,6 kg (7.3kg/m²) and average carrot weight 50.1g.

To conclude, bioactive compost extract has a significant effect on soil microbiology and consequently, on carrot germination rate and yield.

References

1. Ingham, R.E., J.A. Trofymow, E.R. Ingham and D.C. Coleman. (1985). Interactions of bacteria, fungi and their nematode grazers: Effects on nutrient cycling and plant growth. *Ecological Monographs*, 55:119-140.
2. Coleman, D.C. and E.R. Ingham. (1988). Carbon, nitrogen, phosphorus and sulfur cycling in terrestrial ecosystems. *Biogeochemistry*, 5:3-6.
3. Coleman, D.C., E.R. Ingham. (1988). Terrestrial nutrient cycles. *Biogeochemistry* 5 (1), 3-5.

4. Ingham, E.R. (1995). Soil Protozoa. *Soil Science*, 159 (4), 281-282.
5. Ingham, E. R. (1999). *The Soil Biology Primer*. NRCS Soil Quality Institute, USDA.
6. Ingham, E.R. (2001). Micronized compost and microbial life in compost. *Biocycle*, 42 (7), 58-58.
7. Ingham, E.R., M.D. Slaughter. (2004). The soil foodweb-soil and composts as living ecosystems. First International Conference Soil and Compost Eco-Biology, León, Spain.

Poster V.2 Fungal community in declining *Prunus persica* orchards located in the Cova da Beira region

Author

Baltazar, E. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal

Figueira, D. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal; Laboratory for Phytopathology, Instituto Pedro Nunes, Coimbra, Portugal

Rodrigues, S. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal; Laboratory for Phytopathology, Instituto Pedro Nunes, Coimbra, Portugal

Trovão, J. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal; Laboratory for Phytopathology, Instituto Pedro Nunes, Coimbra, Portugal

Garcia, E. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal; Laboratory for Phytopathology, Instituto Pedro Nunes, Coimbra, Portugal

Costa, J. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associated Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal; Laboratory for Phytopathology, Instituto Pedro Nunes, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Baltazar, E., Figueira, D., Rodrigues, S., Trovão, J., Garcia, E., Costa, J. Fungal community in declining *Prunus persica* orchards located in the Cova da Beira region.

The main stone fruit production area in Portugal is located in the Cova da Beira region. Peaches and nectarines are grown mainly in the municipalities of Fundão, Covilhã and Belmonte in the district of Castelo Branco, which is the main production area region in Portugal. In recent years, the market has become increasingly competitive, with the use of several varieties with different characteristics to diversify the supply. However, the use of improved varieties, together with their homogeneity, can increase the susceptibility of fruit orchards to certain biotic and abiotic agents, thus reducing their productivity.

The main diseases found in peach orchards are caused by fungi and bacteria affecting different parts of the plant. In the spring of 2021 and 2022, signs of decline were observed in peach and nectarine orchards. In this work, the fungal community composition in affected peach and nectarine orchards was determined using high-throughput sequencing complemented by culture-based methods. Symptomatic plant material was collected from thirteen orchards and used for fungal isolation and molecular identification using next-generation sequencing (NGS) technology. The combined results allowed a detailed characterization of the fungal communities in these production systems.

Several harmful organisms affecting fruit production were identified. These include diseases that mainly affect leaves, flowers, and fruit (brown rot - *Monilinia* sp.; *Alternaria* sp., *Sordaria fimicola*, *Botrytis cinerea*, *Cladosporium* sp., *Stemphylium vesicarium*, *Ulocladium* sp.) and diseases that mainly affect wood (trunks and branches), including gummosis (*Cytospora leucostoma*), canker (*Diaporthe amygdali*, *Botryosphaeria dothidea*) and rust (*Neofusicoccum parvum*). Organisms with antagonistic potential against some of these diseases have also been isolated, namely *Epicoccum nigrum*. NGS sequencing of infected plant extracts is underway.

Acknowledgements

This research was funded by project CULTIVAR (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), cofinanced by the Regional Operational

Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020, and European Union, and supported by the R&D Unit Centre for Functional Ecology—Science for People and the Planet (CFE) UIDB/04004/2020 and Associated Laboratory TERRA LA/P/0092/2020 financed by FCT/MCTES through national funds (PIDDAC). EB is the recipient of the fellowship UI/BD/150981/2021 from the FCT/MCTES.

Poster V.3 The “benchmarks” project: Building a European network for the characterisation and harmonisation of monitoring approaches for research and knowledge on soils

Author

BENCHMARKS Consortium*

Cunha, L. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Guilherme R. – Direção Regional de Agricultura e Pescas do Centro, Av. Fernão Magalhães, Coimbra, Portugal

Batista V. – Direção Regional de Agricultura e Pescas do Centro, Av. Fernão Magalhães, Coimbra, Portugal

Silva J.S. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Bartz M. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Leitão, R. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Conceição, I.L. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Costa, J. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Sousa, J.P. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

*<https://soilhealthbenchmarks.eu/>

Citation

BENCHMARKS Consortium, Cunha, L., Guilherme R., Batista V., Silva J.S., Bartz M., Leitão, R., Conceição, I.L., Costa, J., Sousa, J.P. The “benchmarks” project: Building a European network for the characterisation and harmonisation of monitoring approaches for research and knowledge on soils.

Recent assessments by the Soil Health and Food (SH&F) mission board, in conjunction with the Joint Research Centre (JRC), highlight a concerning reality: 60-70% of European soils are presently deemed unhealthy due to factors such as pollution, nutrient overloading, compaction, and degradation. Addressing this urgent concern, the SH&F mission aspires to enhance the health or improvement of 75% of European soils by 2030, aligning with crucial European initiatives like the Green Deal, EU Farm-to-Fork Strategy, and the forthcoming EU Soil Monitoring and Resilience Directive. However, assessing the efficacy of these endeavours demands an intricate, unified monitoring system for European soils, accommodating diverse land uses and user-specific needs. Although recent scientific advances have resulted in promising indicator measurements, the prevalent national monitoring systems often adopt a limited, traditional dataset approach, lacking complete biological and physical measurements. This fragmented nature of soil health monitoring often leads to inconsistent advice and regulations, underscoring the need for a unified, transparent, cost-effective framework for assessing soil health.

BENCHMARKS offers a pivotal solution that aims to collaboratively devise a transparent, harmonised, and economically viable monitoring framework across 24 European Case Studies. This initiative leverages scientific knowledge and technologies to provide a clear soil health framework, relying on pertinent indicators suitable for specific regional land uses and objectives. The project integrates traditional laboratory methods, pre-existing data, and innovative earth observation techniques, emphasising and integrating stakeholder involvement at each phase.

Key projected outcomes encompass a co-developed soil monitoring and reporting system at European and Member State levels, a comprehensive soil health dashboard to guide value-chain businesses, and pragmatic tools for

land managers to track soil health shifts due to management modifications. By combining scientific innovation, policy insights, and on-ground expertise, BENCHMARKS stands poised to usher in a new era of soil health assessment and improvement in Europe.

Funding

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement 101091010. Luis Cunha was supported by an FCT grant (CEECIND/01986/2017).

Acknowledgements

The authors thank all farmers in the project workshops for their engagement and effort dedicated to the SHI discussions.

Poster V.4 The mycobiota of *Prunus dulcis* in a gradient of diseases and practices

Author

Figueira, D. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal; Fitolab - Instituto Pedro Nunes, Laboratory for Phytopathology, Coimbra, Portugal
Garcia, E – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal; Fitolab - Instituto Pedro Nunes, Laboratory for Phytopathology, Coimbra, Portugal
Marrão, R – CNCFS - Centro Nacional de Competências dos Frutos Secos, Bragança, Portugal
Santos, A – CNCFS - Centro Nacional de Competências dos Frutos Secos, Bragança, Portugal
Espírito-Santo, C – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal; CATAA - Centro de Apoio Agro-Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Portugal
Costa, J – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal; Fitolab - Instituto Pedro Nunes, Laboratory for Phytopathology, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Figueira, D., Garcia, E., Marrão, R., Santos, A.E., Espírito-Santo, C., Costa, J. The mycobiota of *Prunus dulcis* in a gradient of diseases and practices.

The impact of plant diseases has increased dramatically due to intensification, globalisation and climate change, accounting for more than 15% of total losses despite investments in protection and control. *Prunus* production is no exception and is severely affected by the occurrence of diseases whose

intensity and severity are increasing, without all the aetiological agents having been identified.

In this context, the XylOut project aims to characterise diseases in almond orchards using culture-dependent methods and to study their epidemiology using long-chain sequencing from Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT). The aim is also to understand the virulence determinants, host range and assess the impact of pathogens on the structure and functions of the *Prunus* phyllosphere microbiota to identify taxonomic groups relevant to plant protection mechanisms and provide a biological basis for disease control. Spatial modelling based on ecological and environmental data collected in the project to infer and anticipate the risk of disease establishment and spread under climate change scenarios.

Almond orchards were selected along a gradient of intensity of good practices and disease incidence to collect plant material for isolation of potentially pathogenic fungi and characterisation of the microbiota (bacteria and fungi).

Preliminary results determined the isolation of several organisms associated with disease occurrence in almond trees, belonging to the genera *Alternaria*, *Epicoccum*, *Fusarium*, *Botryotinia*, *Diaporthe*, *Monilinia* and *Nigrospora*. Of particular note is the presence of the fungus *Dothiorela iberica* of the *Botryosphaeriaceae* family, which is responsible for stem cankers associated with severe damage. Characterisation of the microbiota of these samples is underway, which will allow the structure of the populations to be determined, as well as the presence of other organisms relevant to plant health.

Acknowledgements

This work was financed by Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (PTDC/ASP-PLA/3145/2021).

Poster V.5 Two novel *Pseudomonas* species isolated from kiwifruit leaves

Author

Rodrigues, S. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, Associated Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal; Instituto Pedro Nunes, Laboratory for Phytopathology, Coimbra, Portugal

Figueira, D. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, Associated Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal; Instituto Pedro Nunes, Laboratory for Phytopathology, Coimbra, Portugal

Rodrigues, C. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, Associated Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal

Espírito Santo, C. – CATAA – Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Trovão, J. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, Associated Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal; Instituto Pedro Nunes, Laboratory for Phytopathology, Coimbra, Portugal

Garcia, E. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, Associated Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal; Instituto Pedro Nunes, Laboratory for Phytopathology, Coimbra, Portugal

Costa, J. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, Associated Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal; Instituto Pedro Nunes, Laboratory for Phytopathology, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Rodrigues, S., Figueira, D., Rodrigues, C., Espírito Santo, C., Trovão, J., Garcia, E., Costa, J. Two novel *Pseudomonas* species isolated from kiwifruit leaves.

Pseudomonas syringae pv. *actinidiae*, *P. syringae* pv. *syringae* and *P. viridiflava* affect *Actinidia* sp. to different extents, affecting production, so the coexistence of phylogenetically close but phenotypically distinct strains is a critical diagnostic challenge. In this context, the phyllosphere of kiwifruit plants may act as a melting pot where pathogens and other species can coexist in the plant, promoting the evolution of highly adapted strains and/or the occurrence of coevolutionary phenomena associated with the spread and emergence of new diseases. To study the structural diversity of the genus *Pseudomonas* in the phyllosphere of diseased and healthy kiwifruit plants, a culture collection containing dozens of putative isolates from Portuguese orchards was established, typed by BOX-PCR and identified by 16S rRNA gene phylogeny. As a result of detailed morphological, physiological, chemotaxonomic and phylogenetic analyses, two new *Pseudomonas* species were proposed to science.

Briefly, one set of strains clustered separately with the *P. sivasensis* type strain and the OrthoANI and digital DDH values were lower than 89% and 55% respectively. In parallel, another set of strains clustered with *P. savastanoi* and *P. ficuserectae*. The OrthoANI and DDH values against them were close to 96% and 65% respectively. The characteristic fatty acid methyl ester profiles present in all strains confirmed the assignment of the novel species to the genus *Pseudomonas*. Based on comparative genomics studies, a detailed search for pathogenicity islands, genes encoding virulence factors, antibiotic resistance and siderophore production was performed. Pathogenicity studies are ongoing to determine the ability of the new species to induce hypersensitivity and cause disease in *Actinidia*. These results, together with the other data collected in this study, confirmed that the strains represent two new *Pseudomonas* species.

Acknowledgements

This research was funded by project CULTIVAR (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), co-financed by the Regional Operational Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020, and European Union, and supported by the R&D Unit Centre for Functional Ecology—Science for

People and the Planet (CFE) UIDB/04004/2020 and Associated Laboratory TERRA LA/P/0092/2020 financed by FCT/MCTES through national funds (PIDDAC).

Poster V.6 Four novel bacterial taxa isolated from kiwifruit leaves

Author

Coelho, C. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, Associated Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal

Bento, M. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, Associated Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal

Figueira, D. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, Associated Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal; Laboratory for Phytopathology, Instituto Pedro Nunes, Coimbra, Portugal

Garcia, E. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, Associated Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal; Laboratory for Phytopathology, Instituto Pedro Nunes, Coimbra, Portugal
Espírito Santo, C. – CATAA – Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Trovão, J. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, Associated Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal; Laboratory for Phytopathology, Instituto Pedro Nunes, Coimbra, Portugal

Veríssimo, A. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, Associated Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal

Tiago, I. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, Associated Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal

Costa, J. – University of Coimbra - Center for Functional Ecology Science for People & the Planet, Associated Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal; Laboratory for Phytopathology, Instituto Pedro Nunes, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Coelho, C., Bento, M., Figueira, D., Garcia, E., Espírito Santo, C., Trovão, J., Veríssimo, A., Tiago, I., Costa, J. Four novel bacterial taxa isolated from kiwifruit leaves.

Pseudomonas syringae pv. *actinidiae* (Psa), the causal agent of bacterial canker of kiwifruit, can lead to plant death, threatening the sustainability of the sector with significant economic losses. To understand the impact of Psa on the microbial community and to identify microorganisms with biotechnological applications in disease modulation or plant health, the microbiota of healthy and diseased plants was characterized using culture-dependent methods.

In this context, a collection of more than 1000 bacterial strains was established, typed by RAPD analysis and the representative strains were identified by 16S rRNA gene phylogeny. As result of a detailed morphological, physiological, chemotaxonomic and phylogenetic analyses, four new bacterial species were proposed to science.

The KWT182^T and KWT1480^T strains represent two new species within the genus *Acerihabitans*, proposed as *Acerihabitans actinidiae* and *Acerihabitans deliciosae* species, respectively. The KWT128^T strain is a novel species within the genus *Symbiopectobacterium*, proposed as *Symbiopectobacterium verissimus*. KWT595^T is a novel species within the genus *Fron dih abitans*, proposed as *Fron dih abitans actinidiae*.

In terms of plant health effects, none of the strains, even those that have been isolated from diseased kiwi leaves, showed any phytopathogenic potential or antagonistic effect against Psa when inoculated on the fruits or leaves of *A. deliciosa*.

Acknowledgements

This research was funded by project CULTIVAR (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), co-financed by the Regional Operational

Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020, and European Union, and supported by the R&D Unit Centre for Functional Ecology—Science for People and the Planet (CFE) UIDB/04004/2020 and Associated Laboratory TERRA LA/P/0092/2020 financed by FCT/MCTES through national funds (PIDDAC).

Poster V.7 Floral studies and its importance for crop production on Beira Interior – sweet cherry as a case study

Author

Siopa, C. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Loureiro – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Castro, S. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Siopa, C., Loureiro, J., Castro, S. Floral studies and its importance for crop production on Beira Interior – sweet cherry as a case study.

Sweet cherry, *Prunus avium* L., is a vital crop in the Beira Interior region. Floral biology processes are key components in the production of most flowering crops, including sweet cherry. Sweet cherry is an insect-pollinated crop, with successful pollination being determined by available pollination communities and the amount and quality of pollen being delivered to stigmas.

In this study, we aimed to quantify the compatibility among sweet cherry cultivar and evaluate its impact in crop yield. During the flowering period of sweet cherry in 2021, compatibility crossings were performed to assess 1) autonomous pollination levels, 2) natural pollination levels and 3) self and cross-compatibility of cultivars produced in the region, with assessment of pollen limitation levels, i.e., if pollination services were limiting sweet cherry

yield. A total of 7 cultivars were studied in the field, with assessment of fruit set as a production variable. Similarly, a pollination experiment was performed in the greenhouse to assess self and cross-compatibility of sweet cherry cultivars with the number of pollen tubes used as the response variable.

Results showed that most studied cultivars were self-incompatible and partially or fully compatible with other cultivars, depending on the S-allele composition. For cultivars sharing S-alleles, incompatibility was often detected, with low number of pollen tubes and low levels of fruit set. Pollen limitation was detected in most cultivars, and pollinator contribution was essential for all studied cultivars. Greenhouse experiments constituted a promising way of assessing compatibility between cultivars, although aspects such as flowering overlap and pollinator communities are not accounted for in this context.

These results show that floral biology studies are crucial for orchard implementation design and subsequent management in insect-pollinated and self-incompatible crops such as sweet cherry, where reproductive traits and pollination are key components for a successful and sustainable crop yield.

Acknowledgments

Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) financed CS through the fellowship SFRH/BD/145962/2019 and SC through the Scientific Employment Stimulus 2021.02697.CEECIND. This work was funded by the Integrated Program of Scientific Research and Technological Development CULTIVAR (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), co-financed by the Regional Operational Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020 and European Union, through European Fund for Regional Development (ERDF).

Reference

Schuster, M. (2012). Incompatible (S-) genotypes of sweet cherry cultivars (*Prunus avium* L.). *Scientia Horticulturae*, 148, 59-73.

Poster V.8 Plant and pollinator communities in agricultural mosaics of the Beira Interior region – an annual assessment under the cultivar project

Author

Siopa, C. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Gaspar, H. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Lopes, S. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Loureiro, J. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Castro, S. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Siopa, C., Gaspar, H., Lopes, S., Loureiro, J., Castro, S. Plant and pollinator communities in agricultural mosaics of the Beira Interior region – an annual assessment under the cultivar project.

Habitat quality and landscape structure are key factors for plant and pollinator communities. In agroecosystems, neglecting pollinator-friendly habitats threatens pollination services and, consequently, production of economically important pollinator-dependent crops. In some regions, Portuguese agroecosystems are represented by diverse land uses, with traditional agricultural habitats. These habitats are typically managed with less intense

practices, which makes them potential refugee areas for pollinators and, consequently, promote pollination services to surrounding areas. Yet, we lack knowledge about the spatial and temporal variation of plants and pollinators in agricultural mosaics, which is crucial to identify suitable pollinator refuges.

Here, we assessed the intra-annual variation of flowering plant and pollinator communities across 12 land-use types within Beira Interior region. Monthly, plant-pollinator interactions were surveyed, and the abundance and diversity of both insect and flowering plant communities were assessed in each habitat. Studied habitats included agricultural and silvicultural habitats (such as vineyards, grasslands, pine forests, and orchards) and semi-natural habitats (such as shrublands, hedgerows and semi-natural forests).

More than 260 flowering plant species and 350 insect pollinator species were observed, representing a valuable contribution to the knowledge of understudied pollinator species in this region. Flowering plant and insect communities varied significantly among habitats, reflecting their quality and management levels. Monthly variations were observed, with abundance and diversity peaking between March and June for both flowering plant and pollinator communities. Highly intensive management actions, such as soil mowing and heavy vegetation cutting, severely impacted the communities in particular habitats. Contrarily, although low-intensity management such as cattle pasture or manual vegetation control limited plant and pollinator communities' abundance, they allowed for their maintenance over the studied period. These results highlight the importance of promoting sustainable agroecosystem's management to support natural communities (all year around and through all landscapes) that contribute to resilient ecosystem services, particularly pollination services.

Acknowledgments

Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) financed CS through the fellowship SFRH/BD/145962/2019. This work was funded by the Integrated Program of Scientific Research and Technological Development CULTIVAR (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), co-financed by the Regional Operational Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020 and European Union, through European Fund for Regional Development (ERDF).

Poster V.9 Earthworms in different land uses in Beira Baixa region, Portugal

Author

Bartz, M. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal; Centro Municipal de Cultura de Desenvolvimento - Organic Farming: Parceria para Agricultura e Produção Biológica, Centro de Agricultura Regenerativa e Biológica, Idanha-A-Nova, Portugal

Bento, M. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Cunha, L. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Dornellas, L.F. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Durán, J. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal; Misión Biológica de Galicia, Pontevedra, Spain

Leitão, R. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Mendes, S. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Nascimento, E. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Costa, J. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Sousa, J.P. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Bartz, M., Bento, M., Cunha, L., Dornellas, L.F., Durán, J., Leitão, R., Mendes, S., Nascimento, E., Costa, J., Sousa, J.P. Earthworms in different land uses in Beira Baixa region, Portugal.

Earthworms are a universal indicator of soil health, are sensitive to soil management practices, and play an important role in soil functions, impacting agricultural production. The aim of this study was to assess the earthworm abundance and richness in eight land-use types within Beira Baixa region in Portugal, with an intensification rate: almond orchards (intensive and super intensive), olive groves (traditional with no soil mobilization, traditional with soil mobilization and intensive), and pastures (irrigated, Montado with non-controlled grazing and Montado with controlled grazing). Earthworms were sampled via TSBF monoliths, in September 2022, December 2022, March 2023 and June 2023. At each site three grids, at least 500 m apart, were sampled with nine sample points each, totaling 864 samples. A total of 1.845 earthworms were sampled: 20 individuals in September 2022, 1.237 in December 2002, 535 in March 2023 and 53 in June 2023. Earthworm abundance can be ranked as follows: intensive almond orchards (102 ind m⁻²), Montado with controlled grazing presented (41 ind m⁻²); traditional olive groves with no soil mobilization (36 ind m⁻²); intensive almond orchards (25 ind m⁻²); intensive olive groves (23 ind m⁻²); traditional olive groves with soil mobilization (18 ind m⁻²); Montado pastures with controlled grazing (15 ind m⁻²); irrigated pasture (14 ind m⁻²). Regarding the earthworm species richness, a total of 15 species and morpho species were identified, belonging to three families: Lumbricidae, Acanthodrilidae and Ocnerodrilidae. The lowest richness was found at the irrigated and Montado with no controlled grazing (4 spp. both), as well, in both almond orchards (5 spp. both). Seven spp. were found in the traditional olive groves with soil mobilization and intensive olive groves. Traditional olive groves with no soil mobilization and the Montado with controlled grazing presented 8 spp. These preliminary results show the effect of the intensification of land use on the earthworm populations and future analysis will be performed relating the species composition of each land use and environmental variables, like chemical and textural variations as well the historical of the management of the sites.

Funding

This work was made in the scope of CULTIVAR project (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), co-financed by the Regional Operational Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020 and European Union, through the European Fund for Regional Development (ERDF).

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank all the farmers involved in the project for their hospitality and all the time dedicated to the research and the team.

Poster V.10 Are farm to fork strategy goals reasonable and achievable? State of the art of Península de Setubal's winegrowers

Author

Cachão, M. – AVIPE, R. D. João de Castro, Palmela, Portugal
Chambel, A. – AVIPE, R. D. João de Castro, Palmela, Portugal
Pinto, S. – AVIPE, R. D. João de Castro, Palmela, Portugal

Citation

Cachão, M., Chambel, A., Pinto, S. Are farm to fork strategy goals reasonable and achievable? state of the art of Península de Setubal's winegrowers.

The European Union's "farm to fork" strategy sets out several objectives to be achieved by farmers, who, among others, relate to increasing biodiversity, protecting soils and reducing the use of pesticides. The use of pesticides in 235 winegrowers in the Palmela region was evaluated between 2016 and 2021. To support some of the answers, a socio-economic survey was also carried out. The data analysed included the number of treatments, the dosages used, compliance with the pre-harvest interval, the reason why winegrowers performed phytosanitary treatment and how they chose a pesticide. In addition, residue analyses were carried out at the entrance of the grapes into the winery to assess whether the MRL was exceeded and whether were not authorised pesticides were used in the vine. For each year, it was

found that, on average, farmers spray seven times, although the trend was to decrease and the most used pesticide belong to groups 3 (Triazol), according to the FRAC Codes. It was concluded that fear of diseases and pests and “empirical experience” sometimes go beyond knowledge and technology. In addition, the weak valorisation of grapes and discouragement with the implementation of some poorly reported strategies are factors that fuel the concern about the difficulty in achieving the goals.

Theme VI – Ecosystem services as tools for resilience & territorial sustainability

Synopsis - Keynote Speakers

MOSAICO approach for the implementation of fire-smart landscapes

Author

Fernando Pulido – University of Extremadura, Spain

Citation

Pulido, F., MOSAICO approach for the implementation of fire-smart landscapes.

Fire-Smart Territory (FST) has been recently proposed as “a territory with a shared governance model, in which empowered communities with high levels of knowledge and skills are able to decide and manage wildfire risk to keep it very low, through economic and social activities that not only can contain (in the end eliminate) wildfire hazard but promote the benefits of its use” (Tedim et al. 2016). To make the concept operational, we consider FST a territory in which a combination of indirect prevention measures based

on forestry, agricultural and livestock practices performed by local actors and direct prevention measures (fuel management by public agencies) are jointly implemented. Indirect, non-strategic interventions whose expected economic returns justify investments by local land managers with or without public support, has been developed in project MOSAICO using northern Extremadura region (Spain) as a pilot area from 2016 to 2023. Following a participatory process in the region, we received 250 proposals for fuel-reducing interventions (49.6% from agriculturalists, 22.8% from forest producers-mainly resin tappers-, and 27.6% from shepherds). To date, the sole intervention of local land manager results in a low to moderate impact explained by the high frequency of small-scale interventions (agriculture) and the comparatively modest impact on fuel reduction of large-scale interventions (livestock grazing). Relaxing legal/administrative constraints to allow large private intervention would result in the greatest attainable reduction in simulated burned area (ca. 25% in five years). Adaptive management of Mosaico approach must be focussed on improving land managers' capacity to modify larger portions of the territory and prioritizing critical areas such as fire propagation nodes.

Selected Oral Communications

Abstract VI.1 Co-creation of sustainable development strategies for the CULTIVAR study area, based on the ecosystem services framework

Author

Paula, A. – Centre for Functional Ecology - Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Martinho, D. – Centre for Functional Ecology - Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Roque N. – IPCB-ESA - Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, Agrarian School, Portugal; CERNAS Research Centre for Natural Resources, Environment and Society (CERNAS), Quality of Life in the Rural World – Research Unit (QRural) from Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, Portugal

Fernandez P. – IPCB-ESA - Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, Agrarian School, Portugal; MED – Mediterranean Institute for Agriculture, Environment and Development & CHANGE – Global Change and Sustainability Institute, Universidade de Évora, Évora, Portugal

Bouça M. – IPCB-ESA - Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, Agrarian School, Portugal

Figueiredo A. – CEGOT-UC-Centre of Studies in Geography and Spatial Planning, Department of Geography and Tourism, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Castro S. – Centre for Functional Ecology - Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Castro P. – Centre for Functional Ecology - Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Paula, A., Martinho, D., Roque N., Fernandez P., Bouça M., Figueiredo A., Castro S., Castro P. Co-creation of sustainable development strategies for the CULTIVAR study area, based on the ecosystem services framework.

Rural landscapes provide a comprehensive range of ecosystem services (ES) vital to local populations' support, development and well-being. However, those areas face multiple challenges (e.g. agricultural abandonment or intensification) that require the co-creation of sustainable solutions supported by the ES framework. Additionally, these issues should be discussed with local stakeholders and be included in decision-making processes.

To meet this gap, the 'CULTIVAR' research and innovation project for the sustainable development of the agri-food sectors in the Beira Interior region included a co-creation strategy to address the vision and interests of local actors. Based on participatory methodologies (workshops, face-to-face and online surveys), primary ES perceived by the territory's players were identified, and twelve of them were selected to be mapped based on secondary data.

The obtained maps were then presented and discussed with stakeholders in participatory workshops to validate the results and promote a discussion on sustainable development strategies, including a participatory SWOT analysis and a "reverse engineering" approach (TWOS) to help defining suitable strategies to enhance the territory's ES and the agroforestry mosaic that characterises the region.

Acknowledgements

This work was carried out under the CULTIVAR project "Network for sustainable development and innovation in the agri-food sector" (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), co-financed by the Regional Operational

Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020 and European Union, through the European Fund for Regional Development (ERDF). The work was also supported by the R&D Unit Centre for Functional Ecology - Science for People and the Planet (CFE), with reference UIDB/04004/2020, financed by FCT/MCTES through national funds (PIDDAC) and the TERRA Associate Laboratory (LA/P/0092/2020) and by the R&D Research Centre for Natural Resources, Environment and Society (CERNAS-IPCB) financed by FCT through national funds (UIDB/00681/2020) and by the R&D Unit Mediterranean Institute for Agriculture, Environment and Development & Change (MED) financed by FCT through national funds (UIDB/05183/2020).

Abstract VI.2 Demographic tendencies of the EU citizens' perception about the greening subsidies given to farmers

Author

Mata, F. – Center for Research and Development in Agrifood Systems and Sustainability, Instituto Politécnico de Viana do Castelo, Viana do Castelo, Portugal
[Cano - Diaz, C.](#) – Center for Research and Development in Agrifood Systems and Sustainability, Instituto Politécnico de Viana do Castelo, Viana do Castelo, Portugal
Jesus, M. – Center for Research and Development in Agrifood Systems and Sustainability, Instituto Politécnico de Viana do Castelo, Viana do Castelo, Portugal

Citation

Mata, F., Cano-Diaz, C., Jesus, M. Demographic tendencies of the EU citizens' perception about the greening subsidies given to farmers.

The European Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) is a key policy of the EU and has been reformed through the years focusing now on tackling climate change and the sustainable management of natural resources (Fetting, 2020). A positive perception of EU policies is crucial for their success, and the analysis of public opinions on these matters is an important tool to be able to adapt the policies to people's needs and worries (Buckwell et al., 2019). This study aimed to investigate the European's perception of the use of EU subsidies with sustainable targets through the analysis of the European Social Survey, namely the answer to the question: *'The EU is currently making subsidy payments to farmers for carrying out agricultural practices beneficial to the climate and the environment. Are you in favour or opposed to the EU continuing to do so?'* Several socio-economic variables were used to

model the posed question. We used data from the Eurobarometer 97.1 survey (EC, 2023) conducted in 2022 and containing $n=21002$ interviews with EU citizens. To analyse the data we used a multinomial regression with a logit link. We found individuals totally in favour of the support tend to be older, more educated, with a more lefty tendency on the political spectrum, from higher classes of society, from smaller community sizes, and tend also to be more optimistic about the future of the EU. These individuals also tend to have stronger positions on the relationship between climate and agriculture. In conclusion, the European Common Agricultural Policy is a cornerstone of EU policymaking, increasingly oriented toward tackling climate change and promoting sustainable agricultural practices. These insights can inform policymakers as they seek to align EU policies with the needs and expectations of European citizens in their pursuit of a more sustainable future.

Acknowledgements

To the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT, Portugal) for financial support to the CISAS UIDB/05937/2020 and UIDP/05937/2020, including the contract of the first author.

References

- Buckwell, A. E., Harvey, D. R., Thomson, K. J., & Parton, K. A. (2019). *The costs of the common agricultural policy* (Vol. 7). Routledge.
- EC, European Commission (2023) Eurobarometer 97.1 (2022). Cologne: GESIS.
- Fetting, C. (2020). *The European Green Deal*. ESDN report, 53.

Abstract VI.3 Farmers' perceptions of the ecosystem services provided by agriculture

Author

Castro, P. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Marques, F. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Martins, C. – CATAA- Associação Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agroalimentar de Castelo Branco, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Cação, A. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Bartz, M. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Cunha, L. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Paula, A. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Castro, P., Marques, F., Martins, C., Cação, A., Bartz, M., Cunha, L., Paula, A. Farmers' perceptions of the ecosystem services provided by agriculture.

Agriculture faces a major challenge of balancing its productive capacity with environmental sustainability. To achieve sustainable solutions, it is crucial to consider the perspectives of farmers, who are directly involved in managing and working in these systems. As part of the CULTIVAR project framework (<https://icultivar.pt/>), a survey was conducted in the Beira Interior region, where 58 male and 19 female farmers were interviewed face-to-face. The survey aimed to assess their views on the value of their farms' ecosystem services (ES). It also examined whether gender influenced their perceptions of the services and disservices associated with agricultural activity. According to the majority of people, the most important benefits provided by agricultural systems are "Production for Human Food" (84%) and "Production of manure/fertiliser" (48%). When it comes to regulating and supporting services, people believe that all services are provided by agriculture. The most commonly mentioned are "Promoting soil structure", "Carbon sequestration" and "Promoting the soil's ability to retain water". Women are less likely than men to think that agriculture contributes to "Promoting the soil's ability to retain water", "Decomposing organic matter" and "Enriching the soil by fixing nitrogen". In terms of cultural services, agriculture is perceived to contribute significantly to the "Beauty of the landscape", "Spiritual/symbolic value" and "Sense of belonging/connection to the place" for both genders (>90%). Respondents' perception of agriculture's impact on ecosystems and biodiversity is clearly positive, especially in terms of "Promoting soil quality" and "Providing habitats for animals and plants". Women tend to perceive agriculture's impact on "Soil biodiversity" and "Greenhouse gas mitigation" as slightly less positive. Farmers' perceptions are essential to ensuring the effective promotion of services and multifunctionality on farms and must be considered when drawing up action plans and strategies to enhance the sector.

Acknowledgments

This work was carried out under the CULTIVAR project "Network for sustainable development and innovation in the agri-food sector" (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), co-financed by the Regional Operational Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020 and European Union, through the European Fund for Regional Development (ERDF). The work was also

supported by the R&D Unit Centre for Functional Ecology - Science for People and the Planet (CFE), with reference UIDB/04004/2020, financed by FCT/MCTES through national funds (PIDDAC) and the TERRA Associate Laboratory (LA/P/0092/2020).

Abstract VI.4 Production of quality forage using technical itineraries, aiming at the conservation of the soil and reducing the application of phytopharmaceuticals – PRR project

Author

Carita, T. – National Institute of Agricultural and Veterinary Research, IP, Elvas, Portugal
Simões, N. – National Institute of Agricultural and Veterinary Research, IP, Elvas, Portugal
Carneiro, J. – National Institute of Agricultural and Veterinary Research, IP, Elvas, Portugal
Conceição, L. – Polytechnic Institute of Portalegre, Elvas, Portugal
J. Santos-Silva – National Institute of Agricultural and Veterinary Research, IP, Elvas, Portugal

Citation

Carita, T., Simões, N., Carneiro, J., Conceição, L., Santos-Silva, J. Production of quality forage using technical itineraries, aiming at the conservation of the soil and reducing the application of phytopharmaceuticals – PRR Project.

Extensive livestock farming represents an important sector of the territory management and the Portuguese economy. It is based on the use of local natural resources and a low use of external inputs, constituting a important form of food production with a low carbon footprint (ADPM, 2022). In

order to contribute to the improvement of environmental and economic sustainability of this agrarian system, INIAV leads a Project financed by the Recovery and Resilience Plan (PRR), which aims reducing greenhouse gas emissions from livestock and agricultural practices and increasing carbon sequestration in soils. Line of action 3.3 of this project, with the acronym GEEBovMit, has as partners a local development association, two higher education institutions and two seed companies. The objective of this study is to optimize winter forage production by reducing the application of chemical nitrogen fertilizers and by promoting soil conservation techniques, as sowing winter forages (annual ryegrass and biodiverse forage) and direct sowing. These multi-cut crops will be monitored through the use of sensor technologies for remote and close detection (GreenSeeker®). Simultaneously, the crops' capacity for regrowth after winter use, production and quality of dry matter will be evaluated. An annual "crop account" will also be carried out, which is essential for evaluating the costs and revenues of producing each type of forage, in order to be able to accurately assess which is the best solution. This work began in 2022/2023 and will be repeated for two more agricultural campaigns. Currently, the first results are being gathered and analysed and the installation of the next experimental fields is being prepared.

Acknowledgments

This work was carried out within the scope of PRR GEEBovMit - LA 3.3- Mitigation of GHG emissions in the production of beef cattle – pastures, forages and natural additives (PRR-C05-i03-I-000027-LA3.3)

Reference

ADPM (2022). Manifesto: mais pecuária extensiva mais biodiversidade para a Europa. (<https://bit.ly/manifestopecuaria>)

Abstract VI.5 How do territorial approaches contribute to the sustainability of agri-food systems? A systematic review

Author

[Duarte, L.](#) – MED & CHANGE, Universidade de Évora, Évora, Portugal

Méndez, M. R. – MED & CHANGE, Universidade de Évora, Évora, Portugal

Muñoz-Rojas, J. – MED & CHANGE, Departamento de Geociências, Universidade de Évora, Évora, Portugal

Citation

Duarte, L., Méndez, M. R., Muñoz-Rojas, J. How do territorial approaches contribute to the sustainability of agri-food systems? A systematic review.

Food systems are facing a global crisis that is increasingly evident across the environmental, social, and economic domains. A transition is required towards more sustainable food landscapes, with agri-food systems sustained in agrobiodiversity potentially playing a key role. To help tackle such challenges scientific research has evolved resulting in the fields of agroecology, localized agri-food systems, and alternative food networks, amongst others. In such context, the scientific literature is reflective of a move towards the re-localization of food systems, informed by a mix of traditional and scientific knowledge, fostered by empowered local farmers engaging in participatory development projects at the community level. One key discussion arising is on the potential of territorial approaches to foster the sustainability of agri food systems, for which this paper provides a review.

We base this systematic literature review on bibliometric methods which allowed us to identify the most impactful authors, papers, affiliations, and geographical contexts. Trends of topics gaining (and losing) relevance were also detected. Results from clustering, network analysis, and further content analysis are provided. Three distinctive scientific approaches are identified, revealing research specializations defined by their distinctive social-territorial approach: sustainable agroecosystems at the farm level; agroecological initiatives at the community level; and transformation of the food system and societal values at the regional/national level.

We expect this review will trigger and enrich further discussions about future trends and opportunities for enhancing the sustainability of agri-food systems. This is especially urgent since research on these topics is relatively recent, and conflicting approaches are identified for which an overall understanding of potential solutions is largely missing. Reconciling agricultural and biodiversity sustainability stands on top of current political agendas, and thus providing an overall picture of how territorial approaches actually confront this problem shall prove key in guiding better-informed land policy and management decisions.

Funding

This work is funded by public funds under the PhD scholarship program, number 02023.02791.BD, and also under the project UIBD/05183/2020.

Abstract VI.6 Influence of land use and crop types on organic matter decomposition in Mediterranean agroecosystems: An assessment using the Teabag Index methodology

Author

Nascimento, E. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Bartz, M. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal; Centre for Organic and Regenerative Agriculture, Idanha-a-Nova, Portugal

Bento, M. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Dornellas, L.F. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Durán, J. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal; Misión Biológica de Galicia, Pontevedra, Spain

Leitão, R. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Mendes, S. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Cunha, L. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Costa, J. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Sousa, J.P. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Nascimento, E., Bartz, M., Bento, M., Dornellas, L.F., Durán, J., Leitão, R., Mendes, S., Cunha, L., Costa, J., Sousa, J.P. Influence of land use and crop types on organic matter decomposition in Mediterranean agroecosystems: An assessment using the Teabag Index methodology.

Soil health plays a crucial role in the sustainable functionality of agroecosystems, influencing both crop yield and natural resource conservation. Evaluating the decomposition of plant residues is essential for understanding nutrient cycling processes in these systems. In this study, we adapted the “Teabag Index” methodology, using green tea teabags as an indicator of decomposition in three distinct agroecosystems in central Portugal: Two Olive Groves (Traditional and Intensive), two Almond Orchards (Intensive and Super Intensive), and three Pastures (including a Montado – Cork-oak forest). Between September and December 2022, 112 teabags were in the field, and decomposition was measured through the weight loss of plant material.

We found significant differences in decomposition rates between Olive Groves (highest rates) and Almond Orchards (lowest rates), as well as between Pastures and Almond Orchards (higher and lower, respectively). However, no significant differences were found between Olive Groves and Pastures.

We did not find significant differences between areas within Olive Groves, (Traditional vs. Intensive management) or within Almond Orchards (Intensive vs. Super Intensive management). However, decomposition rates within Pastures exhibited significant differences among the three different areas. Specifically, Pasture 3 (with cattle) showed significantly lower decomposition

rates than Pasture 1 (the Montado), which may be explained by differences in the vegetation and irrigation type.

These findings highlight that both crop type and management can have a significant influence on soil organic matter decomposition in Mediterranean agroecosystems. The conclusions have direct implications for the sustainable management of natural resources and the development of more effective agricultural practices in this region.

Funding

This work was made in the scope of CULTIVAR project (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), co-financed by the Regional Operational Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020 and European Union, through the European Fund for Regional Development (ERDF).

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank all the farmers involved in the project for their hospitality and all the time dedicated to the research.

Reference

Keuskamp, J. A., Dingemans, B. J., Lehtinen, T., Sarneel, J. M., & Hefting, M. M. (2013). Tea Bag Index: a novel approach to collect uniform decomposition data across ecosystems. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*, 4(11), 1070-1075.

Posters

Poster VI.1 Demographic characteristics of the EU citizens supporting the protection of the environment and climate change tackling as the main social responsibilities of the EU farmers

Author

Mata, F. – Center for Research and Development in Agrifood Systems and Sustainability, Instituto Politécnico de Viana do Castelo, Viana do Castelo, Portugal
Pinto, R. – Center for Research and Development in Agrifood Systems and Sustainability, Instituto Politécnico de Viana do Castelo, Viana do Castelo, Portugal
Barros, D. – Center for Research and Development in Agrifood Systems and Sustainability, Instituto Politécnico de Viana do Castelo, Viana do Castelo, Portugal

Citation

Mata, F., Pinto, R., Barros, D. Demographic characteristics of the EU citizens supporting the protection of the environment and climate change tackling as the main social responsibilities of the EU farmers.

To study what sectors of the EU society think the main responsibilities of farmers should be more aligned with the protection of the environment to tackle climate change we used data from the Eurobarometer 97.1 survey (EC, 2023) conducted in 2022 and containing $n=21002$ interviews with EU citizens. The answer 'Protecting the environment and tackling climate change' to the question 'What do you think should be the two main responsibilities of farmers in our society?' was used in a multivariate logit links model with the independent variables 'Gender', 'Age Education', 'Political Position', 'Community Size', 'Social Class', 'EU Future', and 'EU Image'. The sectors of the society with higher probabilities of choosing the given answer were as follows. Women have a higher probability of choosing this option. The probability of women choosing this option is 3.9% higher than that observed in men. The probability of an individual choosing the given option: Increases with the education level; Decreases as the political positioning moves to the right; Decreases as the size of the community enlarges, being, therefore, higher in cities and smaller in rural areas; Increases in higher classes of society; decreases in individuals more pessimistic about the future of the EU; Decreases in individuals thinking the EU as a more negative image. Several studies have shown that women and more educated individuals are more attached to the environment (e.g. Triantafyllidis & Darvin, 2021). Individuals living in rural areas are also more aware of the negative impacts of non-sustainable practices in nature (Harper & Snowden, 2017). Individuals more pessimistic about EU policies tend to have higher economic and lower environmental concerns (Drews & Van den Bergh, 2016).

Acknowledgements

To the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT, Portugal) for financial support to the CISAS UIDB/05937/2020 and UIDP/05937/2020, including the contract of the first author.

References

- EC, European Commission (2023) Eurobarometer 97.1 (2022). Cologne: GESIS.
- Drewnowski, S., & Van den Bergh, J. C. (2016). What explains public support for climate policies? A review of empirical and experimental studies. *Climate policy*, 16(7), 855-876.
- Harper, C., & Snowden, M. (2017). *Environment and society: Human perspectives on environmental issues*. Routledge.
- Triantafyllidis, S., & Darvin, L. (2021). Mass-participant sport events and sustainable development: Gender, social bonding, and connectedness to nature as predictors of socially and environmentally responsible behavior intentions. *Sustainability science*, 16(1), 239-253.

Poster VI.2 Strategies to mitigate post-wildfire erosion in NE Portugal through optimized placement of contour barriers and sediment traps

Author

Okada, V. K. – Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO) – Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Bragança, Portugal; Laboratório Associado para Sustentabilidade e Tecnologia em Regiões de Montanha (SusTEC), Bragança, Portugal
Figueiredo, T. de – Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO) – Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Bragança, Portugal; Laboratório Associado para Sustentabilidade e Tecnologia em Regiões de Montanha (SusTEC), Bragança, Portugal
Fonseca, F. – Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO) – Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Bragança, Portugal; Laboratório Associado para Sustentabilidade e Tecnologia em Regiões de Montanha (SusTEC), Bragança, Portugal
Hernández, Z. – Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO) – Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Bragança, Portugal; Laboratório Associado para Sustentabilidade e Tecnologia em Regiões de Montanha (SusTEC), Bragança, Portugal

Citation

Okada, V. K., Figueiredo, T. de, Fonseca, F., Hernández, Z. Strategies to mitigate post-wildfire erosion in NE Portugal through optimized placement of contour barriers and sediment traps.

Soil is a critical non-renewable resource, providing essential support for both human activities and natural vegetation. It is the cornerstone of various ecosystem services, including water cycle regulation and, as the largest

C pool in immersed lands, carbon storage. However, the soil resource is under growing threat due to the adverse effects of inadequate land use, soil mismanagement, climate change and wildfires. They combine to increase soil erosion risk in sloping lands, prompting global concern for issues as soil loss, climate regulation and food security. In northeastern Portugal, vulnerability to water erosion is exacerbated by frequent wildfires that leave burnt soil exposed to rainfalls over the steep slopes where they commonly occur. Consequently, post-fire erosion control measures, as contour barriers, are required for preventing soil loss and facilitating recovery and rehabilitation of the affected areas. The effectiveness of erosion control measures hinges on their precise location in the affected hill-slope or catchment, an optimization problem still lacking adequate research-based solutions. This research aimed to address this knowledge gap in Geographic Information Systems (GIS) environment, using high resolution LIDAR imagery and applying Geoprocessing Techniques. The study area covers 155 ha that were ravaged by the Picões large wildfire (ca. 14000 ha burnt in 2013). Contour barriers implementation is part of the soil recovery strategy, and soil loss measurement devices as sediment traps provide the necessary data to assess erosion control performance of contour barriers. Promising results were obtained using the flow accumulation tool to determine the most suitable location of sediment traps in the study area. This approach avoids location uncertainties that are common in the conventional field observation-based approach, and it provides 4.5 times higher efficiency in soil loss collection than that obtained with a random location of sediment traps.

Acknowledgments

To the SOILING project (EEA Grantxs, Project 11, Call#5) for the financial support of this work.

Poster VI.3 GOOD-agroecology for weeds: Building an agroecological weed management network

Author

Tataridas, A. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Costa, J. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Sousa, J. P. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Oliveira, R. S. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Bartz, M. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Leitão, R. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Alves, J. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Freitas, H. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Tataridas, A., Costa, J., Sousa, J.P., Oliveira, R.S., Bartz, M., Leitão, R., Alves, J., Freitas, H. GOOD-agroecology for weeds: Building an agroecological weed management network.

Weeds negatively affect the sustainability of European Union (EU) farming systems with weed management relying to a large extent on herbicides. The reduction of herbicide use and risk has become major policy targets of EU Farm to Fork strategy, aiming to promote agroecology and the transition to sustainable and resilient farming systems. GOOD is a 4-year project adopting multidisciplinary approach, aspired to create and evaluate Agroecological Weed Management (AWM) systems, and demonstrate that AWM adoption enhances sustainability and resilience of cropping systems. The main ambition is to foster the agroecological transition for weed management across Europe and beyond. This objective will be achieved through the development, evaluation and demonstration of innovative AWM combinations using cover crops, beneficial microorganisms and digital tools for agroecological weed manipulation and management in Living-Labs, co-created with stakeholders in 6 different EU pedoclimatic regions, annual and perennial crops and conventional, organic and mixed farming systems. At the same time, a digital AWM Toolbox will be developed to provide weed management recommendations and assist farmers' decision making to increase their income and crop productivity. The combination of innovative and socioeconomically validated sustainable agroecological practices will generate social, economic and environmental benefits through the reduction or elimination of chemical inputs and optimized use of natural resources. GOOD will create an Agroecological Weed Management Network (AWMN), inspired by the principles of Planetary Health, inviting agroecology practitioners from all continents to an in-depth dialogue and exchange of knowledge and best practices towards agroecology-based diversified agricultural systems to shape the future of humanity and natural systems. This presentation aims to give an overview of GOOD's research and innovation activities to inspire actions and synergies for food, health and our common future.

Acknowledgments

Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 101083589. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Poster VI.4 Integrating morphological and molecular approaches for assessing soil biodiversity in agroecosystems

Author

Dornellas, L. F., – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Mata, V. A. – CIBIO -InBIO, Research Center in Biodiversity and Genetic Resources, University of Porto, Vairão, Portugal

Bartz, M. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal; Centre for Organic and Regenerative Agriculture, Idanha-a-Nova, Portugal

Leitão, R. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Nascimento, E. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Mendes, S. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Costa, J. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Sousa, J.P. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Cunha, L. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Dornellas, L.F., Mata, V. A., Bartz, M., Leitão, R., Nascimento, E., Mendes, S., Costa, J., Sousa, J.P., Cunha, L. Integrating morphological and molecular approaches for assessing soil biodiversity in agroecosystems.

The One Health concept emphasises the interdependence of human, animal, and environmental health, requiring an interdisciplinary approach and a close collaboration between researchers, stakeholders, and politicians. In this context, soil biodiversity, essential for ecosystem functioning and the provision of ecosystem services, remains relatively understudied compared to above-ground organisms, posing conservation and management challenges. Depending on the land management practices, agroecosystems can pose a significant impact on various aspects of the environment, including soil biodiversity, food security, and the provision of essential ecosystem services. Molecular methods (e.g. barcoding, metabarcoding) offer promising results in assessing soil biodiversity more efficiently. This study addresses the problem of effectively assessing soil macrofauna diversity in agroecosystems with differing management intensities; morphotaxonomy and metabarcoding methods were used to explore their validation and integration. At CULTIVAR project we morphologically identified 9418 individuals, representing 13 taxonomic groups; metabarcoding identified 716 OTUs, belonging to 7 classes (22 orders). Significantly higher levels of biodiversity were recorded in the traditional agroecosystems, while improved pastures had the lowest. Moreover, metabarcoding results showed that all sites differ significantly from each other regarding OTU communities, with a separation into two clusters: one encompassing extensively managed agroforests and another with intensive, hyperintense, and improved pastures agroecosystems. This study underscores the importance of an integrative approach that combines morphotaxonomy and molecular methods to improve species identification accuracy, shedding light on the potential of molecular techniques such as metabarcoding to provide fast and precise species identification. However, further refinement of molecular methods is still required, and collaboration between researchers and taxonomists is essential. The data gathered here might help define efficient management practices according to the different land-use types, to promote a sustainable balance between biodiversity and productivity. By adopting an integrative/interdisciplinary approach, we can better understand and conserve soil biodiversity in agroecosystems, ultimately contributing to a more sustainable and secure world.

Funding

This work was made in the scope of CULTIVAR project (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), co-financed by the Regional Operational Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020 and European Union, through the European Fund for Regional Development (ERDF). Luisa Dornellas was funded by Fundação Calouste Gulbenkian with the grant “Novos Talentos Científicos - Sustentabilidade Ambiental” (2021/2022).

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank all farmers involved in the CULTIVAR project.

Poster VI.5 Epidemiology and ecogenomics of regulated *Prunus* diseases in Cova da Beira

Author

Garcia, E., – University of Coimbra, Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Portugal; Instituto Pedro Nunes, Laboratory for Phytopathology, Coimbra, Portugal

Figueira D. – University of Coimbra, Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Portugal; Instituto Pedro Nunes, Laboratory for Phytopathology, Coimbra, Portugal

Trovão, J. – University of Coimbra, Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Portugal; Instituto Pedro Nunes, Laboratory for Phytopathology, Coimbra, Portugal

Barateiro, A. – APPIZERE – Associação de Proteção Integrada e Agricultura Sustentável do Zêzere

Ramos, C. – APPIZERE – Associação de Proteção Integrada e Agricultura Sustentável do Zêzere

Fragoso, P. – APPIZERE – Associação de Proteção Integrada e Agricultura Sustentável do Zêzere

Lopes, S. – APPIZERE – Associação de Proteção Integrada e Agricultura Sustentável do Zêzere

Camelo, A. – University of Coimbra, Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Portugal; CATAA - Centro de Apoio Agro-Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Portugal

Brandão, I. – University of Coimbra, Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Portugal; CATAA - Centro de Apoio Agro-Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Portugal

Veríssimo, A. – University of Coimbra, Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Portugal

Espírito-Santo, C. – University of Coimbra, Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Portugal; CATAA - Centro de Apoio Agro-Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Portugal

Costa, J. – University of Coimbra, Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Portugal; Instituto Pedro Nunes, Laboratory for Phytopathology, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

García, E., Figueira D., Trovão, J., Barateiro, A., Ramos, C., Fragoso, P., Lopes, S., Camelo, A., Brandão, I., Veríssimo, A., Espírito-Santo, C., Costa, J. Epidemiology and genomics of regulated *Prunus* diseases in Cova da Beira.

The impact of plant pests has increased significantly in recent years, reaching epidemic proportions as intensification, globalisation and climate change facilitate their establishment and spread. Despite all investments, they are still responsible for 35% of production and post-harvest losses. At the European level, the number of active substances has decreased and disease prevalence is expected to increase. This supports the need for innovative and rapid approaches to disease diagnosis and modelling. The Beira Interior region is the most productive in *Prunus* sp. with the recent introduction of significant areas of almond trees. This heterogeneity is a relevant factor in the dynamics of the agroecosystem, particularly in terms of plant health. *Prunus* production is severely affected by the regulated bacteria *Pseudomonas syringae*, *Xanthomonas arboricola* and *Xylella fastidiosa*. The high density of genetically heterogeneous *Prunus* trees, where harmful organisms can coexist, favours the development of highly adapted strains and/or the occurrence of coevolutionary phenomena associated with the spread and emergence of new diseases. This coexistence is a critical diagnostic challenge. In this context, we intend to carry out molecular epidemiology studies (who, when, where) by characterising the leaf microbiota of cherry and peach trees using the Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT) long-chain sequencing platform, which allows the identification of bacteria and fungi to species level. This strategy aims not only to detect the introduction and impact of pathogens on the structure and functions of the microbiota but also to identify relevant taxonomic groups for modulation of the microbiota as part of potential bio-based solutions for disease control. *Prunus* orchards were selected according

to disease incidence, as measured by grower surveys, for the collection of composite, random and separate samples of peach and cherry leaves and flowers during 2022, totalling 55 leaf samples from 24 sites and 41 flower samples from 32 sites. Sampling has been repeated in 2023. Total DNA was extracted using the CTAB method and sequenced for the 16S rRNA gene and the 18S-ITS1-5.8S-ITS2-28S region on a MinION Mk1C instrument. Preliminary data allowed us to validate the use of this approach for detailed characterisation of the microbiota and identification of harmful organisms.

Acknowledgments

This work was financed by Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (PTDC/ASP-PLA/3145/2021).

Poster VI.6 Endophytic microbiomes of wild plants susceptible to *Xylella fastidiosa* infection

Author

Ramos, R. – Instituto Pedro Nunes, Laboratory for Phytopathology, Coimbra, Portugal
Camelo, A. – CATAA – Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Garcia, E. – Instituto Pedro Nunes, Laboratory for Phytopathology, Coimbra, Portugal; Center for Functional Ecology – Science for People & the Planet, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal

Rodrigues, S. – Instituto Pedro Nunes, Laboratory for Phytopathology, Coimbra, Portugal; Center for Functional Ecology – Science for People & the Planet, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal

Trovão, J. – Instituto Pedro Nunes, Laboratory for Phytopathology, Coimbra, Portugal; Center for Functional Ecology – Science for People & the Planet, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal

Brandão, I. – CATAA – Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar, Castelo Branco, Portugal; Center for Functional Ecology – Science for People & the Planet, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal

Espírito Santo, C. – CATAA – Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar, Castelo Branco, Portugal; Center for Functional Ecology – Science for People & the Planet, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, Coimbra, Portugal

Costa, J. – Instituto Pedro Nunes, Laboratory for Phytopathology, Coimbra, Portugal; CATAA – Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Citation

Ramos, R., Camelo, A., Garcia, E., Rodrigues, S., Trovão, J., Brandão, I., Espírito Santo, C., Costa, J. Endophytic microbiomes of wild plants susceptible to *Xylella fastidiosa* infection.

Xylella fastidiosa is a phytopathogenic bacterium responsible for a wide range of diseases with high economic, environmental and social impacts. The plant-associated microbiome plays a central role in maintaining fitness, but little is known about the diversity and structure of these endophytic microbial communities. It is therefore essential to study this diversity and the interactions between endophytes and plants to understand the biotechnological potential of these microorganisms. In this context, we aim to characterise the structural diversity of endophytic microorganisms in wild plant species susceptible to *X. fastidiosa* infection and present in the demarcated area of Portugal. Plant samples were selected and tested by qPCR for the presence of *X. fastidiosa*. The microbiome was analysed in plants with and without *X. fastidiosa* using a long-read sequencing approach. The results suggest a functional importance of some core microbiome groups, namely related to the ability to degrade toxic substances, fix nitrogen and promote plant growth. They may also help to explain the lack of visible symptoms and signs of decline in these wild plants, suggesting that certain taxonomic endophyte groups may help to model the infection. Notably, this is the first study in wild plants and the identification of relevant clusters contributes to the understanding of the impact of *X. fastidiosa* on microbiome dysbiosis in nature.

Acknowledgements

This work was made in the scope of CULTIVAR project (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), cofinanced by the Regional Operational Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020 and European Union, through the European Fund for Regional Development (ERDF). The authors would like to thank o DGAV and ICNF for all the time dedicated to the project.

Poster VI.7 Public perceptions of ecosystem services associated with the endogenous resources Pyrenean oak forests, chestnut groves, and cowpea cultivation

Author

Castro, P., – Centre for Functional Ecology, Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Passos, I. – CERNAS-IPCB – Research Center for Natural Resources, Environment and Society, Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, Portugal

Marques, F. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Cação, A. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Duarte, D. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Alves, F. – Open University, Portugal

Figueiredo, A. – CEGOT-UC-Centre of Studies in Geography and Spatial Planning, Department of Geography and Tourism, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Ribeiro, M.M. – CERNAS-IPCB – Research Center for Natural Resources, Environment and Society, Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, Portugal; IPCB-ESA – Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, School of Agriculture, Portugal; TERRA-CEF—Forest Research Centre, Associate Laboratory TERRA, School of Agriculture, University of Lisbon, Lisbon, Portugal

Correia, S. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal; InnovPlantProtect CoLAB, Estrada de Gil Vaz, 7350-999 Elvas, Portugal
Paula, A. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Science for People & the Planet, TERRA Associate Laboratory, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Castro, P., Passos, I., Marques, F., Cação, A., Duarte, D., Alves, F., Figueiredo, A., Ribeiro, M.M., Correia, S., Paula, A. Public perceptions of ecosystem services associated with the endogenous resources Pyrenean oak forests, chestnut groves, and cowpea cultivation.

To understand the resources available in a specific area it is crucial to comprehend how society and the environment interaction affect their availability, use, and development. Involving the local population in developing and implementing conservation plans/actions is equally important. Their effective participation can either support or hinder the political, social, and economic efforts necessary to sustain these resources. Within the framework of the Cultivar project (www.icultivar.pt), we conducted three surveys to gather public opinions on which ecosystem services (ES) people expect to be provided by Pyrenean oak forests, chestnut groves, and cowpea farming (provisioning, regulating and maintenance, and cultural services). Additionally, we aimed to determine the value people place on each ES. People perceive that Pyrenean oak forests provide several benefits, such as firewood, hunting, grazing, and mushroom picking, but only directly benefit from firewood and mushroom picking. The oak forest is considered a natural heritage and a popular recreational and nature observation area that must be protected. Also, respondents perceive that oak forests provide multiple regulation and maintenance services. The study revealed that chestnut grove ecosystems are primarily used to collect chestnuts for food, mushrooms, and firewood. Walking, hiking, participating in nature sports, and building interpersonal relationships are highly valued cultural

services. Cowpea farming is primarily associated with human consumption (food). The survey showed that other provisioning services are not widely considered to be supplied. The regulating benefits most commonly perceived as being provided are the contribution to the water cycle regulation, fire risk reduction, and soil erosion prevention. People associate cowpea with traditional knowledge and consider it a symbol of local culture and identity. These surveys found that respondents value these endogenous resources and believe they should be more valued.

Acknowledgments

This work was carried out under the CULTIVAR project “Network for sustainable development and innovation in the agri-food sector” (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), co-financed by the Regional Operational Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020 and European Union, through the European Fund for Regional Development (ERDF). The work was also supported by the R&D Unit Centre for Functional Ecology - Science for People and the Planet (CFE), with reference UIDB/04004/2020, financed by FCT/MCTES through national funds (PIDDAC) and the TERRA Associate Laboratory (LA/P/0092/2020).

Poster VI.8 Influence of land use on soil aggregate stability in different agroecosystems from central Portugal

Author

Nascimento, E., – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Bartz, M. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal; Centre for Organic and Regenerative Agriculture, Idanha-a-Nova, Portugal

Bento, M. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Dornellas, L.F. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Durán, J. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal; Misión Biológica de Galicia, Pontevedra, Spain

Leitão, R. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Mendes, S. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Cunha, L. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Costa, J. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Sousa, J.P. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Nascimento, E., Bartz, M., Bento, M., Dornellas, L.F., Durán, J., Leitão, R., Mendes, S., Cunha, L., Costa, J., Sousa, J.P. Influence of land use on soil aggregate stability in different agroecosystems from central Portugal.

Soil health is pivotal for sustainable agroecosystem functionality, impacting both crop yield and natural resource conservation. This study conducts a comprehensive assessment of soil aggregate stability, a crucial soil health indicator, in three distinct land-use types within central Portugal: Almond Orchards (Intensive and Super Intensive), Olive Groves (Traditional and Intensive), and Pastures (including cork oak Montados). In September 2022, 144 samples were collected and the stability of soil aggregates between 1 and 2 mm was evaluated using the Wet Sieving method.

Comparatively, Pastures demonstrated the highest percentage of stable aggregates, followed by Olive Groves, while Almond Orchards exhibited the lowest percentage. This distinction was statistically significant, underlining substantial soil variations among land-use types.

Results indicate no statistically significant differences in aggregate stability between Intensive and Traditional Olive Groves. Moreover, uniform soil aggregate stability was observed among the three assessed Pastures. However, notable differences were seen between Intensive and Super Intensive Almond Orchards, with the aggregate stability being higher in the Super Intensive management. Some of the influencing factors contributing to these variations could be linked to management practices (intensity and soil disturbance frequency) and vegetative cover.

This study emphasizes the pivotal role of aggregate stability as a fundamental indicator in assessing soil health in diverse cultivation systems. Understanding soil health intricacies is imperative for advocating sustainable agricultural practices and preserving agricultural ecosystems, particularly in regions of agricultural significance, such as central Portugal. Further analyses and the inclusion of additional indices are underway to gain a comprehensive understanding of the studied ecosystems.

Funding

This work was made in the scope of CULTIVAR project (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), co-financed by the Regional Operational Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020 and European Union, through the European Fund for Regional Development (ERDF).

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank all the farmers involved in the project for their hospitality and all the time dedicated to the research.

Reference

Rieke, E. L., Bagnall, D. K., Morgan, C. L., Flynn, K. D., Howe, J. A., Greub, K. L., ... & Honeycutt, C. W. (2022). Evaluation of aggregate stability methods for soil health. *Geoderma*, 428, 116156.

Poster VI.9 Pollination ecosystem services in the Beira Interior region: Variation across the landscape

Author

Castro, S. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal
Gaspar, H. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal
Paula, A. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal
Martinho, D. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal
Castro, P. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal
Siopa, C. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal
Loureiro, J. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Castro, S.*, Gaspar, H., Paula, A., Martinho, D., Castro, P., Siopa, C., Loureiro, J. Pollination ecosystem services in the Beira Interior region: Variation across the landscape.

Pollination is an ecosystem service dependent on biodiversity, with 90% of wild plants and 75% of crops depending on pollinators, totally or partially, to sustain natural populations and produce human food. However, we are witnessing a decline in biodiversity, including pollinators, resulting from

numerous global threats. Pollinator decline will lead to significant limitations in maintaining terrestrial ecosystems and agricultural sustainability. Under this scenario, pollination services assessments can be used to optimize agriculture and conservation investments, structure spatial planning and design policy instruments to sustain pollination services. In this work, we aimed to quantify pollinator diversity and abundance and map pollination ecosystem services in the *Beira Interior* region, an important production region for key crops in Portugal. For that, pollinators were sampled in representative land-use land-cover (LULC) types, and replicated in three landscape units. Pollinator community was sampled using entomological nets; floristic surveys were made to characterize food resources, and finally, nesting resource availability was quantified. The sampled insects were identified and included in the FLOWer Lab collection. Finally, each LULC type was classified according to pollinator abundance and diversity and mapped based on COS2018 with GIS software. Among the main threats, we highlight landscape degradation, including loss and fragmentation of natural and semi-natural habitats, landscape simplification by increasing monoculture systems in large and continuous areas, and biological invasions. Additionally, we identify management practices and LULC types that promote pollinator diversity in the landscape, including traditional land-uses and small-scale agriculture, resulting in diverse mosaics of LULC types intermingled with semi-natural areas. These results are important tools for stakeholders in the agriculture production sector to design well-managed agroecosystems that are both economically and ecologically productive and have the potential to be used by policymakers to support decision-making.

Acknowledgments

Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) financed CS through the fellowship SFRH/BD/145962/2019, AP through the fellowship SFRH/BD/12669/2022 and SC through the Scientific Employment Stimulus 2021.02697.CEECIND. This work was funded by the Integrated Program of Scientific Research and Technological Development CULTIVAR (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), co-financed by the Regional Operational Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020 and European Union, through European Fund for Regional Development (ERDF).

Poster VI.10 Animal pollinator crops produced in Portugal – assessment of pollinator dependence values using the PolLimCrop database

Author

Siopa, C. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Carvalho, L. G. – Departamento de Ecologia, Universidade Federal de Goiás, Goiânia, Brazil

Castro, H. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Loureiro, J. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Castro, S. – Centre for Functional Ecology, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Siopa, C., Carvalho, L. G., Castro, H., Loureiro, J., Castro, S. Animal pollinator crops produced in Portugal – assessment of pollinator dependence values using the PolLimCrop database.

Under the current scenario of biodiversity decline, pollination services of crops, mainly provided by insects, are threatened. Pollination services are crucial for food production, being crucial to know pollinator's contribution to agriculture. Crop pollinator dependence indexes are valuable tools for

assessing this, assisting policymakers in formulating sustainable and necessary management plans and policies for crop production.

In this study, we present an updated list of pollinator dependence values (PD), calculated from the PollimCrop database (Siopa et al. 2023a). The database was gathered through a literature search to attain pollen limitation levels of crops produced worldwide. This database also led to the creation of a compilation list reporting PD values for more than 130 crops (Siopa et al. 2023b). Using the INE list of produced crops for 2022, here we show how much crops produced in Portugal depend on animal pollination to produce their fruit and/or seeds. Out of a total of 74 crops cultivated in Portugal, 41 are directly dependent on animal pollinators. Among the top 20 cultivated crops, eight crops, including tomato, orange, apple and pear, depend on pollinators. The PD values for these crops are presented in percentages for each selected crop. This quantitative data provides more reliable and accurate estimates of pollinator contribution to food production, facilitating management decisions and policy making in agricultural management.

Acknowledgments

Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) financed CS through the fellowship SFRH/BD/145962/2019, HC through national funds by the framework contract foreseen in numbers 4-6 of article 23, Decree-Law 57/2016, 22 and SC through the Scientific Employment Stimulus 2021.02697.CEECIND. LGC was funded by the Brazilian Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico CNPq (307625/2021-4). This work was funded by the Integrated Program of Scientific Research and Technological Development CULTIVAR (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020), co-financed by the Regional Operational Programme Centro 2020, Portugal 2020 and European Union, through European Fund for Regional Development (ERDF).

References

Siopa, C.; Castro, H.; Loureiro, J.; Castro, S. (2023a). PolLimCrop - A global dataset of Pollen Limitation in Crops (under review).

Siopa, C.; Carvalheiro, L.G.; Castro, H.; Loureiro, J.; Castro, S. (2023b). Animal pollinated crops and cultivars – a quantitative assessment of Pollinator Dependence values and evaluation of methodological approaches. Pre-print version available at <https://www.authorea.com/doi/full/10.22541/au.167828466.63884414> (under review).

Theme VII – Food disruption: Making sustainable, healthy, delicious & appealing foods

Synopsis - Keynote Speakers

A journey from agrifood to lab-driven innovations

Author

Belén Blanco – CARTIF, Spain

Citation

Blanco, B., A journey from agrifood to lab-driven innovations.

In the currently difficult context for food systems, this talk will present an approach on how to drive innovation to the food lab, and being able to develop sustainable, healthy and appealing products from by-products and cheap raw materials by means of extrusion technology.

CARTIF, a technological center with over 200 employees and more than 140 ongoing projects (many of them European), supports innovation in various sectors, including energy, industrial digital systems, and agri-food

processes. In the food sector, CARTIF's research targets urban food system transformation, functional product development, by-product valorization, and food security.

Given the increasing global population and heightened awareness of the link between food production, health, and sustainability, CARTIF aligns its work with global sustainability goals, including the United Nations' SDGs and the European Green Deal's Farm to Fork strategy. Their use of extrusion technology supports the creation of products like snacks, cereals, meat analogs, and fish-based foods, contributing to food system sustainability. This technology enhances protein digestibility, fiber functionality, and the extraction of bioactive compounds, promoting healthier and more sustainable food production.

The nutritional, economic, and social potential of *Arbutus unedo* (strawberry tree) cultivation in the national context

Author

Rui Lopes – Medronho & Canela and Polytechnic of Leiria, Portugal

Citation

Lopes, R. The nutritional, economic, and social potential of *Arbutus unedo* (strawberry tree) cultivation in the national context.

The strawberry tree, or "ervedeiro" (*Arbutus unedo* L.), as it is widely known in Portugal, is a shrub found throughout the Mediterranean basin that produces a very distinctive fruit, the "medronho" (strawberry tree fruit), which has a yellow-orange color in the first stage of maturation and an intense red color in the final stage. At least four cultivars and two hybrids are found in the Mediterranean region (Miguelet et al., 2014). The fruits are the main product derived from the strawberry tree, and in most cases, they are used to produce distilled beverages, namely brandy and liqueurs (Gomes, F., et al., 2018).

Interest in the use of the strawberry tree and its different components in pharmacotherapy, ethnobotany, natural and folk medicine is quite old, and its uses have been documented in different Mediterranean regions. Some researchers, through laboratory tests, have concluded that the use of the leaves, roots, bark, and fruits can lead to antiseptic, diuretic, and laxative effects, or improvement in cardiovascular conditions such as hypertension,

atherosclerosis, and thrombosis (González-Telejo, 1990). In Portugal as well, “medronho” has been widely used in folk medicine, with *in vitro* and preclinical studies confirming these effects (Morgado, S., et al., 2018).

Other studies by researchers from the Mediterranean region have demonstrated the nutraceutical properties of the fruit, leaves and roots (Leonti, M., et al., 2008; Orak, H. H., et al., 201). Ziyat, et al., (2010) described the effect of the aqueous extract of root on the relaxation of the aortic endothelium of mice, suggesting the potential of the chemical compounds of this shrub in the treatment of hypertension in humans. Studies on bacteria such as *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella thyphimurium* and *Enterococcus faecalis* have shown the antibacterial action of compounds extracted from the leaves, particularly the flavonoids (Kivçak B., Mert T., Denizci A.A, 2001).

Mosele et al. (2016) published significant results from a study on the stability and metabolism of bioactive compounds in the strawberry tree fruit, specifically focusing on phenolic compounds and antioxidant activity. By simulating an *in vitro* digestion and fecal fermentation of these components, they highlighted that the fruit is a source of a wide range of phenolic compounds, ascorbic acid, and fat-soluble antioxidants. These findings provide greater assurance to the food processing industry by offering consumers more confidence in the nutritional efficacy and antioxidant activity claims of products that incorporate strawberry tree fruit, such as “Pão Medronho” (Strawberry tree fruit bread). Del Rio (2013) emphasizes the importance of consuming foods containing phenolic compounds in mitigating chronic diseases, including cardiovascular, neurodegenerative, and oncological conditions (D. Del Rio et al., 2013; S. Afkir et al., 2008; Ziyat A. et al., 2002). The anti-hemolytic and antioxidant properties of the leaves and fruits of *Arbutus unedo* have also been studied, with *in vitro* assays using human erythrocytes demonstrating effective anti-hemolytic activity and reduction of oxidative stress when using different dilutions of ethanolic extracts (Mendes, L., et al., 2011).

There are no concrete data on strawberry tree fruit production in Portugal. The last available data presented by the Fórum da Floresta (2005), based on information provided by the Forestry and Territory Secretariat at that time, estimated production at 3M kg, valued at €1.26/kg. According to the Portuguese Strawberry Tree Cooperative (2018), current production is estimated to vary between 500 and 700T/year.

Despite the lack of economic indicators, it is well-known that the strawberry tree has a significant impact on Mediterranean ecosystems. It is considered a fire-resistant shrub due to its resilience and ability to recover after a fire. Additionally, it contributes to the profitability of pine forests and woodland areas that might otherwise be abandoned. The strawberry tree can modulate photosynthesis based on water availability, maintaining an optimal balance between carbon capture and water consumption. It is also an excellent phytoremediator of depleted and contaminated soils, as well as an important source of food for pollinators in the autumn and winter, actively contributing to maintaining the diversity and balance of Mediterranean and Atlantic ecosystems.

The strawberry tree can play an important role in contributing to the family economy of people living in low-density areas, largely marked by smallholdings and native polycultures. The profitability of harvesting this fruit, even in its wild form, could represent a significant income boost for small landowners with plots of less than 1ha.

Engineer João Dias (O Melro O.P., 2023), a specialist in integrated pear and apple production, applied orchard management techniques from the Oeste Region to strawberry tree plantations in Beira Baixa. Over the past few years, he has overseen several strawberry tree farms where he implemented measures such as clone selection, soil correction with fertigation, controlled shrub pruning and management, and the introduction of pollinators, among others. Recently, he presented prospective data comparing these plantations with eucalyptus plantations on a per-hectare basis. While the conclusions are still preliminary and require further analysis and study, they are very promising.

The projected lifetime profitability of each strawberry tree plantation could reach €139,000, compared to €4,800 per hectare for eucalyptus plantations. These results are achievable through an integrated approach to strawberry tree farming, increasing the value of the fruit through its various applications in food products, cosmetics, and pharmaceuticals.

Medronho & Canela (M&C) has been working towards a diversity of applications for the fruit and its by-products and residues since 2010. In researching and developing new raw materials and products, the company has incorporated innovative technologies aimed at optimizing processes and preserving the fruit's nutritional content. Along this journey, Medronho & Canela has developed new technology, consolidated knowledge, and built technical expertise in partnership with various institutions, including CATAA. Raw materials for the baking, pastry, beverage, and cosmetics industries are now a significant reality for M&C.

A forest-to-fork... to industry: A short value chain circular economy solution for acorns from Iberian native forests

Author

Pedro Babo – Landratech, Portugal

Citation

Babo, P., A forest-to-fork... to industry: A short value chain circular economy solution for acorns from Iberian native forests.

The acorns are the nut produced by the oaks, a native genus widespread throughout the northern hemisphere. Despite its historical relevance as a staple food for several cultures, it is currently largely wasted. LANDRATECH is a Portuguese startup founded in 2020 to help the landowners to value the acorns of their endemic oak forests. Through a proprietary industrial process LANDRATECH provides the food industry with a sustainable, gluten-free, healthy and tasty ingredient harvested in our backyard, while valuing the added-value compounds extracted in the process to other industrial verticals. Hence LANDRATECH aims at contributing to change the paradigm of European endemic forest management.

Yogurt making: Keeping up with demands for healthier concepts

Author

Susana Ramos, Ana Rodrigues – Schreiber Foods, Portugal

Citation

Ramos, S., Rodrigues, A. Yogurt making: Keeping up with demands for healthier concepts.

Schreiber Foods is an international company based in the U.S., with several locations around the world, with specific production lines, focusing in different dairy and plant-based products. In Europe, more specifically in Portugal, Castelo Branco's factory focuses mainly in producing yogurts, either drinkable, type Greek, stirred, set and pouched.

In this presentation, we aim to showcase Schreiber Foods as a company by presenting some of our products, and delve into some of the innovations we perform and are implementing concerning the yogurt making world.

Clean label is currently an issue being discussed, and the company has been focusing in several strategies to make their products a healthier option such as substituting modified starch from the products with native starch and eliminating artificial color.

Sugar reduction has also been a priority for food industries, due to public demand for products with less sugar added, so several processes have been applied, ranging from the use of natural added sugars to the use of sweet enhancers of natural origin.

Lastly, products with high protein value are also trending among consumers, and Schreiber has also entered the market with some drinkable options, with no added sugars.

The insect bioindustry as a link for a circular economy

Author

Gonçalo J. Costa – The Cricket Farming CO., Quinta do Galinheiro, S. Pedro, Santarém, Portugal

Citation

Costa, G.J., The insect bioindustry as a link for a circular economy.

The Farm to Fork initiative, a pivotal component of the European Green Deal, aims to establish a sustainable food system grounded in circular economy principles. This initiative focuses on reducing waste and optimizing resource efficiency throughout the food supply chain. My presentation at the Farm to Fork 2023 congress, delves into the significant role that insects can play in achieving these objectives. I explore their diverse ecological functions, their potential as sustainable protein sources, and their contributions to nutrient recycling.

Insects, often described as nature's invisible heroes, boast a remarkable diversity of shapes, functions, ecological niches, and even culinary potential. Their ecosystem services are crucial, particularly in terms of provisioning (such as pollination and serving as food sources) and nutrient recycling (decomposing organic matter and enriching soil). However, the alarming decline in insect populations—commonly referred to as the insect apocalypse—poses serious threats to these services. Key drivers of this decline include habitat loss due to land use changes, excessive pesticide use, and the impacts of global warming. These factors have collectively led to a semi-consensual 25% reduction in pollinator populations, which is particularly concerning given that 70% of global freshwater is consumed by agriculture

and a quarter of arable land has been lost over the past 40 years. These trends have profound implications for food safety and security.

The rise of the insect bioindustry offers a promising solution to these environmental challenges. Insects are a highly sustainable protein source, producing significantly fewer greenhouse gases (GHG) compared to traditional livestock, and requiring much less water and land. For instance, cricket farming produces a fraction of the GHG emissions of cattle farming and requires substantially less feed and water. The bioindustry typically can produce two primary products: insect protein powder and frass, a nutrient-rich fertilizer. These products not only reduce reliance on traditional animal protein sources but also enhance soil health and productivity in agriculture.

Furthermore, insects have the potential to act as bioremediation agents, breaking down waste and pollutants. Although insects used for bioremediation cannot be used as food or feed due to contamination risks, their role in waste management is invaluable. Insects are also gaining traction as both feed and food. As animal feed, they provide a sustainable alternative to fishmeal and soybean meal, contributing to more sustainable livestock farming. As human food, insects are nutritionally comparable to conventional meats such as beef, pork, and chicken, offering high protein content, essential amino acids, and beneficial fats.

Introducing insects into the human diet faces challenges, particularly regarding consumer acceptance. Consumers can be broadly categorized into rational (those who are health-conscious and environmentally aware) and hedonic (those driven by taste and novelty). Lessons can be drawn from the successful introduction of sushi to Western diets, which initially faced resistance but eventually became widely accepted. Education, marketing, and culinary innovation will be crucial in normalizing insect consumption.

The concept of microlivestock emphasizes the efficiency of insect farming, where insects can be raised in high densities and vertically, optimizing space usage. This approach can lead to shorter value chains, where insect farming

facilities are located closer to consumers and waste sources, reducing transportation costs and emissions.

The Cricket Farming CO, a portuguese startup focused on research, development, and innovation (R&D&I) in cricket farming for human consumption, exemplifies the potential of the insect bioindustry. Our company's multidisciplinary team is dedicated to advancing the field, exploring not only the production of insect protein powder but also the extraction of valuable components such as lipids, proteins, and chitin. Chitin can be converted into chitosan, a highly valuable biopolymer with applications in pharmaceuticals.

InsectERA, a mobilizing agenda that unites 42 institutions, aims to boost the insect sector in Portugal by fostering collaboration, innovation, and regulatory support. Despite the promising potential of the insect bioindustry, several challenges still remain. These include ensuring biosecurity to prevent disease outbreaks, updating legislation«, addressing animal welfare concerns, and overcoming market acceptance barriers.

Integrating insects into the circular economy framework offers a viable path towards sustainable food systems. By leveraging their ecological roles and industrial potential, insects can significantly contribute to address global environmental challenges and enhance food security. This presentation underscores the need for continued research, innovation, and collaboration to fully realize the potential of the insect bioindustry, ultimately supporting the goals of the Farm to Fork initiative and the broader circular economy frameworks.

Selected Oral Communications

Abstract VII.1 Food preservation by hyperbaric storage: The effect of pH on the inactivation of *Listeria monocytogenes*

Author

Lima, V., – LAQV-REQUIMTE, Chemistry Department, University of Aveiro, Portugal
Pinto, C. – LAQV-REQUIMTE, Chemistry Department, University of Aveiro, Portugal
Saraiva, J. – LAQV-REQUIMTE, Chemistry Department, University of Aveiro, Portugal

Citation

Lima, V., Pinto, C., Saraiva, J. Food preservation by hyperbaric storage: The effect of pH on the inactivation of *Listeria monocytogenes*.

Hyperbaric storage (HS, food storage under mild pressures) has been proposed as an alternative to conventional refrigeration, but where foods can be stored at room temperature (RT), with virtually no energy costs and substantially lower greenhouse gas emissions. More recently, HS was proposed also as a simultaneously moderate-pressure pasteurization (MPP) methodology, using hydrostatic pressures up to 200–250 MPa for a few hours.

Watermelon juice's interesting nutritional composition is associated with health benefits and includes vitamins, minerals, functionally important amino acids and antioxidants, like carotenoids and phenolic compounds. However, this juice is highly perishable, due to its high pH (5.2–6.7) and high-water activity (0.97–0.99), which results in high microbial growth and enzymatic activity propensity, leading to a short shelf-life (Lemos et al., 2017).

The impact of pH on a food (watermelon juice) stored by HS at RT was here studied for the first time, focusing on the behaviour of the pathogenic *Listeria monocytogenes* inoculated in the juice (adjusted to pH 4.0 and 6.5) and stored at 25–250 MPa for up to 21 days, along with controls stored at atmospheric pressure (AP) under refrigerated or RT conditions.

The results showed that pH and storage pressure level used affected the growth and inactivation of *L. monocytogenes*, as inactivation was achieved quicker and at lower pressure levels in the acidic juice, with reductions often reaching 4–5 log CFU/g, to levels below the detection limit. Concluding, variables like the juice's pH and the storage pressure level should be further studied to better select the adequate HS conditions for food preservation as a function of pH. During HS not only microbial growth can be controlled, but microbial inactivation can reach pasteurization levels, revealing MPP's potential a nonthermal pasteurization technique at room temperature with quasi no energetic costs, being greener and more sustainable.

Acknowledgments

Thanks are due to the University of Aveiro and FCT/MCTES for the financial support for the LAQV research Unit (FCT UIDB/50006/2020 and UIDP/50006/2020) through national funds and, where applicable, co financed by the FEDER, within the PT2020 Partnership Agreement. Vasco Lima would like to thank also FCT/MCTES for the PhD grant SFRH/BD/146080/2019.

Reference

Lemos, Á. T., Ribeiro, A. C., Fidalgo, L. G., Delgadillo, I., & Saraiva, J. A. (2017). Extension of raw watermelon juice shelf life up to 58days by hyperbaric storage. *Food Chemistry*, 231, 61-69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2017.03.110>

Abstract VII.2 Hyperbaric storage as a new methodology for preservation of egg white at room temperature

Author

Matos, G., . – LAQV-REQUIMTE, Department of Chemistry, University of Aveiro, Aveiro, Portugal

Tavares, J. – LAQV-REQUIMTE, Department of Chemistry, University of Aveiro, Aveiro, Portugal

Ferreira, I. – LAQV-REQUIMTE, Laboratory of Bromatology and Hydrology, Department of Chemical Sciences, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Porto, Porto, Portugal

Saraiva, J. A. – LAQV-REQUIMTE, Department of Chemistry, University of Aveiro, Aveiro, Portugal

Citation

Matos, G., Tavares, J., Ferreira, I., Saraiva, J. A. Hyperbaric storage as a new methodology for preservation of egg white at room temperature.

Egg white (EW) holds a significant position in the food industry due to its rich protein content and its ability to impart desirable functional properties. Nevertheless, liquid EW is prone to rapid spoilage, typically necessitating thermal processing to prolong its shelf-life when stored under refrigeration (RF), but this often results in a decline in its functional properties (Rossi et al., 2010). Furthermore, RF is well-documented for its considerable economic and environmental impacts. Thus, there is a need for more efficient methods of preserving EW, guaranteeing microbiological safety, without compromising its quality.

Hyperbaric storage (HS) is a pressure-based food preservation methodology that uses mild pressures (25–150MPa), being an eco-friendly alternative to RF when used at room temperature (RT), since no energy is needed to maintain food under storage. In addition, a longer shelf-life is reported to be achievable with this methodology (Bermejo-prada et al., 2017; Duarte et al., 2022). Considering this, this study evaluates HS/RT as a nonthermal preservation methodology for EW and assesses its potential as an RF replacement.

HS experiments at different pressure levels (25/50/75/100MPa) at RT were carried out up to 60 days in EW. Microbiological evaluation of HS/RT was assessed through counts of inoculated pathogenic microorganisms (*Salmonella Senftenberg*, *Salmonella Enteritidis*, *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Staphylococcus aureus*) for the established pressure/time conditions and the kinetic parameters of microbial inactivation were determined. EW preserved at the optimal conditions was evaluated for functional/physicochemical properties, such as color, soluble protein, viscosity and foaming capacity/stability.

Microbiological results showed that using HS/RT under 50–100MPa in EW allowed to reduce microbial population to counts below 1log CFU/mL, exceeding 5log units inactivation, remaining below the detection limit up to 60 days. Most functional/physicochemical properties remained unchanged under HS/RT, indicating its potential not only to achieve microbial inactivation at pasteurization levels but also for its subsequent preservation at room temperature.

Acknowledgments

Thanks are due to the University of Aveiro, University of Porto and FCT/MCTES for the financial support for the LAQV research Unit (projects FCT UIDB/50006/2020 and UIDP/50006/2020) through national funds and, where applicable, co-financed by the FEDER, within the PT2020 Partnership Agreement. Gabriela Matos also thanks FCT/MCTES and ESF through NORTE 2020 for PhD grant reference 2021.07139.BD.

References

Bermejo-prada, A., Colmant, A., & Otero, L. (2017). Industrial viability of the hyperbaric method to store perishable foods at room temperature. *Journal of Food Engineering*, 193, 76–85. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2016.08.014>

Duarte, R. V., Pinto, C. A., Gomes, A. M., Delgadillo, I., & Saraiva, J. A. (2022). A microbiological perspective of raw milk preserved at room temperature using hyperbaric storage compared to refrigerated storage. *Innovative Food Science & Emerging Technologies*, 78, 103019. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.IFSET.2022.103019>

Rossi, M., Casiraghi, E., Primavesi, L., Pompei, C., & Hidalgo, A. (2010). Functional properties of pasteurised liquid whole egg products as affected by the hygienic quality of the raw eggs. *LWT - Food Science and Technology*, 43(3), 436–441. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2009.09.008>

Abstract VII.3 Valorization of starch and tannins from acorns by high pressure and pulsed electric field technologies

Author

Castro, L. M. G., – Universidade Católica Portuguesa, CBQF – Centro de Biotecnologia e Química Fina – Laboratório Associado, Escola Superior de Biotecnologia, Rua Diogo Botelho 1327, Porto, Portugal; LAQV-REQUIMTE – Laboratório Associado, Department of Chemistry, University of Aveiro, Aveiro, Portugal

Alexandre, E. M. C. – LAQV-REQUIMTE – Laboratório Associado, Department of Chemistry, University of Aveiro, Aveiro, Portugal

Saraiva, J. A. – LAQV-REQUIMTE – Laboratório Associado, Department of Chemistry, University of Aveiro, Aveiro, Portugal

Pintado, M. – Universidade Católica Portuguesa, CBQF – Centro de Biotecnologia e Química Fina – Laboratório Associado, Escola Superior de Biotecnologia, Rua Diogo Botelho 1327, Porto, Portugal

Citation

Castro, L. M. G., Alexandre, E. M. C., Saraiva, J. A., Pintado, M. Valorization of starch and tannins from acorns by high pressure and pulsed electric field technologies.

Acorns are rich in starch and tannins, but 55% of their production is underutilized. Since starch and tannins have great potential applications, this work aimed to value unused acorns. The effect of dehulling by scalding or drying on the nutritional and phytochemical composition of *Q. pyrenaica*, *Q. robur*, and *Q. ilex* acorns regarding manual dehulling was studied. The ash, protein, and carbohydrate contents of all species were unchanged after either

scalding or drying. Changes in fat and polyphenol contents were dependent on the dehulling and species, but fiber content increased after scalding or drying for all species. Acorn starch was mostly resistant, but scalding and drying decreased its contents for all species. Starch and tannin extraction optimization was conducted using water as an extraction solvent under high pressure (HP) and pulsed electric field (PEF). Under optimum conditions, these technologies allowed to the extraction of extracts with a higher tannin content than alkaline extraction and starches that could be used more safely than alkaline ones. Under optimal extraction conditions, HP preserved starch polymorphism, gelatinization temperatures, and enthalpies. The increase in the amylose/amylopectin ratio caused changes in starch properties. For PEF, the amylose/amylopectin contents, gelatinization temperatures and enthalpies, polymorphism, or properties were not altered. Compared to commercial starch, acorn starches showed, higher solubility and swelling power up to 80 °C, lower gelatinization temperatures and enthalpies, lower in-vitro digestibility, and lower resistance to deformation. The replacement of commercial starch by acorn starch in chocolate puddings improved the rheological properties of the puddings, colour stabilization, and texture without affecting the microbiological safety, nutritional composition, internal structure, or digestibility. Sensory analysis revealed that tasters preferred the acorn starch puddings over commercial starch. Chocolate puddings made with PEF-extracted acorn starch had a higher acceptability index than HP-extracted starch.

Acknowledgments

Acknowledgments are given to the Universidade Católica Portuguesa by providing the financial support to CBQF Associate Laboratory under the UID/Multi/50016/2021 FCT project and to Aveiro University and FCT/MCT for the financial support for the QOPNA research Unit (FCT UID/QUI/00062/2021) and Laboratório Associado LAQV-REQUIMTE (UIDB/50006/2020) through national funds and, where applicable, co-financed by the FEDER, within the PT2020 Partnership Agreement. Author Luís M. G. Castro is grateful for the financial support provided by FCT through the Doctoral Grant SFRH/BD/136882/2018 and COVID/BD/152756/2022. Author Elisabete M. C.

Alexandre is also grateful for the financial support of this work funded by national funds (OE), through FCT – Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I.P., in the scope of the framework contract foreseen in the numbers 4, 5 and 6 of the article 23, of the Decree-Law 57/2016, of August 29, changed by Law 57/2017, of July 19.

Posters

Poster VII.1 Valorization of ‘Rocha’ pear residues for gummies development and optimization: A sustainable and healthy approach

Author

Silva, A. – ESTM – School of Tourism and Marine Technology, Polytechnic Institute of Leiria, Peniche, Portugal

Pinheiro, R. F. – ciTechCare – Center for Innovative Care and Health Technology, Polytechnic Institute of Leiria, Leiria, Portugal

Luís, L. S. – ciTechCare – Center for Innovative Care and Health Technology, Polytechnic Institute of Leiria, Leiria, Portugal; ESSLei – School of Health Sciences, Polytechnic Institute of Leiria, Leiria, Portugal

Guarino, M. P. – ciTechCare – Center for Innovative Care and Health Technology, Polytechnic Institute of Leiria, Leiria, Portugal; ESSLei – School of Health Sciences, Polytechnic Institute of Leiria, Leiria, Portugal

Rodrigues, A. C. – ciTechCare – Center for Innovative Care and Health Technology, Polytechnic Institute of Leiria, Leiria, Portugal; ESSLei – School of Health Sciences, Polytechnic Institute of Leiria, Leiria, Portugal; RochaCenter, Centro de Pós-Colheita e Tecnologia, ACE, Rua 6 de Outubro, Bombarral, Portugal

Gaspar, M. C. – ciTechCare – Center for Innovative Care and Health Technology, Polytechnic Institute of Leiria, Leiria, Portugal; ESSLei – School of Health Sciences, Polytechnic Institute of Leiria, Leiria, Portugal

Citation

Silva, A., Pinheiro, R. F., Luís, L. S., Guarino, M. P., Rodrigues, A. C., Gaspar, M. C. Valorization of 'Rocha' pear residues for gummies development and optimization: A sustainable and healthy approach.

'Rocha' pear is a nutritious Portuguese cultivar of the *Pyrus communis* L. species, most produced in the western region. Fruits are stored under controlled atmosphere, but a considerable part is often wasted due to physical damage, or other storage disorders (Almeida et al., 2016; Pedro et al., 2020; Saquet, 2019; Dias et al., 2022).

This study explores a sustainable approach to transform 'Rocha' pear residues into healthy gummies, according to a 2³ factorial design (Gaspar et al., 2020) to optimize their properties. Agar-agar and pectin were used as gelifiers and citric acid as preservative (Ge et al., 2021). Pears were freeze dried, milled and characterized (weight, moisture, color, firmness, and total soluble solids). For gummies, color, pH, and texture were measured, and sensory analysis performed.

Pear color, mean total soluble solids (13.1%), and moisture content (~85%) were similar to literature (Almeida et al., 2016; Kolniak-Ostek, 2016), while firmness was variable (4.17 ± 1.41 kg/0.5cm²) due to different degrees of ripeness and/or physical damage. Results from factorial planning (MATLAB) showed that a* and b* color coordinates of gummies increased by doubling pear concentration (from 10 to 20wt.%) and with pectin (2% w/vwater) inclusion. Textural properties were significantly affected by the inclusion of pectin (Baydin et al., 2022) or the increase in pear concentration, decreasing both hardness and gumminess, contrary to the inclusion of citric acid, which increased them. Gummies pH was lower when pectin or citric acid were added. Sensory analysis revealed overall good acceptability, but texture needs improvement.

In conclusion, pear-based gummies without pectin and with 10wt.% pear presented the most suitable properties. Considering the current trends for

healthier and sustainable products (Gaspar & Braga, 2023), these gummy formulations are promising alternatives to traditional gummy candies. Further studies will be conducted to improve gummies texture and evaluate their shelf life.

Acknowledgements

This work was funded by Portuguese national funds provided by Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia (FCT) (UIDB/05704/2020 and UIDP/05704/2020). M. C. Gaspar acknowledges FCT for the financial support through the Institutional Scientific Employment Stimulus (CEECINST/00060/2021). R. F. Pinheiro is supported by the FCT project 2 ARTs (PTDC/EMD-EMD/6588/2020).

Authors are grateful to CPF (Centro de Produção e Comercialização Hortofrutícola, Lda) for providing “Rocha do Oeste” pear residues for this study.

References

- Almeida, D. P., Carvalho, R., & Dupille, E. (2016). Efficacy of 1-methylcyclopropene on the mitigation of storage disorders of ‘Rocha’ pear under normal refrigerated and controlled atmospheres, *Food Science and Technology International*, 22(5), 399-409. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1082013215610026>.
- Baydin, T., Arntsen, S. W., Hattrem, M. N., & Draget, K. I. (2022). Physical and functional properties of plant-based pre-emulsified chewable gels for the oral delivery of nutraceuticals, *Applied Food Research*, 2 (2), 100225. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.afres.2022.100225>.

Dias, C., Ribeiro, T., Rodrigues, A. C., Ferrante, A., Vasconcelos, M. W., & Pintado, M. (2022). Cold storage demand for 'Rocha' pear ripening: A comparison between a shorter and longer cold period, *Scientia Horticulturae*, 299, 111033. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2022.111033>.

Gaspar, M. C., & Braga, M. E. M. (2023). Edible films and coatings based on agrifood residues: a new trend in the food packaging research, *Current Opinion in Food Science*, 50, 101006. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cofs.2023.101006>.

Gaspar, M. C., de Sousa, H. C., Seabra, I. J., & Braga, M. E. M. (2020). Environmentally-safe scCO₂ P. pinaster branches extracts: Composition and properties, *Journal of CO₂ Utilization*, 37, 74-84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcou.2019.11.027>.

Ge, H., Wu, Y., Woshnak, L. L., & Mitmesser, S. H. (2021). Effects of hydrocolloids, acids and nutrients on gelatin network in gummies, *Food Hydrocolloids*, 113, 106549. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodhyd.2020.106549>.

Kolniak-Ostek, J. (2016). Chemical composition and antioxidant capacity of different anatomical parts of pear (*Pyrus communis* L.), *Food Chemistry*, 203, 491-497.

Pedro, S. I., Coelho, E., Peres, F., Machado, A., Rodrigues, A. M., Wessel, D. F., Coimbra, M. A., & Anjos, O. (2020). Physicochemical Fingerprint of "Pera Rocha do Oeste". A PDO Pear Native from Portugal, *Foods*, 9 (9), 1209. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods9091209>.

Saquet, A. A. (2019). Storage of pears, *Scientia Horticulturae*, 246, 1009-1016. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2018.11.091>.

Poster VII.2 A comparative analysis of two new plant-based drinks: Product development and sensorial evaluation

Author

Dias, S. – INOV.LINEA/TAGUSVALLEY – Science and Technology Park, Abrantes, Portugal

Gonçalves, D. – INOV.LINEA/TAGUSVALLEY – Science and Technology Park, Abrantes, Portugal

Pino - Hernández, E. – INOV.LINEA/TAGUSVALLEY – Science and Technology Park, Abrantes, Portugal

Alves, M. – INOV.LINEA/TAGUSVALLEY – Science and Technology Park, Abrantes, Portugal

Citation

Dias, S., Gonçalves, D., Pino-Hernández, E., Alves, M. A comparative analysis of two new plant-based drinks: Product development and sensorial evaluation.

In non-dairy drinks market, soy-based products are currently the most consumed. However, its consumption is associated with health concerns related to GMOs, allergens and high CO₂ footprint [1]. Other plants, such as pulses, that require smaller amounts of water for their production and are nutritionally rich, can be an alternative. The aim of this study was to conduct a sensory analysis to compare two formulations of chickpea-based drink. The base formula was developed using chickpea, aquafaba, fructose and gellan gum. Ten formulations with different flavors were evaluated in a trained focus group (n= 7). Carob powder (CD) and vanilla flavour (ND) were

the most accepted formulation. All products were pasteurized (98 °C, 12 min). CD and ND formulations were evaluated by naïve sensorial panel (n= 76, 43% consumers and 57% non-consumers of plant-based drinks), with an average age of 42 years old. The hedonic scale of nine points was used to analyse appearance, flavor and overall liking. JAR scale was used to evaluate sweetness and texture. Moreover, buy intention and preference were also assessed. CD and ND, had a score of around 7 (like moderately) in terms of appearance, flavor and overall liking. However, CD was preferred by 63% of panelists ($p<0.05$). Considering non-consumers, 73% preferred CD ($p<0.05$), with an overall liking of 7. More than half of panelists considered the CD sweetness and texture was “just about right”,

21.1% thought the drink was “too much liquid” and penalized the overall liking by 0.47 points. Overall, the new CD drink has potential for a successful market launch. Chickpea can be used as an alternative to soy-based drinks. The results also suggest the existence of an unexpected target public – non-consumers of plant-based drinks. To further improve the market analysis, a comparative sensorial test between dairy chocolate milk drinks and CD should be conducted.

Acknowledgments

This work was financially supported by the project INOVC+ (CENTRO-01-0246-FEDER-000044), WINBIO (POCI-01-0246-FEDER-181335), TAGUSVALLEY2030 IT (CENTRO-01-0246-FEDER000032) and TAGUSVALLEY2030 RHaq (CENTRO-04-3559-FSE-000143), under European Social Fund from the European Union managed by COMPETE 2020, CENTRO 2020 and PORTUGAL 2020.

Reference

[1] Lopes, M., Pierrepont, C., Duarte, C. M., Filipe, A., Medronho, B., & Sousa, I. (2020). Legume Beverages from Chickpea and Lupin, as New Milk Alternatives. *Foods*, 9(10), 1458. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods9101458>

Poster VII.3 Proposal of strawberry tree fruits (*Arbutus unedo* L.) as chutney main ingredient

Author

Oliveira, J. A. – Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Coimbra Agriculture School, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal; Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Coimbra Education School, Coimbra, Portugal

Ressureição S. – Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Coimbra Agriculture School, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal; Research Centre for Natural Resources Environment and Society (CERNAS), Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal.

Dias Santos S. – Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Coimbra Agriculture School, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal; Research Centre for Natural Resources Environment and Society (CERNAS), Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal

Gomes F. – Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Coimbra Agriculture School, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal; Research Centre for Natural Resources Environment and Society (CERNAS), Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal

Botelho G. – Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Coimbra Agriculture School, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal; Research Centre for Natural Resources Environment and Society (CERNAS), Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Oliveira, J. A. , Ressureição S., Dias Santos S., Gomes F., Botelho G. Proposal of strawberry tree fruits (*Arbutus unedo* L.) as chutney main ingredient.

Chutney is a spicy or savory condiment, made from fruits, vegetables and/or aromatic herbs, with vinegar, sugar, and spices. The main objective of this work was to develop formulations of chutneys using strawberry tree fruits (*Arbutus unedo* L.) as raw material. These fruits were crushed and their seeds and sclereids removed by physical separation to obtain a smooth pulp. Three chutney formulations were carried out, all consisting of those pulp, and including different raw materials, such as dry raisin and honey (CH2), pineapple (CH5) and beetroot (CH6). The chutneys were evaluated by an untrained sensorial group (66 tasters), physicochemical and colour analyses (CIEL*a*b* system). From the literature, a low pH level in the chutney is crucial for its stability and shelf life extend. The pH average values reached for each chutney were ≤ 3.50 , as desirable, to increase the stability of these products. Total sugars (g/100g) ranged as CH2 (27.23 ± 0.08) > CH6 (23.54 ± 0.36) CH5 > (17.59 ± 0.06). A similar variation was found for total fiber quantification (g/100g), with the following results: CH2 (8.27 ± 0.06) > CH6 (5.04 ± 0.18) > CH5 (3.89 ± 0.04). Chutney CH5 showed a high acceptability index (AI%) in terms of taste balance (71%), and consistency (70%). Chutney CH6 showed a high AI in terms of colour (85%) and visual appearance (78%). The AI for overall appreciation can be ranked as: CH5 (71%) > CH6 (63%) > CH2 (59%). In summary, this work showed that the incorporation of strawberry tree fruit as ingredient in chutneys have great potential to valorize this endogenous resource and provide a valuable contribution to diversify in agrifood industry.

Acknowledgments

CERNAS is supported by Portuguese National Funds through the FCT - Foundation for Science and Technology, I.P., within the scope of the project Ref. UIDB/00681/2020.

Poster VII.4 Innovative approaches to meat analogue production: High moisture extrusion and the role of plant proteins

Author

Ribeiro, G. – CARTIF, Parque Tecnológico de Boecillo, Valladolid, Spain
Piñero, M. Y. – CARTIF, Parque Tecnológico de Boecillo, Valladolid, Spain
Acebes P. – CARTIF, Parque Tecnológico de Boecillo, Valladolid, Spain
Blanco, B. – CARTIF, Parque Tecnológico de Boecillo, Valladolid, Spain

Citation

Ribeiro, G., Piñero, M.Y., Acebes P., Blanco, B. Innovative approaches to meat analogue production: High moisture extrusion and the role of plant proteins.

The extrusion of protein powders using a twin-screw extruder with a cooling die is one of the technologies with high potential to produce plant based whole meat analogues. This technology implies a double challenge: the choice of raw materials, a key parameter, being necessary the selection of the appropriate vegetable protein source capable of providing the best characteristics to the final product and with a good behavior during processing and, achieve and optimize the process conditions to reach the desired texture in the end product.

In this research, the potential of different vegetable raw materials for the production of meat analogues, including pea isolate (PPI), fava bean isolate (FPI), chickpea concentrate (CPC) and lentil concentrate (LPC), subjected to

high moisture extrusion cooking (HMEC), has been explored. For this purpose, the different critical parameters of the extrusion process, such as screw speed, feed moisture content, barrel temperature, cooling die temperature, have been tested. The techno-functional properties, water binding capacity, oil absorption capacity, emulsifying activity, emulsion stability index, foaming capacity and foaming stability, were also determined.

PPI had the highest water absorption capacity, followed by FPI and CPC. In contrast, there is no significant difference in the oil absorption capacity of the different protein sources studied. PPI presented the highest emulsifying capacity. However, FPI provided the most stable emulsion, presenting low values of stability versus high values of emulsifying capacity. In terms of foaming capacity, PPI, FPI and LPC have the highest values, with LPC showing the highest foaming stability.

HMEC is a promising alternative that emulates the fibrous texture of meat. As for the techno-functional properties, they correlate with each other and are very useful in the selection of the protein source as they allow predicting the behavior during the process, and therefore the sensory attributes in the final matrix.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank all the members of the Meating Plants collaborative Project, financed by the Institute for Business Competitiveness of Castilla y León, for their collaboration in the different tasks carried out during the development of the project.

References

Aiking, H., 2011. Future protein supply. *Trends Food Sci. Technol.* 22 (2–3), 112–120.

Boye, J. I., Aksay, S., Roufik, S., Ribéreau, S., Mondor, M., Farnworth, E. and Rajamohamed, S. H. (2010). Comparison of the functional properties of pea, chickpea and lentil protein concentrates processed using ultrafiltration and isoelectric precipitation techniques. *Food Research International*, 43(2), 537–546. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2009.07.021>

Boye, J., Zare, F. and Pletch, A. (2010). Pulse proteins: Processing, characterization, functional properties and applications in food and feed. *Food Research International*, 43(2), 414–431. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2009.09.003>

Farooq, Zubair & Boye, Joyce. (2011). Novel Food and Industrial Applications of Pulse Flours and Fractions. 10.1016/B978-0-1238-2018-1.00007-0

Ladjal-Ettoumi, Y., Boudries, H., Chibane, M. and Romero, A. (2016). Pea, Chickpea and Lentil Protein Isolates: Physicochemical Characterization and Emulsifying Properties. *Food Biophysics*, 11(1), 43–51. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11483-015-9411-6>

Lin, M.J.Y., Humbert, E.S., Sosulski, F.W., 1974. Certain functional properties of sunflower meal products. *J. Food Sci.* 39 (2), 368–370

Osen, R. and Schweiggert-Weisz, U. (2016). High-Moisture Extrusion: Meat Analogues. Reference Module in Food Science. Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-08-100596-5.03099-7>

Osen, Raffael, Toelstede, S., Wild, F., Eisner, P. and Schweiggert-Weisz, U. (2014). High moisture extrusion cooking of pea protein isolates: Raw material characteristics, extruder responses, and texture properties. *Journal of Food Engineering*, 127, 67–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2013.11.023>

Pearce, K. N. and Kinsella, J. E. (1978). Emulsifying Properties of Proteins: Evaluation of a Turbidimetric Technique. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 26(3), 716–723. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf60217a041>

Zhang, B., Kang, X., Cheng, Y., Cui, B. and Abd El-Aty, A. M. (2022). Impact of high moisture contents on the structure and functional properties of pea protein isolate during extrusion. *Food Hydrocolloids*, 127, 107508. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodhyd.2022.107508>

Poster VII.5 Increasing microalgae biomass feedstock by valorizing wine gaseous and liquid residues

Author

Cachão, M. – AVIPE, R. D. João de Castro, Palmela, Portugal
Chambel, A. – AVIPE, R. D. João de Castro, Palmela, Portugal
Pinto, S. – AVIPE, R. D. João de Castro, Palmela, Portugal

Citation

Cachão, M., Chambel, A., Pinto, S. Increasing microalgae biomass feedstock by valorizing wine gaseous and liquid residues.

Global warming due to greenhouse gases (GHG) has become a serious worldwide concern. The new EU Green Deal aims to achieve GHG emissions reduction by at least 55% by 2030 and a climate neutral EU economy by 2050. The deal strongly encourages GHG reducing measures at local, national and European levels. The REDWine project will demonstrate the technical, economic and environmental feasibility of reducing by, at least, 31% of the CO₂ eq. emissions produced in the winery industry value chain by utilizing biogenic fermentation CO₂ for microalgae biomass production.

REDWine concept will be realized through the establishment of an integrated Living Lab demonstrating the viability of the system at TRL 7. The Living Lab will be able to utilize 2 ton of fermentation off-gas/year (90% of total CO₂ produced in the fermenter) and 80 m³ of liquid effluent (100% of the liquid

effluent generated during fermenter washing) to produce 1 ton (dry weight) of *Chlorella* biomass/year. This biomass will be processed under a downstream extraction process to obtain added-value extracts and applied in food, cosmetic and agricultural end-products and to generate a new EcoWine. REDWine will focus on the recovery of off-gas from a 20.000L fermenter of red wine production existing in Adega Cooperativa de Palmela (ACP, located in Palmela, Portugal).

REDWine's microalgae were tested in 2022 and 2023 with 4 purposes in vineyard: improve flowering stages, contribute to high temperature resistance, biofungicide against downy mildew and increasing in nitrogen content in ripening to help fermentation and improve aromatic compounds. It was also used in winemaking processes as a clarificant or anti-oxidant.

So far, results were interesting on wine making process but need more trials and results to assess vineyard activity.

Poster VII.6 Shelf-life study of carob & chickpea plant-based drink pasteurized by ohmic heating

Author

Dias, S., – INOV.LINEA/TAGUSVALLEY – Science and Technology Park, Abrantes, Portugal
Gonçalves, D. – INOV.LINEA/TAGUSVALLEY – Science and Technology Park, Abrantes, Portugal
Pino-Hernández, E. – INOV.LINEA/TAGUSVALLEY – Science and Technology Park, Abrantes, Portugal
Pereira, R. – Centre of Biological Engineering – University of Minho, Braga, Portugal
Alves, M. – INOV.LINEA/TAGUSVALLEY – Science and Technology Park, Abrantes, Portugal

Citation

Dias, S., Gonçalves, D., Pino-Hernández, E., Pereira, R., Alves, M. Shelf-life study of carob & chickpea plant-based drink pasteurized by ohmic heating.

Nowadays, consumers tend to prefer more natural and minimally processed food products [1]. The mild pasteurization of food products with novel technologies based in electricity has emerged, due of the advantages over conventional heating. In this context, ohmic heating (OH) results from the application of moderate electric fields and has been claimed to enable a fast and uniform heating, as well as to maintain food quality and ensure food safety [2]. The aim of this study was to investigate the long-term stability and inherent quality of a novel Chickpea & Carob plant-based drink pasteurized by OH at two different conditions (77 °C, 2 min and 98 °C, 12 min), and

by conventional pasteurization (CP) (98 °C, 12 min). Shelf-life studies were conducted for 60 days at 4 °C. Physicochemical parameters (pH, brix, color) and microbiological counts (aerobic total at 30 °C, molds and yeasts, Enterobacteriaceae and sulphite-reducing bacteria) were evaluated over time (biweekly). Similarly to other treatments, results revealed that OH-77 °C treatment always maintained the microbiological counts below the recommended threshold. Thus, it is possible to reduce the temperature by 21 °C while assuring the product food safety by at least 60 days in refrigeration. Both technologies, CP and OH were able to ensure all physicochemical parameters and stability throughout the observation period. This study demonstrates that OH presents clear advantages compared to CP since thermal load can be reduced, allowing considerable energy savings. However, its industrial application should be adequately investigated based on the promising results obtained at laboratorial scale.

Acknowledgments

This work was financially supported by the project INOVC+ (CENTRO-01-0246-FEDER-000044), WINBIO (POCI-01-0246-FEDER-181335), TAGUSVALLEY2030 IT (CENTRO-01-0246-FEDER000032) and TAGUSVALLEY2030 RHaq (CENTRO-04-3559-FSE-000143), under European Social Fund from the European Union managed by COMPETE 2020, CENTRO 2020 and PORTUGAL 2020. Ricardo N. Pereira acknowledges FCT for its Assistant Research program under the scope of Scientific Stimulus Employment with reference CEECIND/ 02903/2017

References

- [1] FoodDrinkEurope. (2022). Data and trends EU food and drink industry.
- [2] Alkanan, Z. T., Altemimi, A. B., Al-Hilphy, A. R. S., Watson, D. G., & Pratap-Singh, A. (2021). Ohmic Heating in the Food Industry: Developments in Concepts and Applications during 2013–2020. *Applied Sciences*, 11(6), 2507. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11062507>

Poster VII.7 Novel foods with persimmon: Snacking the smart way

Author

Ramos, F., – CATAA - Agro-Food Technological Support Center Association, Zona Industrial, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal; IPCB-ESA- Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, Agrarian School, Quinta da Senhora de Mércules, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Pintado, C. – CATAA - Agro-Food Technological Support Center Association, Zona Industrial, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Riscado, A. – CATAA - Agro-Food Technological Support Center Association, Zona Industrial, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Beato, H. – CATAA - Agro-Food Technological Support Center Association, Zona Industrial, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Resende, M. – CATAA - Agro-Food Technological Support Center Association, Zona Industrial, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Delgado, F. – IPCB-ESA- Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, Agrarian School, Quinta da Senhora de Mércules, Castelo Branco, Portugal; CERNAS-IPCB-Research Centre for Natural Resources, Environment and Society, Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, Portugal

Citation

Ramos, F., Pintado, C., Riscado, A., Beato, H., Resende, M., Delgado, F. Novel foods with persimmon: Snacking the smart way.

Persimmon (*Diospyros kaki*) is a fruit originally found in China, that rapidly spread throughout the Mediterranean region, especially in countries like Portugal (Bubba et al., 2009). Rojo Brillante distinguishes out among the other cultivars because of its great productivity (Senadeera et al., 2020).

Despite being a seasonal and easily perishable fruit, persimmons contain high bioactive qualities and may have benefits for health (Karaman et al., 2014). There are alternate methods for using and consuming it all year (Senadeera et al., 2020). Various alternatives for year-round consumption being explored, with dehydration emerging as a valued method, this technique not only extends shelf life but also transforms persimmons into a healthy snack and a convenience food (Castillo et al., 2023).

The objective of this research was to develop persimmon-based snacks using the Rojo Brillante cultivar, with the intention of developing a novel food that would enable consumption of an underutilized seasonal fruit, adding value to the product, and reducing food waste.

Four distinct of persimmon-based snacks were developed (slices, sticks, cubes, and gummies), all of these are fat-free and contain only naturally occurring sugars. Slices ($3.1 \pm 0.58\text{g}/100\text{g}$) and sticks ($3.0 \pm 0.67\text{g}/100\text{g}$) are source of fibre, and gummies ($6.1 \pm 0.43\text{g}/100\text{g}$) have high fibre content. This novel snack was subjected to sensory evaluation by a panel of 60 untrained tasters through a hedonic test. The sliced variant emerged as the preferred among consumers, receiving a score of 6.9 points in a scale ranging from 1 to 9.

Dried fruit is a healthy snack option as it provides essential nutrients without recourse to artificial colours or preservatives, making this a clean label product.

Acknowledgments

This work was funded by the project INNOACE, co-funded by the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) through the INTERREG V-A Spain-Portugal (POCTEP) 2014-2020 Programme and CERNAS-IPCB [UIDB/00681/2020] funding by the Portuguese National Funding Agency for Science, Research and Technology (FCT).

References

Bubba, M., Giordani E., Pippucci, L., Cincinelli, A., Checchini, L., Galvan, P. (2009). Changes in tannins, ascorbic acid and sugar content in astringent persimmons during on-tree growth and ripening and in response to different postharvest treatments. *Journal of Food Composition and Analysis* 22:668–677. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfca.2009.02.015>

Karaman, S., Toker, O. S., Çam, M., Hayta, M., Doğan, M., Kayacier, A. (2014). Bioactive and physicochemical properties of persimmon as affected by drying methods. *Drying Technology* 32:258–267. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07373937.2013.821480>

Senadeera, W., Adiletta, G., Önal, B., Di Matteo, M., Russo, P. (2020). Influence of different hot airdrying temperatures on drying kinetics, shrinkage, and colour of persimmon slices. *Foods* 9:5–7. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods9010101>

Castillo, M., Pons-Gómez, A., Albert-Sidro, C., Delpozo, B., Besada, C. Acceptance. (2023). Sensory Characterization and Consumption Contexts for Dehydrated Persimmon Slices, Chips, Leathers and Powder: A Consumer Study. *Foods* 12:1-13. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods12101966>

Poster VII.8 Characterization of acorn flour from *Quercus pyrenaica*

Author

Borges, M. – Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, Bragança, Portugal; Laboratório Associado para a Sustentabilidade e Tecnologia em Regiões de Montanha (SusTEC), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, Bragança, Portugal
Mateus, C.G.S. – Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, Bragança, Portugal; Laboratório Associado para a Sustentabilidade e Tecnologia em Regiões de Montanha (SusTEC), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, Bragança, Portugal
Barros, L. – Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, Bragança, Portugal; Laboratório Associado para a Sustentabilidade e Tecnologia em Regiões de Montanha (SusTEC), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, Bragança, Portugal
Vilas-Boas, M. – Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, Bragança, Portugal; Laboratório Associado para a Sustentabilidade e Tecnologia em Regiões de Montanha (SusTEC), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, Bragança, Portugal
Falcão, S.I. – Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, Bragança, Portugal; Laboratório Associado para a Sustentabilidade e Tecnologia em Regiões de Montanha (SusTEC), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, Bragança, Portugal

Citation

Borges, M., Mateus, C.G.S., Barros, L., Vilas-Boas, M., Falcão, S.I. Characterization of acorn flour from *Quercus pyrenaica*.

Acorns are common wild fruits in Portugal, traditionally used as animal feed. Due to its nutritional value, acorns are an excellent alternative in the human diet, with a composition rich in bioactive compounds and, therefore, with potential for industrial application. A notable characteristic of the acorn is the absence of gluten, which can be a source for obtaining gluten-free flour, thus offering other alternatives for celiac patients.

In this context, this work aims to study the chemical composition of acorn flour from *Quercus pyrenaica* acorns, obtained by different processes to remove the tannins, which are responsible for introducing an astringent flavour and making digestion difficult. For that, acorns were collected in areas of black oak forest within the Montesinho Natural Park, Bragança, Portugal, in October of 2021 and freeze at -20°C until processing. The acorns were shelled, and three different treatments were applied: boiling water, soaking in water at room temperature during 20h and oven roasted, at 200°C for 15 min. After that, the acorns were milled and different nutritional parameters were evaluated such as humidity, ash, protein content, total lipids content, fibers, starch, fatty acids and sugars. A flour obtained from acorns without treatment was also evaluated. The results revealed that the flour obtained by roasting presented lower water content, high content in fibers, proteins and fatty acids. In conclusion, the rich nutritional profile of acorn flour from *Q. pyrenaica* associated with the fact of being a gluten free product, opens good opportunities of applying the acorn flour in innovative products in the food industry.

Acknowledgments

The authors are grateful to the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT, Portugal) for financial support by national funds FCT/MCTES to CIMO (UIDB/00690/2020), for the support through the project ACORNDEW (MTS/SAS/0099/2020) and through the institutional scientific employment program contract with Soraia I. Falcão.

Poster VII.9 Nutritional profile of hazelnuts from Beira Interior: A comparative study of nine varieties

Author

Vasconcelos, V., – CATAA - Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Paulo, L. – CATAA - Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Beato, H. – CATAA - Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Pitacas, I. – Escola Superior Agrária do Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Moitinho, A. – Escola Superior Agrária do Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal; CERNAS-IPCB, Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Espírito Santo, C. – CATAA - Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar, Castelo Branco, Portugal; CFE-UC – Centro de Ecologia Funcional da Universidade de Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Vasconcelos, V., Paulo, L., Beato, H., Pitacas, I., Moitinho, A., Espírito Santo, C. Nutritional profile of hazelnuts from Beira Interior: A comparative study of nine varieties.

Hazelnut (*Corylus avellana* L.) is a very popular fruit in the world. The biggest producer of hazelnut is Türkiye followed by Italy and the United States of America (FAOSTAT, 2020). Considering the dried fruit sector in Portugal, hazelnut is the one with the smallest cultivated area and the lowest annual production (around 232 tons per year) (INE, 2022). Hazelnuts quality depends

on its physical and chemical properties; however, few studies address these parameters from hazelnuts cultivated in Portugal. In this context, the nutritional analysis of nine hazelnut varieties (Gunslebert, Provence, Cosford, Grada de viseu, Barcelona, Negreta, Longue D'Espagne, Ennis and Sergorbe) grown in Beira Interior in Portugal was evaluated. The parameters analysed were moisture, ash, fat, fatty acids, fibre, protein, sodium and sugar profile. The results showed a high content of lipids (46.5 g.100g⁻¹ (Barcelona) - 64.1 g.100g⁻¹ (Negreta)), protein (15.1 g.100g⁻¹ (Negreta) - 23.2 g.100g⁻¹ (Grada de Viseu)) and fibre (7.7 g.100g⁻¹ (Grada de Viseu) - 36.9 g.100g⁻¹ (Negreta)). Regarding fatty acid profile, oleic acid (70.4% (Barcelona)- 81.0% (Ennis)) is the major followed by linoleic acid (9.3% (Cosford) - 21.1% (Barcelona)). In general, hazelnuts with higher oleic acid than linoleic acid have higher oxidative stability and a longer shelf life (Gama et al. 2018). Overall, sucrose, fructose and glucose were identified in the hazelnuts. As a matter of fact, the differences among the varieties evidence the richness of this resource. When explored, this richness can lead to the development of new products, the valorisation of the resource and the strengthening of the hazelnut market in Portugal.

Acknowledgments

This work was funded by National Funds in the scope of CULTIVAR project (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020).

References

FAOSTAT. Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations. <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QCL/visualize>

Ferrão, A. F., Guiné, R., Rodrigues, M., Droga, R., & Correia, P. (2020). Post-harvest characterization of the hazelnut sector. *Millenium*, 2(6), 11-20. <https://doi.org/10.29352/mill0206e.01.00344>

Gama, T., Wallace, H.M., Trueman, S.J & Hosseini-Bai, S. (2018). Quality and shelf life of tree nuts: A review. *Sci. Hortic.*, 242, 116–126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2018.07.036>

INE. (2022). *Estatísticas Agrícolas 2022*. Lisboa, Instituto Nacional de Estatística.

Poster VII.10 EQVEGAN project as a platform for innovation and strengthening skills on plant-based products in the food industry

Author

Botelho, G., – Instituto Politécnico de Coimbra, Escola Superior Agrária de Coimbra, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal; Centro de Investigação em Recursos Naturais, Ambiente e Sociedade (CERNAS), Instituto Politécnico de Coimbra, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal

Rodrigues, C. – Instituto Politécnico de Coimbra, Escola Superior Agrária de Coimbra, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal; Centro de Investigação em Recursos Naturais, Ambiente e Sociedade (CERNAS), Instituto Politécnico de Coimbra, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal

Ferreira, N. – Instituto Politécnico de Coimbra, Instituto Superior de Engenharia de Coimbra, Rua Pedro Nunes – Quinta da Nora, Portugal; Grupo de Investigação em Engenharia e Computação Inteligente para a Inovação e o Desenvolvimento, Instituto Politécnico do Porto, Instituto Superior de Engenharia do Porto, Rua Dr. António Bernardino de Almeida, Porto, Portugal

Rodrigues, I. – Instituto Politécnico de Coimbra, Escola Superior Agrária de Coimbra, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal; Centro de Investigação em Recursos Naturais, Ambiente e Sociedade (CERNAS), Instituto Politécnico de Coimbra, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal

Costa, R. – Instituto Politécnico de Coimbra, Escola Superior Agrária de Coimbra, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal; Centro de Investigação em Recursos Naturais, Ambiente e Sociedade (CERNAS), Instituto Politécnico de Coimbra, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Botelho, G., Rodrigues, C., Ferreira, N., Rodrigues, I., Costa, R. EQVEGAN project as a platform for innovation and strengthening skills on plant-based products in the food industry.

The food industry is changing due to several driving forces, based on consumer shifts towards plant-based diets, leading to an increase in the production the vegan food industry sector, that pursuits to maintain competitiveness needs to master new processes and technologies. Furthermore, the food industry is subject to more demanding sustainability requirements, which together with digitalization and automation trends, are rapidly changing the skills required of its employees. Innovative training covering these technical issues is needed to support the rapid shift towards a vegan food industry adapted to Industry 4.0.

The EQVEGAN project is funded by the European Commission through the Sector Skills Alliance (SSA) Program as part of Key Action 2 projects, consisting of a Sector Skills Alliance made up of 15 institutions from 11 countries (<https://eqvegan.eu/>). The institutions cover a range of profiles, including Vocational Education and Training (VET) providers at European Qualifications Framework (EQF) levels 4 to 7, industry associations, companies, associations of food industry professionals and teachers and researchers, the Ministry of Science and Technology and a qualification agency. The consortium covers the skills necessary to design innovative and highly qualified training, allowing recycling or conversion of skills according to market needs, using quality and EU reference tools, which will accelerate the qualified growth of this sector.

During the 2023 year, in Portugal, three actions were carried out, in the format of short courses with free registration, in the thematic areas of Digitalization and Automation (hybrid format), Meat and Dairy Analogue Technologies (online format) and Green Skills (online format), with a total of 20 participants. Although the actions were widely publicized through the social networks of the Coimbra Agriculture School and direct contacts with around 200 companies and entities, participation in two of the three actions was lower than estimated. In the future, these actions will be publicized and promoted again because the aim is to increase the number of participants.

Acknowledgment: EQVEGAN Project — European Qualifications & Competences for the Vegan Food Industry 621581-EPP-1-2020-1-PT-EPPKA2-SSA-EQVEGAN. European Education and Culture Executive Agency.

Poster VII.11 Novel product using a native sheep breed (Merino da Beira Baixa)

Author

Cristóvão, C., – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco

Rodrigues, A. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco

Silveira, A. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco

Baptista, C. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco

Beato, H. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco

Vasconcelos, V. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco

Paulo, L. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco

Pitacas, I. – Escola Superior Agrária do Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Qt.^a da Sr.^a de Mércules, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Rodrigues, A. M. – Escola Superior Agrária do Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Qt.^a da Sr.^a de Mércules, Castelo Branco, Portugal; CERNAS-IPCB (project UIDB/00681/2020 funding by FCT), Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Espírito Santo, C. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco; Universidade de Coimbra, Centro de Ecologia Funcional, Departamento de Ciências da Vida, Calçada Martim de Freitas, Coimbra, Portugal

Brandão, I. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco; Universidade de Coimbra, Centro de Ecologia Funcional, Departamento de Ciências da Vida, Calçada Martim de Freitas, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Cristóvão, C., Rodrigues, A., Silveira, A., Baptista, C., Beato, H., Vasconcelos, V., Paulo, L., Pitacas, I., Rodrigues, A. M., Espírito Santo, C., Brandão, I. Novel product using a native sheep breed (Merino da Beira Baixa).

Approximately 12,000 years ago, humanity domesticated sheep (*Ovis aries*), the Merino breed emerged during the textile industry development. Renowned for their high-quality wool and resilience to the harsh Iberian Peninsula conditions (Ceccobelli et al., 2023). The “Merino da Beira Baixa” breed, has played a pivotal role in securing three protected designations of origin (PDO) in the Castelo Branco area (Ferreira et al., 2009). However, in recent times, the breed has experienced a decline to near extinction due to scarce wool sales at very low prices and an inability to contend with more milk-productive breeds that were permitted to participate in the production of PDO cheese (Rebello de Andrade, 2019). In an effort to preserve this native breed, our work aims to develop a novel food product using this ancestral breed, slow cooking at low temperatures and smoking techniques.

“Merino da Beira Baixa” breed (the certification of protected geographical indication (PGI) for “Borrego da Beira”) was used in this development. First the head was removed, and the carcass eviscerated and divided into an appropriate size. To achieve a uniform distribution of meat, the carcass is divided into two segments, one encompassing the neck, chuck, rib, and loin (Saddle), and the other comprising the legs (Leg). After two-day marination in a blend of vinegar and brandy is followed by the application of a spice coating, the meat undergoes smoking (60% hickory and 40% oak) for one hour at 25°C in a specialized chamber and then a drying process at 70°C for six hours for the saddle and 22 hours for the leg.

The resulting product was thoroughly analysed concerning nutritional composition and sensorial analysis ($n=3$). The nutritional outcome was high in protein, low sugar content and a fibre source. Both lamb portions received an overall score exceeding seven points on a scale of one to nine in hedonic test

(n=31). Additionally, tasters were asked about the buying intent and the result was a 90% buying intent for the Saddle and 77% buying intent for the Leg.

Acknowledgments

Fusilli (European Union's Horizon 2020 under grant agreement No. 101000717)

References

- Ceccobelli, S., Landi, V., Senczuk, G., Mastrangelo, S., Sardina, M. T., Ben-Jemaa, S., Persichilli, C., Karsli, T., Bâlteanu, V. A., Raschia, M. A., Poli, M. A., Ciappesoni, G., Muchadeyi, F. C., Dzomba, E. F., Kunene, N. W., Lühken, G., Deniskova, T. E., Dotsev, A. V., Zinovieva, N. A., ... Pilla, F. (2023). A comprehensive analysis of the genetic diversity and environmental adaptability in worldwide Merino and Merino-derived sheep breeds. *Genetics, Selection, Evolution : GSE*, 55(1), 24. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12711-023-00797-z>
- Ferreira, I. M. P. L. V. O., Pinho, O., & Sampaio, P. (2009). Volatile fraction of DOP "Castelo Branco" cheese: Influence of breed. *Food Chemistry*, 112(4), 1053–1059. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2008.06.048>
- Rebello de Andrade, C. S. (2019). Merino da Beira Baixa. AniDoP.

Poster VII.12 Perceptions of insect consumption among the Portuguese population

Author

Cristóvão, M. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco Portugal
Rodrigues, A. M. – Escola Superior Agrária do Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Qt.ª da Sr.ª de Mércules, Castelo Branco, Portugal.; CERNAS-IPCB (project UIDB/00681/2020 funding by FCT), Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Citation

Cristóvão, M., Rodrigues, A.M. Perceptions of insect consumption among the Portuguese population.

Entomophagy represents a significant milestone in the evolution of human nutrition (Raubenheimer & Rothman, 2013), with insects serving as an important food source being consumed worldwide (Ramos-Elorduy & Montesinos, 2007). Over 1,600 insect species have found their way onto the plates of more than 2 billion people on a daily basis (Van Huis et al., 2013). This study aims to assess the potential for edible insect consumption in Portugal, conducting an online survey with 491 respondents across the country to evaluate the consumption habits and insect acceptability among the general population.

Surprisingly, only a modest percentage of individuals adamantly reject insects as a dietary option, with just 18.7% of respondents refusing to include insects in their meals. Moreover, when the scope is expanded to consider the application of insects in animal feed, this rejection rate drops to 6.4%. Among the various

forms of insect consumption, birds and fish appear as the most accepted animal species (39%) to be fed insect-containing diets, while direct human consumption of whole insects remains the least popular option (18.7%).

Cultural factors emerge as a prominent reason for this reluctance, as European society still harbours perceptions of insects as repulsive and unappetizing. However, considering that palatability isn't the sole determinant for rejection, and that insects offer a sustainable and nutritious solution to global food security, there is potential for their widespread as a vital component of our diet.

Acknowledgments

CERNAS-IPCB [UIDB/00681/2020] funding by the Portuguese National Funding Agency for Science, Research and Technology (FCT).

References

- Ramos-Elorduy, J., & Montesinos, J. L. V. (2007). Los insectos como alimento humano: breve ensayo sobre la entomofagia, con especial referencia a México. *Boletín de La Real Sociedad Española de Historia Natural. Sección Biológica*, 102(1), 61–84.
- Raubenheimer, D., & Rothman, J. M. (2013). Nutritional Ecology of Entomophagy in Humans and Other Primates. *Annual Review of Entomology*, 58(1), 141–160. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-ento-120710-100713>
- Van Huis, A., Van Itterbeeck, J., Klunder, H., Mertens, E., Halloran, A., Muir, G., & Vantomme, P. (2013). Edible insects. Future prospects for food and feed security. In *Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (Vol. 171)*.

Poster VII.13 PROMEDLIFE: Novel food products for promotion of Mediterranean lifestyle and healthy diet

Author

Riviou, K. – Ellinogermaniki Agogi, Research & Development Dept., Athens, Greece

Citation

Riviou, K. PROMEDLIFE: Novel food products for promotion of Mediterranean lifestyle and healthy diet.

The need to maintain the production of local foods characterized by a high nutritional index, update traditional food production methodologies by developing attractive tech-based approaches, promote healthy eating habits that meet consumers' preferences and acceptability, as well as reducing the complexity of supply chains (Farm to Fork) must be addressed to ensure food and nutrition security. This is especially true in Mediterranean countries undergoing dietary and nutritional changes that affect their inhabitants' health while creating many socio-economic and environmental challenges. These changes have happened despite the health benefits of consuming a Mediterranean diet (MD)[1] demonstrated in numerous epidemiological studies, and because dietary interventions are effective, it is essential to identify and address perceived barriers to healthy eating.

PROMEDLIFE aims to increase adherence to the MD through a multi-actor approach by encouraging the adoption of a healthy eating lifestyle while decreasing the environmental and economic impact of food production and processing. It also aims to attain optimal food communication and education through training programs that target primary and (upper) secondary students as well as their families, from children to older adults. So far, we have conducted a survey on consumers food habits and attitudes towards healthy/local foods in 5 countries (Italy, Greece, Morocco, Tunisia and Slovenia), new healthy snacks have been created (yoghurt/sour milk with saffron, amlou cream, veggie chips, bars) that will be soon tested in an experimental intervention study in 3 countries (Italy, Greece and Tunisia) with 4 experimental students groups and are in the process of creating educational resources and scenarios that will be used in the study. As a final step we will valorise local Mediterranean products through the development of food labelling using innovative tools to increase people's connection with their cultural and local heritage and improve their awareness of food healthy choices.

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the PRIMA programme supported by the European Union, Grant agreement No 2132 (<https://promedlifeproject.eu/>)

Reference

1 Davis C, Bryan J, Hodgson J, Murphy K. Definition of the Mediterranean Diet; a Literature Review. *Nutrients*. 2015 Nov 5;7(11):9139-53. doi: 10.3390/nu7115459. PMID: 26556369; PMCID: PMC4663587.

Poster VII.14 Modelling the inactivation of *Bacillus subtilis* by hyperbaric inactivation at room temperature – dependence of ph and nutrients' availability

Author

Pinto, C. – LAQV-REQUIMTE, Chemistry Department, University of Aveiro, Campus Universitário de Santiago, Aveiro, Portugal

Ganjeh, A. – LAQV-REQUIMTE, Chemistry Department, University of Aveiro, Campus Universitário de Santiago, Aveiro, Portugal

Saraiva, J. – LAQV-REQUIMTE, Chemistry Department, University of Aveiro, Campus Universitário de Santiago, Aveiro, Portugal

Citation

Pinto, C, Ganjeh, A., Saraiva, J. Modelling the inactivation of *Bacillus subtilis* by hyperbaric inactivation at room temperature – dependence of ph and nutrients' availability.

Hyperbaric inactivation (HI) is a nonthermal, moderate pressure-based processing methodology that makes use of hydrostatic pressures (≤ 250 MPa) for long dwell times (hours/days) to inactivate microorganisms in heat and pressure-sensitive foods. Recently, this methodology has shown great potential to inactivate vegetative microorganisms and bacterial spores, which are highly resistant either to thermal or nonthermal pasteurization methodologies, requiring temperatures above 100°C for several minutes to inactivate them. Considering the importance of bacterial spores for food safety and shelf-life, it is of utmost importance to evaluate the feasibility

of this methodology for endospore inactivation in a range of pH-values pertinent for food safety.

This work evaluated the potential of HI to inactivate *Bacillus subtilis* endospores, and the dependence of pH and nutrient-availability on endospore inactivation. *B. subtilis* endospores were inoculated in nutrient-free McIlvaine buffer and Brain-heart infusion broth at different pH levels (4.50, 6.00 and 7.50) and kept under hyperbaric inactivation (150, 200 and 250MPa) up to 7 days at uncontrolled room temperature (18–25°C).

The results demonstrated a dependence of nutrient-availability and pH upon endospore inactivation under HI conditions, which allowed to fit both linear and non-linear (Weibull, Log-logistic and Biphasic) kinetic models frequently used to describe endospore inactivation. Lower pH values hindered endospore inactivation at 150MPa, even in the presence of nutrients, which could be surpassed at and above 200MPa. The presence of nutrients accelerated endospore inactivation, which impacted the inactivation kinetic parameters. A pressure increase to 250MPa did not accelerate endospore inactivation at both pH 6.00 and 7.50. Moreover, phase-contrast microscopy revealed that the endospores were inactivated without reaching the vegetative state, which is an important outcome for food safety.

These results hint HI as an approach for the inactivation of bacterial spores at room temperature, without applying any heat, which could be particularly interesting for heat-sensitive foods and other matrices.

Acknowledgments

This work received support from PT national funds (FCT/MCTES, Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia and Ministério da Ciência, Tecnologia e Ensino Superior) through the projects UIDB/50006/2020 and UIDP/50006/2020. Carlos A. Pinto and Alireza M. Ganjeh thanks FCT/MCTES and the ESF (European Social Fund) for the PhD grants SFRH/BD/137036/2018 and 2022.12558.BD, respectively.

Poster VII.15 When the atypical cases attack - hyperbaric storage/ inactivation as a targeting tool to inactivate *Alicyclobacillus acidoterrestris* and *Byssochlamys nivea* spores

Author

Pinto, C – LAQV-REQUIMTE, Chemistry Department, University of Aveiro, Campus Universitário de Santiago, Aveiro, Portugal

Ganjeh, A. – LAQV-REQUIMTE, Chemistry Department, University of Aveiro, Campus Universitário de Santiago, Aveiro, Portugal

[Saraiva, J.](#) – LAQV-REQUIMTE, Chemistry Department, University of Aveiro, Campus Universitário de Santiago, Aveiro, Portugal

Citation

Pinto, C, Ganjeh, A., Saraiva, J. When the atypical cases attack - hyperbaric storage/ inactivation as a targeting tool to inactivate *Alicyclobacillus acidoterrestris* and *Byssochlamys nivea* spores.

Alicyclobacillus acidoterrestris (ACB) and *Byssochlamys nivea* (BN) are spore-forming microorganisms resistant to pasteurization and prevalent in acidic fruit juices, whose spores are atypical cases, since they can germinate/ outgrow at pH-values below 4.6, thus spoiling juices during storage, due to the production of off-flavours (like guaiacol for ACB) or mycotoxins (like patulin for BN). The most used strategy to inhibit spore germination and development is refrigeration, which is energetically expensive and

environmentally harmful. Hyperbaric storage (HS) is a new preservation methodology, based on storage pressure control, inasmuch temperature control as in refrigeration, to hurdle microbial development. Truly, when performed at uncontrolled room temperatures (RT), it attains considerable energetic savings (Basso et al., 2022).

This work evaluated the performance of HS/RT (50-250MPa) to inhibit ACB and BN spores. The spores were inoculated in commercial apple juice (pH 3.70) and were pasteurized at 80-90°C (for BN and ACB, respectively) for 30 sec, or at 600MPa for 3 min at 17°C, and afterwards kept under HS conditions for up to 30 days.

The results showed that HS/RT hurdled spores' development for both microorganisms, resulting in spore inactivation along storage. For BN spores, a previous pasteurization step was crucial for spore inactivation under HS/RT (of about 3-log units at 150MPa to below quantification limits) after 5 days. For ACB, spore inactivation was observed, regardless of the previous pasteurization step, with an overall 5-log units' reduction after 1 day at 250MPa. Phase-contrast microscopy imaging revealed that the spores do not originate a vegetative cell while under HS/RT conditions, thus eliminating the risk of guaiacol (for ACB) and patulin (for BN) production, despite of being at RT.

These results underline the potential of HS as a technique for avoiding the germination/development of bacterial and fungi spores, while gradually inactivating these structures, offering enhanced food safety and quality.

Acknowledgments

This work received support from PT national funds (FCT/MCTES, Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia and Ministério da Ciência, Tecnologia e Ensino Superior) through the projects UIDB/50006/2020 and UIDP/50006/2020. Carlos A. Pinto and Alireza M. Ganjeh thanks FCT/MCTES and the ESF (European Social Fund) for the PhD grants SFRH/BD/137036/2018 and 2022.12558.BD, respectively.

Reference

Basso, F., Manzocco, L., & Nicoli, M. C. (2022). Hyperbaric Storage of Food: Applications, Challenges, and Perspectives. *Food Engineering Reviews*, 14(1), 20–30. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12393-021-09296-7>

Poster VII.16 Hyperbaric food preservation as a methodology hurdling bacterial toxins production at room temperature

Author

Tavares, J., – LAQV-REQUIMTE, Department of Chemistry, University of Aveiro, Aveiro, Portugal

Matos, G. – LAQV-REQUIMTE, Department of Chemistry, University of Aveiro, Aveiro, Portugal

Pinto, C. – LAQV-REQUIMTE, Department of Chemistry, University of Aveiro, Aveiro, Portugal

Casal, S. – LAQV-REQUIMTE, Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Porto, Porto, Portugal

Teixeira, P. – Universidade Católica Portuguesa, CBQF - Centro de Biotecnologia e Química Fina – Laboratório Associado, Escola Superior de Biotecnologia, Rua Diogo Botelho 1327, Porto, Portugal

Saraiva, J. – LAQV-REQUIMTE, Department of Chemistry, University of Aveiro, Aveiro, Portugal

Citation

Tavares, J., Matos, G., Pinto, C., Casal, S., Teixeira, P., Saraiva, J. Hyperbaric food preservation as a methodology hurdling bacterial toxins production at room temperature.

Approximately 17% of the foodborne illnesses in the European Union are related to bacterial toxins, including *Staphylococcus aureus* enterotoxins (EFSA & ECDC, 2022). Staphylococcal food poisoning is caused by the

consumption of foods contaminated with pre-formed staphylococcal enterotoxins. These enterotoxins are extremely resistant to both physical (high and low temperatures/dehydration) and/or chemical based (pH-shifts) food preservation methods, where normally *S. aureus* does not survive (Grispoldi et al., 2021; Haghi et al., 2021). Therefore, this research aimed studying the effect of a pressure-inspired preservation methodology on pathogenic microorganisms and their virulence factors to produce safer food products with an extended shelf-life.

The behaviour of the enterotoxigenic strain of *S. aureus* (ATCC 29213) was evaluated in tryptic soy broth at 25°C, preserved up to 14 days under constant pressure (25|50|75MPa), with enterotoxin production evaluated at days 7 and 14. Enterotoxins A to E detection/quantification was performed using a commercial immune-enzymatic kit Ridascreen® SET Total (ISO, 2017). Enterotoxins A and E production was detected at 25MPa|25°C but tended to be in lower quantities than the respective control (0.1MPa|25°C). However, at 50 and 75MPa|25°C and in the refrigerated control (0.1MPa|8°C), no production was detected. These results were in accordance with the *S. aureus* growth behaviour at 25MPa, reaching 8.39log CFU/mL at day 14, and allowing enterotoxins production. A growth inhibition pattern was observed due to both the effect of pressure at 50MPa|25°C and the low temperature at 0.1MPa|8°C, with a constant *S. aureus* load. However, at 75MPa, a gradual inactivation was observed, with no toxin's detection. Therefore, these results demonstrate that this pressure-based methodology is effective in controlling the growth of *S. aureus* or enterotoxin production, despite depending on the low/mild pressure applied. Further investigation is needed to deeper understand and evaluate the effects of pressure on the cellular structures and other virulence factors.

Acknowledgments

Thanks are due to the University of Aveiro and FCT/MCTES for the financial support for the LAQV REQUIMTE Research Unit (FCT UIDB/50006/2020 and UIDP/50006/2020) through national funds. Jéssica Tavares would like to thank also FCT/MCTES for the PhD Grant of 2021.07264.BD.

References

- EFSA, & ECDC. (2022). The European Union One Health 2021 Zoonoses Report. In *EFSA Journal* (Vol. 20, Issue 12). John Wiley and Sons Inc. <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2022.7666>
- Grispoldi, L., Karama, M., Armani, A., Hadjicharalambous, C., & Cenci-Goga, B. T. (2021). Staphylococcus aureus enterotoxin in food of animal origin and staphylococcal food poisoning risk assessment from farm to table. In *Italian Journal of Animal Science* (Vol. 20, Issue 1, pp. 677–690). Taylor and Francis Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1828051X.2020.1871428>
- Haghi, F., Zeighami, H., Hajiloo, Z., Torabi, N., & Derakhshan, S. (2021). High frequency of enterotoxin encoding genes of Staphylococcus aureus isolated from food and clinical samples. *Journal of Health, Population and Nutrition*, 40(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41043-021-00246-x>
- ISO. (2017, June). ISO 19020:2017. Microbiology of the Food Chain – Horizontal Method for the Immunoenzymatic Detection of Staphylococcal Enterotoxins in Foodstuffs. <https://www.iso.org/standard/63747.html>

Poster VII.17 The health and sustainability impact assessment in the context of a new bioindustry: The one health concept in InsectERA

Author

Assunção, R. – Egas Moniz Center for Interdisciplinary Research (CiEM); Egas Moniz School of Health & Science, Caparica, Almada, Portugal

Quinteiro, P. – Centre for Environmental and Marine Studies (CESAM), Department of Environment and Planning, University of Aveiro, Campus Universitário de Santiago, Aveiro, Portugal

Citation

Assunção, R., Quinteiro, P. The health and sustainability impact assessment in the context of a new bioindustry: The one health concept in InsectERA.

One Health recognizes that the health of humans, domestic and wild animals, plants and the wider environment are intimately linked and interdependent. In this context, any action or stressor that compromises one of these components has the potential to affect the others, reinforcing the idea of One Health. One Health approach is an integrated, unifying approach that aims to sustainably balance and optimise the health of humans, animals, and ecosystems.

The pandemic period that affected the world has raised awareness of the close interrelationship between human health, animal health and the environment. Therefore, the application of the One Health approach to

minimise harm and maximise benefit from the co-management of human, animal and environmental health is fundamental to the development of efficient and effective strategies to address health issues at the human-animal-environment interface.

One of the major challenges we face today relates to agri-food systems. Indeed, the pressure of food production on the environment is increasing, mainly due to the growth of the human population and the resulting increase in food demand, changes in food consumption patterns and the intensification of production systems, especially for the production of animal-based proteins. The need to transform food systems is therefore urgent and should be underpinned by decisions based on the simultaneous assessment and integration of overall health and sustainability impacts, taking into account economic, environmental and social implications.

The InsectERA agenda, an “Agenda Mobilizadora” funded under the Recovery and Resilience Plan (PRR), brings together stakeholders from different sectors across the value chain who want to harness the potential of insects as bioindustrial tools and solutions. Several products will be developed in this new bioindustry. Assuming that all products may have an impact on human, animal and environmental health, the health and sustainability impacts will be assessed.

Acknowledgments

This work is funded by Agenda Mobilizadora Insectera (<https://www.insectera.pt>), under the Programa de Recuperação e Resiliência (PRR), in the context of NextGenerationEU from the European Commission.

Poster VII.18 Chestnut conservation: Evaluation of the impact of different treatments on quality and conservation

Author

Cristóvão, M., – CATAA- Associação Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Camelo, A. – CATAA- Associação Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Riscado, A. – CATAA- Associação Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Rodrigues, A. – CATAA- Associação Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Silveira, A. – CATAA- Associação Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Baptista, C. – CATAA- Associação Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Beato, H. – CATAA- Associação Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Paulo, L. – CATAA- Associação Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Vasconcelos, V. – CATAA- Associação Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Pereira, F. – CATAA- Associação Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal; Escola Superior de Saúde do Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Avenida D. Afonso V, Bragança, Portugal

Brandão, I. – CATAA- Associação Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal;

Universidade de Coimbra, Centro de Ecologia Funcional, Departamento de Ciências da Vida, Calçada Martim de Freitas, Coimbra, Portugal
Espírito Santo, C. – CATAA- Associação Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar de Castelo Branco, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco, Portugal; Universidade de Coimbra, Centro de Ecologia Funcional, Departamento de Ciências da Vida, Calçada Martim de Freitas, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Cristóvão, M., Camelo, A., Riscado, A., Rodrigues, A., Silveira, A., Baptista, C., Beato, H., Paulo, L., Vasconcelos, V., Pereira, F., Brandão, I., Espírito Santo, C. Chestnut conservation: Evaluation of the impact of different treatments on quality and conservation.

Chestnut were considered a product with high value patrimonial and nutritional (Blaiotta et al., 2014) Portugal is the seventh-largest producer of chestnuts in the world (FAO, 2021). Chestnuts are high pierceable fruit as in 2022 part of Portuguese production (39.9%) was lost due to late rain (Instituto Nacional de Estatística, 2023).

Post-harvest damages make high losses in quality and market value as the optimal status are only maintained for a short period of time. The principal factors in post-harvest depreciation are moulding or rotting by insects or fungi, infections often start by the contact of the fruits with the ground before picking (Jermini et al., 2006). As the storage conditions defined (Cecchini et al., 2011) the controlled atmosphere rage is yet to be optimized.

This study aims to understand the effect of different treatments effect the conservation time of chestnuts. For that there were selected chestnut (cv. Martáinha) by immersion (those that floated were rejected). For the control of the evolution, sixty chestnuts for each treatment were numbered and weighed.

These fruits were then subjected to four different storage conditions: a control group, two controlled atmospheres CO₂ (5%) and O₂ (3%) (C5) and CO₂ (15%) and O₂ (3%) (C15), and a sanitization system (CI) Ionny (Fruit Control) based on high-energy ions.

The chestnuts were stored at -1/-2°C and 90% relative humidity. Throughout the conservation period, the chestnuts were regularly assessed for weight, colour, texture, total soluble solids, and sensory analysis (that included evaluation of appearance, texture, taste, aroma, and overall appreciation using a 9-point hedonic scale).

After 105 days of conservation, both controlled atmosphere treatments (C5 and C15) scored above the acceptance threshold (5 points) 6.4 and 6.9 respectively. However, the control and CI treatments only scored above the acceptance threshold until 60 days of conservation. Furthermore, the CI treatment demonstrated a lower presence of fungi in the shell compared to the other treatments during their conservation period.

Acknowledgments

Município do Sabugal, this work was funded by Projeto CULTIVAR (CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-000020)

References

Blaiotta, G., Di Capua, M., Romano, A., Coppola, R., & Aponte, M. (2014). Optimization of water curing for the preservation of chestnuts (*Castanea sativa* Mill.) and evaluation of microbial dynamics during process. *Food Microbiology*, 42, 47–55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fm.2014.02.009>

Cecchini, M., Contini, M., Massantini, R., Monarca, D., & Moscetti, R. (2011). Effects of controlled atmospheres and low temperature on storability of chestnuts manually and mechanically harvested. *Postharvest Biology and Technology*, 61(2–3), 131–136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.postharvbio.2011.03.001>

FAO. (2021). FAOSTAT. <http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#home>. Accessed in 08/10/2023

Instituto Nacional de Estadística. (2023). *Estatísticas Agrícolas 2022*.

Jermi, M., Conedera, M., Sieber, T. N., Sassella, A., Schärer, H., Jelmini, G., & Höhn, E. (2006). Influence of fruit treatments on perishability during cold storage of sweet chestnuts. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture*, 86(6), 877–885. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.2428>

Poster VII.19 Development and characterization of an orange dehydrated crispy snack

Author

Cristóvão, M., – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco; Portugal

Camelo, A. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco; Portugal

Martins, A. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco; Portugal

Silveira, A. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco; Portugal

Riscado, A. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco; Portugal

Rodrigues, A. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco; Portugal

Baptista, C. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco; Portugal

Beato, H. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco; Portugal

Vasconcelos, V. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco; Portugal

Paulo, L. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco; Portugal

Pitacas, I. – Escola Superior Agrária do Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Qt.ª da Sr.ª de Mércules, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Rodrigues, A. M. – Escola Superior Agrária do Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Qt.ª da Sr.ª de Mércules, Castelo Branco, Portugal; CERNAS-IPCB (project UIDB/00681/2020 funding by FCT), Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Espírito Santo, C. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco; Portugal; Universidade de Coimbra, Centro de Ecologia Funcional, Departamento de Ciências da Vida, Calçada Martim de Freitas, Coimbra, Portugal

Brandão, I. – CATAA- Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro Alimentar, Zona Industrial de Castelo Branco, Rua A, Castelo Branco; Portugal; Universidade de Coimbra, Centro de Ecologia Funcional, Departamento de Ciências da Vida, Calçada Martim de Freitas, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Cristóvão, M., Camelo, A., Martins, A., Silveira, A., Riscado, A., Rodrigues, A., Baptista, C., Beato, H., Vasconcelos, V., Paulo, L., Pitacas, I., Rodrigues, A. M., Espírito Santo, C., Brandão, I. Development and characterization of an orange dehydrated crispy snack.

Oranges are mainly consumed as fresh fruit, processed orange (mostly as juice) represent a global commodity (Gmitter et al., 2012; Multari et al., 2020). Dried fruits are used as versatile foods, usually as snacks or as an ingredient in baked goods or to enrich other foods (Khiari et al., 2018). Dried oranges are commonly used as a dietary supplement for animals in powder form (Delgado-Pertíñez et al., 2021) for human consumption they are used as a food ingredient (Martínez-Navarrete et al., 2023). With the understanding that one of the most appreciated proprieties of a snack is its crunchy texture (Silva-Espinoza et al., 2020) this study aims to create a new product by dehydrating sweet oranges in an innovative format (thin, crunchy pieces), resulting in an original snack that can be used in multiple ways.

The orange was peeled, grounded and dehydrated in a convective hot air circulation dryer with and a built-in sensor to measure the relative humidity and temperature of the drying air.

The product was fully characterised in terms of nutritional value, water activity (aw), microbiology and sensory analysis. The result is a high-energy product with no added sugar, no fat and no salt. The final product has a low aw value

(0.238), which limits enzymatic and chemical degradation reactions and microbial development. After sensory analysis, the snack received an overall score of 8 ± 1 (on a scale of 1 to 9).

Acknowledgments

Fusilli (European Union's Horizon 2020 under grant agreement No. 101000717)

References

Abbasi, H., Seidavi, A., Liu, W., & Asadpour, L. (2014). Investigation on the effect of different levels of dried sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis*) pulp on performance, carcass characteristics and physiological and biochemical parameters in broiler chicken. *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences*, 22(2), 139–146. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sjbs.2014.09.006>

Delgado-Pertíñez, M., Martín-García, I., Mena, Y., Zarazaga, L. Á., & Guzmán, J. L. (2021). Supplementing the diet of dairy goats with dried orange pulp throughout lactation: li effect on milk fatty acids profile, phenolic compounds, fat-soluble vitamins and antioxidant capacity. *Animals*, 11(8). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani11082421>

Gmitter, F. G., Chen, C., Machado, M. A., de Souza, A. A., Ollitrault, P., Froehlicher, Y., & Shimizu, T. (2012). Citrus genomics. In *Tree Genetics and Genomes* (Vol. 8, Issue 3, pp. 611–626). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11295-012-0499-2>

Khiari, R., Zemni, H., & Mihoubi, D. (2018). Raisin processing: physicochemical, nutritional and microbiological quality characteristics as affected by drying process. In *Food Reviews International* (Vol. 35, Issue 3, pp. 246–298). Taylor and Francis Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1080/87559129.2018.1517264>

Liotta, L., Randazzo, C. L., Russo, N., Zumbo, A., di Rosa, A. R., Caggia, C., & Chiofalo, V. (2019). Effect of molasses and dried orange pulp as sheep dietary supplementation on physico-chemical, microbiological and fatty acid profile of comisana ewe's milk and cheese. *Frontiers in Nutrition*, 6. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnut.2019.00001>

Martínez-Navarrete, N., García-Martínez, E., & Camacho, M. del M. (2023). Characterization of the Orange Juice Powder Co-Product for Its Valorization as a Food Ingredient. *Foods*, 12(97). <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods12010097>

Multari, S., Carafa, I., Barp, L., Caruso, M., Licciardello, C., Larcher, R., Tuohy, K., & Martens, S. (2020). Effects of *Lactobacillus* spp. on the phytochemical composition of juices from two varieties of *Citrus sinensis* L. Osbeck: 'Tarocco' and 'Washington navel.' *LWT - Food Science and Technology*, 125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2020.109205>

Pacheco, C., García-Martínez, E., Moraga, G., Piña, J., Nazareno, M. A., & Martínez-Navarrete, N. (2019). Development of dried functional foods: Stabilization of orange pulp powder by addition of biopolymers. *Powder Technology*, 362, 11–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2019.11.116>

Silva-Espinoza, M. A., Camacho, M. del M., & Martínez-Navarrete, N. (2020). Use of different biopolymers as carriers for purposes of obtaining a freeze-dried orange snack. *LWT*, 127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2020.109415>

Theme VIII – Bioactive compounds, nutritional characteristics, food matrices & human health impact

Synopsis - Keynote Speakers

From nature to products: Natural ingredients for the food industry

Author

Lillian Barros – Mountain Research Centre (CIMO), Institute Polytechnic of Bragança, Portugal

Citation

Barros, L., From nature to products: Natural ingredients for the food industry.

Recently, scientific validation of an array of applications and benefits arising from the use of natural ingredients and edible matrices has increased worldwide. Here, the improvement of health conditions through the use of plants and mushrooms represents a rich cultural legacy, with these matrices being traditionally used as sources of micro and macronutrients and in

different medicinal preparations. These are made up of natural ingredients with high added value, acting as natural colorants and preservatives, and providing bioactive properties when added to other products.

Currently, various innovative technologies have been used to optimize extraction systems, increasing the purity of the natural target compounds and extraction yields. Some colorants have been successfully extracted from *Beta vulgaris* L., *Gomphrena globosa* L., *Bixa orellana* L., and *Curcuma longa* L., and used in different food formulations. On the other hand, a wide variety of biowastes and/or by-products have been effectively used as bioactive molecules, such as those from *Agaricus bisporus*, rich in pro-vitamin D2 (ergosterol), and fruit residues, which have shown to perform different bioactivities. Peels from acorn, in turn, have been used as preservatives, and by-products from fish industry used in the formulation of healthy pet food. Additionally, in this field, the use of figs and pumpkins through the extraction of bioactive compounds from all their components and subsequent incorporation into derived products, show satisfactory outcomes, boosting the circular economy of all its constituents. In parallel, bioactive molecules from olive pomace have been recovered for further incorporation into cosmeceutical formulations, while improving sustainable extraction processes and their optimization.

These results highlight the effectiveness of natural ingredients from different natural matrices, promoting their valorisation as sources of naturally-based ingredients able to be incorporated into widely consumed and appreciated food products at an industrial/commercial level.

Water metabolic effects

Author

Maria João Martins – University of Porto, Portugal i3S, Portugal

Citation

Martins, M.J., Water metabolic effects.

Several research groups and international organizations have already highlighted the relevance of the origin, chemical composition and/or pH, as well as the ingested volume, of drinking water in terms of Public Health. Correlations have been reported regarding body composition, cardiovascular disease, type 2 diabetes, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease and/or bone health. Drinking water can be a source of needed minerals. Part of the research done on this topic at the Unit of Biochemistry, Department of Biomedicine, from the Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto, was presented.

Plant-derived foods as a valuable renewable bioresource of a plethora of impactful bioactive molecules

Author

José S. Câmara – University of Madeira Portugal Madeira Chemistry Research Centre, Portugal

Citation

Câmara, J.S., Plant-derived foods as a valuable renewable bioresource of a plethora of impactful bioactive molecules.

This talk will explore the use of plant-derived bioactive compounds as valuable and renewable resources. Living organisms synthesize primary metabolites essential for metabolic processes and secondary metabolites, known as bioactive compounds, which play crucial roles in defense, signaling, and cellular functions. These compounds include polyphenols, carotenoids, polysaccharides, and polyunsaturated fatty acids, found abundantly in foods such as tea, red wine, vegetables, fruits, and spices.

Bioactive compounds exhibit a range of biological activities, including antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-diabetic, and anti-hypertensive effects. They also show potential in preventing chronic diseases like cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, neurodegenerative conditions, and cancer, mainly through anti-inflammatory, apoptotic, and stress-reducing mechanisms. For instance, polyphenols in green tea, such as catechins, play a role in inhibiting neurodegenerative processes.

These compounds have applications in industries like pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, textiles, and agriculture, acting as antimicrobials, antioxidants, and colorants. Advanced extraction techniques, such as ultrasound and supercritical fluids, enhance the recovery of these molecules. Their use in developing innovative products can lead to new business opportunities, contributing to economic growth across various sectors.

Risk assessment of *Cynara cardunculus* L. in PDO cheeses

Author

Luis Pinto de Andrade – IPCB, Portugal

Citation

Andrade, L.P.d. Risk assessment of *Cynara cardunculus* L. in PDO cheeses.

As part of the application for authorization of the use of the enzyme phytapsin from *Cynara cardunculus* L. submitted to the EFSA by QUALIFICA, under Article 17.3 of Regulation (EC) No 1332/2008 on food enzymes and intended to be used in milk processing for cheese production, the EFSA Panel concluded that this food enzyme does not raise safety concerns under the intended conditions of use. This decision were based on data and evidenced provided, such as:

1-The source of the food enzyme

The cardoon extract containing the food enzyme phytapsin is obtained from edible parts of *Cynara cardunculus* L. plants, (flowers) dried and the use of traditional preparations measured applied the *quantum satis* principle, depending on the technological requirements for the type of cheese to be manufactured.

2- Production of the food enzyme

The food enzyme is manufactured according to the Food Hygiene Regulation (EC) N° 852/2004 and in (EC) N° 853/2004, with food safety procedures based on hazard analysis and critical control points, and in accordance with current GMP.

3- Purity of the food enzyme

The food enzyme complied with the content of heavy metals (Lead) and with the microbiological criteria (for *Escherichia coli* and *Salmonella*), as laid down in the general specifications for enzymes used in food processing (FAO/WHO, 2006). As for the presence of pesticides and micotoxins the EFSA Panel considered that the information provided on the purity of the food enzyme is sufficient and did not raise safety concerns.

4- Toxicological data

No toxicological tests were required for the application, as laid down in the Reg. (EC) N°234/2011, amended by Reg. (EC) N°562/2012. Furthermore, *Cynara cardunculus* L. appears on the negative list of botanicals for which the EFSA Scientific Committee could not identify substances of possible concern for human health when used in food and food supplements (EFSA, 2012). Additionally, within the daily diet, the equivalent amount of cardoon flower that can be ingested by a consumer of this type of cheese is negligible given the scarce daily consumption of cheese, in particular cheese of the few types which use this type of coagulant at its manufacturing technology.

5- Allergenicity

The results according with the database search, indicated little allergenicity within the set of methods available, for aspartic proteases of *C. cardunculus*, for phytepsin of *C. cardunculus* and for A to H Cardosins from *C. cardunculus*. The EFSA Panel considered that the likelihood to occur allergic reactions to this phytepsin, when used as food enzyme is considered low.

Acknowledgments

Unidade de Tecnologia e Inovação, Instituto Nacional de Investigação Agrária e Veterinária IP (INIAV); Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco (IPCBr); QUALIFICA/oriGIn Portugal; Direção-Geral de Alimentação e Veterinária (DGAV – DSNA); FCT - UIDB/00681/2020 (CERNAS).

Selected Oral Communications

Abstract VIII.1 Design of edible coatings for deep frying fish products under oceans' bioeconomy concept

Author

Sousa, G., – Universidade de Lisboa, Instituto Superior de Agronomia, LEAF – Linking Landscape, Environment, Agriculture and Food Research Centre, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Lisboa, Portugal

Ferreira-Dias, S. – Universidade de Lisboa, Instituto Superior de Agronomia, LEAF – Linking Landscape, Environment, Agriculture and Food Research Centre, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Lisboa, Portugal

Tecelão, C. – MARE – Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre/ ARNET – Aquatic Research Network, Politécnico de Leiria, Peniche, Portugal

Alves, V. – Universidade de Lisboa, Instituto Superior de Agronomia, LEAF – Linking Landscape, Environment, Agriculture and Food Research Centre, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Lisboa, Portugal

Citation

Sousa, G., Ferreira-Dias, S., Tecelão, C., Alves, V. Design of edible coatings for deep frying fish products under oceans' bioeconomy concept.

Oceans are remarkably diverse in underexplored resources like some fish and seaweed species. Therefore, using marine resources under bioeconomy and biorefinery concepts holds potential to produce nutritious food, rich in bioactive compounds.

Mackerel is an undervalued fish species that is usually deep-fried due to the attractive sensory characteristics that it provides 1 . Nevertheless, deep-frying can lead to high calorie content due to oil absorption, may also cause thermal oxidative degradation of the oil, which may produce acrylamide, a probable human carcinogen 2,3.

To address these challenges, edible coatings have been explored as a strategy to reduce the oil uptake, while maintaining the sensory properties, to obtain healthier fried products 4 . Additionally, bioactive compounds like phenolics can be added to the coatings aiming to delay the degradation of polyunsaturated fatty acids, like omega three fatty acids found in fish.

Green seaweeds contain functional compounds and polysaccharides able to form coatings, but they have not been explored yet 5,6 . The extraction of polysaccharides and bioactive compounds from green macroalgae still have gaps and green extraction technologies, like ultrasounds and microwaves, are being optimized as an alternative to hydrothermal extraction treatment that has low yield and high energy consumption.

Therefore, the valorisation of sea resources, namely less explored fish species, by developing a novel value-added product with improved nutritional properties, is within the scope of a circular marine bioeconomy approach with positive impact on human health.

Acknowledgments

This research was funded by the national funding of FCT – Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT), Portugal, to research units LEAF -Linking Landscape, Environment, Agriculture and Food Research Centre (UIDB/ 04129/2020; UIDP/04129/2020), MARE (UIDB/04292/2020;

UIDP/04292/2020). Gabriela Sousa granted with a PhD scholarship from FCT (2022.13225.BD).

References

1. Negara, B. F. S. P., Tirtawijaya, G., Cho, W. H., Harwanto, D., Sohn, J. H., Kim, J. S., & Choi, J. S. (2021). Effects of Frying Processes on the Nutritional and Sensory Characteristics of Different Mackerel Products. *Processes*, 9(9), 1645.
2. Kurek, M., Repajić, M., Marić, M., Ščetar, M., Trojić, P., Levaj, B., & Galić, K. (2021). The influence of edible coatings and natural antioxidants on fresh-cut potato quality, stability and oil uptake after deep fat frying. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 58(8), 3073-3085.
3. Kurek, M., Ščetar, M., & Galić, K. (2017). Edible coatings minimize fat uptake in deep fat fried products: A review. *Food Hydrocolloids*, 71, 225-235.
4. Salehi, F. (2020). Effect of coatings made by new hydrocolloids on the oil uptake during deep-fat frying: A review. *Journal of Food Processing and Preservation*, 44(11), e14879.
5. Moreira, A., Cruz, S., Marques, R., & Cartaxana, P. (2022). The underexplored potential of green macroalgae in aquaculture. *Reviews in Aquaculture*, 14(1), 5-26.
6. Cikoš, A. M., Čož-Rakovac, R., Šubarić, D., Jerković, I., Ačkar, Đ., & Jokić, S. (2020). Macroalgae in the food industry—opportunities and challenges. *Engineering Power: Bulletin of the Croatian Academy of Engineering*, 15(3), 14-19.

Abstract VIII.2 Uncovering the nutritional and biological properties of honeydew honey from *Quercus pyrenaica*

Author

Falcão, S. I. – Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, Bragança, Portugal; Laboratório Associado para a Sustentabilidade e Tecnologia em Regiões de Montanha (SusTEC), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, Bragança, Portugal

Mouffok, K. M. – Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, Bragança, Portugal; Laboratório Associado para a Sustentabilidade e Tecnologia em Regiões de Montanha (SusTEC), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, Bragança, Portugal

Rodríguez-Flores, M. S. – Department of Plant Biology and Soil Sciences, University of Vigo, Campus As Lagoas, Ourense, Spain

Escuredo, O. – Department of Plant Biology and Soil Sciences, University of Vigo, Campus As Lagoas, Ourense, Spain

Seijo, M. C. – Department of Plant Biology and Soil Sciences, University of Vigo, Campus As Lagoas, Ourense, Spain

Vilas-Boas, M. – Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, Bragança, Portugal; Laboratório Associado para a Sustentabilidade e Tecnologia em Regiões de Montanha (SusTEC), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, Bragança, Portugal

Citation

Falcão, S. I., Mouffok, K. M., Rodríguez-Flores, M. S., Escuredo, O., Seijo, M. C., Vilas-Boas, M. Uncovering the nutritional and biological properties of honeydew honey from *Quercus pyrenaica*.

Honeydew honey consumption has been increasing in the national and international markets and valued by consumers and the food industry due to its strong, characteristic flavour and dark colour. The nutrient profile consists of high levels of carbohydrates, minerals, vitamins, and phenolic compounds, which contribute to its antioxidant properties. These honeys are characterized by less reducing sugar and higher oligosaccharides, which results in distinct sensory qualities and a lower glycemic index compared to floral honeys, making it a healthier option for those concerned with blood sugar levels. 1,2

This work aimed to study the nutritional and biological properties of honeydew honey with origin in *Quercus pyrenaica*. For that, samples obtained in September of 2021, from four apiaries located in areas of black oak forest in Montesinho Natural Park, were characterized through melissopalynological and physicochemical analysis, sugars, phenolic compounds and antioxidant properties.

The melissopalynological analysis showed a high pollen diversity, with a total of 52 pollen types, where the most representative types were *Castanea* and *Rubus* pollen. The results for physicochemical parameters were in accordance with the ones demonstrated by honeydew honeys. The sugar content showed that fructose was the most abundant monosaccharide followed by glucose. The presence of erlose and melezitose indicated the presence of honeydew. The characterization of the phenolic profile revealed the presence of 17 compounds, where flavonoids were the most abundant compounds, specially chrysin and 5-methyl-pinobanksin ether, followed by phenolic acids, such as caffeic acid and ellagic acid. Concerning the antioxidant activity, DPPH values ranged between 0.005 mg/mL to 0.011 mg/mL, while the reducing power values varied between 0,32-1,64 mg GAE/g.

In conclusion, this work provides valuable insights for the increasing application of honeydew honey in functional foods, natural medicines, and cosmetics, opening new possibilities for using the potential health benefits of this exceptional honey type.

Acknowledgments

The authors are grateful to the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT, Portugal) for financial support by national funds FCT/MCTES to CIMO (UIDB/00690/2020), for the support through the project ACORNDEW (MTS/SAS/0099/2020) and through the institutional scientific employment program contract with Soraia I. Falcão.

References

- 1 Seijo, M. C., Escuredo, O., & Rodríguez-Flores, M. S. (2019). Physicochemical Properties and Pollen Profile of Oak Honeydew and Evergreen Oak Honeydew Honeys from Spain: A Comparative Study. *Foods*, 8(4), 126. MDPI AG. <http://dx.doi.org/10.3390/foods8040126>.
- 2 Pita-Calvo, C., & Vázquez, M. (2018). Honeydew Honeys: A Review on the Characterization and Authentication of Botanical and Geographical Origins. *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*, 66(11), 2523–2537. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.7b05807>.

Abstract VIII.3 Grape pomace - a renewable natural source of added-value molecules with potential industrial applications

Author

Abreu, T., – CQM – Centro de Química da Madeira, Universidade da Madeira, Campus da Penteadada, Funchal, Portugal

Jasmins, G. – CQM – Centro de Química da Madeira, Universidade da Madeira, Campus da Penteadada, Funchal, Portugal

Bettencourt, C. – CQM – Centro de Química da Madeira, Universidade da Madeira, Campus da Penteadada, Funchal, Portugal

Teixeira, J. – Justino's Madeira Wines, S.A., Parque Industrial Da Cancela, Caniço, Santa Cruz, Portugal

Câmara, J. S. – CQM – Centro de Química da Madeira, Universidade da Madeira, Campus da Penteadada, Funchal, Portugal; Departamento de Química, Faculdade de Ciências Exatas e Engenharia, Universidade da Madeira, Campus da Penteadada, Funchal, Portugal

Perestrelo, R. – CQM – Centro de Química da Madeira, Universidade da Madeira, Campus da Penteadada, Funchal, Portugal

Citation

Abreu, T., Jasmins, G., Bettencourt, C., Teixeira, J., Câmara, J. S., Perestrelo, R. Grape pomace - a renewable natural source of added-value molecules with potential industrial applications.

Agri-food waste is a worldwide concern that continuously creates problems for society, the environment, human health, and the economy. To help reduce and minimize these concerns, it is necessary to implement

transformation strategies that allow the conversion of agricultural waste into a variety of marketable added-value end products including bioactive compounds, biobased chemicals, biofuels, food additives, among others, to functionalize sustainable bio-economy model. In this study, the volatilomic fingerprint of GP obtained from different *Vitis vinifera* L. grapes was established by solid phase microextraction (HS-SPME) combined to gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), to explore the properties of most dominant volatile organic metabolites (VOMs) in a context of its application on marketable products. A total of 52 VOMs belonging to different chemical families were identified. Alcohols, carbonyl compounds, and esters, are the most dominant, representing 38.8, 29.3, and 24.2% of the total volatile profile of the investigated GP, respectively. Esters (e.g., isoamyl acetate, hexyl acetate, ethyl hexanoate) and alcohols (e.g., 3-methyl butan-2-ol, hexan-1-ol) can be used as flavoring agents with potential use in the food industry, and in the cosmetic industry, for fragrances production. In addition, the identified terpenoids (e.g., menthol, ylangene, limonene) exhibit antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anticancer, biological properties, among others, boosting their potential application in the pharmaceutical industry. The obtained results revealed the potential of some VOMs from GP to replace synthetic antioxidants, colorants, and antimicrobials used in the food industry, and in the cosmetic and pharmaceutical industry, meeting the increasing consumer demand for natural alternative compounds.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by FCT-Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia through the CQM Base Fund - UIDB/00674/2020, and Programmatic Fund - UIDP/00674/2020, by Interreg MAC 2014–2020 Cooperacion territorial through AD4MAC project (MAC2/1.1b/350), by Madeira 14–20 Program, project PROEQUIPRAM - Reforço do Investimento em Equipamentos e Infraestruturas Científicas na RAM (M1420-01-0145-FEDER-000008), and by ARDITI - Agência Regional para o Desenvolvimento da Investigação Tecnologia e Inovação, through the projects M1420-01-0145-FEDER-000005 - Centro de Química da Madeira - CQM+ (Madeira 14–20 Program). Teresa Abreu Phd FCT 2022.11323.BDANA.

Posters

Poster VIII.1 Physicochemical characterization of grilled chicken meat in 2 regions of Portugal, Lisbon and Alto Alentejo

Author

Serrano, M. C., – Instituto Nacional de Investigação Agrária e Veterinária, I.P., Av. da República, Quinta do Marquês, Oeiras, Portugal

Gonçalves, H. – Instituto Nacional de Investigação Agrária e Veterinária, I.P., Av. da República, Quinta do Marquês, Oeiras, Portugal

Louro, M. L. – Instituto Superior de Agronomia Universidade de Lisboa, Tapada da Ajuda, Lisboa, Portugal

Mourato, M. – Instituto Superior de Agronomia Universidade de Lisboa, Tapada da Ajuda, Lisboa, Portugal

Roseiro, L. C. – Instituto Nacional de Investigação Agrária e Veterinária, I.P., Av. da República, Quinta do Marquês, Oeiras, Portugal; GeoBioTec, Nova School of Science and Technology, Caparica, Portugal

Citation

Serrano, M. C., Gonçalves, H., Louro, M. L., Mourato, M., Roseiro, L. C. Physicochemical characterization of grilled chicken meat in 2 regions of Portugal, Lisbon and Alto Alentejo.

Chicken meat, the second most consumed meat in Portugal (42.8 kg/inhabitant/year in 2018), has highly digestible proteins, low amounts of

saturated fat, group B vitamins and minerals (1). The grilling process gives the meat unique sensory properties, but can also have an important effect on its nutritional properties and possible toxicity (2). The food grilling process can have advantages and disadvantages. The fact that food cooks in its own juices, without using water or sauces as a vehicle for heat, means that not only nutrients can be better preserved, but also their flavor. Furthermore, as the fat melts during the process, its content tends to decrease significantly (3). However, during the grilling process, substances are formed, some of which have harmful effects on the health of the consumer, namely heterocyclic aromatic amines and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons. The objective of this work was to evaluate the physical-chemical characteristics of grilled chicken meat in 2 regions of Portugal (Lisbon and Alto Alentejo).

A total of 27 grilled skin-on chicken meat samples (19 - Lisbon and 8 - Alto Alentejo) were analyzed for pH, aW moisture, fat, ash and NaCl content.

The grilled meat samples revealed a high variation in moisture content, with the Lisbon region having average values between 47.01%-64.66% and the Alto Alentejo region values of 57.44%-68.49%. Grilled meats in the Lisbon region presented slightly higher humidity values (62.13%) than those presented in the Alto Alentejo region (60.80%). An identical trend was observed in the fat content. The average fat content presented in grilled chicken in the Lisbon region was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher (8.51%) than that found in the Alto Alentejo region (7.85%). On the contrary, the average ash and chloride levels were higher in grilled meats in the Alto Alentejo region (3.07% vs 2.39% and 1.76% vs 0.74%, respectively).

References

1. Pereira PMDCC, Vicente AFDRB (2013) Meat nutritional composition and nutritive role in the human diet. *Meat Science*, 93(3):586–592.

2. Kondjoyan A, Kohler A, Realini CE, Portanguen S, Kowalski R, Clerjon S, Gatellier P, Chevolleau S, Bonny J-M, Debrauwer L (2014) Towards models for the prediction of beef meat quality during cooking. *Meat Sci* 97(3):323–331
3. Białobrzewski, I., Danowska-Oziewicz, M., Karpin´ska-Tymoszczyk M, Nalepa B, Markowski M, Myhan R (2010) Turkey breast roasting—process optimization. *Journal Food Engineering* 96(3):394–400.

Poster VIII.2 Nutraceutical composition of Tunisian bee pollen towards its geographical origin

Author

Sakhaoui, A., – Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, Bragança, Portugal; Laboratório para a Sustentabilidade e Tecnologia em Regiões de Montanha, Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, Bragança, Portugal; Higher Institute of Biotechnology of Béja, University of Jendouba, Béja, Tunisia

Rodríguez-Flores, M. S. – Department of Plant Biology and Soil Sciences, University of Vigo, Campus As Lagoas, Ourense, Spain

Seijo, M. C. – Department of Plant Biology and Soil Sciences, University of Vigo, Campus As Lagoas, Ourense, Spain

Mejri, M. – Higher Institute of Biotechnology of Béja, University of Jendouba, Béja, Tunisia

Vilas-Boas, M. – Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, Bragança, Portugal; Laboratório para a Sustentabilidade e Tecnologia em Regiões de Montanha, Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, Bragança, Portugal

Falcão, S. I. – Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, Bragança, Portugal; Laboratório para a Sustentabilidade e Tecnologia em Regiões de Montanha, Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, Bragança, Portugal

Citation

Sakhaoui, A., Rodríguez-Flores, M. S., Seijo, M. C., Mejri, M., Vilas-Boas, M., Falcão, S. I. Nutraceutical composition of Tunisian bee pollen towards its geographical origin.

Bee pollen (BP) is a valuable apitherapeutic product greatly appreciated by the natural medicine because of its potential medical and nutritional applications.

This study was designed to investigate the biochemical composition and the nutraceutical potential of polyfloral Tunisian bee pollen. For that, seven polyfloral BP samples were collected from different geographical regions in Tunisia representing different ecological gradient and flora composition. BP samples were subjected to different chemical and nutritional analysis.

Our results indicated that BP from different botanical areas differed in their chemical composition and phytochemical content. Twenty-five botanical families were found amongst the samples. The most abundant families and the most dominant pollen was Asteraceae and Brassicaceae. The greatest protein content was detected in samples from the Central and Northwestern regions of Tunisia 0.024 – 0.023%, when compared to those from the Southern region 0.017%. Lipid content was significantly higher in the sub-humid regions, registering 4,43%, when compared to semi-arid region (1,60%). The samples exhibited a predominance of saturated over unsaturated fatty acids, particularly in those collected from the Northern regions. The carbohydrate content across all samples remained consistently high at 99,93-99,87 g/100g DW, indicating a substantial energy around 400,33 to 400,07 kcal/100g DW. The colour differences are significant, indicating a diversity of botanical origins depending on the region of collection. BP from the South showed the highest moisture content 9.53% while the lowest was recorded in the Centre by 6.03%. The ash content was significantly elevated in the North region by 0,00028% while the lowest was recorded in the centre of Tunisia by 0,00019%.

Our study highlights the influence of plant diversity on the composition and nutritional properties of Tunisian BP collected from different regions. Our findings provide valuable insights into the potential health benefits of BP consumption, provide a basis for further research, development of bee pollen-based functional foods and nutritional supplements.

Acknowledgments

The authors are grateful to the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT, Portugal) for financial support through national funds FCT/MCTES (PIDDAC) to CIMO (UIDB/00690/2020 and UIDP/00690/2020) and SusTEC (LA/P/0007/2021). National funding by FCT—Foundation for Science and Technology, through the institutional scientific employment program—contract with Soraia I. Falcão

Asma Sakhraoui stays at the Instituto Politécnico de Bragança were supported by Scholarships from the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research and University of Jendouba, Tunisia.

Poster VIII.3 Microbiology of Portuguese cheeses

Author

Sorathiya, K. – "Universidade" Católica Portuguesa – Faculty of Biotechnology, Porto, Portugal

Guide: Paula Cristina Maia Teixeira

Citation

Sorathiya, K. Microbiology of Portuguese cheeses.

Traditional fermented foods have become increasingly popular due to a combination of cultural significance, health benefits and a growing interest in traditional and natural foods. Milk and dairy products constitute the most important group among functional foods. The composition of microbial communities that are responsible for the unique and broad diversity of flavours, aromas and textures. Portugal has a rich cheese-making tradition, and many of these cheeses are still made on a traditional farm scale. These Portuguese cheeses are produced through the coagulation of mainly raw ovine and caprine milk. The main objective of this study was to characterize the biodiversity of LAB, molds, yeasts and other microorganisms in traditional cheeses.

Total ten 'protected denomination of origin'(PDO) cheese samples collected from local market of Porto and analysed for presence of Salmonella and Listeria monocytogenes, as well as lactic acid bacteria, Escherichia coli, Enterobacteriaceae, coagulase-positive staphylococci, yeasts, and molds, counts.

From ten cheese four cheeses showing presence of *E. coli*, seven cheese shows presence of Enterobacteriaceae. Furthermore, three cheeses showing unsatisfactory count of *S. aureus* and one cheese showing presence of *Listeria monocytogenes*. The results of this study indicate that pathogenic are present in some Portuguese raw milk cheeses, including products having protected names. The presence of these bacteria may be a result of the utilization of contaminated raw milk, arising from the direct excretion of pathogens from the udder; a result of fecal contamination; or a result of contamination by utensils, equipment, or food handlers during processing. Present results showing lactobacilli, thermophilic lactobacilli and total mesophilic aerobes with values in the order of 7–8 log cfu g⁻¹.

Poster VIII.4 Antioxidant activity of edible halophyte plants for application in lipid food matrices

Author

Antunes, M., – MARE Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre/ ARNET – Aquatic Research Network, Politécnico de Leiria, Peniche, Portugal; LEAF Linking Landscape, Environment, Agriculture and Food Research Center, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Instituto Superior de Agronomia, Universidade de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal

Tecelão, C. – MARE Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre/ ARNET – Aquatic Research Network, Politécnico de Leiria, Peniche, Portugal

Alves, V. – LEAF Linking Landscape, Environment, Agriculture and Food Research Center, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Instituto Superior de Agronomia, Universidade de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal

Ferreira-Dias, S. – LEAF Linking Landscape, Environment, Agriculture and Food Research Center, Associate Laboratory TERRA, Instituto Superior de Agronomia, Universidade de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal

Citation

Antunes, M., Tecelão, C., Alves, V., Ferreira-Dias, S. Antioxidant activity of edible halophyte plants for application in lipid food matrices.

Carpobrotus edulis, *Crithmum maritimum*, *Helichrysum italicum* and *Corema album* are edible halophyte plants present in large amounts in Peniche, Portugal (Parracho et al., 2021). Due to their ability to grow in extreme environmental conditions, namely high salinity levels, they have a powerful antioxidant system, producing antioxidant compounds that can withstand and quench toxic reactive oxygen species, and are able to delay the oxidation of lipids (Amor et al., 2007; Jaleel et al., 2009; Ksouri et al., 2008). Envisaging their application to increase the oxidative stability of edible oils, the non-

polar compounds present in these plants were evaluated. Therefore, the total phenolic compounds, and antioxidant activity of hexane extracts of leaves were investigated. *H. italicum* showed the highest content in phenolic compounds, followed by *C. album*, *C. maritimum*, and *C. edulis*, with values of 100.8 ± 7.3 , 54.0 ± 4.7 , 37.2 ± 2.7 and 16.0 ± 1.4 mg GAE/g, respectively. These values are higher than those obtained by Karker et al. (2016) for the halophyte plant *Reaumuria vermiculata* (31.74 ± 4.17 mg GAE/g). Rodrigues et al. (2014) also analysed the phenolic content of hexane extracts from other five halophyte plants obtaining values between 4.5 ± 0.3 and 39 ± 0.8 mg GAE/g. In what concerns antioxidant activity, the results obtained by DPPH method were 0.25 ± 0.05 , 0.16 ± 0.01 , 0.11 ± 0.01 and 0.06 ± 0.01 mmol TE/g, for *H. italicum*, *C. album*, *C. maritimum*, and *C. edulis* extracts, respectively. Similar results were observed by FRAP method. These preliminary results show that the plants studied, especially *H. italicum* and *C. album*, may have lipid soluble bioactive compound with strong antioxidant potential, capable to increase the oxidative stability of edible oils.

Acknowledgments

This research was funded by the national funding of FCT- Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT), Portugal, to the research units LEAF— Linking Landscape, Environment, Agriculture and Food Research Centre (UIDB/ 04129/2020; UIDP/04129/2020), MARE (UIDB/04292/2020; UIDP/04292/2020). Madalena Antunes is granted with a PhD scholarship from FCT (2022.11509.BD)

References

Amor, N. Ben, Jiménez, A., Megdiche, W., Lundqvist, M., Sevilla, F., & Abdelly, C. (2007). Kinetics of the anti-oxidant response to salinity in the halophyte *Cakile maritima*. *Journal of Integrative Plant Biology*, 49(7), 982–992. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1672-9072.2007.00491.x>

Jaleel, C. A., Riadh, K., Gopi, R., Manivannan, P., Inès, J., Al-Juburi, H. J., Chang-Xing, Z., Hong-Bo, S., & Panneerselvam, R. (2009). Antioxidant defense responses: Physiological plasticity in higher plants under abiotic constraints. *In Acta Physiologiae Plantarum* (Vol. 31, Issue 3, pp. 427–436). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11738-009-0275-6>

Karker, M., Falleh, H., Msaada, K., Smaoui, A., Abdelly, C., Legault, J., & Ksouri, R. (2016). Antioxidant, Antiinflammatory and anticancer activities of the medicinal halophyte *Reaumuria vermiculata*. *EXCLI Journal*, 15, 297–307. <https://doi.org/10.17179/excli2016-187>

Ksouri, R., Megdiche, W., Falleh, H., Trabelsi, N., Boulaaba, M., Smaoui, A., & Abdelly, C. (2008). Influence of biological, environmental and technical factors on phenolic content and antioxidant activities of Tunisian halophytes. *Comptes Rendus - Biologies*, 331(11), 865–873. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crv.2008.07.024>

Parracho, T., Vaz, D. C., Veríssimo, P., & Ribeiro, V. (2021). Sand-dune plants from the Atlantic coast of the Iberian Peninsula: features & applications. In J. Galvão, P. Brito, F. Neves, F. Craveiro, H. Almeida, J. Vasco, L. Neves, R. Gomes, S. Mourato, & V. Ribeiro (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Water Energy Food and Sustainability (ICoWEFS 2021)* (pp. 127–136). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-75315-3_15

Rodrigues, M. J., Gangadhar, K. N., Vizetto-Duarte, C., Wubshet, S. G., Nyberg, N. T., Barreira, L., Varela, J., & Custódio, L. (2014). Maritime halophyte species from southern Portugal as sources of bioactive molecules. *Marine Drugs*, 12(4), 2228–2244. <https://doi.org/10.3390/md12042228>

Poster VIII.5 Chemical composition and nutritional profile of *Atriplex halimus* leaves

Author

Zaouadi, N. – Department of Biological Sciences, Faculty of Natural and Life Sciences and Earth Sciences, Djilali Bounaama University, Khemis Miliana, Algeria
Bensehaila, S. – Department of Biological Sciences, Faculty of Natural and Life Sciences and Earth Sciences, Djilali Bounaama University, Khemis Miliana, Algeria
Lafri, I. – Agro-Pastoral Research Center, Djelfa, Algeria
Mostefa Sari, F. – Department of Biological Sciences, Faculty of Natural and Life Sciences and Earth Sciences, Djilali Bounaama University, Khemis Miliana, Algeria
Mataoui, H. – Department of Biological Sciences, Faculty of Natural and Life Sciences and Earth Sciences, Djilali Bounaama University, Khemis Miliana, Algeria

Citation

Zaouadi, N., Bensehaila, S., Lafri, I., Mostefa Sari, F., Mataoui, H. Chemical Composition and nutritional profile of *Atriplex halimus* leaves.

Plants, constitute an invaluable source of bioactive compounds. The primary aim of this study is to first analyze the chemical composition of the leaves of halophytic plant “*Atriplex halimus*” originating from the Beni Abas region in Algeria and then quantify the amino acids and identify quantify fatty acids using analysis techniques such as UPLC and GC/MS. The leaves of *A. halimus* exhibit a dry matter content of $82.86 \pm 2.77\%$ and a mineral matter content of 25.5%. This mineral accumulation is likely attributed to the halophilic nature of the plant and the pedoclimatic conditions. Regarding proteins, they constitute $14.52 \pm 0.44\%$ of the dry matter, while the fat content is $4.63 \pm 0.08\%$. The amount of mineral elements absorbed by *A. halimus* largely depends on the

soil composition. The plant accumulates 7.23 ± 0.33 g/100g of sodium (Na) and 3.27 ± 0.25 g/100g of calcium (Ca), while the assimilation of phosphorus (P) is lower, likely due to the alkaline pH of the soil (0.15 ± 0.02 g/100g). The aqueous extract of *A. halimus* leaves revealed a total phenol content of 15.69 ± 0.63 mg GAE/g, 7.15 ± 0.45 mg EC/g of flavonoids, and 8.20 ± 0.38 mg EC/g of tannins. The antioxidant activity, measured using the DPPH assay, reached $66.48 \pm 0.61\%$, which is likely attributable to the abundance of flavonols, the predominant class in the Atriplex. The results have shown that the leaves of *Atriplex halimus* contain various amino acids at varying concentrations, with proline, leucine, phenylalanine, threonine, and valine being the most abundant. Proline is the most predominant amino acid in *Atriplex halimus*. The fatty acid profile of *A. halimus* reveals a predominance of palmitic acid (30.82%), followed by lignoceric acid (14.61%) and linolenic acid (12.72%), while stearic acid is present in a lower quantity, at only 1.96%.

References

- Ould Kaddour, A. S., Bouzouina, M., & Lotmani, B. (2019). Contenu phénolique et évaluation in vitro des effets antioxydants des parties aériennes de trois écotypes algériens d'*Atriplex halimus* L. *Plant Archives*, 19(1), 1583-1592.
- Hlfaoui, Y., Kadiri, A., & Ighilhariz, Z. (2018). Induction de la callogénèse d'*Atriplex halimus* (Amaranthaceae) à partir de différents types d'explants. *Journal of Fundamental and Applied Sciences*, 10(1), 20-34.

Poster VIII.6 Relation between eating habits, lipid profile and body mass index

Author

Cabral, E. – Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco – Escola Superior de Saúde Dr. Lopes Dias, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Coelho, P. – Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco – Escola Superior de Saúde Dr. Lopes Dias | Sport, Health & Exercise Unit (SHERU) | Qualidade de Vida no Mundo Rural (Qrural), PhD, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Rodrigues, F. – Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco – Escola Superior de Saúde Dr. Lopes Dias | Qualidade de vida no Mundo Rural (Qrural) | Sport, Health & Exercise Unit (SHERU), PhD, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Citation

Cabral, E., Coelho, P., Rodrigues, F. Relation between eating habits, lipid profile and body mass index.

Nowadays, obesity is considered a global pandemic since in 2014 it reached 1,9 billion people. This problem has been more present in younger populations, being mainly influenced by their eating habits and sedentary lifestyles. This study aims to determine the prevalence of overweight and obesity in children and adolescents, relating it to their risk factors.

327 students aged between 9 and 19 years old (133 were male and 194 were female) participated in this study. They completed a questionnaire and blood pressure, lipid profile, eating habits, and physical activity were evaluated.

Most of the students had a normal body mass index (74,9%). 18% of students were overweight (mostly female) and 4,9% were obese. In the group of overweight and obese students, 43,1% and 50%, respectively, had reduced HDL values and a higher level of triglycerides was observed in 60,3% of overweight students and 56,2% of obese students. 62,7% of overweight students used to include large amounts of red meat in their diet. Vegans/vegetarian students and the majority of students who practiced more weekly hours of physical exercise had a normal body index.

There is a relevant prevalence of overweight and obese individuals in this population. It is confirmed that the role of some risk factors such as physical inactivity and eating habits is really important in the development of this problem.

References

Thomas-Eapen N. (2021). Childhood Obesity. *Primary care*, 48(3), 505–515. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pop.2021.04.002>

Daneshzad, E., Askari, M., Moradi, M., Ghorabi, S., Rouzitalab, T., Heshmati, J., & Azadbakht, L. (2021). Red meat, overweight and obesity: A systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies. *Clinical nutrition ESPEN*, 45, 66–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clnesp.2021.07.028>

Celik, O., & Yildiz, B. O. (2021). Obesity and physical exercise. *Minerva endocrinology*, 46(2), 131–144. <https://doi.org/10.23736/S2724-6507.20.03361-1>

Poster VIII.7 A preliminary study to minimize the enzymatic browning in minimally processed potatoes

Author

Ferreira, J. – MARE – Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre / ARNET – Aquatic Research Network, ESTM - School of Tourism and Maritime Technology, Polytechnic University of Leiria, Peniche, Portugal

Augusto, A. – MARE – Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre / ARNET – Aquatic Research Network, ESTM - School of Tourism and Maritime Technology, Polytechnic University of Leiria, Peniche, Portugal

Silva, S. – MARE – Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre / ARNET – Aquatic Research Network, ESTM - School of Tourism and Maritime Technology, Polytechnic University of Leiria, Peniche, Portugal

[Pinheiro, J.](#) – MARE – Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre / ARNET – Aquatic Research Network, ESTM - School of Tourism and Maritime Technology, Polytechnic University of Leiria, Peniche, Portugal

Citation

Ferreira, J., Augusto, A., Silva, S., Pinheiro, J. A preliminary study to minimize the enzymatic browning in minimally processed potatoes.

Due to the fast lifestyle of contemporary society, consumers are dedicating less time to preparing their meals, opting for ready-to-eat foods. Minimally processed (MP) products respond to this market requirement, providing consumers with fresh food with minimal processing, ready to eat. Like most MP products, potatoes (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) also present a short shelf life mainly due to color changes. Chemical and synthetic additives, that are not

compatible with the current “clean label” trend, are used in the Food Industry to increase the shelf-life of MP potatoes.

The present work aimed to study the impact of two macroalgae extracts, *Fucus vesiculosus* and *Codium tomentosum* [1], as sources of antioxidant compounds capable of inhibiting the colour changes on peeled and cut potatoes (Agria variety) during 10 days at refrigerated storage (5 ± 1 °C). For that, the macroalgae at a ratio of 2g:50mL (m:v) was previously treated with ultrasounds to obtain a rich antioxidant extract. Physical-chemical properties, such as color (CIE Lab color parameters) [2], and enzymatic activity as peroxidase (POD) and polyphenol oxidase (PPO) [1, 3, 4, 5] were evaluated in potato samples treated with macroalgae extracts and compared with control samples (water and synthetic additive).

Overall, both macroalgae extracts demonstrated a beneficial effect on retarding the color change of potatoes, compared to occur in control samples. The enzymatic activity of PPO and POD in samples coated with *F. vesiculosus* extract showed a lower value, around 50% compared to the control sample on the last day of storage ($P < 0.05$). The efficacy of macroalgae application, as a natural source to prevent the enzymatic browning allowed the prevention of the undesirable appearance of MP potatoes. Also, more studies will be performed to validate the efficacy of macroalgae coating in promoting the shelf-life of MP potatoes.

Acknowledgments

This work was funded by national funds through FCT—Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I.P., under the project MARE (UIDB/04292/2020, <https://doi.org/10.54499/UIDB/04292/2020> and UIDP/04292/2020, <https://doi.org/10.54499/UIDP/04292/2020>) and the project LA/P/0069/2020 granted to the Associate Laboratory ARNET (<https://doi.org/10.54499/LA/P/0069/2020>).

References

- [1] Augusto, A., Simões, T., Pedrosa, R., & Silva, S. F. J. (2016). Evaluation of seaweed extracts functionality as postharvest treatment for minimally processed Fuji apples. *Innovative Food Science and Emerging Technologies*, 33, 589– 595. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifset.2015.10.004>.
- [2] Pinheiro, J., Ganhão, R. Gonçalves, E.M. Silva, C.L.M. (2019). Assessment of thermosonication as postharvest treatment applied on whole tomato fruits: optimization and validation. *Foods*, 8(12), 649. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods8120649>.
- [3] Rodrigues, D., Sousa, S., Silva, A., Amorim, M., Pereira, L., Rocha-Santos, T. A. P., Gomes, A. M. P., Duarte, A. C., & Freitas, A. C. (2015). Impact of enzyme- and ultrasound-assisted extraction methods on biological properties of red, brown, and green seaweeds from the Central West Coast of Portugal. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 63(12), 3177–3188. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf504220e>.
- [4] Sulaiman, A., Soo, M. J., Farid, M., & Silva, F. V. M. (2015). Thermosonication for polyphenoloxidase inactivation in fruits: Modeling the ultrasound and thermal kinetics in pear, apple and strawberry purees at different temperatures. *Journal of Food Engineering*, 165, 133–140. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2015.06.020>. [5] Zhang, Z., Yao, Y., Shi, Q., Zhao, J., Fu, H., & Wang, Y. (2020). Effects of radio-frequency-assisted blanching on the polyphenol oxidase, microstructure, physical characteristics, and starch content of potato. *Lwt*, 125(August 2019), 109357. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2020.109357>.

Poster VIII.8 Assessment of decoction treatment on *Fucus vesiculosus* and *Ulva* sp. macroalgae

Author

Caetano, M. – MARE – Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre / ARNET – Aquatic Research Network, ESTM - School of Tourism and Maritime Technology, Polytechnic University of Leiria, Peniche, Portugal

Ganhão, R. – MARE – Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre / ARNET – Aquatic Research Network, ESTM - School of Tourism and Maritime Technology, Polytechnic University of Leiria, Peniche, Portugal

[Pinheiro, J.](#) – MARE – Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre / ARNET – Aquatic Research Network, ESTM - School of Tourism and Maritime Technology, Polytechnic University of Leiria, Peniche, Portugal

Citation

Caetano, M., Ganhão, R., Pinheiro, J. Assessment of decoction treatment on *Fucus vesiculosus* and *Ulva* sp. macroalgae.

Nowadays, consumers are more concerned and careful about food, they are looking for convenience, quality, and affordable costs. Regarding Food Trends, consumers are willing to spend more if innovative food treatments and sustainability are evolving. In this area, the macroalgae has been engaged in a prominent place.

The main goal of this study was to evaluate the impact of decoction treatment in green and brown macroalgae, *Ulva* sp. and *Fucus vesiculosus*, respectively. Decoction was performed at two ratios of macroalgae and

water (1:16 and 1:50, g/mL), during 15 and 30 min of treatment. After, the mixture was filtrated, and the liquid was kept at refrigerated storage until analysis. Color (CIE Lab system), soluble solids content (SSC), pH-value, total phenolic content (TPC) [1] and antioxidant capacity expressed by scavenging activity of DPPH [2] and FRAP [3] were performed in macroalgae extracts after decoction and without treatment (CTR_15min and CTR_30min).

No significant difference ($P > 0.05$, Tukey test), between decoction and untreated macroalgae samples, in physical properties such as pH, soluble solids content (SSC) and color, was achieved. By observation of total phenolic content from both macroalgae, an increase was detected when decoction treatment was prolonged to 30 min. Also, this tendency was observed in the antioxidant capacity of both macroalgae extracts (DPPH and FRAP). Thus, treatments such as decoction in macroalgae will provide healthier, and enriched macroalgae extracts that should be used for the prevention of food changes. In summary, the decoction treatment should be a promising technology to be applied in macroalgae to obtain a nutritive and rich food, as naturally as possible.

Acknowledgments

This work was funded by national funds through FCT—Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, I.P., under the project MARE (UIDB/04292/2020, <https://doi.org/10.54499/UIDB/04292/2020> and UIDP/04292/2020, <https://doi.org/10.54499/UIDP/04292/2020>) and the project LA/P/0069/2020 granted to the Associate Laboratory ARNET (<https://doi.org/10.54499/LA/P/0069/2020>).

References

- [1] Singleton, V.L.; Rossi, J.A. Colorimetry of Total Phenolics with Phosphomolybdic-Phosphotungstic Acid Reagents. *Am. J. Enol. Vitic.* 1965, 16, 144–158.
- [2] Brand-Williams, W., Cuvelier, M. E., & Berset, C. (1995). Use of a Free Radical Method to Evaluate Antioxidant Activity (Vol. 28).
- [3] Ganhão, R.; Pinheiro, J.; Tino, C.; Faria, H.; Gil, M.M. (2019). Characterization of Nutritional, Physicochemical, and Phytochemical Composition and Antioxidant Capacity of Three Strawberry "Fragaria × ananassa Duch." Cultivars ("Primoris", "Endurance", and "Portola") from Western Region of Portugal. *Foods*, 8, 682.

Poster VIII.9 A new life in citrus lemon peels: Potential of different extracts as antifungal agents

Author

Rolo, J., – CICS-UBI – Centro de Investigação em Ciências da Saúde, Universidade da Beira Interior, Covilhã, Portugal; FCS – Faculdade das Ciências da Saúde, Universidade da Beira Interior, Covilhã, Portugal

Gama, A. R. – CICS-UBI – Centro de Investigação em Ciências da Saúde, Universidade da Beira Interior, Covilhã, Portugal; FCS – Faculdade das Ciências da Saúde, Universidade da Beira Interior, Covilhã, Portugal

Domingues, J. – CBPBI - Centro de Biotecnologia de Plantas da Beira Interior, Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Delgado, F. –CBPBI - Centro de Biotecnologia de Plantas da Beira Interior, Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal; Escola Superior Agrária do Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Portugal;

CERNAS: Centro de Recursos Naturais, Ambiente e Sociedade, Grupo de Investigação de Ciências Agrícolas, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Gonçalves, J. C. – CBPBI - Centro de Biotecnologia de Plantas da Beira Interior, Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal; Escola Superior Agrária do Instituto Politécnico de Castelo Branco, Portugal;

CERNAS: Centro de Recursos Naturais, Ambiente e Sociedade, Grupo de Investigação de Ciências Agrícolas, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Palmeira-de-Oliveira, R. – CICS-UBI – Centro de Investigação em Ciências da Saúde, Universidade da Beira Interior, Covilhã, Portugal; FCS – Faculdade das Ciências da Saúde, Universidade da Beira Interior, Covilhã, Portugal; Labfit-HPRD: Health Products Research and Development Lda, Covilhã, Portugal

Martinez-de-Oliveira, J. – CICS-UBI – Centro de Investigação em Ciências da Saúde, Universidade da Beira Interior, Covilhã, Portugal

Palmeira-de-Oliveira, A. – CICS-UBI – Centro de Investigação em Ciências da Saúde, Universidade da Beira Interior, Covilhã, Portugal; FCS – Faculdade das Ciências da Saúde, Universidade da Beira Interior, Covilhã, Portugal; Labfit-HPRD: Health Products Research and Development Lda, Covilhã, Portugal

Citation

Rolo, J., Gama, A. R., Domingues, J., Delgado, F., Gonçalves, J. C., Palmeira-de-Oliveira, R., Martinez-de-Oliveira, J., Palmeira-de-Oliveira, A. A new life in citrus lemon peels: Potential of different extracts as antifungal agents.

The peels of Citrus fruits, extensively produced in Southern Europe, are commonly discarded, despite being rich in bioactive compounds that could be upcycled into new ingredients for the food, pharmaceutical or cosmetic industries. A potential application of Citrus peels in these industries would be as a preservative or antimicrobial agent. In this regard, the antifungal activity is particularly relevant, because there is a high demand for new antifungals, due to the rise in resistance to azoles, the antimycotics mostly prescribed and available on the market as well as the increased frequency in environmental/food or human samples of fungal species that are intrinsically resistant to these compounds. Therefore, in this study we aim to characterize the antifungal activity of different extracts of Citrus lemon, to unravel its potential as new antifungal ingredients.

To achieve our aims, different extracts obtained from Citrus lemon were included in the study: essential oils obtained from the peel (EO) and three different extracts prepared with traditionally farmed lemons - lemon juice (LJ), lemon peel (LP) and whole-lemon (WL). The juice of the lemons was extracted manually with the aid of a juice machine; and the remaining material was freeze-dried and subsequently lyophilized. The extracts were used to assess the minimum inhibitory concentration against *Candida albicans* ATCC 10231 with the microdilution broth assay, and in checkerboard assays with 0.75-25 mg/mL sodium bicarbonate. We found that the most active lemon extract was the EO, that was able to inhibit *C. albicans* growth at 1% (V/V). The remaining extracts were not active against *C. albicans*, but in combination with sodium bicarbonate we found an additive effect in the inhibition of *C. albicans* growth. We conclude that there is potential in lemon extracts as active ingredients, either alone or when combined with other compounds as new antifungal ingredients.

Acknowledgments

This work was developed within the scope of the CICS-UBI projects UIDB/00709/2020 and UIDP/00709/2020, financed by national funds through the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology/MCTES.

Poster VIII.10 Occurrence of 2- and 3-MCPD esters and glycidyl esters in food supplements based on fish and microalgae oils

Author

Oliveira, A. P. E., – Faculdade de Engenharia de Alimentos - Universidade Estadual de Campinas, Campinas - SP, Brasil

Gomes, F. M. L. – Centro de Ciência e Qualidade de Alimentos - Instituto de Tecnologia de Alimentos, Campinas - SP, Brasil

Milani, R. F. – Centro de Ciência e Qualidade de Alimentos - Instituto de Tecnologia de Alimentos, Campinas - SP, Brasil

Vicente, E. – Centro de Ciência e Qualidade de Alimentos - Instituto de Tecnologia de Alimentos, Campinas - SP, Brasil

Tfouni, S. A. – Centro de Ciência e Qualidade de Alimentos - Instituto de Tecnologia de Alimentos, Campinas - SP, Brasil

Bragotto, A. P. A. – Faculdade de Engenharia de Alimentos - Universidade Estadual de Campinas, Campinas - SP, Brasil

Citation

Oliveira, A. P. F., Gomes, F. M. L., Milani, R. F., Vicente, E., Tfouni, S. A., Bragotto, A. P. A. Occurrence of 2- and 3-MCPD esters and glycidyl esters in food supplements based on fish and microalgae oils.

Fish oil supplies the omega food market; however, this animal source depends on aquatic ecosystems gradually depleted. Thus, microalgae are a sustainable alternative to access health beneficial compounds. Nonetheless, since these products can be deodorized, monochloropropanediol esters (MCPDE) and glycidyl esters (GE) must be monitored. Once levels of MCPDE

and GE were reported recently in fish derivatives, the present study aims to evaluate MCPDE and GE in supplements based on fish and microalgae oils. A total of 20 samples commercially available online in the Brazilian market, were analyzed by gas chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (GC-MS) using the official analytical method AOCS Cd 29a-13. Fatty acid composition was performed to evaluate the DHA (docosahexaenoic acid) and EPA (eicosapentaenoic acid) levels declared on label. The values for limit of quantitation (LOQ) were 30 μ g/kg for 3-MCPDE; 80 μ g/kg for 2-MCPD; 80 μ g/kg for GE. Among all samples, 13 contained contaminants levels below LOQ, specifically: 1/20 (3-MCPDE); 10/20 (2-MCPD) and 2/20 (GE). The levels of contaminants for fish oil ranged from <LOQ-780 μ g/kg for 3-MCPDE; <LOQ 160 μ g/kg for 2-MCPD; and 80-292 μ g/kg for GE. For microalgae oils, from 160-1180 μ g/kg for 3-MCPDE; <LOQ-290 μ g/kg for 2-MCPD; and <LOQ-240 μ g/kg for GE. The samples analyzed had DHA and EPA ranging from 25-44g/100g and 0.3-12g/100g (microalgae); and from 3-26g/100g and 5-42g/100g (fish), respectively. Fish oil food supplements were source of EPA, while microalgae oil source of DHA. According to the EU Regulatory Commission 2020/1322, for fish and marine foodstuffs, for end consumers, the levels of 3-MCPDE should be <2500 μ g/kg and GE <1000 μ g/kg. For young children/infant end consumers, the levels of 3-MCPDE should be <750 μ g/kg and GE <500 μ g/kg. None samples presented contaminants above the European regulatory limits. However, supplements based on fish and microalgae oils may contribute to human exposure to the evaluated contaminants and their long-term consumption should be considered in risk assessment studies.

Acknowledgments

Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior (CAPES), Brazil, Financial code (001); Conselho Nacional de Desenvolvimento Científico e Tecnológico (CNPq), Brazil, Grant Number 407131/2021-3.

Reference

Firestone, D. (Ed.). (2014). Official methods and recommended practices of the American Oil Chemists Society. Commission Regulation (EU) (2023). 2023/915 of 25 April 2023 on maximum levels for certain contaminants in food and repealing Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006. <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/915/oj>.

Poster VIII.11 Monitoring the occurrence and levels of patulin in commercial apple juices by μ -QuEChERS/LC-ESI/MS approach

Author

Câmara, J. S., – CQM—Centro de Química da Madeira, Universidade da Madeira, Campus da Penteada, Funchal, Portugal; Departamento de Química, Faculdade de Ciências Exatas e Engenharia, Universidade da Madeira, Campus da Penteada, Funchal, Portugal

Fernandes, P. – Laboratório Regional de Veterinária e Segurança Alimentar, Caminho das Quebradas de Baixo, Funchal, Portugal

Barros, N. – Laboratório Regional de Veterinária e Segurança Alimentar, Caminho das Quebradas de Baixo, Funchal, Portugal

Perestrelo, R. – CQM—Centro de Química da Madeira, Universidade da Madeira, Campus da Penteada, Funchal, Portugal

Citation

Câmara, J. S., Fernandes, P., Barros, N., Perestrelo, R. Monitoring the occurrence and levels of patulin in commercial apple juices by μ -QuEChERS/LC-ESI/MS approach.

Patulin (PAT) is a mycotoxin produced in fruits, especially in apples, by diverse fungal species that can be transferred into industrial apple juice during processing. An accurate, effective, and selective method has been validated for the quantification of PAT in different commercial apple juices by combining a modified μ -QuEChERS procedure with high-pressure liquid chromatography (LC) equipped with a triple quadrupole mass spectrometer (QQMS). This sample extraction procedure reduced interference from the

sugar-rich matrix, and the separation was performed using the C18 Atlantis T3 column within 10 min. PAT was found by MS with electrospray negative ionization (ESI⁻) in the mode of multiple reaction monitoring (MRM). The correlation coefficient ($R^2 = 0.999$) satisfied the prerequisite of linearity for PAT in the concentration range of 2–50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$. The limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) of PAT were 0.32 and 1.15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, respectively, which were compliant with the maximum levels settled in Commission Regulation (EC) No. 1881/2006. The recoveries were within the 92–103% range, at three fortified levels of 2, 20, and 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$, with relative standard deviations lower than 7%. Based on analytical validation, it was confirmed that the $\mu\text{-QuEChERS/HPLC-MS/MS}$ method is an enhanced, reliable, and quick approach for the determination of PAT in apple juice. The current approach proposes reduced sample preparation and analysis time. In addition, it is economical, environmentally friendly, and simpler to implement in comparison to traditional approaches.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by FCT-Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia through the CQM Base Fund - UIDB/00674/2020, and Programmatic Fund - UIDP/00674/2020, by Interreg MAC 2014–2020 Cooperacion territorial through AD4MAC project (MAC2/1.1b/350), by Madeira 14–20 Program, project PROEQUIPRAM - Reforço do Investimento em Equipamentos e Infraestruturas Científicas na RAM (M1420-01-0145-FEDER-000008), and by ARDITI - Agência Regional para o Desenvolvimento da Investigação Tecnologia e Inovação, through the projects M1420-01-0145-FEDER-000005 - Centro de Química da Madeira - CQM+ (Madeira 14–20 Program).

Poster VIII.12 Assessment of the quality of milk from small ruminants used in the production of cheeses with PDO (chemical composition and somatic cells)

Author

Beato, H., – Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar (CATAA), Castelo Branco, Portugal

Resende, M. – Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar (CATAA), Castelo Branco, Portugal

Cristóvão, M. – Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar (CATAA), Castelo Branco, Portugal

Caseiro, C. – Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar (CATAA), Castelo Branco, Portugal

Veloso, A. – School of Agriculture- Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Riscado, A. – Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar (CATAA), Castelo Branco, Portugal

Brandão, I. – Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar (CATAA), Castelo Branco, Portugal; Centre for Functional Ecology (CFE)- University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Espírito Santo, C. – Centro de Apoio Tecnológico Agro-Alimentar (CATAA), Castelo Branco, Portugal; Centre for Functional Ecology (CFE)- University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Rodrigues, A. M. – School of Agriculture- Polytechnic Institute of Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal; CERNAS-IPCB, Castelo Branco, Castelo Branco, Portugal

Citation

Beato, H., Resende, M., Cristóvão, M., Caseiro, C., Veloso, A., Riscado, A., Brandão, I., Espírito Santo, C., Rodrigues, A. M. Assessment of the quality of milk from small ruminants used in the production of cheeses with PDO (chemical composition and somatic cells).

Milk is one of the most nutritious and essential foods in mammalian diet. Milk quality standards have been increasing over time, as producers must meet the demands of a growing consumer awareness of food safety and quality. Mastitis is a mammary gland bacterial infection causing physical, chemical and bacteriological changes in milk. Somatic cell count (SCC) is an indicator of intramammary infection (IMI). SCC are protective for the animal's body and fight infections. A high SCC count has a negative influence on milk quality. Sheep milk had higher protein, fat and total solids than goat milk, as well as potential cheese yield. In turn, goat milk had higher SCC values. Milk used for making Serra da Estrela Cheese PDO showed higher values of protein, fat, total solids, non-fat solids and potential cheese yield than milk used for making Beira Baixa Yellow cheese PDO. The latter showed higher values for SCC, lymphocyte, neutrophil and macrophage counts. Milk used for producing Serra da Estrela Cheese PDO had lower values for the same type of SCC, indicating a greater udder health status. In all cases, an increase in SCC was observed during spring, coinciding with a more pronounced milk shortage and a decrease in the available amount of food throughout the season.

Acknowledgments

Projeto - Programa de Valorização da Fileira do Queijo da Região Centro; código do projeto - CENTRO 04-3928-FEDER-000014

Poster VIII.13 Coffee industry by-products as a source of bioactive compounds

Author

Esperanço, P., – Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Coimbra Agriculture School, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal; Research Centre for Natural Resources Environment and Society (CERNAS), Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal
Areias, B. – Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Coimbra Agriculture School, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal
Ferreira, D. – Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Coimbra Agriculture School, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal
Veloso A.C.A. – Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Coimbra Institute of Engineering, Rua Pedro Nunes - Quinta da Nora, Coimbra, Portugal; CEB – Centre of Biological Engineering, University of Minho, Campus de Gualtar, Braga, Portugal; LABBELS – Associate Laboratory, Braga/Guimarães, Portugal
Henriques, M. – Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Coimbra Agriculture School, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal; Research Centre for Natural Resources Environment and Society (CERNAS), Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal
Rodrigues, C. – Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Coimbra Agriculture School, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal; Research Centre for Natural Resources Environment and Society (CERNAS), Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal
Campos, L. – Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Coimbra Agriculture School, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal; Research Centre for Natural Resources Environment and Society (CERNAS), Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, Bencanta, Coimbra, Portugal

Citation

Esperanço, P., Areias, B., Ferreira, D., Veloso A.C.A., Henriques, M., Rodrigues, C., Campos, L. Coffee industry by-products as a source of bioactive compounds.

As coffee is one of the most popular drinks, its production and preparation produces a considerable amount of waste. Spent coffee grounds and coffee silverskin are two of the main by-products generated in this industry and are usually discarded or used in low-value products. However, these matrices have been reported as rich in bioactive compounds that can be used in a wide range of processes. This study aimed to evaluate the bioactive composition of machine coffee grounds (MCG), capsule coffee grounds (CCG) and coffee silverskin (CSS) extracts. The extracts were produced by conventional and sonication-assisted extraction methods with ethanol (EtOH) 25%, 50% and 75%. The bioactive composition was assessed through the quantification of total phenolic compounds (TPC), total flavonoids (TF) and tannins (TAN) and the antioxidant activity (AA). MCG and CCG extracts showed similar results for all parameters evaluated regardless of the extraction methodology, having the highest values with EtOH 25% for TPC (>0.33 mg GAE/mg extract) and TF (>0.14 mg CATE/mg extract), and with EtOH 50% for AA ($IC_{50} <0.034$ mg/mL). CCS resulted in better extraction yields (between 12.5 and 20.0%) and extracts with higher TAN content (between 3.15 and 5.36%, m/m), for both extraction methods. This study highlights that the by-products studied (spent coffee grounds and coffee silverskin) still possess valuable compounds that can be used in other industries such as food, cosmetics or pharmaceutical. The two types of spent coffee grounds had similar bioactive composition with potential to be used together as new resources. Coffee silverskin present lower bioactive activity but can still be useful in sustainable applications. Furthermore, this research shows the viability of the sonication-assisted method as a greener alternative to the conventional method, and reveals the importance of the solvent in enhancing the bioactive compound content of the extracts. These findings emphasize the promising role of coffee by-products in promoting sustainability and innovative product development across multiple sectors.

Acknowledgments

This work was financed by national funds by FCT- Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia, I.P., through the CERNAS project (UIDB/00681/2020) and MobFood (Lisboa-01-0247-FEDER-024524).

References

Atanassova, M.; Christova-bagdassarian, V. Determination of tannins content by titrimetric method for comparison of different plant species, *J. Univ. Chem. Technol. Metall.*, 2009, 44, 413–415.

Beltrán-Medina, E.A.; Guatemala-Morales, G.M.; Padilla-Camberos, E.; Corona-González, R.I.; Mondragón-Cortez, P.M.; Arriola-Guevara, E. Evaluation of the use of a coffee industry by-product in a cereal-based extruded food product, *Foods*, 2020, 9, 1–15, doi: 10.3390/foods9081008.

Kim, D.; Jeong, S.W.; Lee, C.Y. Antioxidant capacity of phenolic phytochemicals from various cultivars of plums, *Food Chem.*, 2003, 81, 321–326, doi: 10.1016/S0308-8146(02)00423-5.

Mensor, L.L.; Menezes, F.S.; Leitão, G.G.; Reis, A.S.; dos Santos, T.C.; Coube, C.S.; Leitão, S.G. Screening of Brazilian plant extracts for antioxidant activity by the use of DPPH free radical method, *Phyther. Res.*, 2001, 15, 127– 130, doi: 10.1002/ptr.687.

Rodríguez-Rojo, S.; Visentin, A.; Maestri, D.; Cocero, M.J. Assisted extraction of rosemary antioxidants with green solvents, *J. Food Eng.*, 2012, 109, 98–103, doi: 10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2011.09.029.

Staško, A.; Brezová, V.; Biskupic, S.; Mišík, V. The potential pitfalls of using 1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl to characterize antioxidants in mixed water solvents, *Free Radic. Res.*, 2007, 41, 379–390, doi: 10.1080/10715760600930014

Theme IX – Gut microbiota: A key player connecting nutrition & health

Synopsis - Keynote Speakers

Diet in health and disease: the role of microbiota

Author

Ana Faria – Comprehensive Health Research Center (CHRC), NMS, UNL, Portugal

Citation

Faria, A. Diet In health and disease: the role of microbiota.

A huge collection of trillions of microorganisms (viruses, bacteria, archaea and eukaryotes) can be found within human body and is called microbiota. The microbiota starts establishing even before birth and it is influenced by the mother, the type of birth, antibiotic and other drugs exposure, type of feeding, solid food introduction and becomes more stable around 2-3 years old. An unbalanced microbiome (dysbiosis) is known to give rise to intestinal barrier dysfunction leading to translocation of bacterial and/or bacterial derived pro-inflammatory metabolites that, ultimately, result in systemic inflammation

with metabolic dysfunction. Dysbiosis has been observed in many diseases, particularly metabolic, neurological and auto-immune disorders. Diet has been recognized as a major driver for microbiota changes. Diet-induced changes can be detectable after 24-48 h of manipulation, which is not completely surprising. So, host dietary pattern will have a profound effect on the microbiota, favouring the growth of species that uses this fuel sources and this diet-induced microbial structure will have a crucial impact of host physiology and disease process. Microbiota and its metabolites, particularly the ones produced from dietary components, have been implicated in these disorders. The aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AhR) ligands derived from dietary tryptophan such as indole derivatives, the kynurenine pathway intermediates, and short chain-fatty acids are the most likely candidates to play a role in the microbiota-derived metabolic consequences. Microbiota-targeted interventions such as, probiotics, prebiotics, synbiotic, fecal microbiota transplant and dietary interventions, have been proposed has strategies to re-establish the balance in gut microbiota and in its metabolites with a positive impact on host health. These interventions could represent an efficient strategy disease management, therapeutic response, and subsequently an improvement of clinical outcomes.

References

Cani PD, Moens de Hase E, Van Hul M. Gut Microbiota and Host Metabolism: From Proof of Concept to Therapeutic Intervention. *Microorganisms*. 2021;9(6).

David LA, Maurice CF, Carmody RN, Gootenberg DB, Button JE, Wolfe BE, et al. Diet rapidly and reproducibly alters the human gut microbiome. *Nature*. 2014;505(7484):559-63.

Dong P, Feng JJ, Yan DY, Lyu YJ, Xu X. Early-life gut microbiome and cow's milk allergy- a prospective case - control 6-month follow-up study. *Saudi J Biol Sci.* 2018;25(5):875-80.

Ismael S, Silvestre MP, Vasques M, Araujo JR, Morais J, Duarte MI, et al. A Pilot Study on the Metabolic Impact of Mediterranean Diet in Type 2 Diabetes: Is Gut Microbiota the Key? *Nutrients.* 2021;13(4).

Kolodziejczyk AA, Zheng D, Elinav E. Diet-microbiota interactions and personalized nutrition. *Nat Rev Microbiol.* 2019;17(12):742-53.

Marques C, Dinis L, Barreiros Mota I, Morais J, Ismael S, Pereira-Leal JB, et al. Impact of Beer and Nonalcoholic Beer Consumption on the Gut Microbiota: A Randomized, Double-Blind, Controlled Trial. *J Agric Food Chem.* 2022;70(41):13062-70.

Morais J, Marques C, Faria A, Teixeira D, Barreiros-Mota I, Durao C, et al. Influence of Human Milk on Very Preterms' Gut Microbiota and Alkaline Phosphatase Activity. *Nutrients.* 2021;13(5).

Moreira-Rosario A, Marques C, Pinheiro H, Araujo JR, Ribeiro P, Rocha R, et al. Gut Microbiota Diversity and C-Reactive Protein Are Predictors of Disease Severity in COVID-19 Patients. *Front Microbiol.* 2021;12:705020.

Microplastics and microbiota: Is there an interaction?

Author

Diogo Pestana – Center for Health Technology and Services Research (CINTESIS@RISE), Portugal

Citation

Pestana , D. Microplastics and microbiota: Is there an interaction?.

This presentation explores the connection between microbiota, microplastics, and the One Health approach, emphasizing the environmental and health impacts of microplastics. These small particles have become prevalent not only in marine environments but also in human bodies. They can be classified as primary (used directly in products like cosmetics) or secondary (from plastic degradation).

Humans are exposed to them mainly through inhalation and food, particularly seafood and water. Their small size allows nanoplastics to penetrate cells, leading to concerns about their impact on human health, such as endocrine disruption and toxicity in various systems. Additionally, microplastics can carry pollutants and microorganisms, acting as vectors for contamination.

As plastics degrade, they lose their physical properties, releasing harmful contaminants into biological environments. Moreover, microplastics can disrupt both intestinal and environmental microbiota, creating imbalances that affect overall health. This bidirectional relationship, where microplastics alter microbiota and microbiota influence microplastics, is still under investigation.

The presentation highlights the urgent need to understand how these pollutants impact biological systems, reinforcing the importance of One Health in addressing this complex issue.

Using probiotics to engage the natural microbiota back to health

Author

Vitor Cabral – Gulbenkian Science Institute, Portugal

Citation

Cabral, V. Using probiotics to engage the natural microbiota back to health.

The gut microbiota plays a crucial role in human health and disease, by performing essential functions like colonization resistance to potential pathogenic bacteria [1]–[4]. This protective capacity can be significantly compromised by environmental changes such as different diets or medical treatments [5]–[9], leading to increased susceptibility to infections [8], [10].

Restoring dysbiotic gut microbiotas is an important pursuit for both basic research and clinical studies. Approaches vary from single bacterial species to defined communities or even complex undefined microbiota, such as fecal microbiota transplants (FMT)[11]. Undefined communities, however, pose safety risks[12], [13], which can be circumvented by defined protective single- or multi-strain bacterial cocktails. Next-generation probiotics are microbial species native to the host or target location that upon ingestion and/or colonization provide benefits, but require a deep understanding of the organism's safety profile and therapeutic potential.

Patients susceptible to bacterial infections frequently endure antibiotic treatments, increasing their susceptibility to recurrent infections[14], [15], like is the case in Inflammatory Bowel Diseases (IBD) [16], [17]. IBD is affected by genetic background, gut microbiota, and environmental

conditions [18]–[21], with indicators as key features of disease cycles: gut microbiota imbalances[22], persistently higher intestinal inflammation[23], and predisposition to infections[24]. To cope with inflammatory bouts, IBD patients frequently undergo antibiotics or anti-inflammatory therapies[25], which can involuntarily impair the microbiota and intensify the intestinal proinflammatory milieu[14], promoting a loss of natural microbiota protection against infections by *Enterobacteriaceae*, like the proinflammatory adherent-invasive *Escherichia coli* (AIEC) [26].

Limited advantages have been achieved by probiotics as treatments for complex pathologies like IBD [27]. The probiotic strain *E. coli* Nissle 1917 (EcN) has been tested [28] even in clinical trials[29], but the European Society for Clinical Nutrition and Metabolism recommends against probiotics for treatment or prevention of Crohn's Disease[30], due to lackluster results obtained [31]–[34].

We have previously identified a commensal intestinal bacterial strain, *Klebsiella* sp. ARO112 [35] that provides partial colonization resistance against *Escherichia coli* K-12 MG1655 strain and *Salmonella enterica* Typhimurium [35]. Our previous findings have prompted us to test the potential of ARO112 strain as a next-generation probiotic, capable of eliminating colonization by other *Enterobacteriaceae* invading the gut community during dysbiotic events in a disease model.

Its competitive properties and lack of inflammatory potential had a significant impact in an IBD mouse model, where ARO112 exhibited strong potential as a next-generation probiotic, promoting butyrate-producing microbiota recovery from antibiotic-induced dysbiosis, preventing intestinal inflammation, and reducing AIEC loads[36], a common pathobiont in IBD patients[37]. In our previous work we had shown the importance of the nutritional environment of the intestinal milieu to the successful outcome of the interaction between probiotic and invading bacteria [35], since providing a nutrient exclusive for the invader greatly diminished the probiotic protective capacity. In our latest work, we also show how the “microbiolandscape” (the

microbial landscape surrounding a specific interaction) can affect the therapeutic value of a probiotic [36], as different antibiotic treatments and consequent resulting surviving microbiota members can impair or potentiate the protection provided by the probiotic strain. Our studies reinforce the need to deeply understand the available niches left empty by disrupting events, like diet changes, disease flares, and medical treatments, and how this understanding will increase our ability to engineer the desired therapeutic outcomes by using probiotics that leverage the surrounding microbialscape towards that goal.

References

- [1] D. van der Waaij, J. M. Berghuis-de Vries, and L. Lekkerkerk-v, "Colonization resistance of the digestive tract in conventional and antibiotic-treated mice.," *J. Hyg. (Lond).*, vol. 69, no. 3, pp. 405–411, Sep. 1971, doi: 10.1017/s0022172400021653.
- [2] C. G. Buffie and E. G. Pamer, "Microbiota-mediated colonization resistance against intestinal pathogens.," *Nat. Rev. Immunol.*, vol. 13, no. 11, pp. 790–801, Nov. 2013, doi: 10.1038/nri3535.
- [3] N. Kamada, Y.-G. Kim, H. P. Sham, B. A. Vallance, J. L. Puente, E. C. Martens, and G. Núñez, "Regulated virulence controls the ability of a pathogen to compete with the gut microbiota.," *Science*, vol. 336, no. 6086, pp. 1325–1329, Jun. 2012, doi: 10.1126/science.1222195.
- [4] G. Caballero-Flores, J. M. Pickard, and G. Núñez, "Microbiota-mediated colonization resistance: mechanisms and regulation.," *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.*, vol. 21, no. 6, pp. 347–360, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.1038/s41579-022-00833-7.

[5] P. J. Turnbaugh, F. Bäckhed, L. Fulton, and J. I. Gordon, "Diet-Induced Obesity Is Linked to Marked but Reversible Alterations in the Mouse Distal Gut Microbiome," *Cell Host Microbe*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 213–223, Apr. 2008, doi: 10.1016/j.chom.2008.02.015.

[6] E. B. Hollister, C. Gao, and J. Versalovic, "Compositional and functional features of the gastrointestinal microbiome and their effects on human health.," *Gastroenterology*, vol. 146, no. 6, pp. 1449–1458, May 2014, doi: 10.1053/j.gastro.2014.01.052.

[7] R. A. Oliveira, V. Cabral, and K. B. Xavier, "Microbiome–diet interactions drive antibiotic efficacy," *Nat. Microbiol.*, vol. 6, no. 7, pp. 824–825, 2021, doi: 10.1038/s41564-021-00926-8.

[8] I. Sekirov, N. M. Tam, M. Jogova, M. L. Robertson, Y. Li, C. Lupp, and B. B. Finlay, "Antibiotic-induced perturbations of the intestinal microbiota alter host susceptibility to enteric infection.," *Infect. Immun.*, vol. 76, no. 10, pp. 4726–4736, Oct. 2008, doi: 10.1128/IAI.00319-08.

[9] A. C. Fenneman, M. Weidner, L. A. Chen, M. Nieuwdorp, and M. J. Blaser, "Antibiotics in the pathogenesis of diabetes and inflammatory diseases of the gastrointestinal tract.," *Nat. Rev. Gastroenterol. Hepatol.*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 81–100, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.1038/s41575-022-00685-9.

[10] A. Andremont, J. Cervesi, P.-A. Bandinelli, F. Vitry, and J. de Gunzburg, "Spare and repair the gut microbiota from antibiotic-induced dysbiosis: state-of-the-art," *Drug Discov. Today*, vol. 26, no. 9, pp. 2159–2163, 2021, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drudis.2021.02.022>.

[11] R. A. Oliveira and E. G. Pamer, "Assembling symbiotic bacterial species into live therapeutic consortia that reconstitute microbiome functions.," *Cell Host Microbe*, vol. 31, no. 4, pp. 472–484, Apr. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.chom.2023.03.002.

[12] Z. DeFilipp, P. P. Bloom, M. Torres Soto, M. K. Mansour, M. R. A. Sater, M. H. Huntley, S. Turbett, R. T. Chung, Y.-B. Chen, and E. L. Hohmann, "Drug-Resistant *E. coli* Bacteremia Transmitted by Fecal Microbiota Transplant.," *N. Engl. J. Med.*, vol. 381, no. 21, pp. 2043–2050, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa1910437.

[13] S. Gupta, B. H. Mullish, and J. R. Allegretti, "Fecal Microbiota Transplantation: The Evolving Risk Landscape.," *Am. J. Gastroenterol.*, vol. 116, no. 4, pp. 647–656, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.14309/ajg.0000000000001075.

[14] P. T. Santana, S. L. B. Rosas, B. E. Ribeiro, Y. Marinho, and H. S. P. de Souza, "Dysbiosis in Inflammatory Bowel Disease: Pathogenic Role and Potential Therapeutic Targets.," *Int. J. Mol. Sci.*, vol. 23, no. 7, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.3390/ijms23073464.

[15] A. Djukovic, E. M. Gonzalez-Barbera, J. Sanz, A. Artacho, I. Penaranda, B. Herrera, M. J. Garzon, M. Salavert, J. L. Lopez-Hontangas, K. B. Xavier, B. Kuster, L. Debrauwer, J.-M. Rolain, M. A. Sanz, J. B. Xavier, and C. Ubeda, "High Heterogeneity of Multidrug-Resistant Enterobacteriaceae Fecal Levels in Hospitalized Patients Is Partially Driven by Intravenous beta-Lactams.," *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.*, vol. 64, no. 2, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1128/AAC.01415-19.

[16] J.-Y. Lee, S. A. Cevallos, M. X. Byndloss, C. R. Tiffany, E. E. Olsan, B. P. Butler, B. M. Young, A. W. L. Rogers, H. Nguyen, K. Kim, S.-W. Choi, E. Bae, J. H. Lee, U.-G. Min, D.-C. Lee, and A. J. Bäumlér, "High-Fat Diet and Antibiotics Cooperatively Impair Mitochondrial Bioenergetics to Trigger Dysbiosis that Exacerbates Pre-inflammatory Bowel Disease.," *Cell Host Microbe*, vol. 28, no. 2, pp. 273–284.e6, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.chom.2020.06.001.

[17] Y. Zou, L. Wu, W. Xu, X. Zhou, K. Ye, H. Xiong, C. Song, and Y. Xie, "Correlation between antibiotic use in childhood and subsequent inflammatory bowel disease: a systematic review and meta-analysis.," *Scand. J. Gastroenterol.*, vol. 55, no. 3, pp. 301–311, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1080/00365521.2020.1737882.

[18] A. Goethel, K. Croitoru, and D. J. Philpott, "The interplay between microbes and the immune response in inflammatory bowel disease.," *J. Physiol.*, vol. 596, no. 17, pp. 3869–3882, Sep. 2018, doi: 10.1113/JP275396.

- [19] L. G. Albenberg, J. D. Lewis, and G. D. Wu, "Food and the gut microbiota in inflammatory bowel diseases: a critical connection.," *Curr. Opin. Gastroenterol.*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 314–320, Jul. 2012, doi: 10.1097/MOG.0b013e328354586f.
- [20] A. Frolkis, L. A. Dieleman, H. W. Barkema, R. Panaccione, S. Ghosh, R. N. Fedorak, K. Madsen, and G. G. Kaplan, "Environment and the inflammatory bowel diseases.," *Can. J. Gastroenterol.*, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. e18–24, Mar. 2013, doi: 10.1155/2013/102859.
- [21] A. Hviid, H. Svanström, and M. Frisch, "Antibiotic use and inflammatory bowel diseases in childhood.," *Gut*, vol. 60, no. 1, pp. 49–54, Jan. 2011, doi: 10.1136/gut.2010.219683.
- [22] P. Qiu, T. Ishimoto, L. Fu, J. Zhang, Z. Zhang, and Y. Liu, "The Gut Microbiota in Inflammatory Bowel Disease.," *Front. Cell. Infect. Microbiol.*, vol. 12, p. 733992, 2022, doi: 10.3389/fcimb.2022.733992.
- [23] M. Fakhoury, R. Negruj, A. Mooranian, and H. Al-Salami, "Inflammatory bowel disease: clinical aspects and treatments.," *J. Inflamm. Res.*, vol. 7, pp. 113–120, 2014, doi: 10.2147/JIR.S65979.
- [24] P. M. Irving, S. de Lusignan, D. Tang, M. Nijher, and K. Barrett, "Risk of common infections in people with inflammatory bowel disease in primary care: a population-based cohort study.," *BMJ open Gastroenterol.*, vol. 8, no. 1, Feb. 2021, doi: 10.1136/bmjgast-2020-000573.
- [25] A. B. Pithadia and S. Jain, "Treatment of inflammatory bowel disease (IBD).," *Pharmacol. Rep.*, vol. 63, no. 3, pp. 629–642, 2011, doi: 10.1016/s1734-1140(11)70575-8.
- [26] C.-L. N. Small, S. A. Reid-Yu, J. B. McPhee, and B. K. Coombes, "Persistent infection with Crohn's disease-associated adherent-invasive *Escherichia coli* leads to chronic inflammation and intestinal fibrosis.," *Nat. Commun.*, vol. 4, p. 1957, 2013, doi: 10.1038/ncomms2957.
- [27] B. P. Abraham and E. M. M. Quigley, "Probiotics in Inflammatory Bowel Disease.," *Gastroenterol. Clin. North Am.*, vol. 46, no. 4, pp. 769–782, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.gtc.2017.08.003.

[28] M. Schultz, "Clinical use of *E. coli* Nissle 1917 in inflammatory bowel disease.," *Inflamm. Bowel Dis.*, vol. 14, no. 7, pp. 1012–1018, Jul. 2008, doi: 10.1002/ibd.20377.

[29] H. Matthes, T. Krummenerl, M. Giensch, C. Wolff, and J. Schulze, "Clinical trial: probiotic treatment of acute distal ulcerative colitis with rectally administered *Escherichia coli* Nissle 1917 (EcN).," *BMC Complement. Altern. Med.*, vol. 10, p. 13, Apr. 2010, doi: 10.1186/1472-6882-10-13.

[30] S. C. Bischoff, P. Bager, J. Escher, A. Forbes, X. Hébuterne, C. L. Hvas, F. Joly, S. Klek, Z. Krznaric, J. Ockenga, S. Schneider, R. Shamir, K. Stardelova, D. V. Bender, N. Wierdsma, and A. Weimann, "ESPEN guideline on Clinical Nutrition in inflammatory bowel disease," *Clin. Nutr.*, vol. 42, no. 3, pp. 352–379, 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clnu.2022.12.004>.

[31] J. Suez, N. Zmora, G. Zilberman-Schapira, U. Mor, M. Dori-Bachash, S. Bashiardes, M. Zur, D. Regev-Lehavi, R. Ben-Zeev Brik, S. Federici, M. Horn, Y. Cohen, A. E. Moor, D. Zeevi, T. Korem, E. Kotler, A. Harmelin, S. Itzkovitz, N. Maharshak, et al., "Post-Antibiotic Gut Mucosal Microbiome Reconstitution Is Impaired by Probiotics and Improved by Autologous FMT.," *Cell*, vol. 174, no. 6, pp. 1406–1423.e16, Sep. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.cell.2018.08.047.

[32] E. Montassier, R. Valdés-Mas, E. Batard, N. Zmora, M. Dori-Bachash, J. Suez, and E. Elinav, "Probiotics impact the antibiotic resistance gene reservoir along the human GI tract in a person-specific and antibiotic-dependent manner.," *Nat. Microbiol.*, vol. 6, no. 8, pp. 1043–1054, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.1038/s41564-021-00920-0.

[33] J.-P. Nougayrède, C. V Chagneau, J.-P. Motta, N. Bossuet-Greif, M. Belloy, F. Taieb, J.-J. Gratadoux, M. Thomas, P. Langella, and E. Oswald, "A Toxic Friend: Genotoxic and Mutagenic Activity of the Probiotic Strain *Escherichia coli* Nissle 1917.," *mSphere*, vol. 6, no. 4, p. e0062421, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.1128/mSphere.00624-21.

[34] M. Olier, I. Marcq, C. Salvador-Cartier, T. Secher, U. Dobrindt, M. Boury, V. Bacquié, M. Pénary, E. Gaultier, J.-P. Nougayrède, J. Fioramonti, and E. Oswald, "Genotoxicity of *Escherichia coli* Nissle 1917 strain cannot be dissociated from its probiotic activity.," *Gut Microbes*, vol. 3, no. 6, pp. 501–509, 2012, doi: 10.4161/gmic.21737.

[35] R. A. Oliveira, K. M. Ng, M. B. Correia, V. Cabral, H. Shi, J. L. Sonnenburg, K. C. Huang, and K. B. Xavier, "Klebsiella michiganensis transmission enhances resistance to Enterobacteriaceae gut invasion by nutrition competition.," *Nat. Microbiol.*, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1038/s41564-019-0658-4.

[36] V. Cabral, R. A. Oliveira, M. B. Correia, M. F. Pedro, C. Ubeda, and K. B. Xavier, "Gut protective *Klebsiella* species promotes microbiota recovery and pathobiont clearance while preventing inflammation," *bioRxiv*, p. 2023.11.14.566997, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.1101/2023.11.14.566997.

[37] H. C. Mirsepasi-Lauridsen, B. A. Vallance, K. A. Krogfelt, and A. M. Petersen, "Escherichia coli Pathobionts Associated with Inflammatory Bowel Disease.," *Clin. Microbiol. Rev.*, vol. 32, no. 2, Mar. 2019, doi: 10.1128/CMR.00060-18.

YourBiome: Where do we stand on fecal microbiota transplant

Author

Cláudia Marques – Center for Health Technology and Services Research (CINTESIS@RISE), Portugal

Citation

Marques, C. YourBiome: Where do we stand on fecal microbiota transplant.

This talk focused on YourBiome, a spin-off from NOVA Medical School, aimed at leveraging microbiota for therapeutic purposes. The microbiota, crucial for both health and disease, has become an ideal therapeutic target as scientific understanding deepens. YourBiome is dedicated to finding strategies to harness the microbiota's potential for medical treatment.

One of the major challenges addressed by YourBiome is *Clostridium difficile* infection, which is notoriously resistant to antibiotics, making it difficult to treat. Fecal microbiota transplantation (FMT) represents a promising solution, backed by scientific evidence. FMT has shown effectiveness in treating *C. difficile* infections and other conditions, demonstrating its potential as a powerful therapeutic tool.

Through this project, YourBiome has set out to create a stool bank, providing hospitals with the necessary resources to perform fecal transplants. This initiative aims to support the healthcare system by facilitating access to FMT, ultimately improving treatment outcomes for patients suffering from difficult-to-treat infections. In summary, YourBiome represents a significant advancement in microbiota-based therapies, highlighting the importance of microbiota as a target for innovative health interventions.

Exploring the interconnection between edible plant microbiome and gut microbiome and its impact on human health

Author

Wisnu Adi Wicaksono – Institute of Environmental Biotechnology, Graz University of Technology, Austria

Citation

Wicaksono , W.A., Exploring the interconnection between edible plant microbiome and gut microbiome and its impact on human health.

The composition and functioning of the gut microbiota during infancy are crucial for long-term health. The gut microbiota plays a significant role in various aspects of health and disease, such as nutrient metabolism, immune system development, and the onset of immune-related diseases. One of the key factors that influences the development of the gut microbiota in early life is dietary patterns. Although there is a known connection between gut microbiota and human health, further research is still needed on how gut microbiota develops in early life and its impact on health later. Consuming plant-based foods such as fruits and vegetables can potentially enhance the diversity of the gut microbiota by introducing environmental microbiota. Our study analyzed 2,426 publicly available gut metagenomes to investigate the presence of plant-associated bacteria in the human gut, albeit at a low abundance (approximately 2.2%). Factors such as age, frequency of vegetable consumption, and variety of plants consumed were found to influence

the diversity and composition of plant-associated bacteria in the gut. We utilized functional assays, advanced microscopy, and sequencing techniques to assess the effects of food processing and cultivation practices on fruit microbiota diversity. Our results, using apples as a model, demonstrated that different cooking processes resulted in a significant decrease in bacterial diversity and abundance (63.3–86.7%). Additionally, the cultivation and origin of fruits were found to impact their microbiome composition. This research suggests that consuming fruits from different sources exposes individuals to various bacteria, which can affect the diversity of the gut microbiota. Therefore, it is important to consider the effects of food processing and cultivation techniques on native fruit microbiota, a factor that is often overlooked in discussions about the exposome and human health.

Selected Oral Communications

Abstract IX.1 Blueberry leaves biomass: A prebiotic with gut immunomodulatory potential in type 2 diabetes

Author

Vieira, P. – Institute of Pharmacology & Experimental Therapeutics & Coimbra Institute for Clinical and Biomedical Research (iCBR), Faculty of Medicine from University of Coimbra (FMUC), Portugal; CIBB – Center for Innovative Biomedicine and Biotechnology, University of Coimbra, Portugal; Clinical Academic Center of Coimbra (CACC), Portugal; Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, ESTESC-Coimbra Health School, Pharmacy, Portugal

Nunes, S. – Institute of Pharmacology & Experimental Therapeutics & Coimbra Institute for Clinical and Biomedical Research (iCBR), Faculty of Medicine from University of Coimbra (FMUC), Portugal; CIBB – Center for Innovative Biomedicine and Biotechnology, University of Coimbra, Portugal; Clinical Academic Center of Coimbra (CACC), Portugal

Preguiça, I. – Institute of Pharmacology & Experimental Therapeutics & Coimbra Institute for Clinical and Biomedical Research (iCBR), Faculty of Medicine from University of Coimbra (FMUC), Portugal; CIBB – Center for Innovative Biomedicine and Biotechnology, University of Coimbra, Portugal; Clinical Academic Center of Coimbra (CACC), Portugal

Ferreira, C. – Institute of Pharmacology & Experimental Therapeutics & Coimbra Institute for Clinical and Biomedical Research (iCBR), Faculty of Medicine from University of Coimbra (FMUC), Portugal; CIBB – Center for Innovative Biomedicine and Biotechnology, University of Coimbra, Portugal

Alves, A. – Institute of Pharmacology & Experimental Therapeutics & Coimbra Institute for Clinical and Biomedical Research (iCBR), Faculty of Medicine from University of Coimbra (FMUC), Portugal; CIBB – Center for Innovative Biomedicine and Biotechnology, University of Coimbra, Portugal; Clinical Academic Center of Coimbra (CACC), Portugal

Almeida, J. – Immunology Institute, Faculty of Medicine, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Alves, V. – Immunology Institute, Faculty of Medicine, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Sá, H. – Immunology Institute, Faculty of Medicine, University of Coimbra, Coimbra, Portugal

Reis, F. – Institute of Pharmacology & Experimental Therapeutics & Coimbra Institute for Clinical and Biomedical Research (iCBR), Faculty of Medicine from University of Coimbra (FMUC), Portugal; CIBB – Center for Innovative Biomedicine and Biotechnology, University of Coimbra, Portugal; Clinical Academic Center of Coimbra (CACC), Portugal

Viana, S. – Institute of Pharmacology & Experimental Therapeutics & Coimbra Institute for Clinical and Biomedical Research (iCBR), Faculty of Medicine from University of Coimbra (FMUC), Portugal; CIBB – Center for Innovative Biomedicine and Biotechnology, University of Coimbra, Portugal; Clinical Academic Center of Coimbra (CACC), Portugal; Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, ESTESC-Coimbra Health School, Pharmacy, Portugal

Citation

Vieira, P., Nunes, S., Pregoça, I., Ferreira, C., Alves, A., Almeida, J., Alves, V., Sá, H., Reis, F., Viana, S. Blueberry leaves biomass: A prebiotic with gut immunomodulatory potential in type 2 diabetes.

Upcycling strategies for senescent blueberry leaves (BL) agrowaste are promising for the generation of new functional ingredients with a wide-range of applications for human health (Helmstädter & Schuster, 2010; Sidorova et al., 2017). Our group developed a biotechnological approach for BL processing towards the generation of a sustainable prebiotic. Herein, we aimed to characterize the corresponding BL biomass (BB) hypoglycemic/hypolipidemic potential alongside gut immunomodulatory profile in an

animal model of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), comparing their efficacy with metformin (METF) as standard antidiabetic drug.

Male Wistar rats were randomly divided in 5 groups (n=8/group): CTRL/ CTRL+BB/T2DM/T2DM+BB/T2DM+METF. T2DM animals were fed with an HFD (45%) for 8 weeks, followed by a single injection of STZ (25mg/Kg BW, i.p). Then, BB (500mg/Kg BW) or METF (300mg/Kg BW) were orally dosed for additional 8 weeks. Glycemic, insulinemic and lipid profiles were monitored. Flow cytometry allowed intestinal Peyer patches (PP) immunophenotyping of CD4 + T cell subsets (Th1, Th2, Th17, Treg cells). Values are means \pm S.E.M (ANOVA followed by post-hoc tests). This work was approved by the ORBEA of iCBR-FMUC (#12/2018).

Diabetic animals displayed severe glucose and insulin intolerance, hepatic steatosis and intestinal PP remodelling, featured by a robust increase in the frequency of CD4 + Treg cell subset alongside the suppression of CD4 + Th1/Th2 cell subsets. BB oral treatment openly ameliorated glucose and insulin intolerance as well as hepatic triglycerides contents, comparable to METF standard treatment. Notably, T2DM+BB animals displayed regular T cell subset counts in PP suggesting that BB was able to restore intestinal immunological tonus.

Albeit further elucidation is still warranted to unveil the pathophysiological significance of diabetic intestinal immunomodulation, these results pave the way for an innovative nature-based functional ingredient with the potential to tackle unhealthy metabolic paradigms in a circular economy perspective.

Acknowledgments

FCT/COMPETE/FEDER by funding via SFRH/BD/109017/2015, 2020.08560. BD, 2020.09481.BD, 2021.05312.BD, 2022.13182.BD, UIDB/04539/2020, UIDP/04539/2020 (CIBB), POCI-01-0145-FEDER-007440, and SAACCENTRO-46-2016-01_INOVC2020#5625. and Mirtilusa by leaves supply. No conflicts of interests to declare.

References

Helmstädter, A., & Schuster, N. (2010). *Vaccinium myrtillus* as an antidiabetic medicinal plant—research through the ages. *Die Pharmazie-An International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 65(5), 315-321.

Sidorova, Y., Shipelin, V., Mazo, V., Zorin, S., Petrov, N., & Kochetkova, A. (2017). Hypoglycemic and hypolipidemic effect of *Vaccinium myrtillus* L. leaf and *Phaseolus vulgaris* L. seed coat extracts in diabetic rats. *Nutrition*, 41, 107-112.

Abstract IX.2 A blueberry leaves-based nutraceutical improves gut immune imbalance and central impairments in experimental multiple sclerosis

Author

Ferreira, C. – Institute of Pharmacology & Experimental Therapeutics & Coimbra Institute for Clinical and Biomedical Research (iCBR), Faculty of Medicine from University of Coimbra (FMUC), Portugal; CIBB – Center for Innovative Biomedicine and Biotechnology, UC, Portugal; Clinical Academic Center of Coimbra (CACC), Portugal

Palavra, F. – Institute of Pharmacology & Experimental Therapeutics & Coimbra Institute for Clinical and Biomedical Research (iCBR), Faculty of Medicine from University of Coimbra (FMUC), Portugal; CIBB – Center for Innovative Biomedicine and Biotechnology, UC, Portugal; Clinical Academic Center of Coimbra (CACC), Portugal; Centre for Child Development - Neuropediatrics Unit, Hospital Pediátrico, Centro Hospitalar e Universitário de Coimbra, Portugal

Preguiça, I. – Institute of Pharmacology & Experimental Therapeutics & Coimbra Institute for Clinical and Biomedical Research (iCBR), Faculty of Medicine from University of Coimbra (FMUC), Portugal; CIBB – Center for Innovative Biomedicine and Biotechnology, UC, Portugal; Clinical Academic Center of Coimbra (CACC), Portugal

Alves, A. – Institute of Pharmacology & Experimental Therapeutics & Coimbra Institute for Clinical and Biomedical Research (iCBR), Faculty of Medicine from University of Coimbra (FMUC), Portugal; CIBB – Center for Innovative Biomedicine and Biotechnology, UC, Portugal; Clinical Academic Center of Coimbra (CACC), Portugal

Vieira, P. – Institute of Pharmacology & Experimental Therapeutics & Coimbra Institute for Clinical and Biomedical Research (iCBR), Faculty of Medicine from University of Coimbra (FMUC), Portugal; CIBB – Center for Innovative Biomedicine and Biotechnology, UC, Portugal; Clinical Academic Center of Coimbra (CACC), Portugal; Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, ESTESC-Coimbra Health School, Pharmacy, Portugal

Nunes, S. – Institute of Pharmacology & Experimental Therapeutics & Coimbra Institute for Clinical and Biomedical Research (iCBR), Faculty of Medicine from University of Coimbra (FMUC), Portugal; CIBB – Center for Innovative Biomedicine and Biotechnology, UC, Portugal; Clinical Academic Center of Coimbra (CACC), Portugal

Jesus, Â. – Pathological Anatomy Laboratory, Coimbra Hospital and University Center (CHUC), Coimbra, Portugal

Almeida, J. – Institute, Faculty of Medicine, UC, Coimbra, Portugal

Alves, V. – Institute, Faculty of Medicine, UC, Coimbra, Portugal

Sá, H. – Institute, Faculty of Medicine, UC, Coimbra, Portugal

Reis, F. – Institute of Pharmacology & Experimental Therapeutics & Coimbra Institute for Clinical and Biomedical Research (iCBR), Faculty of Medicine from University of Coimbra (FMUC), Portugal; CIBB – Center for Innovative Biomedicine and Biotechnology, UC, Portugal; Clinical Academic Center of Coimbra (CACC), Portugal

Viana, S. – Institute of Pharmacology & Experimental Therapeutics & Coimbra Institute for Clinical and Biomedical Research (iCBR), Faculty of Medicine from University of Coimbra (FMUC), Portugal; CIBB – Center for Innovative Biomedicine and Biotechnology, UC, Portugal; Clinical Academic Center of Coimbra (CACC), Portugal; Polytechnic Institute of Coimbra, ESTESC-Coimbra Health School, Pharmacy, Portugal

Citation

Ferreira, C., Palavra, F., Preguiça, I., Alves, A., Vieira, P., Nunes, S., Jesus, Â., Almeida, J., Alves, V., Sá, H., Reis, F., Viana, S. A blueberry leaves-based nutraceutical improves gut immune imbalance and central impairments in experimental multiple sclerosis.

Multiple Sclerosis (MS) is a demyelinating autoimmune disease, for which intestinal dysbiosis and immune Th17/Treg cells' roles have been increasingly

appreciated, namely regarding CNS autoimmunity (Tryfonos et al., 2019). Recognizing the prebiotic potential of blueberry leaves (Ștefănescu et al., 2020), the present work aimed to assess the nutraceutical potential of a blueberry leaves' biomass (BB) on the gut-immune system-brain axis in experimental MS, employing the cuprizone (CPZ) intoxication model.

Male C57BL/6J mice were divided into six groups (n=10): controls, receiving vehicles only for 5 and 7 weeks, respectively; CPZ-intoxicated groups, receiving CPZ for 5 (demyelination peak – W5) or 7 weeks (early remyelination – W7); and BB-treated groups. The intestinal Treg/Th17 ratio was assessed through flow cytometry analysis of Peyer Patches. Colon histomorphology and mucin density evaluation were performed through Hematoxylin & Eosin (H&E) and Alcian Blue-Periodic Acid-Schiff staining, respectively. Relative gene expression (RT-PCR) of target genes, including inflammatory and myelin-associated genes, was quantified in the gut and brain. Brain histomorphology was evaluated by Kluver-Barrera, Toluidine Blue, and H&E staining of the cerebellum. Results were expressed as means \pm standard errors of the mean (S.E.M.). This work was approved by the ORBEA of iCBR-FMUC (#12/2018).

BB counteracted intestinal Treg/Th17 imbalance paralleling the peak of demyelination, and partially reversed goblet cell loss, mucosa hyperplasia, immune infiltrates and microbial indican production resulting from CPZ intoxication. Remyelinating properties were likewise evidenced by the increased expression of myelin-associated genes in the brain and restored histomorphology myelin staining (W7). Furthermore, BB counteracted the increased levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines promoted by CPZ at W5, but displayed an inverse behaviour at W7, pointing to a chief role of inflammatory mediators in promoting remyelination.

Collectively, these results point to BB biomass efficacy to modulate gut-to-brain communications in experimental MS, opening new avenues for its use as a nutraceutical in MS.

Acknowledgments

FCT/COMPETE/FEDER by funding via SFRH/BD/109017/2015, 2020.08560. BD, 2020.09481.BD, UIDB/04539/2020, UIDP/04539/2020 (CIBB), POCI-01-0145-FEDER-007440, and SAACCENTRO-46-2016-01_INOVC2020#5625. and Mirtilusa by leaves supply. No conflicts of interests to declare.

References

Tryfonos, C., Mantzourou, M., Fotiou, D., Vrizas, M., Vadikolias, K., Pavlidou, E., & Giaginis, C. (2019). Dietary Supplements on Controlling Multiple Sclerosis Symptoms and Relapses: Current Clinical Evidence and Future Perspectives. *Medicines*, 6(3), 95. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicines6030095>.

Ștefănescu, B.-E., Călinoiu, L. F., Ranga, F., Fetea, F., Mocan, A., Vodnar, D. C., & Crișan, G. (2020). The Chemical and Biological Profiles of Leaves from Commercial Blueberry Varieties. *Plants*, 9(9), 1193. <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants9091193>.

Abstract IX.3 The role of trimethylamine on intestinal fatty acid absorption in caco-2 cells

Author

Rodrigues, C. – Nutrition & Metabolism, CHRC, NOVA Medical School, Faculdade de Ciências Médicas, NMS, FCM, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal

Ismael, S. – Nutrition & Metabolism, CHRC, NOVA Medical School, Faculdade de Ciências Médicas, NMS, FCM, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal;

Nutrition & Metabolism, CINTESIS@RISE, NOVA Medical School, Faculdade de Ciências Médicas, NMS, FCM, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal

Barreiros-Mota, I. – Nutrition & Metabolism, CHRC, NOVA Medical School, Faculdade de Ciências Médicas, NMS, FCM, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal

Castela, I. – Nutrition & Metabolism, CHRC, NOVA Medical School, Faculdade de Ciências Médicas, NMS, FCM, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal;

Nutrition & Metabolism, CINTESIS@RISE, NOVA Medical School, Faculdade de Ciências Médicas, NMS, FCM, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal

Almeida, M. J. – Nutrition & Metabolism, CHRC, NOVA Medical School, Faculdade de Ciências Médicas, NMS, FCM, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal

Santos, G. – Nutrition & Metabolism, CINTESIS@RISE, NOVA Medical School, Faculdade de Ciências Médicas, NMS, FCM, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal

Calhau, C. – Nutrition & Metabolism, CINTESIS@RISE, NOVA Medical School, Faculdade de Ciências Médicas, NMS, FCM, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal

Rocha, J. C. – Nutrition & Metabolism, CINTESIS@RISE, NOVA Medical School, Faculdade de Ciências Médicas, NMS, FCM, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal; Reference Centre of Inherited Metabolic Diseases, Centro Hospitalar Universitário de Lisboa Central Lisboa, Portugal

Faria, A. – Nutrition & Metabolism, CHRC, NOVA Medical School, Faculdade de Ciências Médicas, NMS, FCM, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal; Nutrition & Metabolism, CINTESIS@RISE, NOVA Medical School, Faculdade de Ciências Médicas, NMS, FCM, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal
Araújo, J. R. – Nutrition & Metabolism, CINTESIS@RISE, NOVA Medical School, Faculdade de Ciências Médicas, NMS, FCM, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Lisboa, Portugal

Citation

Rodrigues, C., Ismael, S., Barreiros-Mota, I., Castela, I., Almeida, M. J., Santos, G., Calhau, C., Rocha, J. C., Faria, A., Araújo, J. R. The role of trimethylamine on intestinal fatty acid absorption in caco-2 cells.

Introduction

Although elevated blood levels of trimethylamine N-oxide (TMAO) have been associated with atherosclerosis development in humans [1], the role of its gut microbiota derived precursor, TMA, in this process has not been yet deciphered. Taking this into account, and that increased intestinal fatty acid absorption contributes to atherosclerosis onset and progression [2], this study aimed to evaluate the effect of TMA on fatty acid absorption in a cell line that mimic human enterocytes.

Material & Methods: Caco-2 cells were treated with TMA 250 μ M during 24h. Fatty acid absorption was assessed by measuring the apical-to-basolateral transport and the intracellular levels of BODIPY-C12, a fluorescently labelled fatty acid analogue. Gene expression of the main intestinal fatty acid transporters was evaluated by qRT-PCR.

Results

The apical-to-basolateral transport of BODIPY-C12 fatty acid increased in a time dependent and non-saturable manner in both control and TMA-treated cells 0.5, 1, 2, 4 and 6h after its addition to the apical compartment. However, at all-time points, the magnitude of this increase was 20 to 50% ($p < 0.05$) higher in TMA-treated cells. Additionally, intracellular BODIPY

C12 fatty acid levels were 20% higher in cells exposed to TMA compared to those exposed to control conditions, 6h after BODIPY-C12 fatty acid addition to the apical compartment. Fatty acid transport protein 4 (FATP4) and fatty acid translocase (FAT)/CD36 gene expression were not stimulated by TMA, suggesting that TMA-induced increase in fatty acid transport may be mediated by an increase in FAT/CD36 and/or FATP4 activity and/or fatty acid passive transport. Conclusions: This study demonstrated that TMA increases the intestinal absorption of fatty acids. Future studies are necessary to confirm if this may constitute a novel mechanism that partially explains the existing positive association between the consumption of a diet rich in TMA sources (e.g. red meat) and the increased risk of atherosclerotic diseases.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by ERDF through the operation POCI-01-0145-ERDF-007746 funded by the Programa Operacional Competitividade e Internacionalização – COMPETE2020 and by FCT - Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia, IP national support through CINTESIS, R&D Unit (UIDB/4255/2020), CHRC (UIDP/04923/2020 and UIDB/04923/2020) and through the projects PTDC/BAA-AGR/7419/2020, 2022.11716.BD and 2020.06333.BD.

References

- [1] Koeth, R. A., Wang, Z., Levison, B. S., Buffa, J. A., Org, E., Sheehy, B. T., Britt, E. B., Fu, X., Wu, Y., Li, L. Smith, J. D., DiDonato, J. A., Chen, J., Li, H., Wu, G. D., Lewis, J. D., Warrier, M., Brown, J. M., Krauss, R. M., Tang, W. H., Bushman, R. D., Lusis, A. L., Hazen, S. L. (2013). Intestinal microbiota metabolism of L-carnitine, a nutrient in red meat, promotes atherosclerosis. *Nature medicine*, 19(5), 576–585.
- [2] Dash, S., Xiao, C., Morgantini, C., & Lewis, G. F. (2015). New Insights into the Regulation of Chylomicron Production. *Annual review of nutrition*, 35, 265–294.

Closing Remarks

Elvira Fortunato

Former Minister of Science, Technology, and Higher Education in the XXIII Constitutional Government of Portugal

The first “Farm to Fork” International Congress was crucial for discussing pressing issues such as nutrition, health, and sustainability, all of which are key to the green transition and building climate resilience. The teams behind the Cultivar and FUSILLI projects, presented during this congress, need to be congratulated for their work in some of these fields.

The event highlighted the importance of taking multidisciplinary approaches to tackle global challenges. Today’s issues—ranging from cancer and emerging diseases to climate change—are complex and require expertise across various fields. The discussions and presentations emphasized how working together is more essential than ever, reinforcing the value of international cooperation in science and research.

Since becoming minister, strengthening collaboration with Spain, in particular, has been a priority, in which we have made significant progress, especially in the area of space, with the development of the Atlantic Constellation, a project designed to monitor climate change.

Overall, I express my support and appreciation, as a professor and researcher, for this congress and its future editions, recognizing its critical role in addressing these complex global challenges and to help sustain similar initiatives.

Where scientists empower society

Creating solutions for healthy lives on a healthy planet

frontiersin.org

Why publish with us?

Open access

All Frontiers journals are fully open access, meaning every research article we publish is immediately and permanently free to read.

Peer review

Our collaborative peer review is handled by experts in the field who objectively certify the quality, validity, and rigor of research.

Technology

With the latest custom-built technology and artificial intelligence, we're revolutionizing the way research is published, evaluated, and communicated.

Impact

We are the third most-cited publisher with 1.4 billion article views and downloads – reflecting the power of research that is open for all.

Frontiers

Avenue du Tribunal-Fédéral 34
1005 Lausanne, Switzerland
frontiersin.org

Contact us

+41 (0)21 510 17 00
frontiersin.org/about/contact